

PRZESTĘPCZE TENDENCJE ODNOŚNIE DO ŚWIADKÓW W UKRAINIE

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Adnotacja. Na podstawie analizy statystycznych wskaźników, co charakteryzuje kryminogenną sytuację w Ukrainie, stan walki z przestępczością, formy przeciwdziałania organomścigania i uogólniania naukowych wyników ojczystych na zagranicznych badaczy udowodniono obecność postępującej tendencji do faktycznego zwiększenia przestępczości w Ukrainie. Ustalono przyczynę zaznaczonej dynamiki, a mianowicie pewność przestępców w bezkarności przez bezsilność organów państwowych i systemu ochrony porządku prawnego efektywnie przeciwdziałać przestępczości. Świadek przedłuża zajmować główne miejsce w systemie dowodów i domawiania w kryminalnym prowadzeniu, a, zatem, poddaje się sprzecznemu z prawem wpływowi od strony nie zainteresowanych jaźni w sprawiedliwym i prawnym przed sądowym śledztwie i kryminalnym sądownictwie. Formy sprzecznego z prawem wpływu na świadka obierają się zależnie od okoliczności przestępstwa, a ich wyniki bezpośrednio wpływają na pełność i obiektywizm ustalenia prawdy w kryminalnym prowadzeniu. Określono charakterystyczne zagrożenia świadkowi w Ukrainie w związku z wykonaniem ostatnim procesualnych praw i obowiązków w kryminalnym prowadzeniu. Udowodniono, że główną utajoną przyczyną faz przestępstwa odnośnie do świadków jest nienależne informowanie organów ścigania przez nieobecność zaufania ludności do państwowych instytucji, które powołane walczyć z przestępczością.

Słowa kluczowe: przestępstwo, kryminalne prowadzenie, świadek, pokazy, zagrożenie, groźba, gwałt.

CRIMINAL TENDENCIES ARE IN RELATION TO WITNESSES IN UKRAINE

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Abstract. On the basis of analysis of statistical indexes that characterize a criminogenic situation in Ukraine, state of fight against criminality, the forms of counteraction to law enforcement authorities and generalization of scientific results of home on foreign researchers are well-proven presence of making progress tendency to the actual increase of criminality in Ukraine. Reason of the marked dynamics is set, namely confidence of criminals in impunity through insolvency of public organs and law-enforcement system effectively to counteract to criminality. A witness continues to occupy a basic place in the system of proofs and finishing telling in criminal realization and consequently, yields to unlawful influence from the side of disinterested persons in just and legal pre-trial investigation and criminal rule-making. The forms of unlawful influence on a witness are elected depending on the circumstances of crime, and their results directly influence on plenitude and objectivity of establishment of truth in criminal realization. Characteristic threats are certain to the witness in Ukraine in connection with implementation last of judicial rights and duties in criminal realization. It is well-proven that principal reason of latentness of the stages of crime in relation to witnesses

is the improper informing of law enforcement authorities for lack of trust of population to the state institutes, what called to contest with criminality.

Keywords: crime, criminal realization, witness, shows, threat, threat, violence.

ЗЛОЧИННІ ТЕНДЕНЦІЇ СТОСОВНО СВІДКІВ В УКРАЇНІ

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Анотація. На основі аналізу статистичних показників, що характеризують криміногенну ситуацію в Україні, стан боротьби зі злочинністю, форми протидії правоохоронним органам та узагальнення наукових результатів вітчизняних та зарубіжних дослідників доведено наявність прогресуючої тенденції до фактичного збільшення злочинності в Україні. Встановлено причину зазначеної динаміки, а саме впевненість злочинців у безкарності через неспроможність державних органів та правоохоронної системи ефективно протидіяти злочинності. Свідок продовжує займати основне місце в системі доказів та доказування у кримінальному провадженні, а, відтак, піддається протиправному впливу зі сторони незацікавлених осіб у справедливому та законному досудовому розслідуванні та кримінальному судочинстві. Форми протиправного впливу на свідка обираються залежно від обставин злочину, а їх результати безпосередньо впливають на повноту та об'єктивність встановлення істини у кримінальному провадженні. Визначено характерні загрози свідку в Україні у зв'язку із виконанням останнім процесуальних прав і обов'язків у кримінальному провадженні. Доведено, що основною причиною латентності стадій злочину стосовно свідків є неналежне інформування правоохоронних органів через відсутність довіри населення до державних інституцій, які покликані боротися із злочинністю.

Ключові слова: злочин, кримінальне провадження, свідок, покази, загроза, погроза, насильство.

Introduction. Socio-legal disorganization of the rule of law in society causes not only serious changes in the quantitative indicators of crime, but also prompts the transformation of its structure by increasing the proportion of violent encroachments, as well as criminal offenses aimed at counteracting the establishment of legal justice in Ukraine. Of particular concern is the demoralizing effect caused by the mentioned encroachments not only on the participants in criminal proceedings and legal proceedings, law enforcement officers, but also on active representatives of the population who are indifferent to the public position in the fight against crime. The spread of crime, and especially of its dangerous forms, such as terrorism, murder, robbery, drug trafficking, trafficking in human beings, weapons, etc., causes a legitimate concern for every citizen, the psycho-physiological tension of a person that interferes with normal work, social communication and rest. We emphasize that any danger causes a person to be in need of protection.

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M. Kurkin, T. Kurovska, M. Levitskaya, T. Lidovets, E. Lukianchikov, I. Malyutin, V. Malyarenko, V. Marinov, A. Matveev, V. Morgun, V. Nor, E. Orishchenko, T. Panasyuk, T. Patsalova, S. Pashkov, N. Pelipenko, V. Pentegov, I. Petrukhin, M. Polyakov, V. Savchenko, M. Svirin, G. Sereda, A. Sizonenko, V. Smirsky, M. Starchikov, V. Stratonov, I. Stokov, A. Strutts, R. Tragniuk, V. Uvarov, L. Udalova, A. Usenko, M. Tsakhlo, V. Chornous, I. Schwab, L. Shestopalova, R. Shehavitsov, O. Shilo, D. Shilova, T. Shimko, V. Shkarupa, A. Shpotakivska, M. Shumylo, L. Shcherbyna. However, this problem has not yet been properly addressed.

The purpose of the article is to reveal the forms and content of criminal tendencies in relation to witnesses in Ukraine, which affect the completeness and objectivity of the implementation and enforcement of the last procedural rights and obligations in criminal proceedings.

Main part. The realization of this goal involves the consistent solution of such tasks - to generalize and characterize threats to the witness as a participant in criminal proceedings, taking into account current criminal tendencies and the criminal situation in general in Ukraine.

Taking into account the topic of research, goals and objectives, the following methods have been used, in particular, the dialectical method has allowed to consider all components of the problems in the dynamics, to reveal their interconnection and interdependence and contributed to the understanding of the relevance of the research; the dialectical method contributed to the knowledge of the unlawful tendencies regarding the influence on the witness; the systematic method determines the structuring of the threats of the witness; logical-legal method was used to deepen the understanding of the conceptual apparatus of the study; the statistical method summarizes the data of operative and investigative practice, and the sociological method was used during the questioning and analysis of the survey materials of the employees of the operational units and the organs of the pre-trial investigation of the National Police.

Materials of the presented research contain the scientific and theoretical background, which consists of scientific works of domestic and foreign specialists in the field of criminal procedural, criminal law, operative-search activity, legal statistics, criminalistics, criminology, psychology, other branch legal sciences; the normative basis, which is based on the provisions of the Constitution of Ukraine, the Criminal Code of Ukraine, the Criminal Procedure Code of Ukraine, current legislative and sub-normative legal acts defining criminal-law, criminal-procedural, forensic, operative-and-search basis for the protection of witnesses; an empirical basis consisting of the results of the generalization of the operational police, the official and investigative practice of the units of the National Police, the official statistics of the General Prosecutor's Office and the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine for 2012-2018, the actual data of the survey materials of the territorial units of the National Security Police, the results of the questionnaire 100 investigators and officers of the operational units of the National Police of Lviv, Volyn, Rivne, Ternopil, Ivano-Frankivsk regions and the results of the analysis of materials of 100 criminal proceedings and 15 cases of operational proceedings.

One of the important conditions for solving the problems of criminal proceedings is to ensure the implementation of procedural rights with a witness, which is extremely problematic when a person is intimidated and impossible in the event of death of the latter. The activity of counteraction to criminal proceedings in the form of unlawful

influence on its participants is confirmed by statistics of crimes against justice, in particular, in 2016, registered: 506 crimes under st.383 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine; 637 - under art. 384 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine; 23 - for art. 385 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine; 56 - for art. 386 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine. Over the past four years, 3 facts were registered in the Unified Register of Pre-trial Investigations on the basis of Art. 380 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine; 7 - on the grounds of Art. 381 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine; 80 - on the grounds of Art. 387 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine; 27 - for art. 129 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine (threat of killing witnesses). In some cases, there were 2 murder cases, 11 - bodily injuries (varying degrees) of witnesses (*Yedynyj zvit GPU, 2017*).

At the beginning of 2017, long-term protection measures were carried out in Ukraine for about 300 people (only over a quarter are employees of the court or law enforcement agencies) (*Zastosuvannya zasobiv zahystu osib, 2017, s.8*). State witness protection continues to be one of the constitutional guarantees of ensuring the administration of justice and the inevitability of punishment. The share of crime prevention offenses against witnesses in the structure of criminal tendencies is relatively small, however, law enforcement agencies annually register more and more such cases, which mostly remain unpunished. The necessity of improving the state system in this area is practically simultaneously confirmed by representatives of the General Prosecutor's Office, the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the Security Service of Ukraine, and public experts. An example of the failure to protect a witness is the fact of the assassination of Denis Voronenkov, an ex-deputy of the State Duma of the Russian Federation, a citizen of Russia and Ukraine, which clearly demonstrated the criminal self-confidence and negligence of Ukrainian law enforcement agencies in the field of securing valuable witnesses. And this is a negative signal for anyone who is potentially willing to cooperate with the investigation authorities and testify against the perpetrators (*Nevdalyj zahyst Denysa Voronenkova, 2017, s. 1*).

During 2016, in Ukraine law enforcement agencies registered 1124401 criminal offenses. Almost every second registered criminal offense has taken a decision to close criminal proceedings under rehabilitation conditions, that is, in the absence of an event or a crime, or a person's involvement in its implementation, in 531797 cases, or 47.3% (for comparison: in 2015 - in 528132 (48.3%), in 2014 - in 608297 (53.5%), and in 2013 - in 989496 (63.6%)) (*Analysts stan zlochynnosti, struktury i dynamiky za 2013-2016 rr ., s. 1 to 2*). In 2015, in Lviv region, 254 criminal proceedings were filed against 249 law enforcement officers, of which: 193 were the Internal Affairs (National Police) of Ukraine; Prosecutor's Office - 11; Security Service of Ukraine - 1; State Tax Service - 21; State Customs Service - 13; State Penitentiary Service - 10; employees of other law-enforcement agencies - 5. Analysis of criminal-qualification features the following: abuse of power or official position (Article 364 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine) - 42 proceedings; excess of authority or official position (Article 365 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine) - 63; service negligence (Article 367 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine) - 22; 28 - related to unlawful benefits (Articles 368-370 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine); 32 - other crimes in the sphere of official activity. The most typical ways of avoiding the pre-trial investigation of the said crimes are as follows: five criminal proceedings (paragraph 1 of Article 280 of the CPC of Ukraine) were suspended for suspect's illness, six proceedings were suspended (paragraph 2 of Article 280 of the CPC of Ukraine) for not establishing the location of the suspect, evasion of the suspect from the investigation;

refusal to apply preventive measure - detention: refusal by the prosecutors to support the petition - 7 cases; refusal of the court from taking from the guard - 8; Cancellation by the Court of Appeal of a court decision on detention - 13 (*Zvitnist`orgiv dosudovogo rozsliduvannya, 2015 r., p. 2-6*).

According to the polls of prosecutors and investigators, 40% of the crimes against life and health of the person had an unlawful influence on the witnesses. It was committed in the following forms: 43% - violence; 8% - threat of disclosure of information; 24% - bribing. As a result of such actions, about 30% of people changed their testimony and up to 30% avoided participating in criminal proceedings (*Blazhivs`ky`j, Yaky`mchuk, Koz`yakov, Turkot, 2014, p. 208*). The actual questioning of police officers made it clear that 37% of respondents considered a high level of counteraction to the investigation of criminal offenses, and 29% - low. 73% of the respondents claim high level of latency of crimes against participants in criminal proceedings and legal proceedings, and 63% - as witnesses in criminal proceedings. At the same time, the typical forms of counteraction to the investigation of crimes, which are most commonly encountered in practice, 63% of respondents consider the various corruption influences on participants in criminal proceedings; 34% - other unlawful (physical, psychological) influences. In the investigation (accompaniment) of crimes against life and health, the following forms of unlawful influence on a witness were most commonly encountered: a threat to the health of a witness (51%), a threat to the life of a witness (25%), bribing a witness (4%); in the investigation (accompaniment) of crime in the field of official activity - bribing a witness (87%), a threat to the health of a witness (7%), a threat to the life of a witness (2%); in the investigation (accompaniment) of crimes in the field of economic activity - bribing a witness (76%), a threat to the health of a witness (7%), a threat to the life of a witness (3%); in the investigation (accompaniment) of crimes in the sphere of drug trafficking - a threat to the health of a witness (81%), bribing a witness (6%), a threat to the life of a witness (5%); in the investigation (accompaniment) of crimes committed by organized groups, a threat to the health of a witness (49%), a threat to the life of a witness (23%), bribing a witness (8%).

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crime in the field of official activity - bribing a witness (87%), a threat to the health of a witness (7%), a threat to the life of a witness (2%); in the investigation (accompaniment) of crimes in the field of economic activity - bribing a witness (76%), a threat to the health of a witness (7%), a threat to the life of a witness (3%); in the investigation (accompaniment) of crimes in the sphere of drug trafficking - a threat to the health of a witness (81%), bribing a witness (6%), a threat to the life of a witness (5%); in the investigation (accompaniment) of crimes committed by organized groups, □ a threat to the health of a witness (49%), a threat to the life of a witness (23%), bribing a witness (8%).

Earlier, the researchers found that sources of information for criminals on the process of investigation of crimes, distributed as follows: former law enforcement officers - 53%; mass media - 43%; previously convicted - 35%; employees of operational divisions - 15%; investigators - 14%; lawyers - 30%; former investigators - 22%; other law enforcement officers - 38%; criminals who independently exposed methods of operative-search activity - 11%; comrades, friends, relatives - 6%; inevitable carrying out of operational measures - 12% (Bednyakov, 1991, s. 73). In most cases (80%) witnesses refuse to testify because of the use of physical and psychological influence of criminals (their surroundings) and corrupt investigators, prosecutors and judicial authorities. Society does not deny the fact that representatives of different levels of law-enforcement bodies have significant powers and information capabilities that they can be familiar with all investigative (investigatory) investigations conducted to expose guilty people and exercise state influence over them. In addition, knowledge of operative and investigative practices allows them to influence the course of the investigation and to create separate problems with such investigative actions as interrogation, search, arrest of bank accounts, etc. (Xaly'kov, 2011, s. 336).

The main reasons that adversely affect the rapid, complete and unbiased investigation of crimes and the adoption of objective judgments are, at present, the presence of pressure from criminals and their environment on participants in criminal proceedings to conceal unlawful acts known to witnesses or eyewitnesses, forcing them to give false impressions or to abandon evidence altogether. According to the results of the poll of police officers, the main objective of countering the investigation of crimes is the closure of criminal proceedings (52%), the deliberate failure to establish a crime organizer and bring to justice the perpetrators of a crime (37%), stop the pre-trial investigation (11%). Often, the result of the unlawful influence on the witness is the change or refusal to give testimony (92%), the physical neutralization of the witness (2%) rarely happens.

In the context of the threatening state of crime and changes in its nature, the widespread way of counteracting the investigation is the unlawful influence on witnesses, which became a norm that significantly affects the level of public confidence in law enforcement agencies, creates real prerequisites for the growth of latent crime (Panasyuk, 2009, s.) At the same time, according to own research, the main motive, which most contributes to the diligent fulfillment by the person of the procedural duties of a witness, is the desire to punish a crime against a close person (92%), very rarely - belief in justice (3%). Today witnesses are one of the most widespread sources of evidence in criminal proceedings and legal proceedings, despite the fact that for a long time it has been thought that such a way of establishing truth is imperfect. It is the willingness of witnesses to assist in the investigation is a vital element of its

effectiveness (Kovalenko, 2006, s. 362). A witness as a participant in criminal justice plays a crucial role in solving one of the priority tasks of criminal justice - establishing the truth and restoring the picture of the accomplished (Babeczky, 2017, s. 19). Despite the use in the procedure of evidence of material evidence and documents, expert opinions, the results of the review of the place of the event and the investigator of the experiment - evidence that reproduce the objective picture and less subject to change, the main source of evidence base remains and will remain the testimony of witnesses (Poxod`ko, Miroshny`chenko, 2013, s. 217).

The Criminal Procedural Code of Ukraine (Article 65) states that a witness is an individual who knows or may be known circumstances that are subject to proving in the course of criminal proceedings and which is called for giving testimony (Kry`minal`ny`j procesual`ny`j Code, 2017, s. 47). Evidence of witnesses belongs to the category of "valuable evidence" that reflects the personality of the participant in the criminal process, which in turn affects the process of forming testimony and the possibility of obtaining, verifying and using the investigator in the process of proof. A witness is a participant in a criminal process that does not have the status of a victim, accused, suspect, and who knows any circumstances that are subject to establishment in the case, and there are no circumstances that exclude the possibility of his interrogation. Any citizen of Ukraine, if he became an eyewitness of the investigated event, regardless of his position (prosecutor, head of local administration, judge, president of the state, etc.) can be questioned as a witness. A person who knows any circumstances in the case must be questioned as a witness and may not have a different procedural status other than being a witness (Terty`shny`k, 2014, s. 296). A witness as a procedural person is "generated" by the very fact of a crime, and therefore it is irreplaceable. A person called by an investigator, prosecutor or court, as a witness, is required to appear in the specified place and time and give true evidence of circumstances known to her in the case (Article 67 of the CPC of Ukraine). For the refusal to testify and for giving knowingly false testimony, the witness bears criminal responsibility (Articles 384, 385 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine) (Nastil`na kny`ga slidchogo, 2011, s. 638). The witness has constitutional rights (Article 63 of the Constitution of Ukraine) and is not responsible for refusing to testify or explain his or her family members or close relatives circle determined by law. An investigator, a prosecutor and a court before interrogation of such persons are obliged to explain to them the right to refuse to testify, as indicated in the minutes of the interrogation or in the journal of the court session (Sloyny`k yury`dy`chny`x terminiv i ponyat, 2013, s. 484-448). A witness is constantly under the influence of psychological, mental and physical stress. The presence of factors of extreme, deformation under the influence of external morality is required from a person of solid self-discipline, a developed sense of duty.

However, in practice, widespread cases of witnesses use or threaten to use physical or psychological violence to change testimony in favor of a suspect (accused) or even even to refuse to give testimony. Such pressure can be carried out not only on the part of the accused; law enforcement agencies sometimes also resort to unlawful influence on these participants in the criminal process. Often, fearful of unlawful influence, witnesses either refuse to testify or give knowingly false testimony (Paczalova, 2006, s. 138). Forms of unlawful pressure on witnesses during the investigation of crimes are chosen depending on the circumstances. This is due to the existing criminal situation, the type of criminal activity, the establishment or non-

establishment of the law-enforcement bodies of the specific circumstances of the criminal event, the taking of certain persons in custody, etc. (Shhur, 2005, p.25).

According to separate investigations of the current activity of investigating authorities, in most cases there are situations where witnesses refuse to testify or evade procedural actions, change their previous testimonies, provide incomplete or insufficiently clear indications in view of the actual or potential threat of application in the course of criminal proceedings to them, members of their families, close relatives of violence or other forms of unlawful influence on the part of interested persons (Orlean, 2016, p. 87). Forms of counteraction to the investigation of crimes are expressed in coercion to give false testimonies, to suppress known facts, to refuse to testify (Raty`nov, 1967, s. 167), to conceal crimes by destroying the ideal (people) sources of information about a crime (Ovechky`n, 1975 , s. 5), deliberate unlawful activity on the psychological or physical influence on witnesses, victims and other participants in the criminal process in order to interfere with the resolution of the tasks of the investigation (Belky`n, 1997, s. 129), the terrorization of witnesses, victims and their relatives, physical elimination witnesses and victims in order to force them to refuse to testify or to change earlier the evidence (Mizhnarodna policejs`ka ency`klopediya, 2009, s. 810), the use of threats and the use of physical and mental violence, which are extreme methods related to threats and real physical impact, as well as the physical elimination of certain individuals. These methods can be applied to all participants in criminal proceedings, including to witnesses.

Consequently, investigative and judicial practice confirms that today witnesses use different forms of violence, both physical and mental. Physical abuse includes beatings, bodily injuries, torture; to mental violence - intimidation and threats. The threat is ñ a kind of mental violence, which represents a gross promise to cause any evil, trouble. Threats to murder, causing serious bodily harm, destruction of property - are the most dangerous types of threats that are a serious crime and punishable in a criminal way (Bilenchuk, Kurko, OstroLucz`ky`j, 2015, s. 179).

Man (the same witness) lives in a society in which both social and legal injustice reigns. The unwillingness to assist law enforcement agencies is usually conditioned by the fact that the witness as a participant in the criminal process does not believe in the effectiveness of his participation in the case; does not believe that the guilty will bear responsibility; seeks to avoid the negative consequences associated with the duties of witnesses (the loss of time due to repeated calls to inconvenient time, feelings, discomfort in connection with the need to be distracted from ordinary occupations, excitement at interrogations, the need to expose the perpetrators, fear of revenge, etc.); afraid to be alert in business; is afraid of unjustified and incorrect treatment by law enforcement officers (multiple, without valid reasons, long-term and long-awaited expectations, neglect of his official and family duties, disrespectful tone, etc.); knows about the insufficiently high authority of investigative and judicial bodies, etc. (Raty`nov, Adamov, 1976, s. 42-43). This is only part of the problems that people are forced to survive and try to decide when living in a society. In this regard, the main component of ensuring the safety of persons involved in criminal proceedings and legal proceedings is the implementation by law enforcement agencies of measures aimed at protecting the life, health, housing and property of individuals from unlawful encroachment, in order to create the necessary conditions for proper administration of justice. In addition, when analyzing the motives for providing false testimony to the

employee of the operational unit (investigator, prosecutor), it is necessary to draw attention to the fact that the formation of their material often occurs in critical situations that cause a person with strong emotional reactions. A peculiar form of such a reaction is tension and confusion. A person who has witnessed a crime, in particular, a violent one, is in a state of tension, but all its mental processes seem to be inhibited (Psy`xologiya slidchoyi diyal`nosti, 2009, s. 157). Awareness of danger is a fear in man. Fear is a state of excitement, anxiety, anxiety, caused by the expectation of something unpleasant, undesirable (Suchasny`j tlumachny`j slovny`k, 2008, s. 835). Fear can have a different effect on the process of witnessing testimony. In some cases, under the influence of fear, events are perceived with exaggeration, distorted, in others they are badly or not memorized at all, and in the third, they are perceived and evaluated correctly, adequately (Psy`xologiya slidchoyi diyal`nosti, 2009, s. 158). The fear is objectively caused by individual threats to the life and health of the witness's face. The term "threat" has several interpretations, in particular: a rough, decisive promise to inflict some kind of evil and trouble; threats, praise; possibility or inevitability of occurrence of something dangerous, annoying; something that can cause some kind of evil, trouble, danger (synonym - a threat) (*Slovny`k yury`dy`chny`x terminiv i ponyat`*, 2013, p. 303). The threat as an external factor of danger for a person takes into account his particular psychological state (*Zelenecz`ky`j, Kurkin, 2004, p. 26*). A characteristic feature of danger is a particular threat to a particular person (witness), members of his family, close relatives in connection with the possibility of depriving them of their lives, causing damage to their health, destroying property, belonging to their home or other values and goods.

The analysis of data obtained by human rights organizations in 2015 shows that mental violence in the form of threats against witnesses and their relatives remains an integral part of the work of law enforcement officers themselves, but its scale has decreased compared to 2010. Thus, in 2015, 14 cases of blackmail were revealed. he became a witness, and 59 - when his friend, relative, was the victim. Regarding the amount of intimidation, threats from law enforcement officers themselves, the study revealed 119 cases (8 per cent for witnesses and 111 for relatives and relatives). The same is true of cases of abuse and humiliation, - 182 cases (9 - for witnesses and 173 - relatives and relatives) (*Monitory`ng nezakonnogo nasy`l`stva v organax vnutrishnix sprav Ukrayiny`*, 2015, p. 26). The same tendency was reflected in the estimated number of people who were victims of torture during the investigation. According to data from the survey, in 2011 their number exceeded 100 thousand. In 2015, the number of those against whom the torture was used during the investigation decreased to 62 thousand (*Monitory`ng nezakonnogo nasy`l`stva v organax vnutrishnix sprav Ukrayiny`*, 2015, s. 28). It can be noted that anyone is not insured from violence. Thus, if, in general, 55.5% of the respondents indicated that they were subjected to psychological violence, those who were delivered by police to the suspect's status, such 73.5%, invited as a witness - 56.7%, were in a temporary detention center - 60.0%, He was in a detention center - 57.6% (*Monitory`ng nezakonnogo nasy`l`stva v organax vnutrishnix sprav Ukrayiny`*, 2015, p. 40).

During the investigation of crimes, there are threats to the participants in the criminal proceedings. Threats come in different directions: murder, beating, damage or destruction of property, rape, distribution of confidential information about a person - object of influence, etc. They may concern both the participants in the criminal

proceedings, and their relatives and relatives. The most diverse forms of notification are: oral warning, anonymous phone calls, letters, notes, SMS or Internet messages, etc. Sometimes criminals or their followers use more sophisticated methods of transmitting information to subjects of influence, for example, for a long time several people are near the house (apartments of a participant in criminal proceedings) and are observing or accompanying the person without any communication with her. Gestures and facial expressions may be used to convey the threat - this is especially true during investigative actions in which a participant directly contacts a potential source of threat, for example, during simultaneous interrogations of two or more interrogated persons or the identification of suspects can warn the witness to be invisible to the investigator's gestures, a threatening smile, a glance to express danger, to use encoded in content, but understandable to the potential victim of a word, sentence, mention of certain names of people, etc. Thus, we can talk about specific threats, the forms of expression of which can be documented (oral statement, letter, telephone call, note, etc.) and which themselves contain signs of a separate crime, for example, the threat of murder (Article 129 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine) or the destruction of property (Article 195 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine). But there are threats and uncertainties that are expressed in forms that do not imply any legal liability, such as threats with gestures, facial expressions or eyesight. Such methods of influence are quite difficult to oppose anything. Scientists point out that the threat of murder involves intimidation (oral, written, gesture, demonstration of weapons or other dangerous items, etc.) of another person who perceives this threat as concrete and real, which can be realized at any moment or in the near future. To accurately assess the reality of the threat, it needs to be established that the victim or the person present at that time had all the necessary grounds to fear its implementation. It should take into account the degree of perception of the threat to the victim, the way, character, place, time, atmosphere and intensity of her statement, the nature of the previous relationship between the guilty and victim (Naukovo-prakty`chny`j comment Kry`minal`nogo Code Ukrayiny`, 2017, s. 313). To threaten the destruction of property, it is necessary to attribute the actions of the suspect, which consist in clear or written communications (Internet mail, SMS, demonstration of the Molotov cocktail, etc.), the facts must really confirm the intention of another person to be immediate or something that may happen in the near future, the destruction of certain property, which is alien to the guilty. In this case, the victim should perceive such influence as real and concrete, that is, it should have all the real reasons to fear the implementation of this threat (Naukovo-prakty`chny`j comment Kry`minal`nogo Code Ukrayiny`, 2017, s. 443). At the same time, danger is understood as the threat of causing someone to harm or condition when someone is in danger (*Kun`ch, 2007, s 488; Ozhegov, 1973, p. 413*).

The consequence of the assessment by the scientists of the normative design that determines the grounds for the application of security measures to the participants in the criminal proceedings, the generalization of the practice of applying security measures in criminal proceedings, is based on the conclusion that the lawmakers are not quite right in the possibility of taking security measures only in the presence of a "real" threat to a person, since in practice, cases where such a danger is probable, for example, in cases of investigation and judicial review of criminal a violation committed by an organized criminal group whose members used physical and psychological violence against people; in the presence of a criminal prosecution only one witness who directly

perceived the event of a criminal offense and can actually reproduce the picture of the offender; if one of the suspects unlike the other agreed to cooperate with the investigator, the prosecutor for the purpose of revealing the crime; in a situation where a person who committed a criminal offense has previously been prosecuted for unlawful influence on the participants in criminal proceedings, or measures to ensure criminal proceedings have been applied to prevent the unlawful pressure on the subjects of the criminal process (*Kachmar, 2017, p. 16*).

It is also important to note that, at a minimum, there are two entities assessing the existence of a threat: 1) the person against whom it is directed; 2) an official or a body that decides on the need for security measures. And, as practice shows, for the most part, it (evaluation) of these subjects is significantly different, or even is diametrically opposed (*Kry`minal`no-procesual`ny`j kodak Ukrayiny`, 2003, s. 56*). The insecurity of individuals acting in the interests of justice or capable of contributing to the establishment of truth in the case induces them to refrain from fulfilling their civic duty (*Suxars`ky`j, Fedorova, 2007, s. 208*). Ensuring the security of the subjects (participants) of the criminal process is aimed at the effective implementation of their functions and the fulfillment of the tasks of legal proceedings (*Gry`n`kiv, 2009, s. 123*), that is, the creation of the necessary conditions for the proper administration of justice (*Lobjko, 2005, p. 125*).

Conclusions.

In a criminal proceeding, a witness is often exposed to unlawful influence, and the form of threat, the probability of its implementation, the subjects of execution directly depend on the criminal-legal qualification of the investigated act and the social status of persons involved in the crime (criminal offense). The forms of threats of the witness are diverse: from the simplest psychological threats, up to the murder. The reaction of a witness to a threat depends on his social and psychophysiological state.

Given the complex criminal situation in Ukraine, any threats to the witness by law enforcement agencies should be considered with high probability, as the result of such influence may be an inevitable harm to human health and life. Therefore, the problem of the effectiveness of ensuring the guarantees of the rights and obligations of a witness, their compliance with current criminal tendencies is one of the topical theoretical and practical organizational and legal problems, since without the existence of adequate guarantees the idea of deterring the growth of organized crime in Ukraine loses its meaning and the tasks of the law-enforcement system remain empty. idealistic declarations. And this state of affairs is considered a direct threat to the national security of society and the state as a whole at the level of the military aggression of the Russian Federation and corruption in Ukraine. Therefore, one of the priority directions of the state in the areas of ensuring legal justice and reforming law enforcement bodies should be the legislative introduction into Ukraine of the National Strategy in the form of long-term state organizational-legal and financial mechanisms for ensuring the participants of criminal proceedings.

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WYKORZYSTANIE WIEDZY SPECJALNEJ W RAMACH DOCHODZENIA PRZESTĘPSTW, POPEŁNIONYCH W INSTYTUCJACH PENITENCJARNYCH UKRAINY

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Streszczenie. W przepisach artykułu naukowego autor bada możliwości wykorzystania wiedzy specjalnej podczas dochodzenia przestępstw, popełnionych w instytucjach penitencjarnych Ukrainy. Przeprowadza analizę w naukach kryminalistycznych proceduralne i nieproceduralne formy wykorzystania specjalnej wiedzy podczas dochodzenia przestępstw popełnionych w instytucjach penitencjarnych, opisuje podmioty wykorzystania specjalnej wiedzy w instytucjach penitencjarnych Ukrainy i ujawnia specyfikę wykorzystania przez podmioty specjalnej wiedzy podczas dochodzenia przestępstw, popełnionych w instytucjach penitencjarnych Ukrainy i proponuje autorską metodę udoskonalenia przepisów obecnego Kodeksu Postępowania Karnego Ukrainy w części uzupełnień definicją pojęcia wiedzy specjalnej.

Słowa kluczowe: przestępstwo, kryminalistyka, wiedza specjalna, instytucje penitencjarne, specjalista, ekspert, środki techniczne, nagrywanie wideo, urządzenia do wyszukiwania.

APPLYING SPECIAL KNOWLEDGE TO INVESTIGATING CRIMES COMMITTED IN PUNISHMENT EXECUTION INSTITUTIONS OF UKRAINE

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Annotation. In the provisions of the scientific article the author examines the possibilities of applying special knowledge to investigating crimes committed in punishment execution institutions of Ukraine, analyzes in criminal law procedural and non-procedural forms of applying special knowledge to investigating crimes committed in punishment execution institutions of Ukraine, characterizes subjects of applying special knowledge to investigating in PEI of Ukraine, discovers the peculiarities of subjects' applying special knowledge to investigating crimes committed in PEI of Ukraine and suggests the author's way of improving the provisions of the current Criminal Procedural Code of Ukraine in the part of the supplement by the concept 'special knowledge'.

Key words: crime, criminal law, special knowledge, punishment execution institutions, specialist, expert, technical means, video recording, search devices.

ВИКОРИСТАННЯ СПЕЦІАЛЬНИХ ЗНАТЬ ПРИ РОЗСЛІДУВАННІ ЗЛОЧИНІВ, ВЧИНЕНИХ В УСТАНОВАХ ВИКОНАННЯ ПОКАРАНЬ УКРАЇНИ

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Анотація. У положеннях наукової статті автор досліджує можливості використання спеціальних знань при розслідуванні злочинів вчинених в установах виконання покарань України. Проводить аналізувати у науці криміналістиці процесуальних та не процесуальних форм використання спеціальних знань при розслідуванні злочинів вчинених в УВП, характеризує суб'єктів використання спеціальних знань в УВП України та розкриває особливості використання суб'єктами спеціальних знань при розслідуванні злочинів вчинених в УВП України та пропонує авторські шлях удосконалення положень чинного Кримінального процесуального кодексу України в частині доповнення визначенням поняття спеціальні знання.

Ключові слова: злочин, криміналістика, спеціальні знання, установи виконання покарань, спеціаліст, експерт, технічні засоби, відео зйомка, пошукові прилади.

Setting the problem in general and its connection with important scientific or practical tasks. In the process of solving and investigating crimes in punishment execution institutions (further – PEI) specific knowledge, skills and abilities are required for the people who conduct investigation, which they often lack. For this reason other people possessing special knowledge are involved in the process of investigation, they are as a rule: a specialist, an interpreter, an expert, a teacher, a psychologist, a doctor. It is reasonable to mention that the end of 2012 in Ukraine is marked with active discussions among scientists, practical lawyers and other interested public representatives, concerning the new Criminal Procedural Code of Ukraine (further – CPC), adopted in April 2012 by the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine coming into force. It is the very procedural law that changes fundamentally the system of criminal proceedings of Ukraine and can become a guide of further reforming legal system in the part of procedural legislation, the system of law enforcement bodies, judges and other fields of public relations, aimed at the most efficient ensuring protection of constitutional rights and freedoms of a man and a citizen. In the new CPC the approaches to application of experienced people's special knowledge as an evidence source have also changed, which offers the sides of criminal proceedings much more possibilities of its application in proofs of forensic examination institution (*Tkachenko N.M.*). In our opinion, it should be marked that the concept 'special knowledge' nowadays is of debatable character. It is promoted by lack of legislative definition of the 'special knowledge' concept in CPC of Ukraine, where the legislator indicates only the purpose and the subject of special knowledge application.

A lot of national and foreign scientists – proceduralists and criminalists devoted their works to studying the problems of special knowledge application. They include V.D. Arseniev, V.P. Bakhin, I.V. Basysta, R.S. Bielkin, T.V. Varfolomiyeva, A.I. Vinberg, V.G. Goncharenko, I.V. Hora, O.M. Zinin, A.V. Ishchenko, V.Ya.Koldin, N.I.Klymenko, V.A.Kolesnyk, V.K. Lysychenko, V.M. Makhov, Yu.K. Orlov,

I.L. Petrukhin, O.R. Rossynska, M.Ya. Segai, T.V. Sakhnova, O.V. Selina, S.A. Sheyfer, O.R. Shliakhov, O.O. Eisman, M.P. Yablokov and others.

Formulating the purposes of the article (setting the task). Our research is aimed at discovering and studying the possibilities of special knowledge application to investigating crimes committed in PEI of Ukraine. According to the purpose set research tasks are as follows: analysis of establishing in criminal law procedural and non-procedural forms of applying special knowledge to investigating crimes committed in PEI of Ukraine; characteristics of subjects of applying special knowledge to investigating crimes committed in PEI of Ukraine; discovering the peculiarities of subjects' applying special knowledge to investigating crimes committed in PEI of Ukraine; suggesting the author's way of improving the provisions of the current Criminal Procedural Code of Ukraine in the part of the supplement by the concept 'special knowledge'.

Presenting main material. As professor N.I. Klymenko rightly observes, the main thing in the development of forensic tactics is applying modern forensic knowledge to investigatory and forensic practice, for the knowledge an investigator and an expert possess is valuable only when they are used in practical activity (*Klymenko N.I., 2010, p.28*). We believe it is worth agreeing to professor I.V. Basysta's point of view that nowadays the expert in criminal proceeding can be called a person possessing special knowledge and skills of using technical or other means, who can give consultations concerning the problems requiring appropriate special knowledge and skills during pre-trial investigation and trial (*Basysta I.V., Tulyk Kh.I., 2017, p.24*). However, the analysis of the above mentioned opinions of the leading scientists criminalists enable to make a conclusion that there is no clear definition of 'special knowledge' concept on either legislative or scientific and doctrinal level. The current Criminal Procedural legislation of Ukraine that does not reveal the content of 'special knowledge' concept proves it. Articles 69 and 71 of CPC of Ukraine say about using scientific, technical or other special knowledge and skills. (*Criminal Procedural Code of Ukraine*).

In our view, special knowledge implies acquired knowledge, skills and abilities which are constantly improving and are used in any field of human activity, gained in the process of special education, experience and practical activity (except for professional knowledge of the people solving and investigating crimes), necessary for quick and full crime solution and investigation, as well as for considering a case in court.

Professor I.V. Hora notes quite accurately, that forensic and procedural literature distinguishes procedural and non-procedural forms of using special knowledge. In our opinion, such a criterion as an evidence of the result of applying special knowledge to pre-trial investigation and considering criminal proceeding materials should be the basis of dividing forms of applying special knowledge to criminal legal proceedings (*Hora I.V., 2013, p.211*). Special knowledge in solving and investigating crimes in PEI is also used in two forms: procedural and non-procedural.

The procedural form of applying special knowledge to investigating crimes committed in PEI of Ukraine is regulated by the norms of Criminal Procedural Code of Ukraine. The procedural form of applying special knowledge in PEI includes: participation of a specialist in investigatory actions for promoting to detect, withdraw, fix and study evidence, forensic examination, participation of a teacher, psychologist or a doctor during cross-examination of juveniles or minors.

The non-procedural form of applying special knowledge in PEI is a legal system of rules which does not contradict the law, but is not established in CPC of Ukraine, and it concerns applying special knowledge to investigating a crime and trying a case at the initial and the next stages. The non-procedural form of applying special knowledge in PEI includes particularly specialist's consultation, operational research.

Main purpose of applying non-procedural forms of special knowledge in correctional institution consists in investigator's receiving from a specialist criminally important timely information enabling to choose correct order, time and place of taking procedural action, to select its participants, scientific and technical means, to choose tactical techniques and to correctly orientate in the current situation.

A consultation is a scientifically substantiated advice, given by a specialist (orally or in written form). For example, a specialist- criminalist in PEI can consult the person who investigates using these or other scientific and technical methods and means.

It should be mentioned that operational researches imply a form of specialist's assistance rendered to the person undertaking investigation in conducting different researches (criminalistic, chemical, biological, etc.), which are stated in the report.

For more detailed research of the problem concerning application of special knowledge to investigating crimes committed in PEI, we consider it to be worth characterizing the process of applying special knowledge by the subjects participating in investigating crimes in PEI more in detail.

First, it is expedient to begin with the analysis of such a subject of special knowledge as a specialist. A specialist in criminal proceedings is a person who possesses special knowledge and skills of using technical or other means and can give consultations during pre-trial investigation and trying a case requiring appropriate special knowledge and skills. A specialist can be involved in rendering direct technical assistance (photographing, making up schemes, plans, drafts, selecting samples for making examination, etc.) by the sides of criminal proceedings during pre-trial investigation and by the court during the trial. The sides of criminal proceedings have the right to solicit for involving a specialist or using his explanations and assistance (pp.1-3 art.71 CPC of Ukraine) (*Criminal Procedural Code of Ukraine*).

Procedural form of applying a specialist's special knowledge in PEI consists in specialist's participation in investigative actions. When conducting investigative actions in PEI, a specialist is involved, as a rule, in examining the place of an event, dead body, premises, objects and documents, in cross examining, in carrying out investigative experiment. Workers of expert subunits of Ministry of Internal Affairs, experts of forensic medical expert institutions, workers of medical service of PEI, teachers of PEI secondary and vocational schools can be specialists.

In a number of cases the law clearly requires compulsory participation of an expert of a definite field in conducting certain investigative actions. So, art.238 of CPC of Ukraine stipulates, that examining dead body by investigator or procurator requires participation of a forensic medical expert or a doctor, if it is impossible to involve a forensic medical expert in time; art.226 of CPC of Ukraine stipulates, that a juvenile or a minor is cross-examined in the presence of a legal representative, a teacher or a psychologist, if necessary – a doctor (*Criminal Procedural Code of Ukraine*).

Second, an interpreter is the next subject possessing special knowledge. As far as an interpreter in criminal proceedings is concerned, the analysis of provisions of CPC of Ukraine shows that an interpreter's participation depends on the stage of criminal

proceedings, investigator, procurator or trial on condition that the interested person enjoys his right to involve an interpreter, and there are grounds provided for by law. According to p.3 art.29 of CPC of Ukraine, the investigator, judge, court, procurator ensure the participants of criminal proceedings, who don't know or know the state language not enough, the right to give evidence, solicit, make complaints, speak at a trial in their mother tongue or any other language they know, using if necessary an interpreter's services by order provided for by this Code. According to p.1 art.68 of CPC of Ukraine, if the translation of explanations, evidence or documents is necessary in criminal proceedings, the sides of criminal proceedings or the investigator, judge or court involve the appropriate interpreter (surd-interpreter) (*Criminal Procedural Code of Ukraine*). It is worth mentioning that according to the data of investigative practice and our empiric research, an interpreter as a subject possessing special knowledge is not practically involved in investigating crimes committed in PEI (*Batiuk O.V., 2013, 320 p*).

Third, it is especially important to involve a specialist-criminalist in examining the place of event before entering the records in the Single Register of pre-trial investigations, when it is necessary to detect the imprints left in the place of event and fix them in proper time. So, the provisions of p.3 art.214 of CPC of Ukraine can be procedural grounds for applying special knowledge in this case. The given norm establishes as an exception the possibility of examining the place of event in urgent cases before entering the records in the Single Register of pre-trial investigations. Such records are entered just after the examination is completed.

Examining the place of event without involving a specialist-criminalist can result in loss of evidence because of a number of factors influencing the investigation of crimes in a correctional institution.

For example, a convict B. was visited by a convict S. in the room for meat processing and began claiming on returning debt out of time. Making sure that the convict B. cannot return the debt, S. made an attempt to take violent actions of sexual character. Being highly excited, B. gave several blows to the head of S. with the knife for meat processing, as a result, S. died of wounds on the spot. After that, aiming at hiding tracks of the crime, B. secretly took the dead body, hid in the snow and did away with the tracks of the crime. On the same day absence of S. was discovered, during check-up measures were taken to search the convict, including the examination of the correctional institution premises by colony workers, but they had no results.

In the course of examination the main task of a specialist-criminalist is revealing, fixing and withdrawing evidence. Other tasks are also performed together with this specialist-criminalist taking general tasks of examining the place of events into consideration.

We are convinced such tasks should include:

- helping the investigator to define the way of committing the crime and the criminal's actions;
- singling out the imprints and objects concerning the event investigated from all imprints and objects;
- conducting preliminary examining traces, objects, materials, substances, probably left by the criminal, for receiving researching information;
- eliciting the reasons and conditions promoting the crime;

- participating in summing up the examination aimed at suggesting versions directed towards solving and investigating crimes.

In our opinion, a specialist-criminalist establishes the way of committing a crime according to the results of detecting and examining imprints in the place of event. These traces enable to determine the type and character of the actions taken by a person. Knowing the way of committing a crime helps to determine the direction of searching other imprints and objects (for example, the fact of using firearms, seized from PEI workers or hand-made in PEI, determines the direction of shot place search, a person shooting, cartridge-case, etc.).

In most cases of committing crimes on PEI premises (dwelling or industrial area) a great amount of fingerprints and footprints are found during examination. We think the task of a specialist-criminalist is to single out those imprints which could be left by a criminal, taking the way of committing the crime and the character of actions into account.

Examining imprints and other objects in the place of event and the mechanism of their formation can give the information necessary for search "hot in the trail".

Taking part in investigative actions in PEI a specialist-criminalist very often uses means of fixation (photo-, cinema-, video equipment, tape-recorders), search devices, means of detecting and withdrawing fingerprints, footprints and other material evidence. As practice of studying PEI equipment (photo-, video devices) shows that there is no special criminalistic technology in the majority of PEI of Ukraine. Even if there is such, PEI workers make substantial mistakes when using it, lacking skills of operating it, laying the blame on technical device or component parts to it. For example, the following report is significant, which was made by a correctional institution worker, when examining the place of event: "In the course of examining the place of the event photos were taken, but it was impossible to develop the photos as the film turned out to be faulty".

Photographing to fix the course of investigative action a specialist-criminalist uses different methods and techniques in a correctional institution, the choice of which depends on the type of investigative action and condition of taking it.

Photographing in a correctional institution is used mostly when examining the place of event, aimed at discovering and fixing the information of circumstances of committing criminal offence. According to p.3 art.237 of CPC of Ukraine, the procurator can invite specialists to take part in examination, aimed at receiving assistance with the problems requiring special knowledge.

The record of investigative action indicates photographing. In addition to that, camera model, general view of the place of event, the type of lighting, the method of photographing, amount of photo taking is indicated.

Along with photographing in PEI, videoing is widely used to fix the course and result of investigative action. Application of video is especially pressing when examining the place of event, dead body. For example, videoing the place of event when investigating the escape case enables to make up a picture of events happened, and also to fix the situation of the place of event, and at the next stages of investigation to exclude the possibility of changing evidence by both crime witnesses and the accused.

Videoing in PEI is used to fix objects, phenomena in dynamics; to fix the process of discovering material evidence by an investigator and a specialist; to fix the objects of substantial extent, etc.

Video-recording as evidential means of fixing the course of investigative action is used by decision of the person conducting investigation, and all the participants of investigative action are reported about it (art.107 CPC of Ukraine) (*Criminal Procedural Code of Ukraine*).

Before examining the place of event, the person conducting investigation together with an expert-criminalist makes up the plan of examination in advance.

This plan must say what exactly will be fixed with the help of video-recording, succession of fixing main stages of investigative action, its episodes, objects, which need to be fixed. The plan also should take approximate points and methods of videoing into consideration.

In our view, the record of investigative action, during which video was used in PEI, must include: indication about video-recording application, time of its start and informing the participants of investigative action about it; information about technical means and conditions of video-record application, and also about the person who videoed, the mark about reproducing it by a participant, participants' statements saying that they are familiar with the record of investigative action and video-record, the mark of the person taking investigative action, about the time of completing video-recording.

Next particular form of applying special knowledge in PEI is non-procedural one. It enables to apply special knowledge in PEI which includes consultations and operational research, conducted by special subjects.

When examining the place of event a specialist-criminalist consults the person carrying out investigation and establishes a number of data about the suspected:

- whether he is acquainted with the victim (what the situation of the place of event, time and imprints in the place of event indicate);
- data about height, weight and other biological characteristics of the convict committing the crime (according the fingerprints, footprints);
- crime motives (injury character and situation can indicate the motive);
- psychological and social features of the personality according to the analysis of way of committing and hiding the crime (his abilities, skills, professions).

Operational research in PEI consists, as a rule, in determining drugs, psychotropic substances with the help of express-analysis. It is an examination – one of the forms of applying special knowledge – that implies an analysis on the instruction of investigator, judge or court according to the petition of the side of criminal proceedings, conducted by an experienced person (expert), having at his disposal material examination objects (material evidence) and also different documents, aimed at establishing actual data important for criminal proceedings.

The difference of examination from other forms of applying special knowledge consists, first of all, in the character of established facts. With examination the research results, as a rule, are not obvious and require scientific explanation of the person taking the examination. For example, the imprint discovered in the place of event, left by the suspect P., is established by the expert estimating the coinciding features of papillary patterns. The facts, established by a specialist examining the place of event, are of different character. Most often they are the direct result of applying scientific and technical means and don't need interpretation and special estimation. That's why the distinctive peculiarity of forensic examination is gaining actual data on the basis of scientific explanation, interpretation of research results.

Statistic data analysis of forensic practice and our empiric research show, that the most serious crimes committed by convicts in prison, who undergo expert research, are as follows:

1. crimes against life: intentional murder (art.115 CC of Ukraine), murder committed in the state of great emotional excitement (art.116 CC of Ukraine), murder exceeding the limits of necessary defense (art.118 CC of Ukraine);

2. crime against health (art.121-126, 127-129 CC of Ukraine);

3. illegal producing, manufacturing, buying, keeping, transporting, sending or selling drugs, psychotropic substances or their analogies (art.307 CC of Ukraine); illegal producing, manufacturing, buying, keeping, transporting, sending drugs, psychotropic substances or their analogies without selling (art.309 CC of Ukraine); illegal producing, manufacturing, buying, keeping, transporting, sending precursors (art.311 CC of Ukraine);

4. escape from prison or custody (art.393 CC of Ukraine) (*Batiuk O.V., 2013, 320 p*).

Conclusion of the given research. We suggest supplementing article 3 part 1 of the current Criminal Procedural Code of Ukraine with the point 18-1 of the following content: special knowledge is acquired knowledge, abilities and skills, which are constantly improving and are used in any field of human activity, gained in the process of special education, experience and practical activity (with the exception of professional knowledge of the people who make discovery and do investigation), necessary for quick and complete discovering and investigating a crime, and considering a case in court.

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ABSTRAKCJA TEKSTÓW JĘZYKA OBCEGO JAKO ŚRODKI PRZETWARZANIA INFORMACJI

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Streszczenie. Jedną z metod nauczania języka obcego w liceach nieanglojęzycznych jest rozwijanie umiejętności analitycznego i syntetycznego przetwarzania informacji w uczących się języków obcych za pomocą języka obcego. Przez to rozumiemy procesy twórcze, które obejmują rozumienie, analizę i ocenę treści tekstu w języku państwowym w celu wdrożenia próbki niezbędnych informacji i dalszej interpretacji. Osiągnięcie tych celów najlepiej pasuje do procesu wchłaniania tekstu w języku obcym, dlatego odniesienie jest kreatywnym językowym i intelektualnym procesem analitycznego przetwarzania informacji tekstowych na podstawie kompetencji mowy.

Celem artykułu jest ukazanie specyfiki odwoływania się do tekstów obcojęzycznych jako sposobu przetwarzania informacji i określenia metod nauczania odświeżających w instytucjach szkolnictwa wyższego.

Na podstawie przeprowadzonych badań ustalono, że proces szkolenia uchodźców powinien być ukierunkowany, spójny z pełną świadomością i dokładnym opracowaniem każdego etapu; odwoływanie się to racjonalna metoda przetwarzania treści tekstu, dlatego wskazane jest stosowanie następujących ćwiczeń podczas nauczania refleksologii: wybór słów kluczowych i zdań; odpowiedzi na pytania, które przyczyniają się do uogólnienia treści tekstu; uproszczenie struktury złożonych struktur; uogólnienie treści i alokacja głównej idei każdego akapitu; opracowanie logicznego planu tekstu; podział tekstu na wstęp, główną część i wnioski. Do prac przygotowawczych zalecano takie techniki, jak podział tekstu na fragmenty semantyczne, zapewnienie nagłówków tych fragmentów i sporządzenie planu; skrócenie tekstu; peryferie leksykalne, gramatyczne i półhore. Tak więc w procesie absorbowania tekstów obcojęzycznych u kandydatów następuje rozwój umiejętności czytania, mowy ustnej i pisemnej, zdolności analitycznych, krytycznych i twórczych. Zdobyte umiejętności i umiejętności naukowego przetwarzania tekstów umożliwiają wykorzystanie zagranicznych źródeł w procesie doskonalenia specjalności i promowania samodoskonalenia zawodowego.

Słowa kluczowe: abstrakcja, tekst w języku obcym, materiał językowy, algorytm abstrakcyjny, metody nauczania.

ABSTRACTING OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEXTS AS A MEANS OF INFORMATION PROCESSING

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Abstract. One of the methods of foreign language teaching at higher educational establishments is the development of the skills of analytic and synthetic information processing by means of a foreign language. It deals with creative processes that include comprehension, analysis and assessment of the text content in the state language for the implementation of

selecting necessary information and further interpretation. The process of abstracting of a foreign language text corresponds to achievement of these goals, and therefore, abstracting is a creative linguistic and intellectual process of analytical processing of textual information based on speech competence.

The purpose of the article is to reveal the peculiarities of abstracting of a foreign language text as a means of information processing and to describe methods of its teaching at higher educational establishments.

On the basis of the conducted research it is established that the process of its teaching should be directed, consistent, with full awareness and thorough elaboration of each stage. Abstracting is a rational method of processing the content of the text, so it is expedient to use the following exercises when teaching to write abstracts: highlighting keywords and sentences; answers to questions that contribute to the synthesis of the text; simplifying the structure of complex common sentences; generalization of the content and selection of the main idea of each paragraph; drawing up a logical outline of the text; division of the text into the introduction, the main part and the conclusion. As a preparatory work, such techniques as dividing the text into semantic passages, heading these passages and drawing up a plan; abridgement of the text; lexical, grammatical and semantic paraphrase are recommended. Thus, in the process of abstracting foreign language texts, students develop their skills of reading, oral and written speech, analytical, critical and creative abilities. The acquired skills and abilities of scientific processing of texts make it possible to use foreign sources in the process of mastering the speciality and promote professional self-improvement.

Keywords: abstracting, foreign language text, language material, abstract algorithm, teaching methods.

РЕФЕРУВАННЯ ІНШОМОВНИХ ТЕКСТІВ ЯК ЗАСІБ ОБРОБКИ ІНФОРМАЦІЇ

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Анотація. Одним із методів навчання іноземної мови у немовних вузах є розвиток у здобувачів вищої освіти навичок аналітико-синтетичної обробки інформації засобами іноземної мови. Під цим ми розуміємо творчі процеси, що містять осмислення, аналіз та оцінку змісту тексту державною мовою для здійснення вибірки необхідних відомостей і подальший його усний переклад. Досягненню цих цілей найкраще відповідає процес реферування іноземного тексту, а отже, реферування – це креативний мовно-розумовий процес аналітичної переробки текстової інформації, що базується на мовленнєвій компетенції.

Мета статті – розкрити особливості реферування іноземних текстів як засобу обробки інформації та визначити методи навчання реферуванню у закладах вищої освіти.

На основі проведеного дослідження було встановлено, що процес навчання реферуванню має носити спрямований, послідовний характер із повним усвідомленням і ретельним опрацюванням кожного етапу; реферування є раціональним прийомом обробки змісту тексту, тому при навчанні реферуванню доцільно використовувати такі вправи: виділення ключових слів і речень; відповіді на питання, що сприяють узагальненню змісту тексту; спрощення структури складних конструкцій; узагальнення змісту і виділення головної думки кожного абзацу; складання логічного плану тексту; поділ тексту на вступ, основну частину і висновок. Для підготовчої роботи рекомендовано такі прийоми, як поділ тексту на смислові уривки, надання заголовків цих уривків і складання плану; скорочення

тексту; лексичний, граматичний і смисловий перифраз. Таким чином, у процесі реферування іншомовних текстів у здобувачів відбувається розвиток навичок читання, усного та писемного мовлення, аналітичних, критичних та творчих здібностей. А отримані навички та вміння наукової обробки текстів роблять можливим застосування іноземних джерел в процесі опанування спеціальності та сприяють професійному самовдосконаленню.

Ключові слова: реферування, іншомовний текст, мовний матеріал, алгоритм реферату, методи навчання.

Introduction

One of the methods of foreign language teaching at higher educational establishments is the development of the skills of analytic and synthetic information processing by means of a foreign language. It deals with creative processes that include comprehension, analysis and assessment of the text content in the state language for the implementation of selecting necessary information and further interpretation. The process of abstracting of a foreign language text corresponds to achievement of these goals.

The problem of abstracting of texts in foreign language teaching attracted the attention of many domestic and foreign scholars. In particular, it was studied by such scholars as C. Bernier, H. Borko (1975), R. Davis-Haley (2004), N. Fomenko (2004), V. Garkusheva, L. Piatnytska, L. Shamrai (2005), A. Konysheva, A. Veize (1997), N. Riabova (2002), H. Rogova (1991), N. Rybakova (2007), I. Zimnjaja (1992) and others.

The purpose of the article is to reveal the peculiarities of abstracting of a foreign language text as a means of information processing and to describe methods of its teaching at higher educational establishments.

1. The concept of "abstracting" in foreign language teaching

V. Slamecka (2018) states that in popular usage, the term information refers to facts and opinions provided and received during the course of daily life: one obtains information directly from other living beings, from mass media, from electronic data banks, and from all sorts of observable phenomena in the surrounding environment. A person using such facts and opinions generates more information, some of which is communicated to others during discourse, by instructions, in letters and documents, and through other media. Information organized according to some logical relationships is referred to as a body of knowledge, to be acquired by systematic exposure or study. Application of knowledge (or skills) yields expertise, and additional analytic or experiential insights are said to constitute instances of wisdom.

Yu. Kovalova (2010, p. 96–97) emphasizes that abstracting, first of all, is a creative linguistic and intellectual process of analytical processing of textual information based on speech competence. In this regard, the process of its teaching should be directed, consistent, with full awareness and thorough elaboration of each stage. Abstract teaching in a foreign language should be aimed at implementing the practical and educational goals creating a stable unity. Such implementation allows achieving a certain level of communicative competence, ensuring the practical use of language, attracting students to various sources of information, the perception of which is impossible without knowledge of language. It is necessary to take into consideration the requirements for the learning materials intended to form the

communicative competence: functionality (correlation with a certain sphere of communication); situationality (correspondence to the concrete situation of communication, which is imitated in the process of learning); thematicity (conformity with the program); stylistic diversity (use of various functional styles); reflection of the modern stage of the language (the need to use authentic texts functioning in real communication); saturation with socio-cultural facts (presence of socio-cultural realities and reflection of the characteristic features of speech behavior).

N. Rybakova (2007) notes that abstracting is a complex creative process built on the penetration in the essence of the statement. The process of abstracting is not just a reduction of the text, but a substantial rework of the content, composition and the language of the original:

- the text / article highlights the main content, which is expressed succinctly, briefly;

- if the main idea of the text / article is formulated not enough clearly, it should be specified and highlighted in the abstract;

- the same type of facts are grouped, then it gives a generalized characteristic;

- digitized data are systematized and generalized;

- in case of necessity, the timetable is moved in sequence from past to future;

- the language of the original text changes in the direction of normativity, neutrality, simplicity and concordance. Shaped expressions, epithets, introductory words, non-essential definitions, circumstances, and annexes are excluded. There is a reduction of complex syntactic constructions, reducing the number of additional sentences, replacing them with simpler phrases.

The text of the abstract displays the following data: the problem under study, the purpose, the main idea and the content of the work, the subject or purpose of the study; data on the methodology and its comparative precision; conclusions of the author and opportunities and ways of practical application of the results of work; references to bibliography and illustrative material; technology, applied equipment and research conditions; tables, diagrams, graphs, formulas needed to find out the main content of the document; necessary reference data. According to the specifics of the document, the abstract may not contain all of these data, but only a certain part of them.

Abstracting is a complex skill, consisting of a number of individual elements, which, during the entire course of studying English, aims at the following exercises:

- allocation of basic thoughts, facts, positions;

- selection of paragraphs containing basic information;

- heading of the selected paragraphs;

- drawing up an article plan;

- shortening the text;

- the transfer of the content of the text in their own words (paraphrase).

2. Methods of writing abstracts

Work on the writing of the abstract is carried out in accordance with the following algorithm:

- reviewing the text and familiarizing with its general content;

- more careful reading of the text, determining the sense of unfamiliar words by means of the context or a dictionary;

- semantic analysis of the text and distribution of the material of the article into three groups in terms of its importance: I group – the most important information that requires full and accurate reflection in the abstract; II group – secondary information transmitted in a shorter form; III group – insignificant information that can be omitted;

- organization of the selected material, linguistic processing and its presentation.

In the process of reading the text with its further abstracting it is possible to distinguish three main stages:

1. The stage of cognitive orientation in the text, that is, orientation in the text information in the form of "content grouping" and the selection of "content support points". Such a process consists of several steps:

a) scanning reading, which leads to the question of the expediency of abstracting a particular professional text. At this stage, students review the title, and then quickly read the text and determine the practical significance and informational novelty of the source. Key words must form a meaningful guideline that activates the further process of comprehension of the text;

b) selection of encyclopedic, branch dictionaries, reference and special literature, which can help in further work on the text;

c) analysis of the primary source and the choice of the aspect scheme of presentation of the material in the future abstract text.

2. The stage of reconstruction of the logical structure and generalization of perceived information. At this stage, there is a re-grouping of data by the degree of their significance and generalization of information at the level of the whole text. As a result, semi-productive transformations are carried out, with the help of which there is a compression of speech communication at the sentence level or part of it. This stage involves studying reading of the text. In this case, the student does not complete the full written translation of the text. Mental decoding of the foreign language text is carried out under the influence of a guide to abstract analysis. The need to highlight the aspects identified in the abstract plan activates the mental activity of the student and gives it a search character.

3. The stage of curtailing of generalized information to the level of the abstract. Here is the most intense meaningful re-encoding, which results in the compression of the original text at the semantic, lexical and grammatical levels. This step contains the following steps:

a) dividing the text into "aspect blocks";

b) construction (synthesis) of new statements in the native or foreign language, which should briefly and concisely convey the basic meaning of each aspect;

c) recordings of the statements received as a result of the above-mentioned transformations in the sequence given by the plan of the abstract;

d) critical comparison of the texts of the abstract with the original source and the introduction of changes and additions to the text of the abstract;

e) writing and wording of the abstract.

Thus, abstracting of a foreign language text requires the use of certain parts of the text, or meaningful interpretations of the text. The main thing is a selection of information relating to the main elements of the content of the text, and the most compact presentation of it. In addition, in the process of abstracting there is an exclusion of secondary, inessential facts that are not relevant to the object of research and its main characteristics. Therefore, the selection of the most important information and the

transfer of it in the form of an abstract are taken place. This is possible thanks to productive transformations as a result of meaningful perception of the text. They represent operations of curtailing the linguistic reflection and semantic content of the original text in the text of the abstract. As a result of reproductive transformations, abstracts-extracts, abstracts-citations are created. Semi-productive transformations correspond to abstracts-periphrasis, abstracts-generalizations (Shamraj, Garkusheva & Pjatnickaja, 2005).

The quality control of the practical application of the gained knowledge may be either current or final. For the purpose of final control, you can use the following types of abstracts: abstract-summary - a brief summary (conclusion) of the text, or abstract-synopsis - which is larger in volume and includes all the main statements of the original. Writing of narrative, informative or critical abstracts is offered as one of the varieties of independent work in preparation for the discussion of a particular professional topic. As homework, you may give to work out additional sources or study individual problems independently using one or several sources of information, and submit them in the form of an abstract.

For the purpose of current control, students can be offered the exercises that allow them to evaluate their comprehension skills, the selection of basic information and the ability to convey it in a concise form, for example:

- to formulate the basic idea of certain paragraphs of the text material in native or foreign languages;
- to give a title to each paragraph using or without using the words from this paragraph;
- to select sentences containing basic / additional information;
- to shorten sentences by means of specified words;
- to give answers to questions and make an annotation on their basis in a particular language, etc.

It should be noted that when evaluating abstract skills, one must take into account not only the final result of the work, but also a number of factors that directly affect the perception of the text material, namely:

- the socio-cultural level of each individual student;
- the degree of knowledge of a professional subject;
- the level of foreign language proficiency;
- the motivational basis for the student's work, which determines the degree of his activity.

Thus, the use of abstracting of foreign language texts as a form of current or final control has certain advantages that are reflected in the operational nature of this form of control, namely:

- 1) in accordance with the requirements for content and constructive validity;
- 2) in the efficiency of applied professional skills of analysis and systematization in solving problems;
- 3) in the possibility of combining the processes of education and training with self-education (Riabova, 2002).

M. Cohen-Vida (2012, p. 4984–4985) states that writing a good abstract does not mean just reducing a source text and replacing a word with another one, it means finding expressions to replace several relevant components of the original text. It is difficult to make a good abstract of a text when ignoring the subject matter. Experience shows that one does a good summary on a question that he/she knows well. Documentation is very

important when writing an abstract, as well as when translating a text. Writing a good abstract implies having good written expression abilities, being able to express another person's thinking in a concise manner and using a personal way of putting across the ideas of the source text. The scholar presents a number of techniques in order to develop students' skills of writing a good abstract. They are:

1. Abstract in one phrase

In order to write a good abstract, the students should be able to perceive the essential problem of the source text. That's why it is a profitable exercise to reduce the original text to one phrase. This phrase must not be inserted in the abstract at the beginning because it has to present the way of thinking of the author and it would be a mistake to anticipate from the first lines the conclusion of the text. It must not be inserted at the inner part of the abstract either. The students have to know that what they have obtained is not a phrase of the abstract but the axis around which the abstract should be organized.

2. Abstract based on the notes made on the text

For the long and complex texts a good method which precedes the writing of the abstract is to work on the text, to underline and frame certain elements of the original text. This work does not aim to bring up the elements which will be preserved in the abstract, after having changed a few of them, but it must bring up the structure of the original text.

Thus the following elements must be revealed by this work:

- The units of meaning;
- The connectors between these units;
- The connectors inside the units;
- The elements situated on the same level.
- The important elements are underlined;
- The connectors between the great units of meaning are to be framed by a rectangle, while the connectors inside the units will be put in parentheses (if there is a coherent text, the connectors are not so important, juxtaposition being enough to render the relations between the elements).
- The examples, the elements of an enumeration will be surrounded by a circle.
- The great units of meaning which do not necessarily coincide with the paragraphs are separated by a horizontal line, while a dotted line will mark a kind of break within the unit of meaning.

Using this system, the structure of the source text is brought forward, without overloading the text. Those who want to write a few words on the margins of the text are free to do so. As a result of this work, students establish the units of meaning of the source text, the relations between these units and because what they have now are no longer the paragraphs of the source text, but the paragraphs of the abstract. According to the number of words required, they will be able to write a good abstract.

3. Abstract based on the plan of the text

The abstract has a relatively reduced number of paragraphs. What students should know is that paragraphs have to be consistent, each of them corresponding to a unit of meaning. That is why, in order to determine the number of these units, students will find writing the plan of the text useful. For a while they leave their main goal – writing the abstract – in order to focus on the plan of the text (which will be the plan of the abstract, as well). This method allows students to 'rethink' the text and to 'reformulate' it. In

establishing the plan of a text, students are advised to look for the set of oppositions the text is based on, which also have to be found in the abstract.

4. Abstract based on the scheme of the text

It is possible, as well for long and complex texts, to visualize the structure of the text before starting to write the abstract. This method consists in establishing a very suggestive and relatively detailed scheme of the source text. The result will be a well-structured abstract in which the text is really rethought and reformulated, preserving the author's way of thinking and the characteristics of the text.

The best method of writing the abstract is established according to the characteristics of the source text, the required dimensions of the abstract and the students' own choice. More important than this option is the students' ability to understand the text and to re-express it in a concise way, preserving its distinctiveness.

Conclusions

Abstracting is a rational method of processing the content of the text, so it is expedient to use the following exercises when teaching to write abstracts: highlighting keywords and sentences; answers to questions that contribute to the synthesis of the text; simplifying the structure of complex common sentences; generalization of the content and selection of the main idea of each paragraph; drawing up a logical outline of the text; division of the text into the introduction, the main part and the conclusion. As a preparatory work, such techniques as dividing the text into semantic passages, heading these passages and drawing up a plan; abridgement of the text; lexical, grammatical and semantic paraphrase are recommended.

Thus, in the process of abstracting foreign language texts, students develop their skills of reading, oral and written speech, analytical, critical and creative abilities. The acquired skills and abilities of scientific processing of texts make it possible to use foreign sources in the process of mastering the speciality and promote professional self-improvement.

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MOTYWY POPEŁNIENIA KORUPCJI I INNYCH KRYMINALNYCH PRZESTĘPSTW W DZIEDZINIE PENITENCJARNEJ UKRAINY: POJĘCIE, TREŚĆ, WARTOŚĆ TEORETYCZNA I PRAKTYCZNA

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Streszczenie. W postanowieniach artykułu naukowego autor bada pojęcie, treść, teoretyczne i praktyczne znaczenie motywów popełnienia korupcji i innych przestępstw w zakresie penitencjarnym na Ukrainie. Przeprowadzając analizę opinii czołowych uczonych ukraińskich i zagranicznych, autor przedstawia własną definicję pojęcia „motywy popełnienia korupcji i innych przestępstw kryminalnych w zakresie penitencjarnym Ukrainy”, a mianowicie, - to ukształtowane pod wpływem odpowiedniego środowiska społecznego i doświadczenia życiowego, i zawodowego tych osób intencje popełnienia korupcji lub innych przestępstw kryminalnych na podstawie wewnętrznej bezpośredniej przyczyny i które wyrażają ich osobistą postawę wobec tego, do czego jest skierowane dane społecznie niebezpieczne, nielegalne i karalne działanie, które stało wynikiem pewnych negatywnych warunków, stylu życia i konkretnej sytuacji życiowej danej osoby. Autor stwierdza również, że funkcje tworzące system, które składają się na treść tego pojęcia, powinny obejmować: 1) bezprawne intencje osoby; 2) intencje osoby ukształtowane pod wpływem odpowiedniego środowiska społecznego i życiowego oraz doświadczenia zawodowego określonych podmiotów stosunków społecznych; 3) podmiotem realizacji zamiarów kryminalnych są osoby z personelu instytucji penitencjarnych, które z kolei stanowią integralną część całego personelu Państwowej Służby Penitencjarnej Ukrainy; 4) bezprawny zamiar w określonych osobach, mający na celu popełnienie korupcji i innych przestępstw kryminalnych w zakresie penitencjarnym Ukrainy; 5) bezprawna intencja była wynikiem wewnętrznej bezpośredniej przyczyny osoby winnej; 6) bezprawny zamiar wyraża jego osobistą postawę wobec faktu, że jest on skierowany na ten społecznie niebezpieczny, niezgodny z prawem i karalny akt; 7) bezprawny zamiar osoby winnej powstał w wyniku wpływu na nią pewnych zewnętrznych warunków negatywnych, sposobu życia i konkretnej sytuacji życiowej.

Słowa kluczowe: korupcja, kara, przestępstwo, motyw, instytucja penitencjarna.

MOTIVES OF COMMITTING CORRUPTIBLE OR OTHER CRIMINAL OFFENCES IN THE SPHERE OF PUNISHMENT EXECUTION OF UKRAINE: CONCEPTIONS, CONTENT, THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL SIGNIFICANCE

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Abstract. In the provisions of the scientific article, the author examines the concept, content, the theoretical and practical significance of the motives for committing corruption and other criminal offenses in the area of execution of sentences in Ukraine. In conducting an

analysis of the opinions of the leading scholars of Ukraine and abroad, the author submits his own definition of "the motives for committing corruption and other criminal offenses in the field of the execution of sentences of Ukraine", namely, they are formed, under the influence of the appropriate social environment and life and professional experience of these persons, to commit corrupt or another criminal offense on the basis of an internal direct reason and expressing their personal attitude towards what is directed at it is socially dangerous, illegal and punishable dream, which was the result of certain negative conditions, lifestyles and a particular life situation on the person. Also, the author concludes that the system-forming features that make up the content of this notion should include the following: 1) the unlawful intentions of the person; 2) the intentions of the person are formed under the influence of the appropriate social environment and life and professional experience of these subjects of social relations; 3) the subject of realization of criminal intentions are persons from the staff of the administrative departments, which, in turn, is an integral part in the whole staff of the SCF of Ukraine; 4) the unlawful intention of the said persons is aimed at committing corruption and other criminal offenses in the area of execution of sentences of Ukraine; 5) the unlawful intention was the result of the internal direct cause of the guilty person; 6) the unlawful intention expresses its personal attitude towards the fact that it is directed at this socially dangerous, unlawful and punitive act; 7) the wrongful intention of the wine person was formed as a result of the influence on it of certain external negative conditions, a way of life and a particular life situation.

Key words: corruption, punishment, crime, motive, institution of punishment execution.

МОТИВИ ВЧИНЕННЯ КОРУПЦІЙНИХ ТА ІНШИХ КРИМІНАЛЬНИХ ПРАВОПОРУШЕНЬ У СФЕРІ ВИКОНАННЯ ПОКАРАНЬ УКРАЇНИ: ПОНЯТТЯ, ЗМІСТ, ТЕОРЕТИЧНЕ ТА ПРАКТИЧНЕ ЗНАЧЕННЯ

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Анотація. У положеннях наукової статті автор досліджує поняття, зміст, теоретичне та практичне значення мотивів вчинення корупційних та інших кримінальних правопорушень у сфері виконання покарань України. Проводячи аналіз думок провідних науковців України та зарубіжжя, автор подає власне визначення поняття «мотиви вчинення корупційних та інших кримінальних правопорушень у сфері виконання покарань України», а саме – це сформовані під впливом відповідного соціального середовища та життєвого і професійного досвіду цих осіб наміри вчинити корупційне чи інше кримінальне правопорушення у силу внутрішньої безпосередньої причини та які виражають їх особисте ставлення до того, на що спрямоване це суспільно небезпечне, протиправне та каране діяння, що стало результатом дії на особу певних негативних умов, способу життя та конкретної життєвої ситуації. Також автор робить висновки, що до системоутворюючих ознак, що складають зміст зазначеного поняття, слід віднести наступні: 1) протиправні наміри особи; 2) наміри особи сформовані під впливом відповідного соціального середовища та життєвого і професійного досвіду зазначених суб'єктів суспільних відносин; 3) суб'єктом реалізації злочинних намірів є особи з числа персоналу УВП, які, у свою чергу, є органічною частиною у цілому персоналу ДКВС України; 4) протиправний намір у зазначених осіб спрямований на вчинення корупційних та інших кримінальних правопорушень у сфері виконання покарань України; 5) протиправний намір став результатом дії внутрішньої безпосередньої причини винної особи; 6) протиправний намір виражає її особисте ставлення до того, на що спрямоване це суспільно небезпечне, протиправне та каране діяння; 7) протиправний намір у винної

особи сформувався в результаті впливу на неї певних зовнішніх негативних умов, способу життя та конкретної життєвої ситуації.

Ключові слова: корупція, покарання, злочин, мотив, установка виконання покарань.

In scientific sources a motive is meant a pretext, grounds for any action, deed or reason (*Lisova N. V. 2007. 20 p*). The same definition is given in Comprehensive dictionary of foreign words (*Lopokha V. V., 2016. 224 p.*). In criminal and legal aspect a motive is considered as indication of mental element of a crime (*Lopokha V. V., 2016, p.18*), which is meant awareness of a person's impulse to cause the determination of committing a crime, this is an integral psychic state making the person commit socially dangerous action and is its reason (*Lukashenko A. A., 1997. p. 86–91*). Analogical approach to crime motive definition is used in Law encyclopedia (*Lukashevych S. Yu., 2001, p.19*). Gryshchuk V. K. defining the content of philosophical and legal conception of a person's responsibility, closely links crime motive with corpus delicti, which is one of the reason of negative (retrospective) criminal and legal responsibility of a person (*Gryshchuk V. K., 2013, p. 768*). In criminological references crime motive is considered integrated psychic formation caused by external or internal incentives determined by a person's peculiarities, which prompts to the behavior aimed at relieving psychic strain of conscious actualized need of biological or social character by means of breaking criminal and legal prohibition (*Lunyeyev V. V., 1991, p.383*). On the whole, such definition corresponds with general theoretical content of offence motive concept (*Lupinosova O. M., 2007, p.248*). This concept is examined in both narrow and broad aspects in educational and methodical publications of "Criminology" course. Thus, Lykholob V. G. explains crime motive as criminal behavior motivation considering the first one to be and important inner determinant of a criminal behavior (*Lykholob V. G., 1992 p.41*). Besides, according to him, neither a motive nor motivation, nor formal ability to choose determines the content of the taken decision controlled by subject's will and consciousness (*Lykholob V. G., 1992, p.41*). Then V. A Lyovochkin includes the motives of illegal behavior into the mechanism of person's criminal purpose (*Lyovochkin V. A., 2002, p.18*). According to the analysis of scientific works on the definite problem this scholar established that in the light of general psychological theory of purpose motivational process is of great importance, as it 1) defines psychologically acceptable type of behavior chosen among other types; 2) endows this type of behavior with more significance from point of view of value orientations; 3) makes it psychically important; 4) ensures conditions for forming a proper purpose (*Lyovochkin V. A. 2002, p.18*). A.M. Boyko used analogical approach, he is convinced, that in social individual's life and activity different lines and motives of social process do not only intersect and meet, but new social qualities for keeping or modifying old ones are synthesized in them (*Bojko A. M., 2008 p.111*). N.V.Smetanina suggests that criminal behavior motivation should be admitted to be a criterion of criminological crime classification, proving that no other criterion of such classification reflects inner integral amount of crime reasons to the full, as motivation (*Smetanina N. V., 2016 p.93-94*). Proceeding from research results received, the above scientists suggested five groups of criminal motivations: a) political; b) violent and selfish; c) self-interested; d) anarchic and individualistic; e) thoughtless and irresponsible. Taking this into consideration O. M. Lytvynov considers activity of neutralizing person's criminal behavior motivation to be a priority among three aspects of social and legal mechanism of crime counteraction in Ukraine, which he singled out (*Lytvynov O. M., 2008, p.144*). O.G.Kalman attributed a person's criminal

behavior motive to objects of counteracting and preventing criminal offences (*Kalman O.G., Kozyakov I. M., Kucz V.V., 2010, p.30*). S.F. Denysov suggests studying person's criminal behavior motives in the content of crime determinant, considering them as one of integral element of criminal mechanism structure (*Denysov S. F., Denysova T. A., Kulyk S. G., Sheremet O. S., 2015, p.289-299*). In addition to that they understand criminal behavior motive as an intention formed under the influence of social environment and life experience, which is direct inner reason of committing a crime and it expresses personal attitude towards the object this action is aimed at. In his opinion, meaningful side of the motive indicates the intention followed by the person setting a definite aim and choosing illegal way of reaching it. It is the meaningful side of the motive through which the person's direction is expressed, his or her interests, inclination for thinking and readiness to act in a certain way. But the energizing side of the motive is formed with emotions and feelings that stimulate determination and support readiness for purposeful actions. Moreover, emotional experience of criminal intention guides determined process in a certain direction. According to this scientist it is the very motives that are equally a reason and a motive power of purposeful behavioral activity, and so they are direct reason of committing any corruptible or any other criminal offence, including those in the sphere of punishment execution of Ukraine.

Proceeding from the results of this research, it should be mentioned that foreign criminologists also pay great attention to motives and motivation treating the problem about determinants and mechanisms of committing corruptible and other criminal offences. Thus, German scientist H.Y.Shnayder, studying criminal "careers" distinguished four phases of rise and development of criminal motivation, and making a juvenile criminal, in particular, namely: a) delinquency as not an isolated action, but a life process, mounted into criminal career; b) a group pushes a person into criminal career and keeps him there; c) the reaction of the people among his closest surrounding to his illegality is of great importance for forming his personal criminal image; d) finally the teenager is appointed as illegal subject. Kazakh criminologist calls person's needs, interests and motives together with moral qualities essential elements in the social and psychological mechanism of an individual crime. Russian scientist studying person's needs and interests, proves that the latter ones influence greatly person's motivational sphere implying all the motives which are formed and developed during all his lifetime. She distinguished the following motives of criminal behavior: 1) social political: state and society government mechanism, participation in this government, influence on it and so on; 2) social economic: a) satisfying absolute that is the most necessary vital needs; b) satisfying "relative needs" arising in the conditions of social and economic population differentiation and comparative analysis of the people's status; c) reaching the ideal, that is a certain material standard (superwealth) or social standard (penetrating into the high society), the person is oriented to; 3) violent and selfish (physically and psychologically aggressive): a) making the idea of self-assertion absolute, realizing the present needs and interests in any forms; b) self-assertion in the forms acceptable in concrete situations (ill-bread, uncivilized person usually react to any remark with insult), obstacles and difficulties in protecting honour and dignity in legal form cause physical violence against the insulting person. A.I.Dolgova included here the cases when the person living in inhuman conditions is self-asserted in inhuman way; 4) thoughtless and irresponsible: a) lack of need and interest to correlate his deeds with the present norms of behavior and law; b) selectivity of such correlation

(estimation) (for example, only under conditions of strict external control or communicating with high-ranking people, not with subordinates or irresponsible ones, etc.). A.I. Dolgova believes, the indicated types of motives can be displayed in different correlations in criminal behavior (*A. I. Dolgova, 2005, p.289*). In their opinion, there is another logical deadlock in this social and economic theory: why don't all the poor or at least most of them commit a crime? The above mentioned scientists made another important conclusion: a person is a criminal not because he is poor, but he is poor because he is a criminal. Criminal life style does not bring in constant incomes from hard work. As regards this, Russian criminologist D.A. Shestakov observed opportunely, that criminality is hidden, it can't be recognized with mere notion of committed and registered crimes, since it expresses the main thing characterizing the process of crime reproduction, its inner, deep regularity of multivariable conflict behavior of people contradicting with one another (*Shestakov D.A. 2011, p. 17*). In his opinion, criminality is mediated by complicated hierarchy of mass criminal behavior reasons (social contradictions, negative social processes), forming the basis of inability to conforming society interests, aimed at creating its superiority rather than regularity. Russian criminologist Along with this the choice of ways and means of motive satisfaction is realized only in a certain life situation enabling the subject to make a motivational choice of setting a certain goal. Moreover, the goal is chosen as a result of interacting at least three factors: motive, life purpose and a specific situation in which the event takes place.

Having generalized theoretical approaches to motive role in individual criminal behavior, Ukrainian criminologist A.P. Zakaliuk distinguished three approaches concerning its essence determination: a) functional; b) gnoseological and determinate; c) general personal (at the same time the second and the third factors are closely connected with the person, but they are rather specific) (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 287*). He does not doubt the motive function, as it is a stimulus, impulse of person's activity. Likewise, motive belonging to determinate process is indisputable (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 287*). According to A.P.Zakaliuk, gnoseological and determinate motive essence consists in the fact that a motive is a specific attitude towards the subject able to satisfy the needs of the latter, to define ways of the role implementation, to stimulate aspiration (inclination) for action, realizing the need by this subject (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 288*) According to A.P.Zakaliuk, general personal approach to motive notion definition is first of all clarifying correlation between the motive and person or personality notions, the place motive takes in the personality structure (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 289*). In broader sense a motive is meant as constant personal characteristics, defining person's activity in certain directions, spheres of vital functions during a long period or maybe all life. Such motives are often called principal or general, they are believed to be formed since childhood (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 290*). A.P.Zakaliuk proves that such motive conception is more acceptable for motivation content and direction. It is close to such categories as "attitude", "determination", "valuable orientation" and almost does not differentiate with them, though the motive has more distinct stimulating function. Moreover, the mentioned difference concerns more terminology sphere than essence (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 290*). But notwithstanding some differences in defining motivation notion, A.P.Zakaliuk makes it two main variants according to which motivation is: 1) the whole complex or system of psychological determinants, being inner reasons of a crime; 2) the process of emerging,

forming, developing, changing motives, making decision to commit a crime (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 290*). In this case motivation is the process of forming, developing and making personal psychological readiness and motives of activity of a certain direction and social importance (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 291*). A.P.Zakaliuk thinks, motivation itself forms the motives which is inner reason of criminal manifestation (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 291*). He divided motives into three groups: a) social and personal; b) political, profitable, violent and selfish, anarchic and individualistic, thoughtless and irresponsible, timid and cowardly; c) ideological, material incentive including profitable and also with deformed material needs; motives stipulated by interpersonal communication, among which are personal hostility, self-assertion, egocentrism, scornful attitude towards other people, social indifference, passiveness, etc. (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 293-294*). Both criminal motivation and motives are formed under the influence of conditions and way of life.

The conditions that influence criminogenic motivation directly, in the family, in particular, are as follows: 1) examples of criminal and the like illegal behavior: theft, hooliganism, beating, etc.; 2) examples of antisocial habits (hard drinking, drug-addiction, amorality, etc.); 3) indifference to family members' criminal manifestation, attempts of helping to avoid responsibility, to cheat victims, etc.; 4) contentiousness, strain, bitterness in relationship among family members, scandals, on the whole, the atmosphere to get rid of, by means of criminal occupancy of money, property, which enables to change this atmosphere (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 295-296*). Other social groups in everyday life and in free time have analogical conditions of forming criminogenic motivation, including the influence of criminal group (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 296-301*). Some other phenomena of social reality, not embraced the indicated notions, influence forming criminogenic motivation. According to A.P.Zakaliuk, they are: specific life situation, where person's antisocial intentions are formed, his acquiring socially dangerous features, criminogenic orientation and motivation, transformation of the latter one into criminal and finally into the motive of committing a criminal offence (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 301*).

Science divides a specific life situation into the following types: a) promoting type, which embraces conditions making criminogenic motivation and motives of a crime, further –criminal intention realization- easy; b) problematic type, which prevents person's qualities from being formed and developed, but sets the task of overcoming obstacles, of making additional efforts, of search and using corresponding means, etc.; c) conflict type, where influences different according to interests and direction can collide, which causes conflict between them, it makes the person be more reasonable and understand the reason of the conflict (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 304*). There are other ways of classifying a specific life situation. According to the sources influencing its formation, A.P.Zakaliuk divides them into connected with a) a person influenced by the environment while he is criminally formed and realizes the motive and intention to commit a crime; b) the environment and its elements of influence including the object influencing the motive to be realized; c) both sides, a person and environment elements (this situation is called mixed) (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 304*).

All these indicated theoretical and methodological approaches are used in the given monographic research for looking into social and legal nature of motives and motivation of committing corruptible and other criminal offences in the sphere of punishment execution of Ukraine.

So, proceeding from received results we can tell the following definitions of the notion “motives of committing corruptible and other criminal offences in the sphere of punishment execution of Ukraine”, namely – they are intentions formed under the influence of the corresponding social environment and life and professional experience to commit corruptible or other criminal offence because of inner direct reason, and which reflect their personal attitude towards the object the social dangerous illegal and punishable action are aimed at, and which became the result of influencing some negative conditions, way of life and specific life situation.

Thus, the system-forming signs reflecting the content of the marked concept are as follows:

1. They are person’s illegal intentions. In science intention implies a plan, desire to do something (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 289*). Criminologists call intention a direct inducement At the same time they urge that the motive should not be considered “initial moment of crime”, “primary stimulating reason”, because needs, interests, attitude, being the subjects, stand before a motive in a stimulating process. Further more, the sense, that is, a purpose defining the reason of impulse is important in this process too. So, as criminologists state, impulse (intention) is just impossible without sense, that should not be identified with a motive, since they have the role and function of their own in the stimulating and on the whole determination process (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 289*).

2. The indicated person’s intentions are formed under the influence of the corresponding social environment and life and professional experience of social relations. To form means literally to make something have a particular shape or appearance; to mould particular features of character in somebody, etc. Forming criminogenic and further criminal motivation is a result of deepening antisocial direction, acquiring more distinction, intensity, firmness, and above all, social danger which is qualified by antisocial attitude to main conditions of society vital function, that is, by socially dangerous manifestations, formation criminal motives (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 292*).

In scientific sources influence implies the action a particular person of thing or phenomenon applied to another person or thing. As practice proves, different phenomena of social reality (family, school, other educational institutions and working groups) and personal life are criminal influence motivation forming antisocial criminal behavior (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 294*). The course of our research established that the people with little life experience, aged 20-25, and practical professional working experience in SCES of Ukraine (1-3 years) are the most difficult criminological objects in the sphere of punishment execution, their share in the structure of corruptible and other criminal offences in the sphere of punishment execution of Ukraine makes up about 70% (*Borovyk A. V., Kolb O. H. 2019, 360 p.*).

3. PEI staff officials are subjects of criminal intention realization, who are an integral part of SCES personnel. According to the requirements of art. 14 of Law of Ukraine “On State criminal and executive service of Ukraine” SCES consists of the following people: a) private men and commanders; b) specialists without special ranks; c) civil servants; d) other people working on a labour contract. But at the moment of committing corruptible or other criminal offences in the sphere of punishment execution of Ukraine the above mentioned subjects must have SCES personnel status (there must be an authorized person’s order about including in the office staff). As p.2 of the

Plenum Resolution No.15 26.12.2003 of the Supreme Court of Ukraine “On Court practice in cases of exceeding power or official commissions “ indicated, courts are obliged to demand materials of criminal cases of exceeding power of official commissions, copies of normative and legal acts, provisions, instructions, other documents explaining the character of official’s commissions. In broader sense, according to p.2,3 art.11 of CEC of Ukraine PEI personnel includes the people working (serving) in a) prisons; b) correctional centres; c) educative colonies; d) penal colonies; e) investigative isolation ward, in cases when these people punish convicts (those left in IIW according to art. 89, 90 of CEC)

4. Illegal intention is aimed at committing corruptible and other criminal offences in the sphere of punishment execution of Ukraine. The crime notion is given in art.11 of CC of Ukraine, and crime classification (minor, average, felony and grave) – in art.12 of the same Code. Then the stages of crime committing are defined in art.13-15 of CC, each of them contains criminal responsibility (art.16 of CC), if the person guilty of committing a crime on the stage of its preparation or of attempt does not refuse voluntarily (art.17 of CC). It appears that even with formed intention (stimulus) of committing corruptible or other criminal offence the person cannot realize it either because of the reason that didn’t depend on him (art.15 of CC) or of his own will (art.17 of CC).

5. Illegal intention to commit corruptible or other criminal offence in the sphere of punishment execution of Ukraine became the result of guilty person’s inner direct reason. A person’s criminal motivation, that is, practical activity, subjects of which are motives: their emerging, forming, realization in intention and decision to commit a crime is such a reason (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 291*). As practice and results of special criminological researches (168) prove, criminal motivation (exactly intention) isn’t formed at once. In the context of antisocial and socially dangerous (not criminal) motivation a person gets motives referring to the matters belonging to main conditions of society’s vital functions and mainly through intentions and high probability to use criminally forbidden means and forms of activity concerning these motives realization, motivation of the latter passes through criminal stage when criminal motivation has not been formed yet, but is only criminally oriented. Scientists call such orientation and motivation criminogenic (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 291*). It is just the content of direct reason of committing corruptible and other criminal offences by any person, including the sphere of punishment execution of Ukraine.

6. A person’s illegal intention to commit corruptible or other criminal offence in the sphere of punishment execution of Ukraine expresses his personal attitude to the object the socially dangerous, illegal and punishable action is aimed at. Again, as practice affirms, criminal motivation can be different or completely absent in different types of crimes (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 291*). At the same time, motives also have different level of formation, intensity, firmness, different limit of awareness by a person and influence which motives make for the desire of their realization. These personal elements of motive formation process to commit a certain crime together with a socially important object chosen and with the way of satisfying the motive determine its social danger, probability of motivation criminal character (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 291*). But motivation is criminal if it produces committing deliberate crimes, if a person understood socially dangerous character of his action (acts or omission); expected its social dangerous consequences and wished them to appear (p.2 art.24 CC – express

malice), or if a person understood socially dangerous character of his action (acts or omission); expected its dangerous consequences, though did not wish but surmised consciously their coming (implied malice (p.3 art.24 CC)). At the same time, criminal motivation (intention) is narrowed in crimes committed by inadvertence (art.25 CC) (a guilty person did not wish the socially dangerous consequences to come, but surmised them consciously or had to surmise) (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 292*). Besides, there is lack of criminogenic motivation (criminal intention), as well as conscious motive in the so called impulsive crimes when the behavior goes out of control or consciousness under the influence of different circumstances (alcoholic and narcotic drunkenness, strong emotion or other emotional disorder, mental aberration within incrimination (art.19 CC) and limited incrimination (art.20 CC), and others) (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 292-293*). Along with this, it should be remembered that a person's psychical attitude towards realizing illegal intention must correlate to the estimation of social danger, illegality and punishability of committing the action (acts or omission), which are main and necessary features of any crime (art.11 CC). Social danger in the criminal law theory implies objective ability of the crime to do harm or make a threat of doing harm to the objects of criminal and legal protection. Illegality means that socially dangerous action becomes a crime only if it is provided for by law about criminal responsibility, if it contradicts the norm of criminal law and breaks its ban or instructions. Punishability is a criminal and legal repression for committing a crime defined in Law on criminal responsibility.

7. Illegal intention to commit corruptible and other criminal offence in the sphere of punishment execution is formed in a guilty person as a result of influencing certain external negative conditions, way of life and a particular life situation. A.P.Zakaliuk divided the following influences of conditions of ways of life: a) the influence of society's way of life on the whole; b) the influence of its criminal social communities; c) the influence of small groups (micro-environment); d) the influence of individuals (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 294*). He is convinced society's way of life can influence criminal orientation and motivation formation directly or indirectly through the way of life of separate social groups (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 294*). It was above mentioned about the conditions connected with way of life of social groups (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 295-296*), as well as about influence on forming criminogenic motivation and other elements of way of life (family, social groups, everyday, leisure environment, criminal groups, etc.). As A.P.Zakaliuk remarked, these conditions are realized through deeds, behavior of certain people of appropriate environment, especially influential, 'experienced', informal authorities, distinguished out of already convicted people. Besides, the facts of conciliatory attitude towards such people, fawning over them, supporting 'traditions' in the criminal surrounding have strong criminogenic influence (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 296*). Moreover, communication with such people, following their customs and traditions often speed up criminogenic motivation, forming the motive of a crime (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 296*). Besides different forms and conditions of way of life in different social groups and social roles some other phenomena of social reality including specific life situation influence criminogenic motivation. In this connection A.P.Zakaliuk made a conclusion that a criminologist takes interest in a specific life situation, in which a person's antisocial direction, its intensity, acquiring socially dangerous features, criminogenic orientation and motivation, transformation of the latter into criminal one, and finally into crime committing motive are formed (*Zakalyuk A. P., 2008, p. 301*).

So, on the whole, such is the content of the notion “motive of committing corruptible and other criminal offences in the sphere of punishment execution of Ukraine”, which made up the basis of the given monographic research. Theoretical significance of this conception explained in this work consists in the fact that in such a way the limits of scientific knowledge about the motives of criminal behavior of certain social groups (here – in the sphere of punishment execution) are broadened, also doctrinal principles of forming and classifying criminal motivation and motives of illegal activity of the indicated subject categories are deduced. Practical significance of the investigated conception consists in the fact that the problems not regulated in the law but faced in life are defined in this work, they are worth taking into account while organizing preventive activity, connected with committing corruptible and other criminal offences in the sphere of punishment execution of Ukraine because of this or that motive, with neutralizing, blocking, eliminating direct or indirect determinants of the indicated types of crimes.

The results of anonymous survey conducted in the course of our research prove the marked problems to be available. So, 15 respondents among PEI personnel answered the question “Have you been victims of the crimes committed by the people of colony’s staff?” positively, (it is 4% of all survey participants); 346 respondents answered negatively (89%); 27 people answered “partially” (7%). Convicts gave the following answers: 25 respondents answered ‘yes’ (it is 7% of all survey participants), 264 respondents said ‘no’ (66%); 107 people said ‘partially’ (27%) (*Borovyk A. V., Kolb O. H. 2019, 360 p.*).

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ROLA DIGITAL MARKETINGU W STRATEGII OMNIKALNEJ

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Streszczenie. W dzisiejszym społeczeństwie penetracja Internetu stale rośnie, obejmując coraz większą liczbę odbiorców. Internet stworzył nową przestrzeń wirtualną z dalszą koncentracją na jego przestrzeni różnych grup docelowych. Wraz ze wzrostem liczby użytkowników Internetu, rośnie świadomość marek o niezbędności wykorzystania Internetu jako nowego kanału reklamy wśród tradycyjnych mediów w celu prowadzenia komunikacji z ich docelowymi odbiorcami. W tym artykule autorzy przejrzyli cechy prowadzenia digital-aktywności przez marki w kontekście strategii omnikalnej i zbadali sposoby zwiększenia synergicznej interakcji digital z innymi kanałami reklamowymi.

Słowa kluczowe: digital marketing, digital strategia, reklama internetowa, środowisko krosskanalne, grupa docelowa.

THE ROLE OF DIGITAL MARKETING IN OMNICHANNEL STRATEGY

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Abstract. The article deals with developing digital marketing strategy by brands running marketing communication in different channels. Special attention is given to increasing the effectiveness of combining digital channel with TV. It is noted that using digital helps to build effective reach of TA that cannot be covered by TV. The author emphasizes that is important to use effective channel split for digital activity. Recommendations on implementation digital marketing in media strategy are developed.

Keywords: digital marketing, digital strategy, internet advertising, cross-channel planning, target audience reach.

РОЛЬ ДІДЖИТАЛ-МАРКЕТИНГУ В ОМНІКАНАЛЬНІЙ СТРАТЕГІЇ

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Анотація. У сучасному суспільстві проникнення Інтернету постійно зростає, охоплюючи все більшу частину його аудиторії. Інтернет створив новий віртуальний простір з подальшою концентрацією на його просторах різних цільових груп. Зі збільшенням кількості інтернет користувачів відбувається укріплення розуміння брендами необхідності використання Інтернету як нового рекламного каналу серед традиційних медіа для ведення комунікації зі своєю цільовою аудиторією. У даній статті автори розглянули особливості ведення діджитал-активності брендами в контексті омніканальної стратегії та дослідили шляхи підвищення синергетичної взаємодії діджитал з іншими рекламними каналами.

Ключові слова: діджитал маркетинг, діджитал стратегія, інтернет реклама, кросс-каналне серидовище, цільова аудиторія.

Statement of the problem in general form and it's connection with important scientific or practical tasks. In nowadays world the number of information flows is constantly increasing and covering audiences both in real and virtual environment. Advertising channels as newspapers, OOH advertising and even television are retreating, giving way to the Internet. This trend is due to the rapid growth in the number of Internet users with following accumulation of different target audiences on its recourses. As a result, implementation of new methods of brand promotion to TA through the Internet as a part of complex marketing strategy becomes not only an opportunity but also the requirement of present day.

Recently advertiser's interest to internet technologies has been increasing. On practice it appears in increase in SOV of digital in overall advertising budget. Despite the attention paid to internet advertising by many business areas, there were not still comprehensive surveys on increasing the effectiveness of digital marketing strategy of a company. Current works show the positions of different authors on some business tasks in the area of digital, however there is no enough studies on developing digital in omnichannel environment.

Analysis of the latest research and publications, which initiated the solution of this problem and on which the author relies. Some topics of this article were discussed in the paper written by Uspenskiy I.V., where he described the goals and specifics of digital marketing channels. Internet marketing and advertising instruments became a part of the studies of following authors: Ian Dodson, Simon Kingston, Ilyashenko Sergey and other.

Highlighting the previously unresolved parts of the general problem to which the article is devoted. Effective marketing strategy has a great impact on success of marketing activity of the company. It is not only important to develop effective strategies for each media channel but is also needed to improve them by ensuring their synergy. Analysis of studies on internet marketing showed that this topic is not still

explored and the surveys on increasing the effectiveness of digital marketing strategy in omnichannel environment are still needed.

Formulation of the purpose of the article (statement of the problem).

The aim of this article is to analyze and identify all aspects of effective digital marketing implementation in omnichannel strategy. To achieve this aim there were the following tasks posed:

- to analyze the opportunities of different media channels for running communication with target audience and estimate their effectiveness;
- to develop the classification of digital advertising as the basis of preparing digital strategy;
- to define the ways of increasing the synergy between TV and digital and develop the recommendations on improving digital strategy.

Statement of the main material of the research with full justification of the scientific results obtained. Internet became an effective channel of running marketing communication with target audience. For instance, according to TNS research the current rate of Internet usage in Ukraine is about 72% that is nearly 22 million users. Average user spends almost 25 hours a month visiting Internet recourses from PC or notebooks. In general, there are nearly 19,3M internet users on PC, 10,5M mobile users and 2,6M users that goes to the Internet on tablet devices [4].

This statistic shows that Internet created virtual environment with wide range of recourses visited by different audiences in their purposes. Due to this feature a global integration of the Internet with business takes place. It means that advertisers have an opportunity to communicate with their target audiences using different internet marketing instruments.

Herewith, Internet is not only the one channel that can be used by brands in a purpose of running marketing communication with their target audiences. Depending on a company or a product, advertisers can also contact their audience through TV, out-of-home placements, press and other channels.

Picture 1 – Volumes and dynamics of growth of Ukrainian media market in 2006-2018 [5]

Picture 1 above shows the volumes of different media markets and their dynamics of growth from 2006 to 2018 in billion UAH.

According to analytical market overview by VRK (Ukrainian advertising coalition) TV market demonstrated 6% rise in demand in first six months 2018. The

number of brands also increased and reached the level of 2013 that was before the crisis. TV market is constantly growing but with falls after the crisis periods.

Press market mainly relates to increase in the number of special projects, where press is one of the main communicational platforms. Some brands also go into Press in order to build users loyalty, formulate brand's positioning or to deliver the idea. In addition, this channel is quite effective in some regions where users demonstrate high loyalty to regional publications.

Radio market shows lower rise rates than others. The most popular advertising segments are alcohol, entertainment and trade.

Active rise of Ukraine's out-of-home marker in 1H 2018 amounted 35%. But further rates may be lower due to plans of Kiev and Dnepr cities' Councils to reduce the number of big formats.

Regarding the market of Internet advertising, there are some difficulties in its estimation due to dynamic changes in internet technologies so researchers have troubles with tracking, counting and estimating all aspects of internet marketing activities. Besides that, there is no main metrology developed for such estimation, that is caused by the difficulties in data verification and receiving correct information on advertisers' activities.

Despite the rapid growth of Internet advertising market, according to TNS data the highest reach of users 12-65 living in cities with more than 50 k people across all media channels demonstrates OOH.

The Table 1 below shows the level of reach of different media channels in 2016-2017.

Table 1 – Media channels' audience reach [6]

Media channel	Reach 12-65 50k+, %	Δ 2016-2017 p., %
TV	91%	-2%
Internet	72%	+2,6%
Radio	56%	+12%
OOH	96%	+0,2%
Press	44%	-7%

This table shows that TV occupies the second place, covering 91% Ukrainian audience, while Internet is on the third place with 72% reach.

In the same time, media channels show different quality of personal contact that relies to the level of user's attention and trust. The Table 2 shows a quality of the contact of different media channels in percent measured from 1 to 100.

Table 2 – Media channels' contact quality, % [6]

Media channel	Attention	Trust
TV	56,6	18,1
Internet	30,9	12
Cinema	15,2	4,2
OOH	34,4	8,8
Newspapers	20	16,1
Magazines	16,9	4,6

Among media channels, the highest quality of the contact is on TV. Basing on the level of Attention the second place is occupied by OOH and depending on Trust by Newspapers. Internet is on the third place by both indicators.

As media channels have different potential for grabbing user's attention and being trustworthy, it becomes important for brands to develop an effective split of channels in order to achieve marketing goals. Herewith, there should be defined the main and additional media channels. Such attitude allows to focus on the most effective channel for communication and additionally to get in touch with target audience through other channels.

Even though OOH have the highest reach across all media – 96% (Table 2) and shows high potential for attracting user's attention, recently its potential has not been fully used by single brands due to price. So, TV becomes the main communication channel for most brands running reach campaigns where OOH in most cases is used only additionally to contact audience with bond to the place.

As it was previously mentioned, it is required to use the mix of channels in order to generate maximum TA reach and get effective cost per reach and ROI. However, no one channel can work on this so effectively as the combination of TV and Internet. In most cases it is caused by difficulties in communications with many sellers from other channels especially when they belong to different regions and high cost per reach. Regarding TV, almost whole inventory is focused between four main media groups: «Inter», «StarLightMedia», group «Ukraine» and «1+1». Internet traffic is available across local and foreign sellers and programmatic platforms that make it easy to start advertising campaign.

As a result, marketing strategy that is based on the mix of TV and Internet becomes the most effective not only because of eCPR, but also due to high contact quality and opportunities for planning and realization of strategies for these channels. Herewith, one of the main digital tasks in such strategy is building supplementary target audience reach to TV. Taking into account that TV becomes more and more expensive each year due to price inflation, media mix optimization by increasing digital budget drives ROI and incremental revenue. In order to achieve these goals, it is important to develop effective digital strategy that will work in synergy with TV.

Today companies start to understand high role of digital in media strategy and on practice it leads to increase in digital budgets. Picture 2 blow shows the dynamics of investments in digital from 2014 to 2018.

Picture 2 – Investments in digital advertising, mln UAH [5]

This data shows that digital investments are constantly increasing and there was average rise of investments for 33% each year starting from 2016. Total investments increased almost in three times starting from 2014.

To achieve the main goal of Digital in omnichannel strategy – building incremental TA reach to TV, there are different aspects of Digital that must be considered before running the communication. The Table 3 below shows the classification of digital advertising.

Table 3 – classification of digital advertising

№	Classification feature	Digital marketing components	Data source
1.	Digital channels	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Display • Video • Mobile • Search • Social • E-mail • SEO • PR • Website 	The Interactive Advertising Bureau [7]
2.	Key performance indicators (KPI)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Impressions • Reach cookies • Reach real users • Frequency • Clicks • CTR • Price • Budget • Audience composition • Affinity 	Developed by author
3.	Payment form	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CPM • CPC • CPV • CPR • CPA 	The Interactive Advertising Bureau [7]
4.	Type of materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Banner (static, animated) • Video • Text 	Developed by author
5.	Type of targeting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender • Age • GEO • Time • Interests • Behavior • Remarketing • Devices etc 	The Interactive Advertising Bureau [7]

The information above shows that advertisers should considered a lot of aspects for running digital communication. Attention should be paid to mediaplanning that

focuses on choosing relevant digital channels and planning KPI for them by developing media plan. It is important to find out how to contact TA effectively using available targeting options. All such aspects of running digital communication and argumentation on them must be developed in digital strategy.

In order to build effective incremental reach through digital, the strategy has to focus on quality and quantity. On the one hand it is important to use the websites with high target audience composition and highly-viewable formats, on the other hand it means that online advertising should be carried out thorough the channels and on the websites with high reach potential and low cost per reach. Media planning helps to combine quality and quantity and includes estimation of the indicators and developing the argumentation that confirms usage of different internet marketing instruments in media split.

According to the researches people percept 45% information visually, 36% auditory and 19% kinesthetically. So both video and audio contact is the best way to make people perceive 81% information. And this can be made through TV and digital, but not in any other advertising channels with such results. In the same time, TV and Digital offer to make such contact in different formats that increases overall effectiveness of advertising by ensuring synergy [8].

To meet the criteria of visibility and audibility it's important to pay much attention in digital strategy to the usage of video format. According to IAB formats classification there are three main types of video placements: in-stream, content-roll and video banner. In-stream advertising helps to display ads through video player on the websites with video content. In-stream placement includes pre-roll, mid-roll, pause-roll and post-roll. In-stream is the most effective type of video placement due to high VTR and viewability, where pre-roll plays important role on this. Content-roll is a type of video placement when video is placed in the content of the website. This placement has lower rates than in-stream, but it's cheaper. Video banner is the cheapest type of video placement and used to show video instead of banner through banner placement. To make advertising effective it is important to consider in-stream as the main type of placement with focus on pre-roll. Depending on budget, content-rolls can also be added to the plan as an additional placement that will work on decreasing cost per reach.

There are local and foreign suppliers that provide inventory for video advertising. Picture 3 below shows reach potential of video sellers.

Picture 3 – Monthly reach potential, TA 18-35 [4]

Gemius overnight data shows that almost 80% video inventory of TA 18-35 is focused on YouTube. Herewith, YouTube offers many targeting options despite other

publishers, so it should be used as the main resource of video inventory in the media plan. Admixer as local seller has access to 67% of this audience. Adpartner is on the third place with 53%. Starlight and Edipresse also offer enough inventory for video advertising. Advertiser can also go into social networks or use them as additional placements in the media plan to decrease eCPR. However social networks demonstrate lower viewability rate due to available formats.

According to the researches 56% of internet users skip video ads [9]. As a result, video that is used on TV in most cases is not effective in Digital. Effective media strategy has to contain different attitudes for creating video content for TV and for Digital. In Digital in order to deliver the idea and get high VTR it is important to follow the next recommendations for preparing video:

- video for digital activity should be short – often up to 15 seconds;
- it has also to be attractive, dynamic and interesting for target audience to grab users' attention on website's page;
- it has to contain the main information in the first part in order to deliver it to more users as they may skip;
- it has to be device friendly - additional vertical version of video must be prepared for mobile phones as their users consume content with mobile phone almost in vertical position.

Advertising on TV and Digital has to start in the same time to make them work in synergy. If digital activity starts later it would lead to decrease in incremental reach to TV. There may also be three additional attitudes used to increase the effectiveness of Digital strategy.

1. The first attitude is based on storytelling, when advertisers re-reach the same audience with different creatives delivering the story.

2. The second attitude is based on combination of long and short video versions, when advertising starts with short 6 seconds video to tease the audience. Then the main 15 seconds video is displayed to deliver the main message and to effectively work on incremental TV reach. And advertising finishes with short 6 sec video to echo the previous activity by delivering the follow-up message. There may also be used combination only of one 6 seconds and one 15 seconds videos.

3. The third attitude is based on the research that nearly 30% TV viewers move their attention from TV to other activities including mobile phones in first 2,5 seconds after TV advertising starts. According to this attitude digital activity may be combined with TV in real time through special services that will make the Ad displayed on users' mobile phones in the same time or after another ad is displayed on TV. Getintent is one of the biggest platforms that offer such kind of advertising.

Building digital strategy it is also needed to plan frequency. Frequency helps to control how many times the ad will be displayed to each unique user. Table 4 shows the connection between frequency and adrecall.

Table 4 – Influence of frequency on adrecall [3]

Weekly frequency	AdRecall index
1	1x
2	1.7x
3-5	2.2x
6+	2.7x

Average frequency 1-3 is the most effective in terms of adrecall and eCPR. Increasing frequency above 3 leads to ineffective budget spend. Running communication through different digital placements it is important to consider their intersection as it may increase overall frequency of the campaign. However there is no service that makes it available to define the level of intersection between placements, so on practice it can be estimated basing on the results of previous activities that can be measured.

As it was previously mentioned YouTube offers wide range of targeting options for placing video content and should be considered as the main inventory source in digital plan. Herewith, YouTube also allows carrying out Brand lift as an additional service for measuring the effectiveness of digital campaign. Brand lift helps to find out how advertising leads to increase in adrecall, brand awaraness, brand favorability or purchase intent metrics. This is a survey that compares the rates of these metrics across the audience that the ads were showed to with the metrics of the audience that has not seen advertising. As higher this correlation is as advertising is more effective. This option is free for advertisers and helps to get results that may be used for improving digital strategy.

Conclusions from this research and prospects for further developments in this area.

The recommendations on implementation of digital strategy in omnichannel environment developed by the authors have important practical value for the companies running digital activity, especially those that in parallel communicate through other channels.

Media channels' reach and their effectiveness in terms of grubbing user's attention and being trustworthy were analyzed in order to define the attitude to building the media split. Herewith, basing on the results of the researches on how people perceive information and on opportunities on planning and running the campaign, it was stated that TV and Internet are the best channels to deliver the message both visually and audibly.

Digital advertising classification that includes the types of digital channels, KPIs, targeting options and other instruments was developed in order to show the range of aspects that must be taken into consideration while developing digital strategy.

It was defined that video can be placed on the website in one of the following formats: in-stream, content-roll, video banner. Herewith, in-stream placement includes pre-roll, mid-roll, pause-roll and post-roll. And in-stream is the most effective type of video placement due to high VTR and viewability, where pre-roll plays important role on this. Content-roll and video banner may be used as additional placements in order to decrease eCPR.

YouTube should be considered as the main source of traffic for video activity due to available targeting options. But the placements on the websites of local sellers like Admixer, Adpartner, Starlight, Edipresse and in social networks may also be additionally used. In some cases banners can also be added to the plan in order to decrease overall CPR.

Video content of the ads has direct impact on their effectiveness. There must be special versions of video prepared for digital instead of TV video. It is important to use attractive short versions – often up to 15 seconds with the main information in the first part. Video must be device friendly.

Running digital campaigns there may be used some strategies on increasing their effectiveness. They are: storytelling, when we deliver the story to the user; the second strategy start with tease, than the main message and ends with follow-up; the third strategy considers real time activity when the user sees the video in the internet in the same time when it is displayed on TV to him.

Preparing the digital plan it is important to take into account frequency and intersection as they influence adrecall and effective budget spend.

Finally, this study may be used as a basis for further researches regarding estimation the practical role of digital marketing in omnichannel strategy.

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WDROŻENIE INNOWACYJNYCH TECHNOLOGII W METODYCZNYM PRZYGOTOWANIU PRZYSZŁYCH NAUCZYCIELI BIOLOGII

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Streszczenie. W artykule skuteczność wykorzystania innowacyjnych technologii nauczania w metodycznym przygotowaniu przyszłych nauczycieli biologii na uniwersytetach pedagogicznych jest uzasadniona i praktycznie zweryfikowana. Ujawniono istotę metodycznego przygotowania przyszłych nauczycieli i innowacyjnych technologii nauczania. Opisano cechy takich innowacyjnych technologii, jak technologie interaktywne, technologie case, technologia projektu, warsztaty metodyczne i portfolio metodyczne. Technologie interaktywne zapewniają interakcję między uczniami, ich wzajemne uczenie się i współpracę. Technologia case ułatwia uczniom rozwiązywanie rzeczywistych sytuacji w praktyce szkolnej. Technologia projektu zapewnia wszechstronne badanie materiałów dydaktycznych i stworzenie ostatecznego produktu metodycznego. Warsztat metodyczny zapewnia uczniom możliwość zdobycia wiedzy, aby wykazać zdolności twórcze. Portfolio metodologiczne pomaga uczniom śledzić ich rozwój zawodowy. Autor analizuje aktualny stan wykorzystania innowacyjnych technologii w metodycznym przygotowaniu przyszłych nauczycieli biologii. Opisano wyniki badania skuteczności wprowadzenia tych technologii w procesie edukacyjnym instytucji szkolnictwa wyższego. Ustalono, że wykorzystanie tych technologii w grupach eksperymentalnych pomogło zmniejszyć liczbę uczniów o niskim poziomie osiągnięć o 20,5%, przy średnim poziomie 5,0%, przy wzroście liczby studentów o wystarczającym poziomie 19,3%, a przy wysokim – o 6,2%. Perspektywy dalszych badań znajdują nowe metody i środki do poprawy metodycznego przygotowania studentów biologii na uniwersytetach pedagogicznych.

Słowa kluczowe: metodyczne przygotowanie, innowacyjne technologie, przyszli nauczyciele biologii, technologie interaktywne, projekt, portfolio, case, warsztat metodyczny.

THE IMPLEMENTATION OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN METHODOLOGICAL TRAINING OF FUTURE BIOLOGY TEACHERS

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Abstract. The article deals with the effectiveness of the usage of innovative teaching technologies in the methodological preparation of future biology teachers in pedagogical universities. The content of the article is theoretically grounded and practically verified. The essence of methodological preparation of future teachers and innovative teaching technologies are revealed. Features of such innovative technologies as interactive technologies, case technologies, project technology, methodical workshop and methodical portfolio are described. Interactive technologies provide interaction between students, their mutual learning and cooperation. Case technology facilitates the students' ability to solve real situations from school practice. The project technology provides a comprehensive study of the teaching material and the creation of a final methodical product. The methodical workshop provides students with the opportunity to acquire knowledge, to demonstrate creative abilities. The methodical portfolio

helps students to track their professional growth. The author analyzes the actual state of using innovative technologies in the methodical preparation of future biology teachers. The results of testing the effectiveness of the implementation of these technologies in the educational process of institutions of higher education are described. It was established that the usage of these technologies in experimental groups helped to reduce the number of students with a low level of achievement by 20,5%, with an average level by 5,0%, with an increase in the number of students with a sufficient level by 19,3%, and with high level by – by 6,2%. Prospects for further research are to find new methods and means for improving the methodological training of biology students at pedagogical universities.

Key words: methodological preparation, innovative technologies, future biology teachers, interactive technologies, project, portfolio, case, methodical workshop.

ВПРОВАДЖЕННЯ ІННОВАЦІЙНИХ ТЕХНОЛОГІЙ У МЕТОДИЧНІЙ ПІДГОТОВЦІ МАЙБУТНІХ УЧИТЕЛІВ БІОЛОГІЇ

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Анотація. У статті теоретично обґрунтовано і практично перевірено ефективність використання інноваційних технологій навчання у методичній підготовці майбутніх учителів біології в педагогічних університетах. Розкрито сутність методичної підготовки майбутніх педагогів та інноваційних технологій навчання. Схарактеризовано особливості таких інноваційних технологій, як інтерактивні технології, кейс-технології, проектна технологія, методична майстерня та методичне портфоліо. Інтерактивні технології забезпечують взаємодію студентів, їх взаємонавчання та співпрацю. Кейс-технології сприяють формуванню в студентів умінь вирішувати реальні ситуації зі шкільної практики. Проектна технологія забезпечує різнобічне вивчення навчального матеріалу та створення кінцевого методичного продукту. Методична майстерня дає можливість студентам самостійно здобувати знання, виявляти творчі здібності. Методичне портфоліо допомагає студентам простежити своє професійне зростання. Автором проаналізовано реальний стан використання інноваційних технологій у методичній підготовці майбутніх учителів біології. Описано результати перевірки ефективності впровадження цих технологій в освітній процес закладів вищої освіти. Встановлено, що застосування цих технологій в експериментальних групах сприяло зменшенню кількості студентів з низьким рівнем успішності на 20,5%, з середнім рівнем – на 5,0%, з зростанням кількості студентів достатнім рівнем на 19,3%, а з високим – на 6,2%. Перспективи подальших досліджень полягають у пошуку нових методів і засобів удосконалення методичної підготовки студентів-біологів у педагогічних університетах.

Ключові слова: методична підготовка, інноваційні технології, майбутні вчителі біології, інтерактивні технології, проект, портфоліо, кейс, методична майстерня.

Introduction. The Concept «New Ukrainian School» states that a graduate of a comprehensive educational institution must be a holistic person, fully developed, capable of critical thinking, a patriot with an active position and an innovator who can change the world around, compete on the labor market, learn throughout the whole life course (*Nova ukrayins'ka shkola: kontseptual'ni zasady reformuvannya seredn'oyi shkoly*, 2006, p. 6).

A teacher must also be an innovator in order to educate an innovator at school: a teacher must use innovative technologies, demonstrate a creative approach to the organization of educational activities and constantly work on self-improvement.

Current students will come to work at the New Ukrainian School, so they should be the carriers of innovations. However, during their studies at a university, future teachers are often confronted with outdated approaches, methods and learning forms, lack of necessary scientific literature and modern teaching tools. Future teachers, who have to form new generations of citizens of our state, are traditionally trained with the help of the boards and the chalk. Thus, there is a contradiction between the existing traditional teacher training system and the new requirements for the professional qualities of future professionals.

The methodological training, which combines knowledge of psycho-pedagogical and natural sciences, is considered as a systematic component of future teachers training.

We consider the methodological training of future biology teachers as a purposeful process of methodical knowledge formation, skills, competences of students in the context of solving methodological problems from the school's course of biology (*Hrytsai, 2016., p. 23–24*). The future teachers are introduced to the latest approaches in biological education, they study the peculiarities of innovative teaching technologies, learn to apply them in practice during the methodological training course. A high school teacher must enrich his professional activity with innovative forms, methods, means and learning technologies because methodological training is crucial in the professional development of future professionals, in the choice of their further professional activities.

Methodological training of future teachers of natural sciences was studied by N. Burinska, A. Hrabovy, M. Grynova, M. Krylovets, N. Chaychenko, V. Sharko, O. Yaroshenko.

Scientific works by V. Verbitsky, O. Ivantsiv, V. Onipko, I. Potashnyuk, V. Tanskaya, O. Tymets (Braslavska), Yu. Shapran, S. Yalanskaya and others are devoted to the problems of professional training of specialists in the field of biological education.

Current issues on methodological preparation of future biology teachers were studied by Ukrainian and foreign scientists: N. Andreeva, T. Bondarenko, L. Bulavintseva, S. Vovk, A. Yermakova, G. Zhirska, V. Kisil, M. Kolesnik, M. Marinescu, L. Mironets, N. Mishchuk, I. Moroz, N. Raicheva, V. Stavinsky, A. Stepanyuk, C. Sumatohin, D. Traitak, L. Tushinskaya, K. Ushakova, J. Fruktova, N. Tsanova, O. Tsurul', M. Shvetsova, V. Shuldyk, N. Yanovich and others.

Problems of methodical preparation of future teachers of biology on various aspects were studied in dissertations by I. Azizova (the system of methodological preparation of students-biologists on the basis of the strategy of subjective reflexive learning), O. Arbuzova (the designing of a reflexive learning system by the usage of an innovative teaching and methodical complex in a biology teaching methodology), L. Orlova (a system of methodological training of biology teachers). However, the usage of innovative teaching technologies in the methodological training of students-biologists wasn't the subject of a special scientific research. It is worth mentioning only some publications by T. Bondarenko (the method of concrete situations), N. Mishchuk (the case method), O. Tsurul' (the technology of critical thinking development).

The purpose of the research is: to justify theoretically and test practically the efficiency of the innovative teaching technologies usage in the methodical preparation of future biology teachers in pedagogical universities.

Tasks of the research work: to find out the essence of innovative teaching technologies, to identify and characterize technologies that have the greatest potential for application in the methodological training of future biology teachers, to verify the

effectiveness of the usage of the proposed technology during a pedagogical experiment in higher education institutions.

Methods of research: theoretical analysis of scientific sources, observation of educational process in higher education, questioning of teachers of higher education with the purpose of finding out the real state of using innovative technologies, pedagogical experiment on the introduction of innovative technologies in methodological preparation of future biology teachers in higher educational institutions.

The experiment covered 482 students of higher educational institutions in Ukraine. Future biology teachers were divided into two groups: the control group (CG) – 243 students and the experimental group (EG) – 239 students.

In the experimental group, innovative teaching technologies were introduced, that contributed to a better understanding of methodological knowledge, the development of methodological thinking of future teachers, their creative abilities, methodological reflection. In the control group the teaching was conducted according to the traditional method.

Methodological preparation of future biology teachers at pedagogical universities takes place while studying the methodology of teaching biology and other disciplines of methodological direction. Teaching these disciplines involves a combination of traditional and innovative learning technologies.

In the conducted research work, we will consider innovations which are based on new knowledge, skills and competence of students and that are aimed at the formation of highly skilled biology teachers in general education institutions. According to V. Strelnikov and I. Britchenko, innovation technologies are characterized by such features as a forward-looking character, a personally oriented approach, structuring of personal knowledge, reliance on the totality of information and knowledge systems, the focus on the organization of an independent cognitive-research activity of the student, etc. (*Strelnikov, Britchenko, 2013.*)

Scientist and methodologist O. Igna names a number of requirements for the techniques of a qualified methodological training of the teacher: the activation of learning; modeling of future professional activity; independent decision-making by students; high theoretical level of educational material; intensification of training; personal orientation; providing a liaison with the professional activity of the teacher; practical orientation; problematic nature of educational material; motivation increasing for future professional activity (*Igna, 2013*).

In order to obtain information on the practical use of innovative technologies in the methodological preparation of future biology teachers, a questionnaire was conducted among the teachers who deal with the methodology of biology teaching and other methodically oriented disciplines. 34 teachers from 26 universities of Ukraine (pedagogical and non-pedagogical) took part in the inquiry.

Teachers-methodologists use the following innovative teaching technologies in the methodological training of students-biologists: interactive technologies (38,2%), information and communication technologies (29,4%), design technologies (29,4%), game technologies (20,6 %), multimedia technologies (20,6%), technologies of research training (17,6%), personally oriented technologies (17,6%), technologies of problem learning (11,8%), technologies of critical thinking development (8,8%), technologies of distance learning (8,8%), trainings (8,8%), technology for creating a situation of success (5,9%), individual lifelong learning (5,9%), technologies of professional competencies

forming (5,9%). Individual respondents indicated a case study, a productive learning, a portfolio technology, a module of training development, a technology of collective learning, a technology of developmental education, pedagogical workshops, etc. (Hrytsai, 2016, p. 64).

The theoretical analysis of scientific sources, the generalization of teaching practice in higher education institutions and the experience of teaching methodological disciplines has led to the assertion that the following innovative technologies are effective in the methodological training of future biology teachers: interactive learning technologies, a project technology, a technology of a methodological workshop, a portfolio technology, a problem learning technology, a contextual learning technology, case technologies, information and communication technologies, etc. (Table 1).

Table 1

Innovative learning technologies that are used in the methodological training of future biology teachers

<i>The name of technology</i>	<i>Significance in methodological preparation of students</i>
Interactive technologies	Provide interaction between students, their mutual learning and cooperation
Case technologies	Promote the formation of the students' abilities to solve real situations which are from school practice
Project technology	Contributes to the versatile study of educational material and the creation of a final methodological product
Methodological workshop	Allows students to acquire («build») knowledge on their own, to show creative abilities
Methodological portfolio	Helps students to track their professional growth, contributes to the objective assessment of methodological competences of future teachers, the formation of methodological reflection

In general, these technologies contribute to the activation of cognitive activity of biology students, the development of their methodological competences, the enhancement of motivation for future professional activity, the growth of the level of methodological readiness, the formation of an individual methodological style and the methodological formation of future biology teachers. Let's consider them more closely.

Interactive teaching technologies are important among the latest technologies that are being introduced in the methodological training of future biology teachers. The scientific and teaching research works by O. Pometun and L. Pirozhenko reveal the essence of interactive learning and characterize the types of interactive learning technologies. It has been established that interactive learning technologies envisage continuous active interaction of all students, group and collective learning in collaboration, when the teacher and students are equal subjects (Pometun, Pyrozhenko, 2006).

O. Lavrentieva notes that certain patterns make the psychological basis of interactive methods. They are: better assimilation of facts, phenomena and values by a person that takes place in direct practical activity, if information is provided in all possible types (verbal, visual, acoustic, etc.) in the process of mutual learning (Lavrent'eva, 2006).

The organization of interactive training in practical and laboratory classes on methodological disciplines involves the usage of role-playing games, simulation of

learning situations, the creation of a problematic situation, brainstorming, training, etc. Interactive interaction eliminates the dominance of one participant in the learning process over the other and one thought over another. In such classes, future teachers learn how to think critically, make informed decisions, participate in discussions and communicate with others. Thus, the educational process creates an atmosphere of interaction and cooperation.

The plan for conducting a practical lesson by using interactive technology may be as follows: 1) motivation for a learning activity (story, conversation, examination of a pedagogical situation, video demonstration, etc.); 2) the presentation of the theme and the purpose of the lesson; 3) discussion of theoretical material on the subject; 4) interactive part – work in pairs, small groups, brainstorming, discussion; 5) summing up and evaluating (*Pometun, Pyrozhenko, 2006*). The most commonly used interactive technologies are «brainstorming», «microphone», «debate», «aquarium», «jigsaw», «learn by teaching», etc.

The benefits of interactive learning are that future educators learn to interact and make collaborative decisions, participate in discussions, develop communication skills, develop their own thinking and find a compromise.

Case technologies. Case- technologies are based on learning by solving concrete tasks – situations (cases).

As a result of the theoretical analysis of scientific literature, it was found that the case method was used at the Harvard Business School for the first time at the beginning of the XX century. Today, there are two classic case-study schools – Harvard (American) which is characterized by the searching for the only one correct decision and Manchester (European) which is characterized by a multivariate problem solving (*Adonina; Dolgorukov;*) 13]. Case technologies are applied predominantly in business education, as well as in sociology, medicine and other fields of knowledge.

«Case» (event, situation) – this is a very detailed description of any particular educational situation. Case studies are based on real situations as a reflection of the actual problems of teaching methods.

We agree with K. Gerasimenko, who considers the technology of case-study as a technology of active problem-situational analysis, which enables to present academic theory from the point of view of real events, promotes active learning of knowledge and skills of information processing (*Gerasymenko, 2011*).

Case technology includes case studies, situational analysis method, situational tasks, analysis of specific situations, method of «incident», method of analyzing business correspondence, method of situational-role games, method of conducting a discussion. O. Shimutina asserts that the method of situational analysis, which is used for case technologies, it is the analysis of specific situations (a detailed study of the real and the simulated situation) and this method has the following varieties: situational exercise (it is a proposed text with a detailed description of the situation and the problem for resolution) and case study (familiarization with a description of the problem, an independent analysis of the situation, the presentation of own ideas and a problem solving in the discussion with other participants) (*Shimutina, 2009*).

As a result of scientific research, it has been found, that among case technologies, the most common case-method is the method that combines the methods of cognition: modeling, system analysis, description methods, problem method, classification method, game techniques, brainstorming, discussion, morphological and synectical analysis

(Gerasymenko, 2011; Shimutina, 2009; *Situatsionnyy analiz, ili anatomiya keys-metoda*, 2002; Yeriomina M., 2004).

Case is a kind of learning tool that simulates the real life situation during a lesson (school practice), which needs to be discussed and it should be found a well-founded solution.

Each case has a certain structure. So, Yu. Surmin names the plot part (events that reveal the contents of the case), the information part (information that is necessary for analysis), the methodical part (the task case formulation) (*Situatsionnyy analiz, ili anatomiya keys-metoda*, 2002, p. 168). K. Gerasimenko points out the following components: a situation-case, a problem or a story from a real life; the context of the situation (time, place, actions of the participants); commentary on the situation; questions or tasks for working with a case; applications (Gerasymenko, 2011). The case must be relevant, possess an appropriate level of complexity, meet the purpose of the class, describe the real situation and promote the development of critical thinking in students.

The case method is aimed at solving a problem that is not presented in the finished form, but it is formulated in accordance with the conditions of a real learning situation. The process of teaching biology at school, which means students' future professional activities, is the main source of methodical cases.

The essence of the case-method is that the future teachers of biology are offered a «case», which describes the real situation in school practice. Students need to get acquainted with it in advance, to understand the problem and to find ways to solve it. Then, future teachers discuss the situation in small groups and offer a variety of options to solve it, choosing the best at the time of their auditorium classes.

Creative groups are formed for the solution of the methodical case in classes on methodological disciplines. After individual case analysis by each student, a group goes to a joint discussion, develops a general draft decision and its design and determines the way of presentation in the class. In order to increase the efficiency of work, M. Yeriomina recommends to chose a «coordinator» (organizes the work), a «secretary» (fixes the results of work) and a «skipper» (presents the project to a collective discussion). The analyzed and solved case is presented by the students personally at the time of presentation by showing their personal interest in the problem. When presenting a case, it is desirable to use visual materials to keep the audience's attention and give presenters the opportunity to examine the issues in details (Yeriomina M., 2004).

Thus, the working technology of future biology teachers with a methodological case involves the following stages: 1) individual independent work with case materials (familiarization with the situation, the allocation of the main problem, proposals for its resolution); 2) work in microgroups to solve the problem, analysis of the consequences of making one or another decision, the development of a single position; 3) presentation of the results of the work of microgroups in the process of discussion, the choice of one or several solutions to the problem; 4) analysis of the activities.

Methodological cases are similar to the tasks solved by students in laboratory and practical classes on methodological disciplines. But the objectives of the tasks and cases are different: the tasks are focused on the learning of the teaching material, and case studies contribute to the formation of a wide range of different skills and abilities (analytical, constructive, practical, creative, communicative, social, self-analysis skills). In addition, tasks usually have one correct solution and cases possess many alternative solutions.

Case studies provide students with the ability to analyze situations, think critically, evaluate alternatives and choose the best option. By examining the case, future teachers actually get a ready-made solution that can be used in similar circumstances in future professional activities. The more cases will be analyzed by a student, the better he will cope with similar situations when working at school.

Thus, case technologies combine features of training and future professional activities that directly affect the process of personal growth of a student, his methodological formation, the formation of a subjective experience of solving problems in future professional activities on the basis of methodological situations analysis. The ability to test theoretical knowledge in practice, skills developing to argue own views and listen to the thoughts of others, the formation of team skills and the ability to find rational solutions to the problem are the main advantages of case technologies.

Cases about the formation of cognitive interest of schoolchildren in the lessons of biology, sexual education of schoolchildren in the lessons of biology and extracurricular work, the development of critical thinking of schoolchildren in the study of evolutionary concepts, etc. are the most interesting cases in the methodology of teaching biology.

The project technology takes a special place in the methodological training of future teachers. During the implementation of projects, students have the opportunity to form a holistic view of future professional activities.

The project-based learning method appeared in the United States in the 20's of the twentieth century, due to the educational activities of John Dewey and his followers, V. Kilpatrick and E. Collings. In the 20-30's of the twentieth century, this method was used in the USSR, but after 1937 it was removed from the school curriculum, as the scientific works by J. Dewey's were also excluded from the libraries. Since the 90s of the twentieth century, the project-based learning method has returned to educational practice (Hrytsai, 2016; Zosymenko, 2011; *Novyye pedagogicheskiye i informatsionnyye tekhnologii v sisteme obrazovaniya*, 2002; Shyyan, 2011).

The essence of the concept «project» implies its pragmatic focus on the result that we obtain when solving a given theoretically or practically significant problem. We agree with the scientists V. Bespalko, O. Kobernik, Y. Polat, O. Pekhota, V. Slastyonin, N. Shiyan, etc., who name the project-based learning method a technology which covers various teaching methods: research, search, problem (Zosymenko, 2011; *Novyye pedagogicheskiye i informatsionnyye tekhnologii v sisteme obrazovaniya*, 2002; Shyyan, 2011).

The researchers identified the main requirements for using the project-based learning method: the presence of a significant problem, which requires integrated knowledge, research search for its solution; practical, theoretical, cognitive significance of the expected results; independent activity; structuring of the content part of the project; the usage of research methods (*Novyye pedagogicheskiye i informatsionnyye tekhnologii v sisteme obrazovaniya*, 2002, p. 68).

The advantage of the project-based learning method is that its application helps to strengthen the connection between the theory and the practice; it is accustomed to the activities planning, facilitates the formation of the ability to observe, verify, analyze and generalize. The content of the professional activity of the teacher is modeled at the time of project preparation.

The theoretical analysis of scientific sources made it possible to determine the following features of the project-based learning technology: orientation to action; work

in a team; self-organization of students; situational orientation; correlation with real life; reliance on previous achievements of the student, on the existing experience; interdisciplinarity; connection with actual sociocultural tendencies; integrity; focus on the finished product, on a certain result; focus on cooperation, not competition. The project work is oriented towards the student, although the teacher offers his support and guidance throughout the execution of the project (*Hrytsai, 2016; Zosymenko, 2011; Novyye pedagogicheskiye i informatsionnyye tekhnologii v sisteme obrazovaniya, 2002; Shyyan, 2011*).

The project-based learning technology consists of the following stages, such as: *preparatory* (formation of groups, selection of the theme of the project, definition of purpose, structure, form of the final product); *educational* (collecting information by students, processing and analysis of information); *final* (preparation for the presentation of the final product, presentation and evaluation of the project by all participants).

In most studies, there are five stages of work on the project: the first stage – initiation (search of an idea, definition of the theme and problems); the second stage – work planning; the third stage – project implementation; the fourth stage – presentation of the project; the fifth stage – reflection of the project (*Novyye pedagogicheskiye i informatsionnyye tekhnologii v sisteme obrazovaniya, 2002; Shyyan, 2011*).

At the initial stage of work it is determined which type of a project will be implemented: individual, pair or group. If the project is pair or group, then microgroups are formed by interests, they distribute roles, types of practical activity in the project. For example, N. Shyyan offered the following division of responsibilities: the project manager, or the project administrator (management of the group activities, contact with the teacher), the developer of ideas (generation, concept, original proposals), a designer (registration of the main ideas for the project), a technologist (processing of the descriptive part), specialists in the specific tasks preparation (*Shyyan, 2011*).

The results of scientific research have led to state that in studying the discipline «Methodology of teaching biology» and other disciplines of methodological direction, there are great opportunities for of the project technology application. So, we consider the following themes of the projects as relevant: «Teaching biology in the profile school», « Interdisciplinary connections usage at the lessons of biology», «A computer as a means of teaching biology», «Virtual excursions on biology», etc.

A specific feature of methodological disciplines is their practical and they are of oriented character, therefore, the involvement of future biology teachers in the project activity will make it possible to enhance the practical orientation of learning. Printed notebooks, programs for the clubs activities, extracurriculars, electronic manuals, visual teaching aids, presentation of lessons, methodological recommendations, etc. can be the final product of methodological projects.

The technology «methodical workshop». In France, in 1922, the public movement GFEN (le Groupe francais d'education nouvelle – French group of new education), which promoted the ideas of free education by J. J. Russo, S. Frenne, the humanistic psychology by J. Piaget, K. Rogers, etc. At the beginning of the movement were psychologists Paul Langevin, Henri Wallon, Jean Piaget. The leading idea of the movement is «All capable!» (*Origines et jalons historiques*).

The representatives of GFEN developed the technology «workshop», which involves «building» knowledge simultaneously with the «construction» of the individual. In France, this technology is called «les Ateliers» (studio, workshop).

According to I. Mukhina, the pedagogical workshop is a form of learning that creates conditions for the ascent of each participant to new knowledge and new experience through an independent or collective discovery (*Mukhina*).

The technology of the pedagogical workshop is similar to the technology of problem learning and technology of research training. The peculiarity of the technology of the workshops lies in the creation of a special developing space, which enables participants during self-search and group discussions to «self-build» of their knowledge through a critical attitude to information and the implementation of creative abilities.

The technology of the workshop has received such a name because its participants independently acquire («build», «grow») knowledge and skills and the teacher appears as a counseling Master, who helps to organize training, gives advice on the gaining knowledge, creates conditions for expression of participants in the workshop through their creativity. The Master selects such questions that do not have a concrete answer, but promote creativity, stimulate, motivate action. The technology is aimed at immersing the workshop participants in the process of searching, cognition and self-knowledge. While working in a workshop, the increase of self-estimation of participants, they aspire to gain knowledge on their own.

In the works of I. Mukhina and T. Yeromina, the principles of the pedagogical workshop are substantiated: 1) the value-semantic equality of all participants; 2) the right of everyone to error; 3) activities without evaluation; 4) freedom within the framework of accepted rules; 5) significant element of uncertainty, incomprehensibility; 6) dialogue as the main principle of interaction, cooperation, co-creation; 7) organization of the space in which workshop works, depending on the task of each stage; 8) restriction of participation, practical activity of the Master (*Mukhina; Yeriomina T., 2007*).

The methodical workshop is used in methodical preparation of future biology teachers. The methodical workshop is a technology of training future teachers, which creates a training space for modeling the situations of professional activity, which systematically develops and improves the methodological competence of students (*Hrytsai, 2016, p. 320*).

The methodical workshop as a technology that is built on a certain algorithm, the most common of which is as follows: induction – self-construction – socio-construction – socialization – advertisement – break – reflection. The essence of each of the elements (stages) is given in table. 2.

Table 2

The main elements of the technology «methodical workshop»

№	Element's name	The essence
1.	Induction	Motivation for creative activity
2.	Self-construction	Individual problem solving, creation of a creative product
3.	Socio-construction	Work in mini-groups, creating a joint (collective) product
4.	Socialization	Collective discussion of the problem
5.	Advertisement	Presentation of the results of the problem
6.	Break	Internal emotional conflict
7.	Reflection	Analysis of the work stages and feelings

Other variants of the algorithm of work are possible, subject to compliance with the general principles and rules of the methodical workshop conducting.

The methodical portfolio. A portfolio (briefcase) is a peculiar «dossier of achievements» of a person, his self-presentation. The idea of using a portfolio in the educational industry appeared in the United States in the 80's of the twentieth century.

In the pedagogical science, the portfolio is interpreted as a collection of works, a way of accumulating and evaluating individual achievements, an alternative way of evaluation, an exhibition of educational achievements etc. A portfolio can be of different types depending on the purpose: a portfolio of documents, process, exemplary; reflexive, problem-research, thematic portfolio; a portfolio of external achievements and a personal development (*Peyp, Choshanov, 2000; Dolzhenkov, Postoyan, 2015; Hal, Keresten', 2010*).

A portfolio is a technology of students' work with products of their creative, project activities, intended for demonstration, analysis, development of reflection, awareness of the results of their activities.

We agree with J. Peip and M. Choshanov that the pedagogical philosophy of the portfolio is to shift the emphasis on what the student does not know and cannot do to what he knows and can do; to transfer the pedagogical emphasis from the estimation of learning to self-estimation (*Peyp, Choshanov, 2000, p. 76*).

Researchers O. Dolzhenkov, T. Postoyan point out the following functions of the portfolio: diagnostic (fixes changes and growth rates of training); motivational (encouraging interaction in achieving positive results); content (maximally reveals the range of achievements and performed work); developmental (provides continuity of the process of development, education and upbringing); rating (shows the range and level of skills and abilities); goal-setting (supports educational goals defined by the standard) (*Dolzhenkov, Postoyan, 2015*). In our opinion, the reflexive function of the portfolio which consists in developing skills for evaluating oneself and own learning activities, forming reflexive abilities is one of the most important.

In the methodological training of future biology teachers, the creation of their own methodological portfolio will provide an opportunity to demonstrate the methodological knowledge and skills of students, their creative abilities, professional growth, it will help to identify and take into account the individual characteristics of the student, the formation of the ability to analyze and evaluate the results of their activities. While studying the disciplines of methodological direction, each student forms his own collection of materials, supplemented by its information which is obtained during the study of psychological and pedagogical disciplines, materials of pedagogical practice, etc.

Methodical portfolio is a collection of materials on the methodology of biology teaching, which serves for generalization and systematization of information, analysis of the experience of teaching biology, the presentation of own methodological ideas, as well as the reflection of own abilities, the comparison of achievements, etc.

In our opinion, the following structure is the most appropriate for a portfolio:

- «My portrait» («My profession and I»);
- «Methodical treasury» – a collection of practically significant information for the student on the methodology of teaching biology;
- «My results» – the materials which show the progress of the author of the portfolio in methodical work.

The technology of the portfolio consists of the following stages: *familiarization* (familiarization with the methodology for the portfolio production); *content* (definition of portfolio content); *procedural* (production of portfolio, collection and sorting of material); *reflexive* (mutual discussion with the student); *corrective* (remarks, additions, and corrections); *evaluative* (evaluation of learning outcomes by using a portfolio) (Hal, Keresten', 2010, p. 33).

Self-presentation and demonstration of a methodological portfolio is carried out in the form of a conference, competition-defense or a business game «Competition of a professional skill» or «Recruitment» (Zelenko N. V., Mogilevskaya, 2009, p. 63). Self-presentations involve demonstration of pedagogical knowledge and skills, theoretical substantiation of the proposed methods, forecasting directions of further work, joint analysis and evaluation of students' creative abilities and their methodological achievements. The future teacher should explain why he considers this work as own achievement, what changes he has seen in his pedagogical work, what else should be worked out. Unlike the traditional approach, where evaluation is fragmentary, according to individual tasks, the portfolio provides an opportunity to make a comprehensive assessment of student methodological training.

Pedagogical experiment on the introduction of innovative technologies in the training of future biology teachers took place at the Poltava National Pedagogical University named after V. G. Korolenko, Rivne State University of Humanities, Sumy State Pedagogical University named after A. S. Makarenko, Melitopol State Pedagogical University named after Bogdan Khmelnytsky, Kriviy Rig Pedagogical University, Chernihiv National Pedagogical University named after Taras Shevchenko, Central Ukrainian State Pedagogical University named after Volodymyr Vynnychenko, Uman State Pedagogical University named after Pavlo Tychyna, Kharkiv National University named after V. N. Karazin.

The results of the students' achievement in the control and experimental groups of methodical disciplines before and after the experiment are given in table. 3 and on fig. 1.

Table 3

Success of students of the control and experimental groups on methodological disciplines

	The control group (n=243)				The experimental group (n=239)			
	Before the experiment		After the experiment		Before the experiment		After the experiment	
Low	82	33,7%	77	31,7%	83	34,7%	34	14,2%
Average	107	44,1%	102	42,0%	104	43,5%	92	38,5%
Sufficient	50	20,6%	56	23,0%	49	20,5%	95	39,8%
High	4	1,6%	8	3,3%	3	1,3%	18	7,5%

As we can see from the table, in the experimental groups the following dynamics took place: the number of students with a low level of success decreased from 34,7% to 14,2% (increase - 20,5%), with the average level decreased from 43,5% to 38,5% (increase -5,0%), with a sufficient level increased from 20,5% to 39,8% (increase +19.3%), and with a high level – increased from 1,3% to 7,5% (increase +6,2%).

In the control group, the increase according to the levels was as follows: low – - 2%, average – +2,1%, sufficient – + 2,4%, high – + 1,7%. A slight increase gives grounds to argue that the traditional method is less oriented to master the

methodological knowledge and to develop the ability to perform various types of methodological activities.

Fig. 1. Results of students' progress in the control and experimental groups on methods of biology teaching

The effectiveness of the implemented of innovative technologies in methodological training of future biology teachers was proved using the testing of statistical hypotheses method according to the Pierson criterion.

Conclusions. Innovative learning technologies are important in the methodological training of future biology teachers. They contribute to the conscious learning of methodological knowledge, the formation of the necessary methodological skills and competencies, the development of student autonomy, their creative abilities, methodological reflection, critical thinking and the development of an individual methodological style, which ensures an increase in the level of methodological readiness of students for future professional activities.

Interactive technologies, case technologies, a project technology, a methodological workshop technology, a methodical portfolio are effective in the methodological training of future biology teachers. The usage of these technologies in experimental groups helped to reduce the number of students with a low level of success by 20,5%, with an average level by 5,0%, with a sufficient level by 19,3% and with a high level by 6,2 %.

The prospects for further research are seen in the search for new methods and means for improving the methodological training of students-biologists in pedagogical universities, the development of electronic textbooks and manuals on methods of teaching biology and other disciplines of methodological direction.

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OCENA ZGODNOŚCI KRAJOWEGO SYSTEMU TRANSPORTOWEGO DLA ZRÓWNOWAŻONEGO ROZWOJU¹

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Adnotacja. Artykuł zawiera wyniki badania dotyczącego utworzenia systemu monitorowania służącego do oceny stanu zgodności i procedur funkcjonowania krajowego sektora transportu w celu spełnienia wymogów i celów zielonej gospodarki. W artykule przeanalizowano stopień rozwoju infrastruktury transportowej i taboru pod względem ich jakości, niezawodności, trwałości i zgodności z krajowymi celami zrównoważonego rozwoju, w tym infrastruktury regionalnej i transgranicznej; monitorowanie procedur przekazywania wszystkich rodzajów transportu do trakcji elektrycznej i dostępności odpowiedniej sieci infrastruktury.

Utworzono system wskaźników zgodności infrastruktury transportowej i taboru z celami dziewiątego celu zrównoważonego rozwoju, przeprowadzono analizę sektora transportu i systemu wskaźników określających poziom bezpieczeństwa innowacyjnej infrastruktury drogowej i transportowej gospodarki narodowej. Wprowadzono monitorowanie zakresu stosowania ICT w transporcie i zbudowano system wskaźników ich zgodności z ustalonym krajowym CSR.

Rzeczywistość i celowość przeprowadzonych badań są określone przez zobowiązania Ukrainy do osiągnięcia Celów Zrównoważonego Rozwoju (CSR) zatwierdzonych na Szczycie ONZ w sprawie zgodności z globalnymi celami stworzenia przyjaznego dla środowiska, bezpiecznego i atrakcyjnego gospodarczo kompleksu transportowego;

Praktyczna orientacja uzyskanych wyników wynika z celowości ich wykorzystania przez władze państwowe w tworzeniu skuteczności legislacyjnej i programowej funkcjonowania przemysłu transportowego i dziedzin pokrewnych w zakresie zasad i zasad «zielonej» gospodarki oraz zgodnie z krajowym CSR.

Słowa kluczowe: «Zielona» gospodarka, kompleks transportowy, wskaźniki jakości, cele zrównoważonego rozwoju.

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ASSESSMENT OF THE CONFORMITY OF THE NATIONAL TRANSPORT SYSTEM FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. The article contains the results of the study on the formation of a monitoring system for assessing the state of compliance and procedures for the functioning of the national transport sector to meet the requirements and objectives of the green economy. The paper analyzes the degree of development of transport infrastructure and rolling stock in terms of their quality, reliability, sustainability and compliance with the national goals of sustainable development, including regional and cross-border infrastructure; monitoring of the provision of procedures for the transfer of all modes of transport to electric traction and the availability of the appropriate infrastructure network.

The system of indicators of the correspondence of transport infrastructure and rolling stock with the objectives of the Ninth Sustainable Development Goal has been formed, an analysis of the transport sector and a system of indicators for determining the level of security of the innovative road and transport infrastructure of the national economy have been carried out. The monitoring of the extent of the use of ICTs in transport was introduced, and the system of indicators for their compliance with the established national CSR was constructed.

Actuality and expediency of the conducted research are stipulated by Ukraine's obligations to achieve the Objectives of Sustainable Development (CSR) approved at the UN Summit on compliance with the global goals of creating an environmentally friendly, safe and economically attractive national transport complex;

The practical orientation of the results obtained is due to the expediency of their use by the state authorities in the formation of legislative and software effectiveness of the functioning of the transport industry and related fields on the principles and principles of the "green" economy and in accordance with the national CSR.

Keywords. «Green» economy, transport complex, indicators of quality, goals of sustainable development

Problem solving in general and its connection with important scientific or practical tasks.

Urbanization of the country, which leads to an accumulation of a large number of residents in cities, an increase in the number of personal vehicles from the population, an increase in cargo and passenger traffic in the traditional way of operating the transport system, will lead to uncontrolled deterioration of the state of the environment and, consequently, the quality of life of the population.

Today, the level of energy consumption and CO₂ emissions tend to increase, in spite of repeated warnings by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) that concluded (1) that in order to maintain a long-term increase in average temperature in the range of 2.0⁰ C to 2.4⁰C, global emissions of CO₂ to 2050 should decrease by at least 50% compared with 2000. Recent studies show that climate change is even faster than anticipated, and even the goal of "50% by 2050" may not be sufficient to prevent dangerous climatic changes.

In recent years, much attention has been paid to the importance of policy measures that focus on the mechanism of carbon emissions as a way to stimulate the development and dissemination of clean technologies necessary for the energy revolution. The

Copenhagen Climate Treaty, which has been signed by many countries, recognizes market approaches as a way of improving economic efficiency, but such measures (for example, the sale of carbon emission quotas) are most likely not necessarily the most effective for short-term investments in more expensive technologies that will benefit from long-term emission reductions. Moreover, a truly low-carbon world market is likely to be created only after many years. And so far, it is advisable to use a wide range of other tools that will help to create markets for advanced technologies that are consistent with national policy goals and which are supported, including by regulatory enactments, tax incentives, private programs, subsidies and information public shares. However, it is necessary to provide for a gradual reduction of state support, until its complete elimination after the technologies become competitive, or vice versa, if it turns out that they are unlikely to be able to become such. According to the IEA (2), conducted in 2010, to achieve 50% CO₂ emission reduction, state funding for low-carbon technologies should be two to five times the current level. The identified problems are a priority for many scholars - domestic and foreign (3-6), but the dynamics of change demonstrate the urgent need for research that should take into account the pace of degradation and unpredictable consequences. Moreover, the objectives set for the Sustainable Development Goals include the need to develop a high-quality, reliable and sustainable infrastructure, increased use of electric vehicles and the availability of an appropriate infrastructure network for it, and the provision of innovative road infrastructure development through, among other things, the expansion of state participation in various infrastructure projects, application of information and innovation technologies, etc. The fulfillment of these tasks requires the development of a system for assessing the quality of their achievement and ability for the long-term use in practice.

The purpose of the work is to create a monitoring system for assessing the level of compliance of the state and procedures of the functioning of the national transport sector with the requirements and objectives of the green economy in the directions defined by the goals of sustainable development for Ukraine.

Presenting main material.

Formation of indicators for developing a high-quality, reliable, sustainable infrastructure, including regional and cross-border infrastructure. The construction of any estimation system should be in line with the set objectives and the ultimate goal of the study, which may be complicated by the limited statistical data and factual material for performing qualitative work. In order to determine the state of development of the Ukrainian transport system within the objectives of the Sustainable Development Goals, the formation of indicators for the quality of its functioning, a number of indicators of the transport sector's activity in dynamics over the course of 5 years were analyzed with correlation both to the base period (2007) and to the values of the indicators established The United Nations as a guide for the desired level of development of national economies individual sectors. Separate the most significant indicators of transport activity, which are crucial for a general, holistic view of the state and problems associated with the transport complex of Ukraine for the period under study.

The determination of fluctuations in the number of cargos carried by all modes of transport in 2017, which amounted to 1582 million tons, led to the conclusion that the decrease compared to 2007 was 20.5%. However, despite such a worsening of volumes of transportation, in relation to the target indicators set for the UN 2020, 2025 and 2030, the value of 2017 differs from those set at 4.1%, 9.6% and 16.8%, respectively, which is

not is a critically different indicator of activity. The number of passengers carried for 2010-2017 in comparison with 2007, decreased by 43.4%, reaching 4,648 million people. Comparison with established target indicators shows a shortage of 10%, 15.5% and 22%, respectively, for years.

The dynamics of the chain indexes indicates a slight change in the indicators for 2010-2017 in Ukraine. Nevertheless, the largest drop in the volumes of cargo transportation was observed in 2014 – by 11.6%, and the number of passengers carried in the next, 2015, by 12.5%, which is due primarily to military actions on the Ukrainian territory and its consequences for all segments of the population and national economy. During the investigated period, 2010-2017, the most effective in both the volume of cargo transportation and the number of passengers carried is 2011, an increase of 6.9% and 2.0%, respectively. In subsequent years, the dynamics of changes are insignificant.

Against the background of the established changes, the degree of fixed assets wear for the "Transport, warehousing, postal and courier activities" in Ukraine remains rather high. So, in 2017, the share of wear was more than 50.0% of the total number of major. The worst situation with the available main means of transport, postal and courier activities was in 2014, when the total depreciation of assets reached 97.9%. Due to the decrease in fixed assets in 2015, when their share in total fixed assets at the initial (revalued) value decreased by 85.5%, an increase in the residual value of fixed assets in more than 3 times and a reduction in the percentage of their depreciation 97.9% to 51.7%, followed by a downward trend. Contrary to this improvement, the overall level of competitiveness of Ukraine is steadily deteriorating, and in 2017 it is 88th among 140 countries, in terms of infrastructure quality and its level of competitiveness - 81st place (primarily due to unsatisfactory state of highways). The analysis of the change in indicators shows a steady positive dynamics with regard to the degree of depreciation of fixed assets, starting in 2014, all other types of investigated variables changed without significant fluctuations.

Fig. 1. Dynamics of indexes of indicators of transport products, rolling stock and fixed assets to base year

Monitoring of the state of ensuring the expansion of the use of electric transport and the corresponding network of infrastructure was carried out through the analysis of the indices of rolling stock of electric vehicles for the study period, which showed a general reduction by 29.4%, and in the case of electric-battery cars of internal communication, the dynamics is – the number of trolleybus cars decreased by 39.3%, tram cars - by 30.1% and metro cars increased by 15.7%.

Fig. 2. Dynamics of rolling stock indices

With regard to the growth rate of movable property of all types of electric-battery cars, there is a slight annual fluctuation with the largest drop in trolleybus cars in 2014 by 25.1%, and the largest increase in subway carriages in the same year by 2.6%. The calculation of the indices of the number of rolling stock of electric-battery cars to the volumes of 2007 and the values of the UN target indicators identified a significant shortage of resources to achieve the established goals of sustainable development.

The amount of property for the analyzed years amounted to only 8.2% of the total number of all types of electric vehicles from the total rolling stock of the transport complex in 2011, and in its least value - 4.7% in 2014. With the set goal, the achievement of 65.0% of the rolling stock of electric-battery cars from the total volume to 2020 (70.0% and 75.0% in 2025-2030 respectively), the deficit is 60.2, 65.2 and 70.2 points from the values of 2017, respectively .

In connection with the lack of statistics on the total number of units of electric transport of domestic consumption (taking into account the number of private and public electric-based vehicles), absence of indicators of the total mileage of various types of electric vehicles in statistical data, indicators of the indirect determination, namely calculation of indices and rates of growth of total mileage of trucks and passenger buses indicators, performed on gasoline and diesel fuel. The use of such an approach will make it possible to form an idea about the scope of the use of innovative approaches to the introduction of principles and methods of the "green" economy into the work of the transport complex of Ukraine.

For the years studied, the volumes of freight cars and bus passenger transportation, which are performed on fossil fuels - gasoline and diesel fuel, despite the slight fluctuations, have a steady tendency to preserve the environmentally sensitive type of transportation both for goods and passengers. The growth rates of these indicators were the largest in 2011 by 11.5% of the mileage of trucks, which was performed on diesel fuel, and by 25.3% of the mileage of passenger buses, also performed on diesel fuel. The lowest figures are recorded in 2014, a 25% drop in gas mileage, and a drop of 37.4% of passenger buses, also performed on gasoline in the same year.

Against the background of the general reduction of traffic volumes in 2014, which was the result, first of all, of fighting in eastern Ukraine: by goods – only by 9.1%, by passengers – by 25%, data on volumes performed on fossil fuels , indicate the predominance of this type of transportation in industrialized regions of Ukraine, which exacerbates the extremely threatening condition of these regions in terms of environmental quality and insufficiency of environmental protection measures.

Even worse, the situation was in 2007, when the deviation from the indicators shows a drop in the volumes of transportation of goods in cars with gasoline engines by 41.2 points, with the growth of volumes of transportation on diesel fuel by 19 points (the overall deviation is a fall of 5.9 points).

In passenger traffic, in comparison with 2007 and 2017, the total volume drop was 10.1 points, gas transportation by 40 points, but the use of diesel fuel increased by 12.9 points.

The trend towards the transition to using diesel fuel as "dirty" fuel will form an extremely difficult environment, a threat to public health, which will result in the irreversibility of destructive processes and huge amounts of recovery funds in cases of expediency of implementing environmental protection procedures.

An analysis of the availability of road transport infrastructure based on the use of innovative technologies has been carried out by assessing and developing a system of indicators for such a level of security. The dynamics of changes in the rate of growth of indicators for the availability and quality of public utilities is practically stable, but the largest decrease was observed in 2014, by 4%, due primarily to the loss of territory of Ukraine, military actions in the country, slowdown of support and updating of the current infrastructure, deterioration of the general state of the national economy of Ukraine. Nevertheless, in comparison with 2007 and 2017, the share of hard-coated roads increased from 97.76% (2007) to 97.9% (2017) and amounted to 165.6 thousand km and 159, 6 thousand km respectively. One of the goals of sustainable development is the increase in the number of transport units, whose movement should be provided with renewable energy sources, instead of fossil fuels and lubricants. The precondition for this task is to provide a sufficient number of kilometers of roads of the requisite quality equipped with the necessary means of support - power stations of general use, points of car service with the relevant specialists, etc. Operating length of electric transport lines in comparison with 2007 decreased by 23,1% and in total it was only 5 thousand km - 3.4 thousand km of trolleybus lines, 1.6 thousand km of tram tracks and 113.4 km of tracks underground respectively. The analysis of the operational length indices did not reveal significant fluctuations in either or the other side. In terms of electric transport, the largest decline was observed in 2014, 2015 and 2016 in terms of the length of trolleybus electric lines (by 36.7% compared to the base year) with a gradual increase of 2.3% in 2017. The dynamics of the change in the length of the electric lines for trolleybuses practically repeats the overall trend (trolling and tram), namely a decline of 24.6% in 2015-2016 and a gradual increase in 2017 to 76.9%.

Another dynamics is observed with respect to the length of the metro tracks. During all studied years, kilometrage gradually increased from 5.2% in 2010 to 10.0% in 2017. The cross-sectional analysis with the number of rolling stock for these types of transportation showed: - an increase in the number of subway cars by 15.9 points, which logically forms a positive trend for the desired level of development of this type of transport. Concerns are caused by indicators of other modes of transport of domestic use - trams and trolleybuses, which show both the fall in the length of electric lines and the number of rolling stock - by 29.4 points in general compared with the base year, and even worse - by 60.2, 65.2 and 70.2 points respectively of the target.

The stopping of the development of domestic electric transport in Ukraine does not correspond to the obligations assumed by the government of Ukraine with the conclusion of international agreements and the approval of the Transport Strategy of

Ukraine until 2030 and may have consequences in the form of deterioration of the environment, lowering the quality of life of the population (in including increasing the incidence rate, especially through the most vulnerable sectors of the population - the elderly and children), the loss of the country's ability to consider the country as a reliable and investment but attractive partner. One of the important quantitative indicators of the trends taking place in the country is the availability of the infrastructure for ensuring the tasks defined by the main framework documents of the sectors of the country's economy. With regard to the transport sector, such a document is the Transport Strategy of Ukraine until 2030. The objectives laid down in it, declare a gradual, but irreversible, departure from the use of vehicles that are moving due to the work of their internal combustion engines (ICEs) – by 50.0% Until 2030, unfortunately, statistics on the number of cars on privately owned domestic vehicles from 2011 are absent, but the data for previous years are as follows: in 2007 – 5630.9 thousand units, in 2008 – 6090.4 thousand units, 2009 – 6216,7 thousand., In 2010 – 6470,5 thousand units, in 2011 – 6514,5 thousand units. Official statistical collections do not offer data on the registration of electric vehicles in Ukraine, while independent automobile associations offer the following data: by 2017, the number of registered cars has more than doubled and amounted to 3818 units. (+ 251%) (2016 – 1521 units (+ 364%), till 2016 – 418 units). Providing infrastructure - electric stations, including stations free of charge within the Tesla Club Ukraine program, are developing at the same pace: by 2016 – 62 units, 2016 – 144 units. (+ 232%), in 2017 – 577 units. (+ 400,7%), with practically increasing geometric progression in the development of this trend.

At the same time, these trends do not show any impact on the use of traditional methods of transfer and, accordingly, the use of the provisioning infrastructure for this. The number of petrol stations for fossil fuels has a steady tendency to increase, with the largest figures in 2013 by 17.5% and the lowest in 2017 – 2.4% in the base year. However, the rapid increase in the number of power stations to provide electric vehicles in recent years and the consolidation of the world trend for a massive transition to the use of electric vehicles, primarily private users, the refusal of many countries – primarily Norway (by 2015 100% switch to electric-based transport, now 24% of the automotive market is the niche of electric vehicles), France (from 2040 complete suspension of the sale of gasoline and diesel cars), Great Britain (zero emission of exhaust gases by 2050), Germany plans to 2030, although there are certain obstacles from the major automobile corporations, India (refusal to 2030), China – the leader of the sale of electric vehicles – 351 thousand units. for 2017, Israel, etc., on the use of internal combustion engines, on the one hand, sets the direction of development of the road transport market for Ukraine, on the other hand, increases the risk of forming the market for the sale of vehicles with internal combustion engine.

In this sense, the legislative conditions that need to be formed as a support for the expansion of the use of electric-based vehicles in Ukraine and the prevention of the introduction of obsolete models into its territory are important.

To date, the Verkhovna Rada has 2 Draft Laws "On Amendments to the Tax Code of Ukraine" that deal with the development of this area. This is the bill No. 5494-1 dated December 20, 2016, which proposes the introduction of cardinal preferences to support the processes of electromobility - the abolition of import duties for electric vehicles (today it amounts to 109,129 euros per unit), the abolition of value added tax - 1) operations importation into the customs territory of Ukraine and the subsequent delivery

on the customs territory of Ukraine of vehicles equipped exclusively with electric motors; 2) operations on the supply of services for the carriage of passengers by taxi, equipped exclusively with an electric motor (one or more); 3) operations on the provision of passenger transport for lease (leasing, hire, transportation to order). In addition, it is proposed temporarily, until January 1, 2025, to exempt from payment of the cost of parking services persons who place vehicles equipped with electric motors, on platforms for parking vehicles of state and communal forms of ownership, and to amend the rules of the road, which allow vehicles equipped with electric motors and vehicles equipped with internal combustion engines other than electric motors (hybrids), stroke, intended for the use of route transmissions sports facilities. At the meeting of the Transport Committee of the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine on September 5, 2018, nine draft laws were considered that are directly related to the development of the electric vehicle market in Ukraine and the provision of infrastructure for it. These are: draft Law No. 4033 of 07.19.2016, No. 5494 of 06.12.2016, 5494-1 of 20.12.2016, 7156 of 10.03.2017, 7156-1 of 17.10.2017, 7156-2 dated 17.10.2017, 7177 entry 05.10.2017, 8159 dated March 19, 2018, 8160 dated March 19, 2013. Such a rapid increase in the significance of issues of preservation of the natural environment and health of citizens should form and support the image of Ukraine as a modern social state. However, despite all the positive trends, there are a number of issues to be solved in the near future. The benchmark for these processes may be the number of petrol stations on fossil fuels, the largest share in 2012 – an increase of 2.4%, and a gradual decline in 2016 – by 0.8%, and in 2017 – by 3.8 % (as compared to the previous year). In addition, the index of the number of petrol stations in the base year was the largest in 2012 – 11.5% and the lowest – in 2017 – 2.4% with a gradual decline: in 2016 it is 106.5%, in 2017 – 102,4%.

It is expedient to use the index of expenses of fossil fuels – gasoline and diesel fuel for operation of trucks and passenger buses of enterprises and organizations of Ukraine, which we consider in dynamics, and in comparison with the base year. Unfortunately, these indicators are derived from the form of state statistical reporting, starting from 2016, so we can investigate the changes we have only this year. Nevertheless, there are certain trends, namely, the fall in the consumption of gasoline and cargo and passenger transport – the highest in 2013, by 26,9% (freight traffic) and in 2014 – by 39,0% (passenger transportation); the largest increase – in 2015, by 5.4% (passenger transportation). Regarding the consumption of diesel fuel: the largest drop, compared to the previous year, amounted to 22.3% (passenger traffic) in 2014 and – 14.1% (freight traffic) in the same year. The largest increase in 2011 is 25.0% of passenger buses and 13.6% of cargo vehicles.

Visually see the trend of change in the longer time range of the study and by comparison to the year chosen for the base. In this case, there is clearly a steady decline in the volume of fossil fuel use during the years under study: in 2014, the fall in gasoline use by 73.8% by passenger buses and by 2013 by 52.2% by trucks; a decline of 15.2% in diesel fuel used in trucks by 2015 and a 39.4% increase in passenger buses by 2015. Nevertheless, there is a general steady tendency to reduce the use of fossil fuels on Carriage: In 2015, the fall in gasoline volumes – by 69.2% (freight transport) and 73.8% (passenger transportation); diesel fuel – by 15.2% (freight transport) and by 9.7% (pass. transportation). Below is a visual representation of the obtained values (Fig. 3)

It is important to draw attention to the fact that the use of diesel fuel in the internal combustion engine leads, on the one hand, to a significant drop in carbon

dioxide emissions, on the other hand, the amount of emissions of combustion products in the form of fine particulate matter, as the most vulnerable fraction of harmful substances to human health and the environment, is quite large, which relates this type of fuel to extremely "dirty" and harmful energy sources. However, this type of fuel is both the most energy-intensive and the one that makes sense to be used in heavy work (careers, construction sites, processing of large sown areas, etc.), therefore, international practices have formed certain mechanisms for reducing the level of this fuel's hazard or completely preventing undesirable consequences. First of all, it is the use of high quality cleaning fuel, minimum Euro-5, and secondly, the equipment of internal combustion engines with special filters of multi-stage cleaning. These measures minimize the damage (ecological, social, and, consequently, economic) from the use of diesel fuel.

Fig. 3. Costs of fossil fuel for carriage of goods by car and passengers by bus

As indicators that are markers of compliance with the processes of providing environmental protection measures, we suggest the use of indicators of the number of protective plantings on Ukrainian highways. Taking into account the fact that road transport is the most "dirty" mode of transport, at least for today, those trends that show developed countries in transition to environmentally friendly modes of transport (marine, river, electric), and the volumes of use in this particular mode of transport in Ukraine (the share of road transport in the total volume of transport was: 66% in 2010, 70% in 2014, 71% in 2017, for comparison – 2 million tons of cargo was transported by sea, 4 million tons – by river in 2017, which is the indicator of the specific gravity of the partly small, so that the statistical analysis, unfortunately, not included) important environmental protection reduce the degree of adverse effects on the environment and population. In this sense, indicators can be used as a criterion: the number of protective plantings on public roads along the length of roads with protective stripes, the length of decorative protective strips, the number and area of green nurseries

The monitoring of the degree of application of ICTs in transport and the indicator proposed for determining the level of informatization of the transport complex of Ukraine (7–9) is an indicator of the share of value added at the cost of production of enterprises belonging to the medium-high technology sector of the processing industry, namely motor vehicles, trailers and semitrailers; other vehicles according to the CRED, in the total added value of production costs. Due to the fact that the proposed values of the target indicators are based on the various types of enterprises in the medium-tech industry sector of Ukraine, without separating the enterprises of production of means of transport, we have adopted these indicators only as such without the use of specific

quantitative values. The analysis of the dynamics of the share of value added shows steady tendencies to reduce the share of added value of innovations in the activities of vehicle manufacturers – from 21.6% (the largest value) to the total volume of innovative results in industrial enterprises of Ukraine, to 5.7% (the smallest value in 2011) compared to the previous year. Taking 2007 as a base, a negative trend is being made in reducing the innovation component in the volume of sales and in the amount of value added from this type of activity. Namely, the smallest indicator in 2011 is a fall of 15.9 points, the most positive results, with a decline of only 1.6 points in 2013 (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Dynamics of added value of innovative products at transport industry enterprises Make according to data: (10, 14-16)

The indicator proposed by us in addition is an indicator of the number of traffic counters - means for determining the intensity of traffic and the composition of the traffic flow on public highways. Analysis of the availability of the required number of meters as technical means of transport processes is appropriate in the case of studying the dynamics of intellectualization of transport flows and the determination of emissions of harmful substances, based on indicators of traffic intensity.

Qualitative assessment of the dynamics of changes in indicators for achieving Ukraine's sustainable development goals

Indicators for monitoring Sustainable Development Goals "Creating Sustainable Infrastructure" included an expanded set of indicators for the development of a high-quality, reliable, sustainable and sustainable infrastructure, including regional and cross-border infrastructure; ensuring the expansion of the use of electric transport and the corresponding infrastructure network; accessibility of road transport infrastructure based on the use of innovative technologies, in particular through expanding the forms of state participation in various infrastructure projects; application of information and communication technologies in transport.

Table 1

Indicators of achievement Sustainable development goals

The goal of sustainable development	Indicators adapted to Ukraine (basic)	Indicators using the OECD methodology	Author's indicators	Total
« Creating a Sustainable Infrastructure »	5	-	18	23

The analysis led to the conclusion that there is a steady tendency to increase the number of rolling stock on the electric traction, which indicates the need for appropriate measures to form the infrastructure of these processes, support of rolling stock users and investors involved in the development of this area, institutional procedures for their settlement. In 2017, the number of registered electric vehicles increased more than 2 times and amounted to 3818 units. (+ 251%) (2016 – 1521 units (+ 364%), till 2016 – 418 units). Providing infrastructure - electric stations, including stations free of charge within the Tesla Club Ukraine program, are developing at the same pace: by 2016 - 62 units, 2016 – 144 units. (+ 232%), in 2017 – 577 units. (+ 400,7%), with practically increasing geometric progression in the development of this trend.

In terms of electric public transport, the largest decline was observed in 2014, 2015, and 2016 in terms of the length of trolleybus electric lines (by 36.7% compared to the base year) with a gradual increase of 2.3% in 2017. Dynamics of change in the length of electric lines for trolley buses practically repeats the general trend (trolleybuses and trams), namely a decline of 24.6% in 2015-16 and a gradual increase in 2017 to 76.9%.

The dynamics of changes in the number of rolling stock of electric transport of domestic use is also negative, in 2017 this figure amounted to 4.8% of the total number of rolling stock, and compared with the base year showed a drop of 29.4%.

In comparison with the target indicators of the installed relative amount of electric transport of domestic use, the shortage is: compared with 2020 – 60.2 points, from 2025 – 65.2 points, and from 2030 – 70.2 points. This tendency is extremely negative, and in the absence of any cardinally directed development strategies for this type of transport, it indirectly contributes to supporting the increase of vehicles on internal combustion engines and raising the level of pollution of residential areas.

The tendency is a tendency to decrease the wear and tear of vehicles, warehousing, postal and courier activities, where the indicator amounted to 50.8% in 2017, which practically reaches the value of 2020 set by the goals of sustainable development by 49% and only by 5 points does not correspond to the indicator set for 2030. This tendency forms a steady basis for improving the state of the air due to the reduction of the chemical, noise load on it, updating the rolling stock on modern environmentally friendly means of transport.

Negative is the dynamics of the number of goods and passengers transported by all types of transport. But if the value of freight rates increased by 4.7% in 2016, then passenger traffic showed a 4.2% decrease compared to 2017, as well as a general drop in comparison with the base year and cargo, and by passengers by 20.5% and 43.4% respectively. That is, the problems of raising the level of mobility of the population remain unresolved, especially through the use of an environmentally-protected transportation method. The study of the dynamics of output by the index of industrial output shows a decline in industrial production. This is indirectly confirmed by an analysis of the dynamics of transport product indicators through volumes of transported cargoes (falling by 20.5%), since transport is closely linked to inter-branch links with all other industries and is largely inclined to influence these industries on the results of their activities. In comparison with the targets for 2020, 2025 and 2030, the national transport system has a shortage of goods in transportation of 4.5%, 9.6% and 16.8% respectively, and for transported passengers – 10.6%, 15.5% and 22.5% respectively. Nevertheless, the tendency of increase of indexes of freight and passenger transportation carried out on

fossil fuel is negative. Although the total volume of such freight transport in Ukraine decreased by 17.4% in 2017 and by 70.4% in gasoline, during this period the volume of transport carried out on diesel fuel increased by 15.1% compared to the previous year. The analysis of indicators in accordance with the base year also showed a drop in the total volume of freight transport in fossil fuels by 5.9%, of which gasoline transportation was carried out by 41.2% less, but the use of diesel fuel increased by 19.0%. Regarding passenger transportation, the analysis of data for 2017 in comparison with the previous one shows the following: a fall in the total volume of fossil fuel transportation by 18.0%, of which 76.7% is lower in gasoline and 21.1% increased volumes of transportation on diesel fuel. Data on the base year looks more encouraging: a drop of 10.1% of the total volume, or 40.0% on gasoline. However, in relation to diesel fuel, the same happened as in the transport of goods, and the growth in passenger traffic by 12.9%. The analysis of fuel consumption volumes has the same trend (relative to the base year): with a maximum drop in 2015 by 69.2% of freight traffic, and a drop of 72.4% of passenger traffic carried out on gasoline. An important component of the tracking of traffic flows, the formation of ideas about the state of roads, tensions, volumes of transportation, is the availability of traffic counting counters. Reducing their number deprives the opportunity to conduct high-quality monitoring of traffic flows, to take necessary corrective measures. Such tendencies should be constantly investigated at the state level not only in terms of the impact on the state of the environment, but also on the quality of life of the population and its health. First of all, this concerns the necessity of taking protective measures in the settlements, in places of the greatest concentration of citizens, production and transport routes, and the necessity to use the fuel of the necessary quality, it is expedient to form and implement programs of ecologization of cities and villages, to design new transport systems quality and safety, to implement state policy in the field of interaction with investors by creating attractive mutually beneficial conditions for attraction of investments on the development of modern transports systems.

One of the most important conditions for the implementation of the above is the increase of the share of enterprises in the total volume of production, which will receive added value from the sale of innovative products. Analysis of the dynamics of the share of value added of such products at the cost of production of vehicle manufacturers shows that, contrary to the growth of this indicator by 10.4% in 2015, the value in comparison with the base year decreased by 70.0%, first of all, due to a steep drop in the share of innovative products in the total value added in 2011 to 5.7%

That is, the tasks set out in the program document on achieving Ukraine's Sustainable Development Goals for the next decade can be achieved through the introduction of a national Strategy for the Development of Environmental, "Green" Transport, which should include radical transformations in this area, reinforcing its intentions with institutional provision, economic and financial implementation mechanisms, tools for implementing state supervision and monitoring the fulfillment of the established requirements.

Contrary to the positive trend of growth of some indicators, such as the length of operation length of electric transport lines of domestic use and the number of traffic meters in the total flow, all the latest survey data showed a general fall in the calculation as in previous years, even more in comparison with the base year. In fact, the analysis of the results of the transport sector, which was the subject of this study, reflects the

national vulnerability of infrastructure provision and the lack of modern rolling stock. Requirements for observance of environmental measures defined by the Transport Strategy of Ukraine until 2030 do not have practical support for any assets, their system modernization, growth of use of innovative transport products, etc.

Among the positive trends, we must emphasize the decline in vehicle wear, starting from 2015 (from 97.9% to 50.8% in 2016), reducing the run of trucks and passenger buses, which are performed on gasoline, and the total cost of fossil fuels, gasoline and diesel fuel, for the transport of trucks and passenger buses.

Conclusions. Among the areas for improvement of the situation in Ukraine in relation to the goal of "Creating a Sustainable Infrastructure" in the direction of the goals and objectives of the "green" economy, the following should be highlighted:

- road equipment with a sufficient number of traffic counters, which will lead to an examination not only of the average daily and hourly traffic volume, but also the composition of the traffic flow through the use of vehicle classifiers. That is, the distribution of vehicles by their types is an essential element of the procedures for regulating and coordinating the environmental tension of the studied areas. Although there is a certain trend in the growth of the number of traffic counters for the period from 2007 to 2017, which is positive, unfortunately, it is burdened by a decrease in the index of value added of innovative products at the expense of enterprises – the production of vehicles for the same period, which does not have the necessary cumulative positive environmental protection effect from the impact of transport flows on the state of the environment and public health. As the traffic flow is not only a source of chemical and noise pollution, but also the largest user of fossil fuels and a source of agricultural land degradation from mobile vehicles and stationary equipment, the source of environmental overheating from the operation of ICEs and stationary installations on fossil fuels, sources of electromagnetic radiation and vibration, large volumes of carbon in the form of soot, ash elements, etc., the combined negative effect of transport on the environment and health of people is a serious threat to national scale.

- the transition of rolling stock moving on the territory of Ukraine to Euro 4 - Euro 6 fuel by introducing preferential schemes for encouraging rolling stock owners to use fuel of this type. However, the general tasks set by the Articles of the National Transport Strategy until 2030 with a radical reduction of emissions of pollutants, carbon dioxide, nitrogen oxide, sulfur dioxide, etc. can not be solved without the introduction of innovative technologies in the production of vehicles, in the equipment of stationary devices, environmental protection measures, use of fuel type, not less than Euro 4–Euro 6 for vehicles with ICE, increase in the volume of use of vehicles on electric traction, etc., therefore

- institutional support to support the use of rolling stock on an electrical traction through the adoption of the Draft Law "On Amendments to the Tax Code of Ukraine", which will promote the creation of attractive conditions for owners of such rolling stock and investors in the development of infrastructure maintenance of electric vehicles;

- increase of the share of public electric transport in the total amount of travel by the population by: – bridgement of route cars, major transport polluters of settlements; – increasing number of units of modern rolling stock of public transport, including taking into account the needs of people with disabilities; – implementation of the policy of encouraging the population to use public transport; – forming a flexible, convenient fare

system ("single" flowers, electronic flowers, fixed-flowered flowers, provided that they are used within a certain period of time, etc.);

– creation of preferential conditions for enterprises in which the share of innovative products in the total value added demonstrates positive changes in the dynamics;

– an increase in the length of the roads with hard cover and the total area (and the number) of protective strips, which will ensure that the level of air pollution will be reduced due to mechanical, chemical and noise pollution of the environment, will stop the rapid degradation of rural lands. Negative are the tendencies of reducing the length of roads with hard cover, the number, area and length of green plantations along the roads of general use, against the background of the growth of total volumes of use of fossil fuels and increase of mileage of motor transport on diesel fuel (10-19), reduction of rolling stock of electric transport of internal use. It is possible to consider the positive dynamics as the rapid growth over the last years under study, 2016-2017, the number of mobile vehicles by electric traction and the number of infrastructure objects that ensure their movement.

Results in the area of formation the indicators of achievement The goals of sustainable development allow us to determine the overall dynamics of changes (growth, decrease) of key indicators for 2007-2017 in Ukraine, and provide a qualitative assessment of such changes (positive – P, negative – H, without significant changes – BZ, the target indicator has not been reached – TNR, evaluation needs additional research – AR). A qualitative assessment of the direction and nature of changes in the indicators for achieving the goals of sustainable development is presented in Annex 1.

Appendix 1

Table 1

Qualitative assessment of the dynamics of changes in the indicators of achievement of the Goal of Sustainable Development

Index	Dynamics of changes: increase ↑ decrease ↓	Estimation of dynamics: P; H; BZ; TNR; AR*
1	2	3
1.1. Develop a high-quality, reliable, sustainable and sustainable infrastructure, including regional and cross-border infrastructure.		
1.1.1. Volume of transported cargoes, million tons	↓	H, TNR
1.1.2. Number of passengers transported, million people	↓	H, TNR
1.1.3. Degree of depreciation of fixed assets for the NED "Transport, warehousing, postal and courier activities", %	↓	P, TNR, AR
1.1.4. Indices of carriage of goods and passengers, % in 2007, target indicators 2020-2025-2030	↓; ↓	H, AR
1.1.5. Indices of the degree of wear and tear of fixed assets in% to 2007, target indicators 2020-2025-2030	↓	P, AR
1.2. Ensure the expansion of the use of electric vehicles and the corresponding infrastructure network		
1.2.1. The share of rolling stock of electric vehicles, %	↓	BZ, AR
1.2.2. Dynamics of the share of rolling stock of electric vehicles, %	↓	H, TNR, AR

1.2.3. <i>Indices of indicators of rolling stock of electric vehicles in % to 2007, target indicators 2020-2025-2030</i>	↓	H, TNR, AR
1.2.4. <i>Total mileage of trucks of enterprises and organizations of Ukraine, and those performed on gasoline and diesel fuel, thousand km</i>	↓ ↓ ↑	BZ, AR P, AR H, AR
1.2.5. <i>The dynamics of the growth rate of the total run of trucks and passenger buses of enterprises and organizations of Ukraine, and those performed on gasoline and diesel fuel points</i>	↓ ↓ ↑	BZ, AR P, AR H, AR
1.2.6. <i>The total mileage of passenger buses of enterprises and organizations of Ukraine, and those performed on gasoline and diesel fuel, thousand km</i>	↓ ↓ ↑	BZ, AR P, AR H, AR
1.2.7. <i>The index of total mileage of trucks of enterprises and organizations of Ukraine, and those performed on gasoline and diesel fuel, %</i>	↓ ↓ ↑	Π, AR Π, AR H, AR
1.2.8. <i>The index of the total mileage of passenger buses of enterprises and organizations of Ukraine, and those performed on gasoline and diesel fuel, % to 2007</i>	↓ ↓ ↑	P, AR P, AR H, AR
1.3. Ensure accessibility of road transport infrastructure based on the use of innovative technologies, in particular through expanding the forms of state participation in various infrastructure projects		
1.3.1. <i>The share of public use roads of national importance with a rigid covering that meet the regulatory requirements, %</i>	↓	H
1.3.2. <i>The dynamics of the share of public use roads of national importance with a hard covering that meet the regulatory requirements, (+, - to previous year)</i>	↓	BZ
1.3.3. <i>The index of length of public roads with hard cover (+, - compared with 2007)</i>	↓	H, AR
1.3.4. <i>Length of operating length of lines of electric transport of internal use, km</i>	↑	P
1.3.5. <i>Dynamics of the growth rate of lines of electric transport over the years</i>	↑	P
1.3.6. <i>Index of length of operation length of lines of electric transport to base year</i>	↓	H, AR
1.3.7. <i>The length of the transport routes, which are equipped with protective stripes, thousand km</i>	↓	BZ
1.3.8. <i>The index of the length of the traffic routes, which are equipped with protective bands, to the base year</i>	↓	H
1.3.9. <i>The length of decorative plantations, km number of green nurseries, units. area of green nurseries, units.</i>	↓ ↓ ↓	BZ, AR BZ, AR BZ, AR

1.3.10. <i>The index of the length of the decorative plantations, km</i>	↓	H, AR
<i>number of green nurseries, units.</i>	↓	H, AR
<i>area of green nurseries, units.</i>	↓	H, AR
1.3.11. <i>Number of petrol stations, units.</i>	↑	H, AR
1.3.12. <i>The number of petrol stations to the base year</i>	↑	H
1.3.13. <i>Gasoline consumption index to base year:</i>	↓	P, AR
<i>- trucks</i>	↓	P, AR
<i>- by passenger buses</i>	↓	P, AR
1.3.14. <i>The index of diesel fuel consumption to the base year:</i>	↓	P, AR
<i>- trucks</i>	↓	P, AR
<i>- by passenger buses</i>	↓	BZ, AR
1.4. Ensure accessibility of road transport infrastructure based on the use of innovative technologies, in particular through expanding the forms of state participation in various infrastructure projects		
1.4.1. <i>Share of value added at the cost of production of enterprises belonging to the medium-high-tech manufacturing sector, namely motor vehicles, trailers and semitrailers; other vehicles according to the CRED, in the total added value of production costs,%</i>	↓	H
1.4.2. <i>Dynamics of the share of added value of innovative products at the cost of production of enterprises producing vehicles</i>	↓	H
1.4.3. <i>The dynamics of the index of added value of innovative products at the cost of production of enterprises producing vehicles</i>	↓	H
1.4.4. <i>Counters of traffic accounting, units.</i>	↑	P
1.4.5. <i>Index of traffic count meters,% to base year</i>	↑	P

*Prepare by autor (10-20)

** Legend: **P** – positive dynamics; **H** – negative dynamics; **BZ** – without significant changes; **TNR** – the target indicator has not been reached; **AR** – evaluation needs additional research.

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PROBLEM ROZWOJU MYŚLENIA KRYTYCZNEGO: HISTORIA I TERAŻNIEJSZOŚĆ

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Adnotacja. W artykule przeanalizowano poglądy naukowe zagranicznych i ukraińskich nauczycieli na temat rozwoju myślenia krytycznego. Wyjaśniono główne cechy myślenia krytycznego, podkreślono elementy myślenia krytycznego, określono jego cechy, zaproponowano strukturę krytycznego myślenia, przedstawiono podstawowe umiejętności, które mogą scharakteryzować stopień rozwoju myślenia krytycznego. Podsumowując różne podejścia do interpretacji istoty myślenia krytycznego, autor rozpatrytuje myślenie krytyczne w kontekście pedagogicznym za zdolność tych, którzy się uczą analizować informacje o szkoleniu, stosować wyniki zarówno w standardowych jak i niestandardowych sytuacjach i zadaniach. Autor artykułu podkreśla, że myślenie krytyczne jest przede wszystkim myśleniem indywidualnym, ponieważ obejmuje zdolność studenta do samodzielnego wyciągania wniosków na podstawie analizy informacji, szukania argumentów w tekście, oceny ich wiarygodności i wartości, podczas gdy myślenie krytyczne ma charakter społeczny, ponieważ każda opinia jest weryfikowana i uzasadniana tylko wtedy, gdy jest udostępniona innym uczniom.

Słowa kluczowe: myślenie, myślenie krytyczne, technologia rozwoju myślenia krytycznego, cechy myślenia krytycznego, elementy myślenia krytycznego.

PROBLEM OF DEVELOPMENT OF CRITICAL THINKING: HISTORY AND PRESENT

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Annotation. The article analyzes the scientific views of foreign and Ukrainian teachers on the problem of developing critical thinking. The main characteristics of critical thinking are highlighted, elements of critical thinking are defined, its signs are identified, the structure of critical thinking is proposed, basic skills are presented that can characterize the degree of critical thinking development. Summarizing the various approaches to the interpretation of the essence of critical thinking, the author of the article considers critical thinking in the pedagogical context as the ability of learners to analyze educational information, to apply the results in both standard and non-standard situations and tasks. The author of the article notes that critical thinking is primarily individual thinking, because it implies the student's ability to independently draw conclusions based on the analysis of information, look for arguments in the text, evaluate their reliability and value, and at the same time critical thinking has a social character, since thought is verified and justified only when it is shared with other students.

Keywords: thinking, critical thinking, technology for developing critical thinking, signs of critical thinking, components of critical thinking.

ПРОБЛЕМА РОЗВИТКУ КРИТИЧНОГО МИСЛЕННЯ: ІСТОРІЯ ТА СЬОГОДЕННЯ

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Анотація. У статті проаналізовано наукові погляди зарубіжних та українських педагогів на проблему розвитку критичного мислення. Висвітлено основні характеристики критичного мислення, виділено елементи критичного мислення, визначено його ознаки, запропоновано структуру критичного мислення, представлено основні вміння, які можуть охарактеризувати ступінь розвитку критичного мислення. Узагальнюючи різні підходи щодо трактування сутності критичного мислення, автор статті розглядає критичне мислення в педагогічному контексті як здатність тих, хто навчається, аналізувати навчальну інформацію, застосовувати отримані результати як в стандартних, так і в нестандартних ситуаціях і завданнях. Автор статті наголошує, що критичне мислення є передусім мисленням індивідуальним, оскільки передбачає здатність учня самостійно робити висновки на основі аналізу інформації, шукати в тексті аргументи, оцінювати їх достовірність і цінність, та водночас критичне мислення має соціальний характер, так як кожна думка перевіряється і обґрунтовується лише тоді, коли нею діляться з іншими учнями.

Ключові слова: мислення, критичне мислення, технологія розвитку критичного мислення, ознаки критичного мислення, компоненти критичного мислення.

Introduction. The urgency of developing critical thinking is still obvious, since social changes and the latest achievements of modern science and practice place high demands on applicants for education. The development of critical thinking and the ability to make decisions is considered the basis of learning in the 21st century.

Today, the problem of developing critical thinking is actively considered by psychologists, educators, and methodologists. It is important to turn to the origins of the idea of developing critical thinking, to carry out a more in-depth analysis of this phenomenon, to trace the evolution of the idea of developing critical thinking in education.

The purpose of the article is to reveal the essence of the concept of «critical thinking» as a pedagogical category through the prism of historical analysis.

Main part. The issue of developing critical thinking is not new for Ukrainian and foreign education because about the need to develop elements of critical thinking among students was asserted in ancient times by well-known teachers and practising teachers. Thus, in the Middle Ages, scholastic-dogmatic methods of teaching prevailed, since education was influenced by the Christian church, therefore the formal-logical thinking prevailed. The dogmatic way of thinking was criticized by progressive educators who opposed scholastic school education. In particular, M. Montaigne called on teachers to teach children to think, creatively comprehend what they read, to build learning on the independent adoption the material: «Let the tutor compel the student to sift through the sieve everything that he gives him, and the student, if he can, makes a choice on their own» (Volinka, 1991, p. 114). M. Montaigne recommended teachers to evaluate students not by what knowledge they have, but by what they can do with the help of this knowledge.

J. Comenius in the work of «The Great Didactic» writes: «The method of teaching all subjects shows that schools strive to teach children to look with other people's eyes, to think with someone else's mind. Schools are not taught to open up sources and to bring out various streams from there» (Kamenskij, 1983, p. 37). J. Comenius argued that it is necessary to teach so that children gain knowledge not only from books and verbal reasoning but also from observations, things that surround them, through the study of causal relationships.

J. Locke continued these ideas in the pedagogical work «Some Thoughts Concerning Education» arguing that the student should not passively reproduce the studied material, but to draw conclusions, generalizations independently, and the teacher should, first of all, develop the logical thinking of the pupils (Volinka, 1991, p. 114).

During the Renaissance, teachers developed pupils' abilities through active learning, independent knowledge of the world around them, tried to form an interest in knowledge, to create in an educational institution an environment where learning would become easy and enjoyable, to promote self-knowledge of pupils, to develop creative thinking. J. Pestalozzi created a peculiar system of developing pupils' skills of independence and creativity. At the center of his concept is a pupil who develops harmoniously in the process of learning, he considered the tandem of the teacher and pupil inseparable (Pestalocci, 1981).

Famous Ukrainian educators wrote about the development of independent, creative thinking. H. Skovoroda in his writings drew attention to cognitive activity as an effective means of self-knowledge and self-improvement, the development of a conscious initiative, creative thinking, which must form pupils' desire to study independently (Skovoroda, 1992). A. Dukhnovich, author of the first textbooks in Zakarpattia, affirmed the principle of natural conformity in the school educational process, taking into account the age and individual characteristics of the pupils. The educator promoted such forms of organization of the lesson that develop children's attention, observation, and ability to learn independently. K. Ushinsky wrote about the independence of thinking, believed that other people's thoughts were harmful, a person adopts them faster than he understands. The strong foundation of any effective learning is the development of the student's creative cognitive activity, provided that it will be: diverse in types, based on own observations and analysis of facts, based on previous experience, introducing a new element (Ušins'kij, 1949).

About the development of independent thinking of schoolchildren spoke I. Franko (1960), who defended learning that contributes to the formation of a free man, with a sense of personal dignity and with the right to choose, condemned the educational process, which makes the student take and praise only those thoughts «which came into his head, but does not allows you to treat them critically, does not allow to ask: So it should be? Where is it from?» (p. 186). I. Franko sharply criticized the education system, which was built as if on purpose «in order to kill every living, healthy thought in the minds of young people, turn it to objects of the dead and empty, and distract them from life and honest work, demoralize them as a slave in front of the strong and the rich, and destroy any spark of criticism and own initiative» (p. 191).

B. Hrinchenko was convinced that the main goal of the school should be a well-organized educational system, which stimulates the development of pupils' mental strength, and does not provide ready information. Independent thinking, according to the teacher, will help schoolchildren in working with new information.

V. Sukhomlynsky (1977) paid a lot of attention to the development of independent creative thinking. In his writings, he advised to educate pupils in the desire to learn the world around them, performing complex mental operations: analysis, synthesis, comparison, a generalization; to learn to observe, to explore, to make their own conclusions.

As we can see, domestic and foreign scientists note the inseparable relationship between learning and thinking. In different historical periods, the approaches to learning were also not the same: to replace the dogmatic way of thinking, when pupils took over the experience of others without proper understanding, information – without in-depth analysis, it came independent, creative one. Modern scholars and practising teachers criticize the educational process, focused on the preparation of obedient, passive performers, pupils who are incapable of active creative activity, they advised paying attention to the development of logical, independent and critical thinking. Therefore, in recent decades, in the European and domestic educational system, special attention has been paid to the development of critical thinking, since it allows a person to solve actual problems. A person who can think critically is able to consciously perceive the surrounding reality, doubt, analyze, defend his opinion, is able to self-realize and assert himself.

In pedagogical literature, critical thinking is considered as a higher-order thinking based on information, during the processing of which an opinion rating, hypotheses, and ways of proving them take place.

In their writings, domestic scholars often rely on the ideas of foreign teachers: J. Dewey, D. Cluster, A. Crawford, K. Meredith, S. Matthew, R. Paul, K. Popper, J. Stila, C. Templand, and others. Thus, the founder of the Institute of Critical Thinking at the Montclair State University, Professor at Columbia University M. Lipman considered critical thinking as an urgent need for life in the modern world, because this ability allows you to solve properly a wide range of practical problems in any professional activity: architect, lawyer, doctor etc., in human relationships, in scientific activities, in everyday life.

According to M. Lipman, critical thinking is thinking characterized by constant self-improvement of the individual; a process when pupils move from simple value judgments and elementary argumentation to mastering the corresponding way of thinking – the ability to perform a meaningful analysis; This type of thinking is necessary for solving extraordinary practical problems when we faced with difficult choices that require thinking and evaluation. With the help of critical thinking, it is best to teach pupils to correctly argue their thoughts, to identify mistakes in their or alien argumentation, to determine the validity or unlawfulness of evaluations, ideas and solutions.

«We must stimulate the students to think independently, not only to study what others have come to, as well as to formulate their own good judgments and sentences», asserted M. Lipman (Lipman, 2006, p. 17-18). Therefore, according to the scientist, it is necessary to know the defining characteristics, signs, features of critical thinking in comparison with other types of thinking, and also to find out the results and the fundamental conditions of its formation and development. The researcher (Lipman, 2006) emphasized that critical thinking contributes to high-quality judgment, because: a) it is based on criteria; b) is such that it itself is adjusted; c) is sensitive to the context (p. 18).

M. Lipman identifies six main elements of critical thinking:

1) possession of certain techniques that collectively create an effective information processing methodology that has been tested in practice;

2) responsibility, which provides that a person, turning to others, is aware of the obligation to provide listeners or readers with arguments and examples in accordance with accepted standards or to question them with the help of convincing reasoning;

3) the formulation of independent judgments as a product of thinking;

4) reliance on criteria, which are provisions, takes into account a critical-minded person, evaluating ideas in the process of analyzing or criticizing them (for example, standards, laws, secondary legislation, rules, regulations, guidelines, instructions, behavior guidelines, requirements, terms, restrictions, conventions, norms, agreements on unification, principles, predictions, definitions, ideals, goals, intentions, test results, experimental data, methods, procedures, etc.);

5) the possibility of self-correction of their own judgments in order to correct or improve them;

6) attention and sensitivity to the context which should not contradict the use of common criteria.

D. Cluster (2001) emphasizes that critical thinking is informative thinking, which begins with the formulation of a question, strives for convincing argumentation and has a social character. (p. 37). J. Dewey argues that, due to critical thinking, routine learning becomes a purposeful activity, in which pupils are involved in intellectual work and solve of real-life problems.

Interesting for our study are the characteristics of the critical thinking of D. Cluster, to which he relates the following:

1) independence: each formulates his ideas, values and beliefs independently of others. No one can think critically of the other; everyone does it exclusively for himself. However, critical thinking does not have to be completely original: one person may perceive the idea or belief of another person as his own. The main thing is that everyone at the same time decided what to think;

2) focus on thinking, evaluation, and not on knowledge, because information is the starting point, not the final point of critical thinking. Knowledge creates a base without which a person cannot think critically. To express a complex thought, it is necessary to process a considerable amount of facts, ideas, theories, concepts;

3) the persuasion of the argumentation: a critical-minded person finds his own solution to the problem and reinforces this decision with reasonable, feasible evidence. She also realizes that other solutions to the same problem are possible, and she tries to prove that her solution is optimal. A critical thinker with convincing arguments is able to resist even such authorities as the strength of tradition, the opinion of the majority — such a person cannot be manipulated;

4) sociality: every thought is checked and improved when it is shared with others. When people discuss, argue, exchange ideas with other people, they clarify and deepen their position (Kluster, 2001, p. 39-40).

The accumulation of knowledge, the level of theoretical training are important for mental development, but the amount of knowledge, acquired in the learning process, does not always indicate a positive change in mental development. Quite often, pupils mechanically memorize a certain set of facts, concepts, laws, not understanding, not realizing them, which leads to the formalism of knowledge and their reproduction on a pattern. For modern education, it's not so much the knowledge itself is important, but also the ability to operate it in solving theoretical and practical problems, the ability to use it in different conditions and acquire new knowledge. Therefore, psychologists and

educators note that «for the development of thinking are important both the accumulation of a fund of knowledge and a fund of well-developed and well-established mental techniques (intellectual operations)» (Kruteckij, 1986, p. 16), through which the acquisition of knowledge and operating them.

It is very important in the learning process «to take care not only to give pupils knowledge but also to form their respective skills», therefore, the methods and techniques of mental activity, the intellectual skills that a pupil uses during the acquisition of knowledge, is one of the objective indicators of the level and the quality of knowledge. At the same time, the intellectual development of the individual is not limited to a set of knowledge and mental skills; mental activity, in addition to intellectual processes, also includes cognitive interests, attitude to learning – what is called the motivational aspect and the necessary condition for mental activity.

S. Matthews believes that in the classroom with the use of critical thinking technology, teachers model the thinking process and support pupils when they talk about their thinking strategies; there is an atmosphere of search and openness; pupils have support, but such and only to the extent that they really need; the learning space is built in such a way as to make the cooperation and communication of pupils easy and natural (Krouford, 2006, p. 16).

According to scientists A. Crawford, V. Saul, S. Matthews, D. Macinster, pupils learn the material most fully and for the benefit of themselves by means of active methods, if they are oriented towards the achievement of specific goals and well organized. Such studies, according to researchers, are most successful, because pupils are encouraged to think independently and to do critical thinking. Pupils reflect on what they study, apply what they have learned in real life or for further study and are able to continue to learn independently. Researchers make an important conclusion for us that learning, the results of which can be used and the products of which are durable, it is an effective use of the teacher's time and the means of society than the education that leaves students passive, tires the teacher with monotony and the products are soon forgotten because are not used in practice and do not develop in any way (Krouford, 2006, p. 11)).

Recently, many works of Ukrainian scientists have appeared on the problem of the formation of critical thinking of pupils and students. In particular, O. Pometun, S. Terno, L. Terletska, A. Marchenko, T. Khachumyan, and others offer their own studies of the development of critical thinking. O. Pometun asserts that critical thinking is: a) thinking, which promotes to the formation of a person's ability to be aware of his position on a particular issue, the ability to find new ideas, to analyze events and critically evaluate them; b) non-standard thinking based on the ability to see and evaluate alternatives, priorities, determine the reliability and expediency of facts, phenomena, events; c) practical thinking, which, based on theoretical knowledge, makes it possible to make the necessary decisions; d) reflexive thinking is a way to correct and repair by a person for mistakes made in the process of his thinking, which is in continuous search; e) a multilevel and variable phenomenon, it reflects moral and ethical attitudes, socio-political features, evaluative experience, value orientations, human knowledge, ways of mental and practical actions; f) thinking which aimed at finding strategies to solve life and learning problems, identifying and evaluating alternatives and priorities, their feasibility, determining the reliability of facts, phenomena, events, development of it promoted skills and abilities, synthesis, comparison, a juxtaposition of facts, formulation of reasonable conclusions; g) thinking, which is based on the ability

of a person to distinguish the value of information, in other words, to separate the necessary information from the unnecessary. It is aimed at processing information using effective thinking techniques (analysis, synthesis, comparison, a combination of facts, etc.) and its assessment relative to the source, experience, observation, correct reasoning and collected data (Pometun, 2010, p. 47).

O. Pometun emphasizes that the educational process focused on the formation of critical thinking of children must necessarily be organized as a study of a specific topic, which is carried out through the interactive pupils' communication. To be effective in this case, teachers should use cooperative learning as common tools with all the methods and techniques of working in small groups, projects, experimental exercises, simulations, sociological research, etc. (Pometun, 2010, p. 6).

According to the researcher, the teacher acts as an organizer of the learning process, a consultant, a facilitator, and does not «lock in» the training for herself. Relationships between pupils, their interaction and cooperation are key in the learning process. With such an organization of training, its results are achieved by the mutual efforts of the participants: the pupils and the teacher take mutual responsibility for them (Pometun, 2010, p. 9).

L. Terletska identified signs of critical thinking:

- depth (penetrating thinking) – the ability to penetrate the essence, to see the vague, where to others everything seems to be quite clear and understandable;

- sequence – the ability to comply with logical rules, not to contradict themselves, to substantiate the conclusions;

- independence – the ability to ask questions, find new approaches to their clarification;

- flexibility – the ability to change the way to solve a problem, to find new ways, to be free from a stencil;

- speed – the ability to quickly cope with cognitive tasks;

- strategic – consistent hypothesis, the definition of signs (scanning and focusing) in the process of performing tasks (Terlec'ka, 2004, p. 479).

The position of L. Terletska is confirmed by O. Marchenko, who notes that critical thinking is usually defined as the conscious control of the personality over the course of its own intellectual activity (Marčenko, 2007).

O. Marchenko believes that «the basis of critical thinking is the valuation mental activity of an individual to improve the process of thinking, finding and correcting mistakes in his own and partner activities, analyzing his own thoughts, actions, actions, behavior» (Marčenko, 2007, p. 27). According to her research, the majority of domestic and foreign scientists (in particular I. Avdeyeva, F. Frumin, V. Yevdokimov, T. Oleinik, A. Tylo, D. Halpern, T. Khachumyan, etc.) believe that in the pedagogical context, critical thinking is necessary to consider as the ability of students to analyze educational information, to apply the results in both standard and non-standard situations, questions, problems (Marčenko, 2007, p. 27). Critical thinking is defined by the author as an estimate, ascertaining and corrective mental activity aimed at ensuring its competence, the young person's ability to suitable constructive changes in all spheres of life, suitable self-esteem, a stable critical position in society (Marčenko, 2007, p. 31).

N. Vukina, N. Dementievska, I. Sushchenko (2007) note that «such thinking is called critical, helps us to distinguish what seems to be from the truth, facts from judgments» (p. 15). The evaluation component is also noted (in particular, whether we

have analyzed the information well, whether made the right conclusions from it, whether made the right decision, etc.), the direction of thinking to get the desired result, etc. (Vukina, 2007, p. 14).

V. Konarževska considers critical thinking as «a special kind of mental activity, the characteristic features of which is the development of strategies, making decision in solving tasks, problem situations based on receiving and processing information; the implementation of reflexive actions (analytical, controlling, evaluative) in relation to any object or phenomenon, including its own thinking process; a balanced analysis of various opinions and attitudes, the identification of own position, an objective evaluation of the results of both one's own and third-party activities» (Konarževska, 2009, p. 15).

T. Vlasova describes critical thinking as «an active process of learning and achieving true knowledge» (Vlasova, 2005, p. 44). To the skills of critical thinking, she involves reflection of all the pros and cons, the ability to foresee the consequences of a decision, the consideration of a problem from different points of view, the consideration of different opinions as skills of critical thinking. «A critical thinker», the author argues, «does not accept dogmas and stereotypes. The basis of this thinking is working with information, understanding it, comparing various points of view, evaluation».

«Critical thinking as an individual feature of human mental activity», M. Sheremet says, «determines the attitude of a person to the surrounding life, the level of awareness of its value, causes and meaning of what is happening around» (Šeremet, 2003, p. 133). The author notes that critical thinking is a multilevel phenomenon since it reflects moral and ethical instructions, socio-political features, appraisal experience, value orientations, human knowledge, ways of mental and practical actions.

Close to the above, there are views on the nature of critical thinking A. Bandurka, N. Tikhonskiy, A. Tashila, C. Kupisevich, T. Khachumyan and others. The overwhelming majority of them note that critical thinking implies an assessment of the quality of the thinking process, the presence of specific thinking operations, namely evaluative, reflexive actions, self-assessment and adjustment skills that contribute to the improvement and effectiveness of the human intellectual activity.

Valuable for our study is the interpretation of the concept of critical thinking by S. Terno, as a conscious, independent, reflexive, purposeful, grounded, controlled and self-organized thinking. The scientist considers propensity to doubt, independence and flexibility (search for new information, new methods of knowledge and activity), search for evidence, and verification of the validity of the knowledge gained as important components (Terno, 2012, p. 29).

O. Tyaglo defines critical thinking like a modern kind of logical activity, which aims to systematically improve the process and the results of thinking on the basis of their critical analysis, understanding and evaluation. At his discretion, critical thinking can be represented as an algorithm, a sequence of well-coordinated intellectual actions, the skilful accomplishment of which will make it possible to achieve the goal. This algorithm includes four main phases: analysis, understanding, evaluation, and, actually, criticism. (Tâglo, 2008, p. 13).

Analyzing the studies of foreign and domestic scientists, Academician O. Tyaglo (2008) notes that from the experience of the educational system of the United States and other countries, two basic approaches to teaching critical thinking are known. The first involves the teaching of a separate academic discipline (school subject) «Critical

Thinking». Within its framework, one or another previously established thinking algorithm is studied and the ability to apply it is formed.

The second approach is the development of critical thinking through other disciplines and subjects. It does not require the allocation of an independent discipline since the training of such thinking is embedded in the study of any of the disciplines – a foreign language, mathematics, history, and the like. The components of the critical thinking algorithm, in this case, are often not absorbed from the outside but are found by the pupils, to stimulate and support the teacher. With this approach, the problem material appears not so much as a source of illustrations, but rather as «raw material», from which a pupil or student to a certain extent independently «extracts», the necessary knowledge and skills of cultural criticism. (p. 47)

Close to this approach is the position of M. Weinstein, who believes that critical thinking is not something additional to one of the aspects of the curriculum at school, but should be deeply integrated into the very essence of the entire educational system. Therefore, according to the researcher, it is better to introduce critical thinking into those school subjects that are studied according to the current curriculum.

T. Khachumyan proposes a structure of critical thinking of four interrelated components:

- 1) motivational – reveals the attitude of the individual to the process of cognition;
- 2) meaningful – assumes the presence of factual knowledge in a particular subject area and knowledge of the methodology of knowledge, methods of intellectual and practical activities;
- 3) intellectual-procedural, which is manifested in the conscious control of the individual over the course of their own thought processes;
- 4) emotional-volitional, which implies purposefulness, perseverance in mental activity. (*Hačumân, 2005, p. 38*)

T. Khachumyan considers critical thinking as a special kind of mental activity, the characteristic features of which are: «the development of strategies for making the right decisions in solving any tasks based on receiving, analyzing, processing information; implementation of reflexive actions (analytical, testing, controlling, evaluative), which are performed with respect to any object or phenomenon, including their own thinking process; a balanced analysis of various opinions and attitudes, the manifestation of their own position, an objective assessment of the process and the results of both their own and outside activities» (*Hačumân, 2005, p. 10*).

Despite various interpretations, in the opinion of A. Avershin and T. Yakovenko, the concept of «critical thinking», their general meaning comes down to the following: to think critically means to consciously evaluate, reason, think, that is, manifest a person's mental, emotional, cognitive activity, that should be aimed at solving a specific problem. (*Avershin, 2009, p. 134-145*).

I. Mitina considers critical thinking as a complex mental process, which begins with the attraction of information and ends with a decision; It is a process of considering ideas from many points of view according to their meaningful connections and comparison with other ideas. Critical thinking is not an object of study, but a learning outcome (Mitina, 2013, p. 25-26).

G. Sholom (2013) notes that the level of development of critical thinking depends on the degree of formation of each of its components. Therefore, in the learning process, it is necessary to use such methods, means, forms of learning, create conditions that

ensure the formation of all components of critical thinking, affecting all areas of activity of students. (p. 47).

The principles of critical thinking defined by D. Shakirova on an interdisciplinary basis deserve attention:

1. Information richness of educational and practical material for the use of arguments, evidence or refutations based on specific facts, sources, data.

2. Social dependence of the subject of reflection, because critical thinking is social thinking, therefore, the identification of problems tasks, topics for discussion should be carried out taking into account this special property of critical thinking.

3. Communicativeness in the process of understanding the problem and its discussion, since critical thinking as an individual and independent thinking turns out to be in disputes, discussions, consideration and public speaking, therefore, the communicative skills of the participants in understanding the problem to form this type of thinking play a crucial role in achieving success in communication.

4. The researcher explains the problem content of the material with the connection of problem and critical thinking in general properties, methods and ways of teaching.

5. Motivation and the need for knowledge, because an important stage in the development of critical thinking is a reflection, which is possible only when the student is motivated to learn, understand, comprehend, establish the truth or get a result.

6. Scientific, reliable and accessible information.

7. Continuity learning thinking (*Šakirova, 2006, c. 21-25*).

As we can see, some of these principles are general didactic, however, others, like the problematic content of the material, are specific to critical thinking, and therefore interesting for our research.

In confirmation of the principles of critical thinking determined by D. Shakirov on an interdisciplinary basis, the position of I. Bondaruk on the main skills that can be characterized by developed critical thinking:

– analyze information collected from different sources, evaluate its reliability, the adequacy of a specific problem situation, the inconsistency of data, arguments for proof, that is, use certain methods of information processing, allowing to obtain the desired result;

– evaluate your thoughts and extraneous influences on them, identify strengths and weaknesses in them, not take every conjecture with truth, but subject it to doubt and test, evaluate the positive and negative features of both the information received and the thought process itself, phenomena of reality;

– to balance consideration of various approaches to the problem in order to make informed decisions on it;

– to make logical conclusions, to formulate independent judgments and build a convincing argument;

– to carry out reflection, self-assessment and adjustment of cognitive actions and activities.

Conclusions. So, the analysis of scientific papers on the studied problem gives reason to argue that the problem of developing critical thinking is relevant for the past decades. Summarizing various approaches to interpreting the essence of critical thinking, we noticed that this is primarily individual thinking, since it implies the ability of the pupil to independently draw conclusions based on the analysis of information, look for arguments in the text, evaluate their reliability and value, and at the same time, critical thinking has social character, since every thought is verified and justified only

when it is shared with other pupils. We consider critical thinking as a directional thinking process, the goal of which is to solve a problem, and the essence is to perform certain operations - techniques: analysis, synthesis, evaluation of one's own thoughts and results of activity.

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DO PROBLEMÓW OKREŚLENIA GRANIC NADZWYCZAJNEJ REGULACJI PRAWNEJ

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Streszczenie. Artykuł poświęcony jest badaniom współczesnych doktrynalnych podejść do granic nadzwyczajnych regulacji prawnych. Przeanalizowano główne europejskie doktryny nadzwyczajnych regulacji prawnych i stan ich badań w dziedzinie nauk prawnych. Ustalono związek między stosowaniem nadzwyczajnych regulatorów prawnych a możliwością zarządzania procesami społecznymi w sytuacjach kryzysowych. Określono cechy granic prawnych nadzwyczajnych regulacji prawnych jako czynników zapewniających prawa i wolności człowieka i obywatela. Uzasadnione jest, że możliwość prawna i dopuszczalność stosowania nadzwyczajnych organów regulacyjnych jest ściśle związana ze zdolnością do zarządzania procesami społecznymi w sytuacjach kryzysowych. Określono główne międzynarodowe akty prawne ustanawiające kryteria ograniczania ingerencji państwa w prawa i wolności obywateli podczas wdrażania nadzwyczajnych regulacji prawnych. Udowodniono, że granice nadzwyczajnej regulacji prawnej są granicami natury obiektywnej i subiektywnej, które określają ustawodawstwo i międzynarodowe akty prawne, w których dokonuje się szczególnie i wyłączny wpływ prawny na stosunki społeczne w nadzwyczajnych okolicznościach.

Słowa kluczowe. Regulacja prawna, nadzwyczajne tryby administracyjno-prawne, nadzwyczajne regulacje prawne, doktryny nadzwyczajnych regulacji prawnych, prawne ograniczenia nadzwyczajnych regulacji prawnych.

PROBLEMS OF THE DEFINITION OF BOUNDARIES OF EMERGENCY LEGAL REGULATION

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Abstract. The research deals with the modern doctrinal approaches to the boundaries of emergency legal regulation. The main European doctrines of emergency regulation have been analyzed as well as their development in the legal science. The interrelations between the application of emergency legal regulators and control of the social processes in crisis have been defined. The features of the legal boundaries of emergency regulation have been defined through the prism of the rights and freedoms of a person and a citizen. The basic international legal acts establishing the criteria limiting the state's interference with the rights and freedoms during the implementation of extreme legal regulation have been listed. The boundaries of extreme legal regulation have been defined as the limits of objective and subjective nature which are determined by the national and international legislation which stipulate special legal influence on social relations in extraordinary circumstances.

Keywords. Legal regulation, administrative and legal regimes of emergencies, emergency legal regulation, doctrines of emergency regulation, legal boundaries of emergency regulation.

ДО ПРОБЛЕМ ВИЗНАЧЕННЯ МЕЖ НАДЗВИЧАЙНОГО ПРАВОВОГО РЕГУЛЮВАННЯ

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Анотація. У статті проведено дослідження сучасних доктринальних підходів до меж надзвичайного правового регулювання. Проаналізовано основні європейські доктрини надзвичайного правового регулювання та стан їхнього дослідження у правовій науці. Встановлено взаємозв'язок застосування надзвичайних правових регуляторів із здатністю управління соціальними процесами у кризових ситуаціях. Визначено риси юридичних меж надзвичайного правового регулювання як чинників що забезпечують права та свободи людини і громадянина. Обґрунтовано, що правова можливість та допустимість застосування надзвичайних правових регуляторів тісно пов'язана з питанням здатності управління соціальними процесами у кризових ситуаціях. Визначено основні міжнародні правові акти, що встановлюють критерії обмеження втручання держави в права та свободи громадян при здійсненні надзвичайного правового регулювання. Доведено, що межі надзвичайного правового регулювання – це межі об'єктивного та суб'єктивного характеру, що визначаються законодавством та міжнародними правовими актами, у рамках яких здійснюється спеціальний та винятковий юридичний вплив на суспільні відносини в надзвичайних обставинах.

Ключові слова. Правове регулювання, надзвичайні адміністративно-правові режими, надзвичайне правове регулювання, доктрини надзвичайного правового регулювання, юридичні межі надзвичайного правового регулювання.

Introduction. Significant socio-political transformations that have taken place in Ukraine over the last five years significantly change the nature of legal regulation of social relations, influence the development of law, and require legislation to be updated. The armed conflict in eastern Ukraine and the consequences of its prolonged existence contribute to the need to update certain segments of national legislation. The need for an adaptive transformation of law is a requirement of the national interests of the state as one of the means to eliminate the threats to its national security.

Effective legal regulation of relations arising in the context of various socio-political and military conflicts, natural disasters, man-made disasters and catastrophes, is usually carried out through the application of emergency measures that are different from those used in the usual conditions. Legal regulation in such conditions is connected with the notion of extraordinary administrative-legal regimes, the development of which is closely linked with the development of the modern doctrine of national security of Ukraine and entered into the legal science under the name "extraordinary legal regulation", in particular administrative - as "administrative- legal regulation".

Given that the extraordinary administrative regimes are a powerful legal instrument that, together with other legal phenomena, provide the necessary regulatory influence on all social relations in crisis situations, the need for their scientific understanding as a legal regulator does not lose its relevance.

The purpose of the article is to study modern doctrinal requirements to the limits of extraordinary legal regulation.

Proceeding from the stated goal, the following tasks are defined: to carry out an analysis of recent studies of extraordinary legal regulation; to analyze the basic doctrines

of extraordinary legal regulation, as well as to establish legal features of the limits of extraordinary legal regulation.

The research of extraordinary legal regulators (regimes) in the administrative-legal science was undertaken by such scholars as O.M. Bandurka, V.V. Beljevtseva, MV Bilokin, Yu.P. Bityak, V.V. Bogutsky, O.G. Bratel V.V. Govorukha, V.O. Golub, D.O. Goryachov, P.V. Derevyanko, D.O. Yezersky V.Ya. Kastyuk, S.V. Kivalov, T.O. Kolomoets, A.Ya. Kolinko, O.O. Krestyaninov, O.G. Kushnirenko, V.A. Lapy, V.A. Lipkan, S.O. Magda, R.I. Melnik, V.Ya. Nastyuk, K.K. Protasenko, A.M. Sychevskaya, A.S. Spassky, A.S. Filippenko N.V. Harechko and others. The authors in their research and intelligence raised the constitutional and legal aspects of extraordinary legal regimes, organizational and legal, and, of course, administrative-legal. The essence of the concept of "extraordinary legal regime" was clarified (S.S. Alekseev, D.M. Bakhrach, B.Ya. Blichoman, E.F. Shamsumova and others); investigated the administrative and legal nature of the phenomenon of extraordinary legal regulation (V.M. Zavgorodnya, Z.R. Kisil, O.I. Ostapenko and others); determined the branch affiliation of one or another extraordinary legal regime (V.M. Komarnytsky, V.Ya.Nastyuk); They carried out their classification (A.T. Komzyuk, O.V. Makovskaya), and others like that.

At the same time, given the "youth" of extraordinary legislation for Ukrainian law, one can not fail to note the lack of scientific research of this institute. Most works are devoted to the specifics of the activity of law-enforcement bodies, or the peculiarities of limiting the constitutional rights and freedoms of citizens.

Presenting main material. The boundary is a certain spatial or temporal boundary of something; what restricts; Apogee (Ivchenko, 2002, p. 93). In international legal acts that provide for the restriction of human rights, several terms are used that reflect such a phenomenon as the limits of the discretion of state intervention in the field of human rights. Thus, in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, the Copenhagen Conference Document on the CSCE Human Dimension Conference uses the term "limits", "restrictions", while in the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, the term "departing from their obligations", the American Convention on Human Rights - the "suspension of guarantees" - in the European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms - both of the above-mentioned concepts (*Strekalov, 2007, p. 193*).

The restriction of human rights is an inalienable attribute of their validity, as indicated directly by the provisions of articles 3, part three of article 8 and article 64 of the Constitution of Ukraine. Recognizing as the highest social value of human dignity, the Constitution of Ukraine in Article 3 establishes that the establishment and guarantee of human rights and freedoms is the main duty of the state. It is in the Constitution of Ukraine that determines the grounds and limits of the implementation of human rights that can not be arbitrarily expanded or supplemented by current legislation.

Emergency legal regulators are a complex, multifaceted legal phenomenon, consisting of a specific set of methods and means of regulation. It is fixed in the normative and closely connected with the regime-functional group of social relations, which is the subject of legal regulation itself (*Nastjuk, 2009, p. 16*).

Modern legal science does not raise the debate about the application of extraordinary legal regimes as extraordinary legal regulators. The existence of the

relevant legislation, which entered into science under the name of "extraordinary legislation" is considered as a habitual and natural phenomenon. However, theoretical discourse requires answers to individual questions.

In particular. What are the conditions and limits of extreme legal regulation? What are the regulatory features of emergency law in the context of its application? To what extent is extreme legal regulation possible?

The answer to these questions will allow to extrapolate the theoretical concept into a practical model of extraordinary legal regulation, provide it with a scientific basis for the further development of extraordinary legislation and its application.

In the modern legal science of Ukraine, the term "extraordinary legal regulation" is not popular. Instead, the following are used in Ukrainian legislation and legal literature: "extraordinary law", "state of emergency", "legal regulation in emergency situations", "emergency law", etc. For all the similarity of these categories there are serious differences between them. Combines these concepts only with the fact that it is a question of legal aspects of the state's activities in extraordinary circumstances.

In our opinion, the term "extraordinary legal regulation" should be used in the broadest sense as legal regulation in an extraordinary situation that threatens the political, economic, social, spiritual, informational and other security of society and the state. In favor of such a broad understanding of extraordinary legal regulation, a number of arguments can be called.

Extreme legal regulation, as a form of legal regulation, can be defined as the legal effect of using exceptional legal means on social relations in extreme conditions in order to ensure security and restore order and organization in a social life in which the application of general legal principles and norms is limited or abolished (*Schmidt, 2014, p.36*).

Extraordinary legal regulators are characterized by a significant change in the legal status of subjects of legal relations. At the same time, the competence of public authorities significantly expands, mainly due to the restriction of rights and freedoms. The legislator extends the competence of the management apparatus, gives him additional powers to intervene in the direction of reduction in the scope of rights, while extending the permissive type of legal regulation. The purpose of such a reorientation of types of legal regulation is to achieve the most effective possibilities of control of social order.

Let us note that generalization and standardization are characteristic of law, since it is not regulated by a specific legal situation, but by the types of social relations, which are typical both for typical and for the difference.

The law, designed to regulate ordinary social relations in exceptional, unusual, abnormal, different from normal conditions, beyond the usual limits, that is, extraordinary, may prove to be inadequate to ensure proper regulation. Therefore, the localization, minimization or complete elimination of negative legal consequences can be ensured by providing to the public authority powers which, although coming out of the law, are, however, based on such means as would normally be regarded as non-legal.

The basis for the present doctrine of legal regulation in extraordinary circumstances began to emerge in the second half of the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries. and scientifically substantiated by the fundamental works of such lawyers as VM Hessen, V.F. Deryuzhinsky, Ya.M. Shopper, B.O. Kistyakovsky N.M. Korkunov and others. However, the works of these scholars did not appear in the empty space, but

were based in turn on the teachings and philosophical thoughts of John Locke, Charles Louis Montesquieu, Ernest Lening, and others.

The content of the doctrine listed by the scholars is that, under normal circumstances, public authority acted exclusively and clearly with the requirements of the law. However, in a situation when the state or society faces social or natural threats, the state may apply extraordinary measures that go beyond the law to eliminate them.

It should be noted that the German interwar philosophical and legal thought was dominated by the vision of the need for the use of rigid regulators to ensure social order. Thus, the political philosophy of Walter Benjamin, which was first presented by the scientific article "On Criticism of Violence", was based on the aspirations to justify the demands for the establishment of violence and its true meaning (characteristic of the Frankfurt school students - Max Gorkheimer, Theodor Adorno, Herbert Marcuse).

The theory of the possible granting of unlimited discretionary power to public authorities in extraordinary circumstances became practically implemented in the pre-war period in the doctrines created by Nazi Germany's lawyers such as Karl Rudolf Werner Best, Hans Michael Franck, Carl Schmitt "On Legal Aid to the State in a State of Emergency," " about the necessary defense of the state ". However, the implementation of these doctrines led to the transformation of temporary extraordinary norms into permanent management technology, which completely distorted the right, the form and method of its application, created conditions for the arbitrariness of power, usurpation of its powers for 12 years, as well as the elimination of most democratic institutions and preferential resolution of crisis situations by force.

At the same time, refusal to provide the state with certain discretionary powers in extraordinary circumstances creates conditions for delaying the resolution of the crisis in time, provokes a radical confrontation with the solution of problems, and complicates controllability of social relations, which in aggregate pose a threat to national security. Examples are the organizational and legal inactivity of the Salvador Allende government in Chile during the 1972-1973 crisis, and, consequently, the loss of controllability by the state, which led to a coup d'état.

On this occasion, T.N. Schmidt rightly pointed out that the problem of the possibility and the admissibility of extraordinary law is closely linked with the question of controllability of social processes in crisis and transitional states. In an extreme situation, the possibilities of not only the right, but also state power, affect the stabilization of the emerging social relations. World history knows a lot of cases when crises led to chaos, civil wars, revolutions, revolutions and uprisings, and power turned out to be an ineffective tool for solving this situation (*Schmidt, 2014, p. 43*).

Regarding the theories of Carl Schmitt, it should be noted that this outstanding German scientist, although he built his scientific career during the reign of the Nazis, was, however, a consistent supporter of the national conservative philosophical and political-ideological course of the "conservative revolution". This scientist defends the theory of "exceptional circumstances" (German - Ernstfall (literally "unpredictable") and "Solution" (German - Entscheidung), which tries to prove that the approval of all legal and social rules takes place precisely in "exceptional circumstances" and initially based on a solution spontaneous and simultaneously predetermined (*Nazmutdinov, 2016, p.156-158*).

Karl Schmitt believed that not the law provides for the overcoming of the crisis in extraordinary circumstances, but the willful decision of the nation, which is based on

traditions, historical past, cultural determinants. At the same time, such a solution shows a divergence between existing and formed legal norms. Over time, the extraordinary norm turns into a permanent rule, and eventually into law, forming and developing in this way the right. (Schmidt, 2014, p. 43).

The French followers of Schmitt, creating their doctrine of extraordinary legal regulation, even developed a special term "desyzonizm" (French "decision" - a decision), which emphasizes precisely in exceptional circumstances in situations where society is threatened by social or natural disasters, and for the establishment of order is not enough the usual means of control on the basis of the law (Dugin, 1994, p.12).

It should be noted that in the modern French and Italian legal doctrines the concept of "extraordinary legal regulation" is realized through the notion of "urgent decrees", as well as the administrative-legal regime "state of siege" political or fictitious (Agamben, 2011, p.12). And Anglo-Saxon predominates the terms "martial law" and "emergency powers".

The work of Swedish lawyer and political scientist Herbert Tingsten "Absolute powers. The expansion of government powers during and after the Great War" is also dependent on the teachings of Carl Schmitt. The book outlines the view of the transformation of democratic regimes as a result of the continued expansion of executive powers, as well as the state of emergency during and after two world wars, when the "state of emergency" became a rule. Tingsten dwells in detail on the problem of the evolution of contemporary democratic regimes, as a result of the extension of powers of the executive power into the field of legislation through legislative means, and also as a result of delegation to the authorities under the laws of "absolute authority" (Tingsten, 1934, p. 33).

Polish researcher of the phenomenon of extraordinary legal regulation, Krzysztof Prokop built his theory on the concepts and institutions of Roman law, in particular on such a product as *iustitium*, which literally means "temporary suspension of law", but broader its interpretation in one of the options is considered as a stop of legal proceedings and public works declared by public authorities in times of disaster, dangers and public disturbances (Latin *decernere, edicere, indicere*) which the Italian philosopher Giorgio Agamben extrapolates into modernity as a "suspension" the action of law is needed in order to overcome the turmoil in the state (Agamben, 2011, p.101).

By its nature, extraordinary circumstances, in the vast majority, are atypical, and sometimes rare and unique phenomena. Therefore, modeling the task of regulating social relations in extraordinary circumstances through the application of general legal rules should take into account the fact that: it is almost impossible to predict and determine in advance the nature and course of extraordinary circumstances in advance; extraordinary circumstances beyond the normal life of a person, social groups or society, generating new and previously unknown relationships and social implications; methods of crisis management and overcoming its consequences, as a rule, are individual in nature and can not be precisely planned for all details in advance and calculated.

Thus, legal norms, such as social regulators, designed for law enforcement in normal relationships, can be ineffective in an emergency, and even impotent. Therefore, the emergence of a crisis situation, ineffective or powerless law can only be secured by providing certain public authorities with discretionary powers provided by coercive institutions. Thus, the legal possibility and the admissibility of the use of extraordinary legal regulators is closely linked to the ability to manage social processes in crisis

situations, since they (in crisis situations) significantly narrow the possibilities of ordinary - not a special right.

The acuteness of the legal assessment of the problems of legal regulation in extraordinary circumstances, the application of legal measures aimed at limiting the rights and freedoms of man and citizen, expressed in the establishment of certain prohibitions, which are used to eliminate those circumstances that led to the introduction of a special regime, in law science sometimes gives rise to attempts to name these legal regulators discriminatory (*Kolinko, 2011, p.14; Melnik, Chubko, 2016, p.127*).

The boundaries of extraordinary legal regulation are one of the characteristics of the doctrine, since the application of extraordinary legal measures raises the question of limiting the rights and freedoms of man and citizen.

The legal aspect of the state is to clearly define the legal procedures, the forms and limits in which it should exist and should operate. Legal limits are, first of all, human rights (*Kozyubra 1995, p 36*).

In accordance with international treaties, the use of human rights should not be limited. Nevertheless, when necessary, they establish clear justifications, specific limits to the imposition of restrictions on the rights and the purpose of possible derogations from those rights protected by international agreements. On the one hand, it allows the state, with reference to the operation of the relevant international legal norms, to introduce compulsory restrictions on the use of certain rights, and, on the other hand, protects citizens from arbitrary actions by the state to restrict their rights (*Vozhrin, 2013, p. 52*).

Consideration of this issue should be made by referring to the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights of December 16, 1966, adopted by the General Assembly of the United Nations, ratified by the Decree of the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the Ukrainian SSR No. 2148-VIII of October 19, 1973, the content of Article 4 of which is to oblige the state to apply extraordinary legal regulators only to the extent that it is dictated by the severity of the situation, provided that such measures are not incompatible with their other obligations under international law and do not entail discrimination in exclusion but on the basis of race, color, sex, language, religion or social origin. The Pact eliminates possible derogations concerning: guarantees of the right to life, the adoption of genocide, restrictions on the use of the death penalty, the prohibition of torture, slavery or detention of a person in a state of incapacity, restrictions on deprivation of liberty for failure to fulfill contractual obligations, confiscation solely on the basis of a decision the court and on the basis of the law, the prohibition of violations of the right to recognize the personality of a person, guaranteeing the right of conscience.

The Convention on the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (European Convention) stipulates only four restrictions: the inviolability of the right to life, the prohibition of torture, the prohibition of forced labor, and the prohibition of the use of punishments not specified by law.

Criteria for the use of extraordinary legal regulators have been developed at the Paris Conference of the International Bar Association as "Minimum Standards for Basic Human Rights in Exceptional Situation", among which: emergency regulators are used exclusively in a critical situation based on the norms set forth in the law; the procedure and minimum time limits for the introduction of emergency regulators should be established by constitutional rules; the introduction of emergency regulators is carried

out exclusively by the legislature for a term that can not go beyond the period of time necessary for normalization of the situation; the legislature should have the right to cancel the extraordinary legal regimes and to extend it; in conditions of emergency legal regimes, the immunity of a representative body of power should be guaranteed; elections can be postponed to restore order; a ban on the transfer of restrictions on the rights of individuals within the limits of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights; the assessment of the legality of the use of emergency regulators and the proportionality of restrictions on the rights and freedoms of citizens is carried out by the courts; the abolition of emergency regulators is carried out without a special announcement; after the abolition of emergency legal regulators of the right and freedom to recover in the same volume.

We would like to pay special attention to the principle of proportionality of the use of extraordinary legal regulators, which came from the Prussian legal system in the second half of the 18th century and became widespread in European law through the practice of the European Court of Human Rights. The principle of proportionality is one of the most important criteria for determining the inadmissibility of state intervention in the essential content of fundamental rights and freedoms, even with the cover of the need to protect the viability of the nation.

In this context, it is worth pointing out the Syracuse principles for interpreting the restrictions and derogations from the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights adopted by the UN Economic and Social Council.

However, the practice of the European Court of Human Rights, despite the above circumstances, suggests that, even in case of derogation from their international legal obligations, the state should take all necessary measures to restore the constitutional order, including human rights and freedoms.

Undoubtedly, the fact that the limits of the discretion of state interference in the sphere of human rights must be defined in laws in one way or another. But the legal nature of the laws itself is not sufficient evidence that the state is legal. A clear mechanism of compliance is needed, since the state can apply an anti-legal form of influence. Since the legal constraints on the content of the law deal with the legal (regulatory) activity of the state, one should conclude that the relation is discussed: the boundaries of state influence are somewhat wider than the limits of legal regulation.

The domestic legislation of the boundaries of extraordinary legal regulators establishes Article 64 of the Constitution of Ukraine by stipulating the prohibition on limiting the rights and freedoms provided for in Articles 24, 25, 27, 28, 29, 40, 47, 51, 52, 55, 56, 57, 58, 59, 60, 61, 62, 63 of the Constitution of Ukraine. This means that the state can not refuse its certain responsibilities, even when departing from its obligations to ensure human rights and freedoms.

Among the constitutionally stipulated principles regarding the limits of state intervention in the sphere of human rights, include: 1) the inadmissibility of narrowing the content and scope of existing rights and freedoms in the process of adopting new laws or amending existing ones; 2) the inadmissibility of restrictions of a discriminatory nature, that is, on the basis of race, color, political, religious and other beliefs; 3) inadmissibility of the subordinate restriction of fundamental rights and freedoms; 4) the impossibility of any restrictions on individual rights and freedoms expressly provided for by the Constitution; 5) the inadmissibility of introducing such amendments to the Constitution of Ukraine, which imply restriction of human rights and freedoms.

As one sees the legitimacy of state intervention in the sphere of human rights, despite the relative appreciation and ambiguity of the question, it is an independent and important element within the Institute of Human Rights and Freedoms. Its importance is observed both in the context of significance for the mechanism of legal protection of the individual, and within the framework of building a rule of law with the actual, rather than declarative, law.

M. Savchyn, defining, in a constitutional sense, the measure of state interference with the rights and freedoms of man and citizen, distinguishes three elements of such interference, which actually form the essence of the principle of proportionality: intervention should be based on the law, it must be necessary in a democratic society, and the measures to be implemented must be sufficient and appropriate (*Savchyn, 2016, p. 215*). In this case, as a rule, under the need to understand, the softest among several equally effective means.

In determining the permissible limits of human rights restrictions when applying extraordinary legal regulators, it is important to determine the suitability of the means used to ensure legitimate goals - the protection of human rights and freedoms, the sovereignty and territorial integrity of Ukraine. In international law, such circumstances are defined by the phrase "life threatening the nation", which at the same time serve as the basis for the introduction of extraordinary legal regulators (*Goryachiv, 2016, p.91*).

The limits of emergency legal regulation can not be reduced to the limits of the restriction of human and civil rights and freedoms.

The appeal to domestic sources of emergency legal regulation, namely, the Laws of Ukraine "On the Legal Regime of Emergency" No. 1550-III and the Law on the Legal Status of Wives, No. 389-VIII, makes it possible to distinguish between other legal boundaries, namely the territorial boundaries of the operation of extraordinary legal regulators - the territory specified by the relevant legal act, as well as temporal (time) limits of emergency legal regulation - the period of validity of the legal regulator.

As we see, the legal limits of emergency regulation are the legal framework for the application of emergency regulation, which the state restricts interference with the life of a person and society.

The boundaries of extreme legal regulation, formulated by the legal science, but lacking practical consolidation in the law, can be distinguished in a separate group. By the way, they are most clearly seen in Syracuse principles.

Such restrictions and deportations are based on the principle of proportionality, which is based on the concept of "the exceptional and inevitable danger that threatens the life of the nation", "the state, by imposing restrictions, must prove that they do not harm the democratic life of society", "only then, when there are sufficient guarantees and effective remedies against abuse "and others.

Conclusions Thus, the boundaries of extraordinary legal regulation are the limits of objective and subjective nature, which are determined by the legislation and international legal acts, in which the special and exclusive legal influence on social relations in extraordinary circumstances is exercised.

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KONCEPTUALNE MOMENTY ORGANIZACJI PRYWATNEJ DZIAŁALNOŚCI DETEKTYWISTYCZNEJ (ŚLEDCZEJ) NA UKRAINIE

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Streszczenie. Artykuł poświęcony jest odrębnemu zagadnieniu badania problemów i perspektyw funkcjonowania prywatnych detektywów na Ukrainie. Przeanalizowano osobliwości projektu Ustawy Ukrainy "O prywatnym detektywie (śledztwie)", przedstawiono ich sprzeczności i propozycje harmonizacji.

Słowa kluczowe: prywatna działalność detektywistyczna, detektyw, usługi detektywistyczne, doświadczenie międzynarodowe, regulacje prawne dotyczące prywatnej działalności detektywistycznej.

CONCEPTUAL MOMENTS OF THE PRIVATE INVESTIGATION DETECTIVE (ROSSUK) IN UKRAINE

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Abstract. The article is devoted to individual issues of the study of the problems and prospects of private detectives in Ukraine. The features of the draft Law of Ukraine "On Private Detective (Investigation) Activities" are analyzed, their contradictions are identified and proposals for their coordination are provided.

Keywords: private detective work, detective, detective services, international experience, legislative regulation of the implementation of private detective work.

КОНЦЕПТУАЛЬНІ МОМЕНТИ ОРГАНІЗАЦІЇ ПРИВАТНОЇ ДЕТЕКТИВНОЇ (РОЗШУКОВОЇ) ДІЯЛЬНОСТІ В УКРАЇНІ

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Анотація. Стаття призначена окремим питанням дослідження проблем та перспектив функціонування приватних детективів в Україні. Проаналізовано особливості проектів Закону України «Про приватну детективну (розшукову) діяльність», визначено їх суперечності та надані пропозиції щодо їх узгодження.

Ключові слова: приватна детективна діяльність, детектив, детективні послуги, міжнародний досвід, законодавче регламентування здійснення приватної детективної діяльності.

Formulation of the problem. The steady increase in the demand for security and detective services raises the need for the development of domestic private security and detective activities. And if the domestic private security activity has been developing for a long time and successfully, the development of private detective activity in Ukraine is just beginning. In such conditions, the need to introduce foreign experience, with its unconditional adaptation to Ukrainian legal, economic, social realities and taking into account the prospects for further development of this industry, becomes of particular importance.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The following scientists and practices in the field of security and law were devoted to the organization and legal support of private detective activity in Ukraine: V. Krutov, O. Frantsuz, V. Litvinenko, V. Cherkov, Y. Karmazin, O. Bandurka, V. Onopenko, V. Moysik, V. Shvets, V. Malyshev, M. Palamarchuk, A. Kozhemyakin, O. Prodan and others.

The purpose of the article is to study the problems and prospects of legalizing private detective activity in Ukraine on the basis of the draft Law of Ukraine "On Private Detective (Investigative) Activity".

Presenting main material. After the dignity revolution in Ukraine, an active process of constructing a modern democratic state has begun. Transformation of the post-totalitarian state is an essential element of another, even more complex and very important for our country's future process related to European integration.

Successful integration into European structures is impossible without bringing to European standards all aspects of life and activity of our state and society. This applies to politics, economics, legislation, the law enforcement system, the relationship between government and business, government and civil society, freedom of speech and democracy.

Particular attention should be paid to the modernization of the non-state security system in the transformation of society and the state towards the transition to European values and standards. An important component, which is a private detective activity.

This is evidenced by the fact that since 2000, Ukraine has developed 6 draft laws regulating this type of professional security activities (*Pro pryvatnu detektyvnu*

diyalynist': Zakonoproekt vid 01.07.2004, Pro pryvatnu detektyvnu diyalynist': Zakonoproekt vid 05.04.2000 №5237, Proekt Zakonu Ukrayiny «Pro pryvatnu detektyvnu (rozshukovu) diyalynist'» vid 13. 12. 2012 r.).

The last of them is the Law of Ukraine "On Private Detective (Investigation) Activity" (No. 3726), sponsored by the People's Deputies M. Palamarchuk, A. Kozhemyakin, O. Prodan, A. Teteruk was adopted by the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine on April 13, 2017 year (*Pro pryvatnu detektyvnu (rozshukovu) diyalynist': Proekt Zakonu № 3726 vid 14.02.2017 r.*), but, unfortunately, he was honored by the President of Ukraine. On the one hand, it speaks of the importance of private detective activity, but on the other hand, it shows that in this complex form of professional activity the interests of the state, society, citizens and business are seriously overlapping.

Private detective activity is the new direction in Ukraine in providing security and protection services, legal rights and interests of individuals and legal entities in our country. It is carried out for the purpose of searching, collecting and fixing information, searching for objects, property, people and animals, establishing facts and clarifying different circumstances on the order of the customer and in accordance with the contract on the provision of private detective (search) services.

The main areas of private detective activity are:

- 1) ensuring constitutional rights, freedoms and security of citizens of Ukraine;
- 2) ensuring the safety of business activities and economic security of economic entities;
- 3) assistance to state authorities and law enforcement agencies in combating crime and ensuring national security.

The subjects of private detective activity can be solved the following tasks:

- 1) search for missing people;
- 2) search for lost property of individuals and legal entities;
- 3) information provision of participants in the trial;
- 4) determination of the location of people;
- 5) information support for the preparation and conduct of business negotiations;
- 6) subjects of economic activity;
- 7) obtaining objective information about the business partner in order to determine the degree of its reliability;
- 8) security in the recruitment of new employees of economic entities and state institutions;
- 9) participation in measures to protect commercial secrets of a business entity and others (*Samoilenko A.A., 2013, p.87*).

Private detective activity is a very complex and responsible kind of professional security activity.

Like every new one, the field of professional security activities private detective activity faces problems. One of them, the successful decision of which is crucially the civilized development of private detective activity in our country, is the training of highly skilled personnel for detective activity. This problem consists of two interconnected and mutually popup parts. The first of these is due to the lack of experience in training such specialists. At present, there is no model for a specialist in this profile; his competence is incomprehensible and, as a result, it is not clear what training plans should be, the disciplines being studied and their content. And the second part of the problem is connected with the teaching staff who should prepare private detectives.

The situation with the implementation of private detective activity is also greatly complicated by the history, traditions and mentality in the field of law enforcement, which we got from the former USSR and unfortunately, still in varying degrees, and at present. The peculiarity of private detective activity is that it is carried out in the general system of functioning of law enforcement bodies of the state. The main task of this system is to ensure the security of the state and society, and that it is very important - the constitutional rights and freedoms of Ukrainian citizens. In order for the subjects of private detective activity to carry out their activities effectively and in the legal field, it is necessary to organize their interaction with the subjects of the law-enforcement system of the state, including with the units of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the SBU, as well as with the prosecutor's offices. To do this, it is necessary to create the appropriate mechanisms of interaction (*Krutov V.V., 2009, p. 408*).

The construction of an effective mechanism of interaction is beneficial both for subjects of private detective activity and law enforcement agencies. Therefore, the main feature of such a mechanism of interaction is that it should function exclusively in the legal field.

This is dictated primarily by the fact that law enforcement bodies operate exclusively in the legal field. Their functioning is regulated not only by the Constitution of Ukraine and the general legislation of the state. Adopted as special laws that directly regulate their activities. For example, the legal regulation of the activities of the National Police is regulated by the Law of Ukraine "On National Police" and other legislative acts.

Particular attention when organizing and managing private detective activities should be paid to consumers of this service. Relations with clients of a detective agency should be extremely delicate. The basis must be the mutual trust and confidence of customers in the unconditional preservation of confidential information that they report to a private detective. It is so important for clients that it is expedient to develop a code of honor for a private detective. The trust of clients and their confidence in the high professionalism of private detectives is what can be the basis for the stable work and development of the subject of private detective activity. Therefore, the principle of confidentiality should become one of the main activities of private detectives. In view of this, private detectives should pay constant attention to issues related to the protection of information regarding their professional activities and the interests of their clients. Information protection should be comprehensive and include organizational, legal and engineering-technical measures. Particular attention should be paid to ensuring the reliability of personnel involved in the organization and conduct of private detective activities. This requires careful selection of candidates for work in a company that specializes in providing private detective services.

The process of complete transformation and reloading of the entire political system, launched in 2014, significantly influenced the law enforcement agencies of Ukraine. This process is by far the most significant, cardinal and requires a certain amount of time to complete it. Under these conditions, when the level of public confidence in the law enforcement agencies has decreased significantly, while the National Police of Ukraine is only a difficult stage of formation and adaptation, a number of powers, rights and duties that relied on law enforcement bodies were temporarily left without proper control.

In this regard, those who needed help were forced to turn to private detective structures. However, the question is the question of the possibility of obtaining qualitative, legally regulated detective services. Indeed, in Ukraine, private detective activity has not yet been regulated by law, as opposed to most countries of the world, where such activity is recognized at the state level and is a phenomenon common, established and sufficiently regulated by national legislation.

In order to track the process of emergence of interest and the need for the establishment of a private detective (search) institution, it is worth referring to existing bills. So far, a number of bills have been developed, the purpose of which is to regulate private detective (search) activities as a set of non-state measures aimed at improving the mechanism of ensuring constitutional rights and freedoms, protecting the legal rights and interests of legal entities.

In particular, the draft Law of Ukraine "On Private Detective Activity" (author - People's Deputy Y. Karmazin) dated April 5, 2000 No. 5237, draft Law of Ukraine "On Private Detective Activity" (authors - People's Deputies V. Kafarsky, O. Bandurka and V. Moysik) dated April 7, 2004 No. 5380, the draft Law of Ukraine "On Private Detective Activity" (authors - People's Deputies Y. Karmazin, V. Onopenko and M. Onischuk) dated July 1, 2004 No. 5380-1, the draft Law of Ukraine "On Privately Detective (Investigative) Activity" (author - deputy V. Moysyk) dated 12.04.2010 No. 6288, project C On the private detective (search) activity "(authors - people's deputies V. Shvets, V. Malyshev) from 13.12.2012 № 1093, the draft Law of Ukraine" On private detective (wanted) activity "(authors - people's deputies) M. Palamarchuk, A. Kozhemyakin, A. Prodan, A. Teteruk) from 28.12.2015 № 3726 (*Pro pryvatnu detektyvnu diyalnist': Zakonoproekt vid 01.07.2004, Pro pryvatnu detektyvnu diyalnist': Zakonoproekt vid 05.04.2000 №5237, Proekt Zakonu Ukrayiny «Pro pryvatnu detektyvnu (rozshukovu) diyalnist'» vid 13. 12. 2012 r.*).

When investigating the problematic issues of legislative proposals concerning the legalization of private detective activity, it is necessary first of all to assess the concept of such activity and to determine the requirements to the subjects of such activity, taking into account the ambiguity of fixing these definitions in the aforementioned bills.

Thus, in the draft Law of Ukraine "On Private Detective (Investigation) Activity" dated December 13, 2012, No. 1093, private detective activity is defined as follows: "Private detective (wanted) activity - the activity of private detectives or private detective agencies allowed by internal affairs bodies, their associations and branches, to provide customers (individuals and legal entities) on paid contract basis detective services in order to protect their legitimate rights and interests. Private detective (search) activity is by its very nature entrepreneurial activity "(*Proekt Zakonu Ukrayiny «Pro pryvatnu detektyvnu (rozshukovu) diyalnist'» vid 13. 12. 2012 r.*).

In the draft Law of Ukraine "On Private Detective (Investigative) Activity" dated 28.12.2015, No. 3726, it was stated that "private detective (wanted) activity - allowed by the authorities of the National Police of Ukraine independent professional activity of private detectives or private detective enterprises (agencies) in relation to providing to clients on a paid contract basis detective services in order to protect their legitimate rights and interests on the grounds and in the manner prescribed by this Law "(15). But at the same time, Article 5 of this draft stipulates that a private detective may engage in private detective (search) activity as a self-employed person (ie, to pursue independent professional activity) or as an individual entrepreneur.

Consequently, it can be concluded that the essence of private detective activity is not clearly defined in this project, since on the one hand it is considered to be the activity of self-employed persons, and on the other - entrepreneurial.

In our opinion, it would be advisable to give the following definition of private detective (search) activity: private detective (wanted) activity - provided by this law and permitted by the bodies of the National Police of Ukraine business activity of private detectives or private detective enterprises (agencies) for providing customers with paid contract based on detective services to protect their legitimate rights and interests.

With regard to the requirements for individuals who intend to engage in private detective (search) activities, in our opinion, none of the bills, does not reflect them sufficiently full. We believe that the list of such requirements needs to be clarified and supplemented, as:

- Firstly, in most bills there is no age requirement for individuals who want to engage in private detective (search) activity. We believe that it must be at least 22 years old;

- secondly, the availability of draft clauses in alternative conditions: "he has undergone special training for the purpose of carrying out a private detective (search) activity or has experience in operational units or pre-trial investigation bodies of at least three years," leads us to the fact that the length of service in the relevant divisions frees a person from special training.

In our opinion, special training should be for all individuals who intend to engage in private detective (search) activities, only in different programs, depending on their work experience.

Particular attention, from our point of view, requires the provisions of bills on the order of training, retraining and professional development of persons engaged in private detective (search) activities. Thus, in most bills it is proposed to carry out training, retraining and advanced training of persons engaged in detective activity by non-state educational institutions, since such institutions are not in a position to provide educational services in their entirety in the field of detective activity, due to the fact that they do not have the appropriate technical equipment (special equipment) and pedagogical support (instructors in tactics, fire training, special physical training, etc.). Therefore, it is appropriate to identify higher education institutions with specific learning conditions that are part of its management areas that will be responsible for this area of work.

The provisions of the bills that stipulate the rights and obligations of the subjects of private detective (search) activity are also debatable, as some of the rights enshrined in the bills of the subjects of such activities according to the current legislation coincide with the functions of law enforcement agencies, which raises the question of the legality of such actions by the subjects of private detective (search) activity, because, in accordance with the current legislation, the possibility of obtaining information protected by law on an individual without his consent, including her personal and family life, only law enforcement agencies are entitled.

In turn, it will be appropriate to analyze the list of restrictions and prohibitions that contain the considered bills.

Thus, private detectives during the conduct of private detective (search) activities are prohibited:

1) to hide from law enforcement agencies the facts of the committed crimes (criminal offenses) or crimes that are being prepared, which became known in the process of carrying out a private detective (search) activity;

2) to impersonate the subjects of operative and investigative activity, law enforcement officials, representatives of other state bodies;

3) collect information related to personal life, with political and religious beliefs of individuals (without the written consent of such person);

4) transmit your certificate or certificate for use by others (*Pro pryvatnu detektyvnu (rozshukovu) diyalnist Proekt Zakonu № 3726 vid 14.02.2017 r.*).

It should be noted that there are other disadvantages of the bills under consideration (for example, some provisions of the bills are duplicate, need to be substantially revised or not consistent with other legislative acts). Thus, it can be argued that the bills proposed to date need to be substantially refined, as incompletely and unclearly regulate the issues of private detective (search) activity.

Conclusions.

Private detective (search) activity in most countries of the world is recognized at the state level, regulated by laws and optimally used to increase the ability of citizens and legal entities to protect their legitimate rights and interests (Bezug I. electronic resource)

Under private detective activities are understood as independent professional activities, which is a system of search activities carried out by private detectives on a contractual basis for the provision of detective services and the use of technical means.

The content of private detective activities, as a rule, includes services for collecting information on criminal proceedings on a contractual basis with process participants, the search for persons fleeing from legal proceedings, as well as the search for stolen property of the client. At the same time, private detective activity has a more diverse character.

Therefore, at the present stage, private detective activity plays a significant role in ensuring the security and protection of the rights of economic entities.

In Ukraine, a number of bills have been developed to date, the purpose of which is to regulate private detective (search) activities as a set of non-state measures aimed at improving the mechanism of ensuring constitutional rights and freedoms, protecting the legal rights and interests of legal entities.

Analysis of the data of the bills indicates that there are problematic issues regarding the legalization of private detective activity. This applies, in particular, to the definition of the concept of such activities and requirements to the subjects of such activities, the procedure for training, retraining and retraining of persons engaged in private detective (search) activities, as well as the scope of rights and obligations of subjects of private detective (wanted) activity.

Of course, Ukrainian legislation is at the stage of development of this type of activity, but already has a certain basis for preventing crime through detective activity. Accordingly, after the adoption of the Law of Ukraine "On Private (Investigative) Activity", private detective activity will achieve greater efficiency and independence.

So, taking into account all the factors, it is necessary:

1) clearly identify the place of detectives and detective agencies, their participation in the fight against crime;

2) identify and consolidate the legal status of information that can be extracted and used by private detectives or their associations;

3) to develop curricula, which could be trained by future private detectives, to organize training of the latter;

- 4) Specify the permitted actions that will fall within the competence of private detectives;
- 5) Ensure access to databases and information technologies so that detectives begin to provide real services;
- 6) determine the order and system of interaction between private detective agencies or private detectives and state law enforcement agencies.

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PRZEKSZTAŁCENIE ZARZĄDZANIA W WARUNKACH GLOBALNYCH WYZWAŃ

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Streszczenie. Artykuł uzasadnia konieczność przekształcenia administracji publicznej w kontekście globalnych wyzwań. Szybkość nowoczesnych procesów społeczno-gospodarczych, ekologicznych i informacyjnych wzrasta w zależności od prędkości sieci Internet. Zarządzanie w tych warunkach powinno być odpowiednie, zapewnione przez zapobiegawcze zarządzanie. Zarządzanie jest uważane za proces, którego wydajność jest określana przez odpowiednią sieć. Podczas pisania artykułu wykorzystano metody analityczne, procesowe i sieciowe. Treść metody prewencyjnej charakteryzuje się zdefiniowaniem dziesięciu etapów, które zapewniają pewność terminologiczną, analityczną charakterystykę obecnego stanu, konkretny cel i przewidywane, pożądane i możliwe wyniki, określenie uprawnień i odpowiedzialności podmiotów, inwentaryzację i obliczenie niezbędnych zasobów, charakterystykę sił napędowych, opracowanie strategii i taktyki osiągnięcia celów, stworzenie systemu gwarancji osiągnięcia celów, opracowanie systemu pomiaru i oceny skuteczności procesu osiągania wyznaczonych celów. Dane podejście pozwala przewidzieć przyszłe problemy i wczesne opracowanie mechanizmów ich eliminacji. Problemy są łatwiejsze do przewidzenia niż do wyeliminowania.

Słowa kluczowe: szybkość procesów, adekwatność zarządzania, prewencyjność, pewność, integralność, bliskość, kompletność, cykl, ocena, wydajność.

TRANSFORMATION OF MANAGEMENT IN THE CONDITIONS OF GLOBAL CHALLENGES

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Abstract. The article substantiates the necessity of transforming public administration in the context of global challenges. The speed of modern socio-economic, environmental, and information processes is increasing according to the speed of the Internet. Management under these conditions should be adequate, provided by preventive management. Management is considered as a process, the efficiency of which is determined by the corresponding network. When writing the article, analytical, process, networking methods were used. The content of the preventive method is characterized the definiteness of the ten stages that provide terminological certainty, the analytical characteristic of the current state, the specified goal and the predicted desired and possible results, the determination of the powers and responsibilities of the subjects, inventory and calculation of the necessary resources, the characteristics of the forces, the development of strategy and tactics of achieving the goals, the formation of the system guarantees of achievement of goals, development of a system of measurement and evaluation of the effectiveness of the process of achieving the goals set. This approach provides prediction of

future problems and early development of mechanisms for their elimination. Problems are easier to predict than to eliminate.

Key words: speed of processes, management adequacy, preventive, certainty, integrity, closeness, completeness, cycle, evaluation, efficiency.

ТРАНСФОРМАЦІЯ УПРАВЛІННЯ В УМОВАХ ГЛОБАЛЬНИХ ВИКЛИКІВ

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Анотація. У статті обґрунтовується необхідність трансформації державного управління в умовах глобальних викликів. Швидкість сучасних соціально-економічних, екологічних, інформаційних процесів зростає відповідно швидкості мережі Інтернет. Управління в цих умовах має бути адекватним, що забезпечується превентивним управлінням. Управління розглядається як процес, ефективність функціонування якого визначається відповідною мережею. При написанні статті застосовувалися аналітичний, процесний, мережевий методи. Зміст превентивного методу характеризується визначеністю десяти етапів, які забезпечують термінологічну визначеність, аналітичну характеристику сучасного стану, конкретизовану мету та прогнозовані бажані й можливі результати, визначеність повноважень і відповідальності суб'єктів, інвентаризацію та розрахунок необхідних ресурсів, характеристики рушійних сил, розробки стратегії й тактики досягнення цілей, формування системи гарантій досягнення цілей, розробки системи виміру та оцінки ефективності процесу досягнення поставлених цілей. Цей підхід забезпечує прогнозування майбутніх проблем та завчасної розробки механізмів їх усунення. Проблеми легше передбачити, ніж ліквідувати.

Ключові слова: швидкість процесів, адекватність управління, превентивність, визначеність, цілісність, замкненість, завершеність, цикл, оцінка, ефективність.

Introduction. At the beginning of the XXI century, humanity is undergoing globalization shifts. Transforms spheres that globally affect national states, societies, migration processes, employment of people, labor movement, etc. It is about the rapid development of the Internet, which is accompanied by the development of artificial intelligence, robotics, technology, technology, which led to the formation of the foundations of digital civilization, the transformation of the world economy, the emergence of new electronic currencies (crypto-currency) transformed world trade. Transformation is carried out at the speed of light: the rate of transformation is measured by the change in the speed of world money, which today is equal to the speed of the Internet. The result of the global influence of new spheres of the world economy is the formation of new forms of social organization "megassociety", and "the state loses the status of a single subject of integration and representation of the interests of large communities. The locus of management activity is dramatically expanding, shifting the emphasis from national to supranational and subnational levels. Globalization shifts led to a structural transformation of power systems and mechanisms, and revealed the pathology of the traditional administrative-bureaucratic concept of public administration "(Radziyevsky, 2006).

M. Castells, D. Kettle, O. Neclesa, G. Peters, and others made significant contributions to the systematization of new phenomena of a global scale. M. Castells considers "the formation of international business and cultural networks and the development of information technology - as a phenomenon that is inextricably interconnected. All spheres of life, starting with the geopolitics of the great national powers and ending with the daily activities of people, are changing in the information space and global networks "(Castells, 2000, p. 5-7).

D. Kettle believes that in the 1980s the "global reform movement in the sphere of public administration" began. Firstly, it has captured many countries from Mongolia to the United States, and secondly, the reforms that are envisaged include broad-based goals: governments in the course of reforms define the role of the state and its relations with citizens in a new way (Kettl, 2004). O. Neclesa notes that "the change of current management codes is one of the most important aspects of change. New organizational schemes and technology sometimes simply undermine former institutions, changing the usual form of government. The tendency of marginalization of the corps of "legal power", national public policy, its alienation from the solution of a number of key issues, the substitution of social regulation by an alternative system, and the power of informal, transnational, geo-economic "(Economics of knowledge: the challenges of globalization and Ukraine, p. 230) begins to be seen. G. Peters emphasizes the fact that the global market, supranational authorities and institutions, local governments, and branch network structures (public and private) are struggling to be the driving force of society (Peters, 2004).

The development of globalization processes is not linear. Integration trends of globalization are accompanied by the development of regional structures. "National governments are in the grip between global forces and local needs. Today, the global market, supranational institutions, local authorities, and large public and private network structures compete for the right to play the role of the core power of social development management (Radziyevsky, 2006). Under these conditions, it is important to develop and develop instruments that national governments and local self-government bodies must meet with the needs of citizens in the formation of digital civilization, which can be ensured through the transition of the management system at the state and local levels to preventive principles.

The purpose of the article is to reveal the content of the management transformation in the context of global challenges, based on preventive methods of a closed, completed type.

Main part

Implementation of this goal requires the following tasks: to disclose the content of the preventive method; formalize the algorithm of the preventive management method.

In the process of writing the article applied methods: analytical, process, network. The implementation of the powers of local governments (local government) is considered as a closed, completed cycle, which is implemented on the basis of cycles: "citizen-state", "people-state", "cause-consequence", "beginning-end", "freedom-responsibility", "Justice - efficiency", "justice - force", "goal - results", "contradictions - harmony", "chaos - order", "unit (linear) - network"; criteria for evaluation of the closed cycle: social, economic, ecological, demographic, political, legal, informational, spiritual, moral, territorial, national, technological, etc. Each criterion has its own indicators, each indicator has its own measure (maximum, minimum, standard, fact).

Practical significance - Local governments receive incentive mechanisms for local communities, local authorities to improve local production; central authorities receive methodological tools for preventive management, in particular, preventive assessment of the effectiveness of the ratio of state power and local self-government.

Results. The closed cycle of public administration is a causal and interdependent category that denotes a system of methodological foundations that, on the basis of appropriate mechanisms, should ensure the functioning of the primary network of society, realize the right of the people to be the bearers of sovereignty, the only source of power, and ultimately - to provide for themselves decent living conditions. Assessment of the degree of isolation - the standard of living of citizens is carried out according to social, economic, environmental, demographic, political, legal, informational, spiritual, moral, territorial, national, technological and other criteria. Each criterion has a set of indicators, each index has its own measure (maximum, minimum, standard, fact, absolute, relative).

In theory, a closed loop on which processes are carried out in different systems has the following characteristics. Closed Loop MRP (MRP) is a system built around Material Requirement Planning (MRP), which includes additional planning functions, such as production planning (aggregate planning), development of a main scheduling plan production planning (master production scheduling) and capacity requirements planning (planning). After the planning phase has been completed and plans have been adopted as realistic and achievable, plans are started, including production management functions, as measured I input-output (capacity) measurement, input-output (capacity) measurement, formation of detailed schedules and dispatching, as well as reporting on the expected lag from schedules from the factory and from suppliers, the formation of delivery schedules, etc. The term "closed cycle" "Means that these elements are not just included in the general system, but there is also a feedback from the execution functions, so that planning is always correct (Wikipedia. Closed MRP cycle).

Closure of a cycle is a process of organized actions of business entities aimed at ensuring the needs of citizens through causal transformations and displacement in time and space of software, material and intangible resources, etc.

The closure of the cycle in the economy serves as a collective consumption of goods as services. For example, public transport (metro, railways, bridges, tunnels, highways) guarantee the needs of citizens in transport.

Any action has the beginning and the end, which is one or another cycle. It is completed and not completed. The degree of completeness, closure of the cycle is established by a system for evaluating the effectiveness of local governments (local government). Completed is the cycle in which the goal is achieved, and the source components - more than the amount of incoming. Incomplete is a cycle in which the goal is not achieved. "Completed" and "not completed" cycles are methodological constants that should be taken into account when realizing the rights and freedoms of a citizen.

The terms "seclusion", "completeness" characterizes the existence of a causal relationship between the purpose of government and its results in time and space. They consider the functioning of the national economy (territorial community) as an appropriate cause-and-effect network, which should ensure the realization of the interests of the people (the local population) through the bodies of state administration (local self-government) that guarantee the provision of high-quality education services to the citizen, the population (community), culture, medicine, social protection, housing

and communal services, ensuring the protection of public order and other vital areas, and which are endowed with sufficient and financial, infrastructure, personnel and other resources. Each closed loop has a start, extension, and end, resulting in the loop closure of the completed form (Rule of the completed loop. Discussion on LiveInternet ...)

Formation of the bases of state, municipal management on the basis of a closed and completed cycle is a methodological basis, which should provide this process with high efficiency and efficiency. The degree of completeness of a cycle depends on the quality of methodological and methodological support, in particular, the conformity (accuracy) of terms, definitions, principles, methods, mechanisms of content and forms of community self-governance; completeness of the process of self-management by them; the same understanding of the cycle of self-governance by its actors involved in this process.

The closure of the cycle of state, municipal management is realized on the basis of the functioning of many cycles, in particular, such as: citizen - state, people - state, reason - consequence, beginning - end, freedom - responsibility, justice - efficiency ", " justice - force ", " goal - results ", " contradictions - harmony ", " chaos - order ", " unit (linear) - network ", etc. The development of managerial decisions of the Public Administration (local government), which should be based on the above mentioned cycles, should establish the truth in these ratios, that is, whether the goal set in the state (local) plans is achieved. If any of these and not named cycles will be established not optimally, citizens will not be able to provide a decent living conditions, the goal will not be achieved. The cycle will not be complete, not optimal.

Leading in the named system of cycles are cycles "cause - consequence", "meta - results". In the ratio of "cause - consequence", each side of the cycle must stand in its place. If the reason and the effect of changing places, the "meta-results" ratio radically changes, because the results will be directly opposite to the purpose.

In recent years, as a result of the reform of governance in Ukraine, local communities must take part in the process of ensuring living conditions. In the context of Article 5 of the Constitution of Ukraine, "The people are the bearers of sovereignty and the only source of power" (Constitution of Ukraine, 1996, p. 5), everything is logical. But at the same time, in order to implement this assertion, local communities need to be provided with adequate tools and resources in line with new authority.

As an integral system, a closed loop represents ten consecutive and functional steps that should be the basis of managerial decision on a preventive basis.

The first stage. Theoretical and methodological principles of managerial decision.

The second stage. Analysis of the state of development, adoption and implementation of managerial decisions.

The third stage. Formation of the purpose of managerial decision.

Fourth stage. Forecast of desired and possible results.

The fifth stage. Subjects of development, acceptance and realization of managerial decisions.

The sixth stage. Analysis of the status of resources, the potential for implementation of management decisions.

Seventh stage. Research of driving forces of development, acceptance and realization of managerial decisions.

Eighth stage. Development of strategy and tactics for the implementation of managerial decisions.

Ninth stage. Formation of a system of guarantees of implementation of strategy and tactics of managerial decisions.

Tenth stage. Formation of a system for evaluating the process of developing, adopting and implementing managerial decisions.

The development of these stages should take into account the challenges of the XXI century: the speed of the processes of transformation of the world economy; formation of digital civilization; formation of the digital total equivalent; the birth of artificial intelligence; information and network revolution; environmental challenges, global warming, environmental pollution; a constant increase in the cost of military means to destroy all living things on our planet; absence of guaranteed rules of international relations; migration processes; persistent military conflicts between countries, etc.

At the **first stage**, theoretical and methodological principles of managerial decisions are considered. The object and subject of public administration, methods, principles, mechanisms, tools and others are determined. Specifies the definitions, categories, methods, principles, etc., which should be unambiguous for the understanding of all participants in the socio-economic, political, etc. processes. These definitions should be made and consistent with the content of social processes. The object of public administration must be civil society, people. The subject is the standard of living of citizens.

The new algorithm for the development of managerial decisions involves identifying the starting point of the process from which any steps are taken, measures to match the object and subject of public administration. Such a point is the establishment of the principles of relations between actors on which all methods, mechanisms, definitions, terms, categories, instruments, etc. should be based.

The relations of the subjects of state and local government are based on the binary principles of freedom and responsibility, efficiency and justice.

We call these principles binary because they act only together in a certain ratio, which must be constructed to the appropriate extent and characterizes the level of civilization development of the state's economy. The guiding principle that determines their integrative interaction is the principle of freedom, which means the free choice of each subject of economic activity, equal access to business resources, fair protection of private property, etc. Activities of subjects of social development can not be arbitrarily limited either by the state or from the market.

In addition, the functioning of one principle at the expense of another is impossible without reducing the overall effect of their interaction. Compliance with the principle of freedom as the basic principle of a liberal economy must be ensured for entrepreneurs - an independent choice of areas of production activity; free access to financial, labor, natural resources; the need to protect their private property, in effective social activities, etc. ; citizens - free access to investment goods, end-consumer goods, free access through appropriate infrastructure to public administration; the state - satisfaction of the requirements for filling the budget for the implementation of investment functions, the organization of infrastructure for the implementation of its functions by civil society, etc.

The principle of freedom is realized through the binary principle - the principle of responsibility of subjects of management on the vertical: the state - the collective - the person and horizontally: the collective - the collective. The viability of the economic

system and the efficiency of social production depend on the level of responsibility of the subjects. It should be noted that the decisive advantage of a market economy system is the direct inclusion of each entity of state ownership in the liability relationship, the feature of which is the impossibility (in the presence of competition) of its absolute and concentration on one of the subjects of management (for example, the state or one of the subjects of the market) or self-removal from it leads to a command-administrative economy and the actual removal of other entities from ensuring the socio-economic efficiency of production. Self-exclusion from liability of individual economic entities leads, for example, to further shadowing of the economy observed in Ukraine, which by eliminating resources from official circulation reduces the potential of social development.

The main problem is the removal of uncertainties of the ratio of these principles to the vertical, horizontal and their optimization depends on time, place, measure, subjects (individuals, collective, civil society, state).

To eliminate the uncertainty of the correlation of these principles SB Crimean believed that "the standard of values characterizes scientific rationality as an alternative to dilettantism" (Crimean, 2003, p. 99). In modern view, the measure has not only quantitative-qualitative but also value aspects, acts not only as a unity of quality and quantity, but as a standard of any activity, the basis of harmony and expediency in modeling a person and his world.

For modern Ukraine finding optimum use of freedom, responsibility, justice, efficiency - the issue of ensuring the independence of the state. Indeed, it is necessary to adequately assess the time that Ukraine is living today; a place occupied geographically by Ukraine in the world economic space; the extent of these principles, when the domination of one of them leads to a fundamental change in the state system. For example, the use of unrestricted state laws of freedom leads to chaos in the state, and the use of unlimited liability, as shown by historical practice, leads to dictatorship.

The main problem when finding the optimum is to identify high-profile professionals. In this context, the transition from public administration to public administration involves changing not only the name but also the subject's changes. Civil society is replacing the state - the main trend of the modern world. The formation of civil society as the main subject brings powerful driving forces into economic development. In those countries where this does not happen, and only the name "state administration" changes to "public administration", the revolution is constantly being carried out. Power goes from one to the other, but nothing completely changes.

The second stage is an analysis of the state of development, adoption and implementation of management decisions. First of all, it is necessary to provide an objective assessment of the object and subject of managerial decisions - the state of economic development, determine where the country is, to indicate the world trends in the development of the economy, the state of the environment, social sphere, demography, technological and technological state, informatization and other and take this into account in new managerial decisions. For example, radical transformations are carried out in the economic sphere. The labor theory of value, as the basis for the formation of the price of goods, is replaced by the digital value of the goods, where the direct dependence of the price of the goods on the labor input disappears. This leads to the formation of a new total equivalent, which was gold and paper money, formed a digital cryptography, digital economy. The cardinal changes become the market of goods, which becomes the whole world. The work force moves freely around the

world. In addition, robotics, which reduces jobs, is actively developing; In recent years, there is a large migration of active labor force. As a result, the economic boundaries of the state disappear, and, therefore, in the future, the state will be transformed with the change of geographical boundaries.

The Internet is the most significant development, informatization of production, formation of world production networks, materials with new properties appear, new sources of energy are developing. Humanity is on the verge of a revolution in the energy sector. Oil and gas as energy carriers will be replaced by the latest sources.

The third stage involves the formation of the goal of state and local government. The most important thing in this context is the certainty of purpose. The question is always urgent: What society, which state we are building? At the state level, this concerns, first of all, the planning of measures to strengthen the state and the development of civil society as a subject, state and public administration. The state should, first of all, be interested in the development of public institutions, infrastructure, which should ensure the implementation of the functions of the subject of public administration. For this purpose, a network of citizens' education for their participation in public administration should be developed. Without a developed civil society, stable development of the state is impossible without forceful methods. And this leads to periodic revolutionary speeches of citizens who are not satisfied with state power.

At the fourth stage, the forecast of the desired and possible results of the implementation of public administration is being carried out. At this stage, positive and negative results of management decisions are projected. This is necessary in order to predict possible problems even before they arise, because after the problems arise, it is difficult to eliminate them, and sometimes it is impossible. Preventive measures should be developed not only to eliminate problems, but, above all, to predict them. This is the essence of the new procedure for the development, adoption and implementation of public decisions. This requires a detailed analysis of the past period of development of one or another sphere, which may contain problems that are only "waiting" for their launch. And this requires an analysis of the past 50 years or more. For example, social development scenarios should be foreseen when one of the actors - a state or a civil society - wants to usurp power.

At the fifth stage, the subjects are analyzed, which should participate in the development, adoption and implementation of management decisions. This is especially true for the participation of civil society institutions. So, in order for society's reforms to be perceived and implemented in the process of their preparation, civil society institutions should participate. Without this, all reforms will be on paper, but, as Ukrainian practice has shown, with negative consequences for people.

At the sixth stage, an analysis of the status of resources, the potential for the implementation of management decisions. First of all, at this stage, it is necessary to define the terms "potential", "resources". It is a matter of the fact that at each stage, the terms used in the planning of management decisions at each stage should be specified. For example, in Ukraine, terms that are not relevant to the content are often used. Yes, they argue that Ukraine has great potential, but there are no real results. Potential is what is actually used, and not something that can be used in the future. In this case, it is only the availability of resources, the realization of which requires the corresponding conditions that need to be created.

When developing management decisions, the amount of those resources, as it is, should be determined, those resources are determined that are necessary to achieve the goals, names and volumes of resources that are not available to achieve the goals. This approach removes uncertainty in the development of managerial decisions, makes them real, and not virtual.

At the seventh stage, the driving forces of developing, adopting and implementing managerial decisions are explored. At the theoretical level, the driving forces are dialectical contradictions. This means that the development of the economy, society in this case occurs through revolution, insurrection, radical change of power, a new level.

At this stage, state bodies with the respective powers, functions, mechanisms and instruments must specify the problems of cooperation between public authorities and civil society institutions, which are today inhibiting and destabilizing social development in Ukraine.

Social development requires new driving forces, which are based not on contradictions, but on harmony, harmonization, and preventive. The point is that the main driving force of social development is the harmony of relations between government and civil society. The most valuable resource, which lies in one of the main conditions of the economic potential of the state, is the trust of civil society to power. Without this confidence, the real driving force is controversy, but through the revolution. True, during the revolution, huge resources are spent without benefits to meet the needs of citizens.

At the eighth stage, the development of strategy and tactics for the implementation of management decisions. After the uncertainty has been removed at the previous stages of development of management decisions by finding adequate terms and categories, an analysis of the situation in Ukraine and the world has been made, the goal for the authorities and civil society has been specified, the desired and possible results of the implementation of management decisions have been determined, an analysis of available and required resources has been made. and capacity, specified powers and responsibilities of actors in the process of developing, adopting and implementing management decisions, provided the scientific characteristic of p shiynyh forces specified existing and potential problems, training strategies and tactics development, adoption and implementation of management decisions. An analysis of the practice of transformation of economic development shows that concepts, strategies, programs are chaotically developed, minor problems are considered, but the strategies of economic development, civil society, state and public institutions are being developed chaotically, without observing the corresponding procedures, sequences and rules. The first steps in implementing such strategies, programs show that many issues were not explored, omitted, ignored, etc. The leading direction in developing the strategy of public decisions is the formation of mutual counterbalances between the state and civil society, which ensure the harmonious development of the economy, personality, and infrastructure of civil society. The main task of the tactics of public decisions is to develop institutional support for the harmonious influence of public authorities on civil society and institutional provision of the influence of civil society on state authorities. The legislative, executive, judicial branches of power and civil society influence the economic, political and other development of the main subjects of the economic process.

The lack of harmony of relations between the subjects of state and local government leads to chaos in society or to dictatorship.

At the ninth stage, a system of guarantees for the implementation of strategy and tactics of management decisions is implemented. All previous steps in this section should be holistic, interconnected, closed, complete content and form. In the system of guarantees, the leading link is the semantic guarantees, the essence of which is that, on the one hand, all public decisions are made in the interests of the people, the provision of decent living conditions, on the other hand, when as a result of public decisions, deteriorating living conditions of people, then sanctions (moral, administrative, political, criminal, etc.) are applied to those who violate them. The responsibility of public authorities (ensuring the conditions for achieving the goal of public decision) and sanctions (inevitable punishment system, when the goal is not achieved, and living conditions deteriorated).

In this context, after acquiring international experience, one should turn to European and world experience. For example, only a wrongly word (in the context of its civil society assessment) automatically leads to the application of moral and administrative sanctions - such a person resigns.

Constitutional guarantees of public decisions should become the Basic Law of the state, which should contain a system of counterweight against the tyranny of state authorities (legislative, executive, judicial). For example, in the past years of the existence of the Ukrainian state, senior officials "tweaked" the Constitution "for themselves", which led to the usurpation of power. The protection of this should be the introduction of a new article of the Constitution of Ukraine that any version of the Fundamental Law leads to the dissolution of the Verkhovna Rada and the President, indicating that this composition of deputies in the future is not entitled to work in state authorities.

This will ensure the stability of the Constitution of the state and eliminate the attempts of various political forces to usurp power in society. The development and implementation of managerial decisions in public administration must be provided with a system of economic, political, environmental, information, social, etc. guarantees. Without a system of guarantees, as evidenced by the analysis of the experience of implementation of concepts, strategies, programs, since 1991 in Ukraine, they all remain on paper. No program of the Government, the concept of political parties on the reform of socio-economic development of Ukraine since 1991 has not been implemented, and the life of the people is constantly deteriorating, the number of citizens living below the poverty line is constantly increasing, there is an outflow of labor abroad, and state authorities (legislative, executive, judicial) are engaged in "struggle" against themselves (so-called struggle against corruption).

At the tenth stage, a system is developed for assessing the effectiveness of developing, adopting and implementing public management decisions, which completes the scientific and methodological support of this process. The effectiveness of public administration in general depends on the objective assessment of the decisions made. The assessment system includes criteria, indicators, time, place, grade, subjects and objects of evaluation, evaluation mechanism. In Ukraine, at the theoretical level, a methodology for evaluating the effectiveness of public management decisions [3] has been developed, but in the scientific articles, in the practice of management in the system of estimation there is a methodological chaos, there are no systematized methodological and methodological

principles of evaluation, there is confusion between criteria and indicators of evaluation, there is no systemic, an objective view of the place, time, measure of evaluation. So, for example, between the criteria and indicators of evaluation put the sign of equality. Under the criteria understood indicators, but these are terms that reflect different processes, stages of evaluation. Criteria are characterized by various factors of the process: economic, environmental, social, informational, etc.; the indicators specify each criterion. For example, the economic criterion may have many indicators: output of gross output, labor productivity, etc. The nature of the criteria, indicators depends on time, place and measure. For example, Ukrainian officials justify rising gas, light and water prices, arguing that prices in these countries are much higher in European countries. In this case, the economic situation in one country is automatically imposed on the economic situation in Ukraine, which leads to the absurdity of comparative assessment of prices for utilities, because it is necessary to take into account the place (country), time, and measure. In addition, evaluation systems need to take into account the closed, completed cycle in public administration, which should include the incomes of citizens in Ukraine, compare with them the possibility of paying citizens to raise prices for electricity, gas, etc. All this needs to be taken into account in the process of developing, adopting and implementing decisions in public administration.

The assessment of the effectiveness of the ratio "meta - results" characterizes the level of living conditions of citizens. For society, it is important that the results of public management meet the goal, which is a decent life for citizens. The standard of living of citizens is measured by the integrative index - the index of human development (HDI). In 2017, Ukraine was ranked 88th out of 189 countries for the HDI (Human Development Index, 2018).

Characteristics of the standard of living of citizens are carried out, for example, by determining the ratio of the cycle "justice - force". It should be noted that ensuring the rights and freedoms of man and their guarantees must determine the content and direction of the state. The state must respond to the person for their activities. The affirmation and maintenance of human rights and freedoms must in practice be the main responsibility of the state. "The right to determine and change the constitutional system in Ukraine belongs exclusively to the people and can not be usurped by the state, its organs or officials. No one can usurp state power" (Constitution of Ukraine, 1996). The lack of active force of the people to exercise their right to be the only source of power is confirmed by the current standard of living of citizens who have received an independent state, but almost 30 years do not yet have a decent standard of living. As a result, a situation emerged, about which in the seventeenth century. wrote the famous scholar Blaise Pascal: "Justice and power are disunited in this world, because the power does not want to listen to the voice of justice, does not want to know its evidence, nor arguments. The power itself is obvious and indisputable, it is more convincing than any arguments, and justice without power can be challenged. To justice rule the world, it must make it strong or force to be fair. But, failing to make a just strong, strong people declared fair." Thus, this tyrannical force reigns - because force without justice is tyrannical" (Pascal, 2013).

An analysis of the practice of interaction between central government and local self-government has shown that the energy of the linear combination of components (actions of subjects, resources, legislative and normative support, etc.) of local self-government is used. Inclusion in the process of meeting the needs of citizens of the

energy of network synergy requires the formation of closed, completed cycles of interaction between central government and local self-government.

Application of linear method of formation and realization of functions and tasks of local self-government, constant "naznirovanie" new laws, programs, tasks, etc. does not complete the next stage of reform (according to the relevant criteria, for example, time), makes it permanent, transforms the process of reforming the relationship "center - region - community" into "stupid infinity." Confirmation of endless reformation is disharmony in the "meta-results" cycle, none of the declared programs of local self-government reform in Ukraine has achieved its goals.

The main function of a closed, completed cycle is to provide a causal relationship and the co-ordination of successive stages of the cycle, the transformation of local resources, actions of the subjects of relations, etc. in the potential of local self-government. The main result of the functioning of the local government network should be the new social value, new social values that should be: increased resources, new mechanisms, perfect tools, etc. Guaranteeing the rights and freedoms of the citizen and local communities.

Conclusions

Modern processes at the global level have led to the transformation of the state as an institution that faces the challenge of combining the pressure on the internal environment of global change with the need to ensure decent lives for citizens at the state and local levels. An analysis of practice certifies degradation of the social function of the state, which is the main factor of danger to the state system.

The transformation of the global environment, which is carried out at a rapid pace, makes it necessary to bring the state administration system, the relationship between public authorities and local governments into an adequate state, taking into account modern challenges at the state and local levels. One of the effective means is the use of preventive management method: problems are anticipated in advance, measures are being taken to prevent them. The essence of a completed, closed loop is revealed in the ratio of the purpose of government and its results. If the results meet the goal, the state administration has a completed, closed loop. Failure to achieve a socially important goal makes the cycle unfinished, which becomes a factor in the political, economic instability of the state. The publicly important goal of state administration should be to ensure a decent standard of living for the people.

The cycle has the appropriate sequence, the development of each phase, which is aimed at predicting problems, preparing tools for their elimination: preparation of definitions, definitions, categories; characteristic of object, object; carrying out an analysis of their functioning in practice; setting the goal of management; forecasting of desired and possible management results; establishment of subjects that will participate in the achievement of the goal, the definition of their powers, responsibility, the establishment of sanctions for non-fulfillment of authority; inventory of available resources that are needed to achieve the goal; definition of driving forces, contradictions, problems that are and which can be in the process of achieving the set goal, development of methods and mechanisms for their removal; development of strategy and tactics for achieving the goal; preparation of a mechanism for ensuring the achievement of the goal; development of a system for measuring and assessing the level of achievement of the set goal. Interaction and interdependence between the stages is universal: the change of parameters in one of the stages necessitates the alignment of all

other stages. Changes can be made in real-time, providing an adequate response to internal and external challenges.

Promising areas for further research are improving tools for predicting possible problems and developing mechanisms for their elimination.

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ZABEZPIECZENIE PRAWNE PRZYJĘCIA DECYZJI ZARZĄDCZYCH PRZEZ KIEROWNIKÓW JEDNOSTEK POLICJI NARODOWEJ UKRAINY

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Streszczenie. Konieczność i niezbędność podejmowania decyzji zarządczych jest główną funkcją aktywności zawodowej szefów organów i jednostek Policji Narodowej Ukrainy. Ujawnienie istoty wsparcia prawnego przy podejmowaniu przez kierowników decyzji zarządczych pozwoli na terminowe korygowanie i ukierunkowanie działalności kierowników w celu zwiększenia efektywności i skuteczności ich zarządzania. Osiągnąć skuteczność wsparcia prawnego przy podejmowaniu decyzji zarządczych przez kierowników w jednostkach Policji Narodowej Ukrainy można zapewnić w przypadku harmonizacji wymagań przepisów zewnętrznych i wewnętrznych. Przygotowywanie i przyjmowanie aktów prawnych przez Policję Narodową jest jedną z głównych procedur w działalności wykonawczej i nadzorczej jej kierowników. Opracowywanie i wdrażanie aktów prawnych ma na celu zapewnienie prawidłowego wykonywania obowiązującego prawa w działalności Policji, określenie specyfiki realizacji norm prawnych oraz poprawę skuteczności działań w zakresie egzekwowania prawa.

Słowa kluczowe: działalność egzekucyjna, kierownicy, jednostki Policji Narodowej Ukrainy, wsparcie prawne, zewnętrzna baza normatywna, wewnętrzna baza normatywna, podejmowanie decyzji zarządczych, skuteczność działalności zarządczej.

LEGAL PROVIDING APPROVAL OF MANAGEMENT DECISIONS BY HEADS OF DEPARTMENTS IN NATIONAL POLICE OF UKRAINE

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Abstract. The necessity managerial decision-making is explained by the fact that exactly decision-making represents the main function of professional activity of epy heads of organs and units of the National Police of Ukraine. The disclosure of the essence of legal support while managerial decision-making allow timely correct and direct the activities of managers in order to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of management. Achievement of efficiency is possible due to the harmonization of external and internal regulations of legal acts. The preparation and adoption of legal acts by the National Police is one of the main procedures in the executive and supervisory activities of its leaders. The development and implementation of legal acts are intended to ensure the proper implementation of the current legislation in Police activity, to determine the peculiarities of the implementation of legal norms and to increase the effectiveness of all law enforcement activity.

Key words: law enforcement activity, units of the National Police of Ukraine, legal support, external normative base, internal normative base, managerial decision-making, effectiveness of management activity.

ПРАВОВЕ ЗАБЕЗПЕЧЕННЯ ПРИЙНЯТТЯ УПРАВЛІНСЬКИХ РІШЕНЬ КЕРІВНИКАМИ ПІДРОЗДІЛІВ НАЦІОНАЛЬНОЇ ПОЛІЦІЇ УКРАЇНИ

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Анотація. Необхідність і обов'язковість прийняття управлінських рішень є головною функцією професійної діяльності керівників органів і підрозділів Національної поліції України. Розкриття суті правового забезпечення при прийнятті управлінських рішень керівником дасть змогу вчасно корегувати та спрямовувати діяльність керівників з метою підвищення ефективності та результативності їх управління. Досягти ефективності правового забезпечення прийняття управлінських рішень керівниками в підрозділах Національної поліції України можна за умови узгодженості приписів зовнішніх та внутрішньовідомчих нормативно-правових актів. Підготовка та прийняття правових актів Національною поліцією є одними з основних процедур у виконавчо-розпорядчій діяльності її керівників. Розробка та реалізація правових актів покликані забезпечити належне виконання чинного законодавства в діяльності поліції, визначити особливості реалізації правових норм та покращити ефективність правоохоронної діяльності.

Ключові слова: правоохоронна діяльність, керівники, підрозділи Національної поліції України, правове забезпечення, зовнішня нормативна база, внутрішньовідомча нормативна база, прийняття управлінських рішень, ефективність управлінської діяльності.

Introduction.

The creation of the National Police of Ukraine on July 2, 2015, required the resolution of many issues related to the provision of its activities with the necessary regulatory framework, material, financial, human resources and other resources. There was also an urgent need to review the basic principles of police activity, to form new approaches to the definition of tasks, functions, principles, powers of the newly created body, as well as to increase the effectiveness of its activities.

One of the important factors that influence the effectiveness of the functioning of the units of the National Police of Ukraine is the management of their managers. Increasing the efficiency of managerial labor is a major measure to improve the overall mechanism for managing labor resources. The head ensures the rights of the unit, combining the interests of society and employees of the team, manages the social processes of work of all its members, ensures the integrity and systematic nature of the joint activities of the team under its control.

Among all areas of professional activity of heads of units of the National Police of Ukraine, the process of making managerial decisions takes the leading place: their development, implementation and control over implementation. The necessity and obligation to make a management decision is the main function of the professional management of the heads of bodies and units of the National Police of Ukraine. And since the principle of legality permeates everything that the head does, so understanding the features of legal support when making managerial decisions is extremely important for the success, professionalism and skill in the art of management.

Thus, law enforcement, which is accompanied by the adoption of numerous managerial decisions, is connected with the realization of the rights, freedoms and legal interests of individuals and legal entities, therefore the problems of legal provision of

management decisions in the departments of the National Police of Ukraine are very relevant.

Different aspects of the issues of making managerial decisions were investigated in the writings of VB Averyanov, O. F. Andryko, G. V. Atamanchuk, O. M. Bandurka, V. M. Bevzenka, A. I. Bezpalova, Yu. P. Bityak, V. M. Garashchuk, S. M. Gusarova, A. V. Jafarova, T. E. Kaganovskaya, R. A. Kalyuzhnyj, V. K. Kolpakova, V. V. Kopeichikova, V. O. Kryvolapchuka, O. V. Kuzmenko, A. M. Kulish, K. B. Levchenko, D. M. Lukyanets, A. I. Mykolenko, A. M. Muzychuk, V. I. Olefira, A. I. Ostapenko, VF Opryshka, A. M. Podolyaki, R. A. Serbin, O. Yu. Sinyavskaya, V. V. Sokurenko, S. G. Stetsenko, M. M. Tischenko, V. M. Shapoval al. The works of these scholars have revealed the main characteristics, components, requirements for managerial decisions, features of the process of preparation, implementation and control. However, the peculiarities of legal support for making managerial decisions by the heads of the National Police of Ukraine are not yet fully disclosed in our opinion.

An assessment of the effectiveness of any unit of the National Police of Ukraine is closely linked with the assessment of the professional activities of its head. Therefore, the purpose of the paper is to disclose legal support when making managerial decisions by the manager, which will enable them to timely correct and direct the activities of managers in order to increase the efficiency and effectiveness of their management.

1. The normative legal basis of the activities of the heads of the units of the National Police in Ukraine for the adoption of managerial decisions.

In the theory of management under the decision means a compulsory implementation of the socially necessary action of the will of the subject of governance, associated with the choice of purpose, ways and means of achieving it and the definition of performers. Management decision is an initial and fundamental point in the organization of the activities of each manager, because it is the main content of the management process (Management by the bodies of the National Police of Ukraine, 2017, pp. 174-175).

In the narrow sense of decision-making - this is the choice of the best solution from many alternatives. In the broader sense, decision making is identified with the whole process of management, and therefore the concept of decision-making covers their development, implementation, as well as control and analysis of the results of their implementation (Managed by the bodies of the National Police of Ukraine, 2017, pp. 169-170).

The quality of managerial decisions determines the whole course of the management process, the final results of law enforcement activities. Every practical operation of the police unit, whatever it may be (in the course of a search, detaining the suspect, sending information, an act of permission or prohibition) begins with the adoption of a decision that provides for a continuous chain of measures for its implementation. The diversity of managerial decisions that are made at different levels of management of the heads of the police units must meet certain general requirements:

- managerial decisions must be reasonable, objective, take into account all the peculiarities of the situation, meet the specific conditions, objectives and opportunities for achieving them;

- management decisions must comply with the requirements of legislative acts, orders of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, instructions and guidelines;

- managerial decisions must be taken within the competence of the subject of management, that is, to conform to the functional duties of the official who accepts them;

- Management decisions must be timely: delayed decisions, like premature, reduce the effectiveness of management and can lead to grave consequences;

- the managerial decision in the police departments is always policy-oriented, imperious and binding on everyone to whom it is addressed; execution of the decision is guaranteed by the rules of law, and in cases of necessity may be ensured by coercive measures;

- the management decision in the police units is taken unilaterally, even if it is the result of a collective discussion or the result of the agreement between the various subjects of management;

- management decision establishes mandatory rules of conduct or regulates individual management relationships; it can apply to the entire team or its individual members;

- managerial decision is the result of creative work; it requires a scientific approach, must be concise and consistent, understandable to the performer and not contradict the previously adopted decision or exclude them;

- the administrative decision in the police organs is taken in the established procedural order, which is regulated by the relevant normative acts (*Management by the bodies of the National Police of Ukraine, 2017, pp. 170-171*).

Managerial decision is the initial and fundamental point in the organization of each manager's activity, as it is the main content of the management process. The need for development and decision-making is conditioned by the presence of problems related to professional activity, ie, such theoretical issues or practical situations, for solving which it is necessary to carry out a number of actions both to actors and objects of management.

The administrative decision in the police units is based on laws and regulations, an analysis and assessment of the operational situation, the act of the respective head of the unit of the National Police of Ukraine. This act, which contains the statement of objectives, justification of their means of implementation, is adopted in accordance with the established procedure and ensures organizational sustainability and improvement of the activities of police units in carrying out tasks for ensuring the protection of human rights and freedoms, the interests of society and the state, combating crime, maintaining public security and order, as well as the provision of police services (*Office of the National Police of Ukraine, 2017, pp. 175*).

Legal support in making managerial decisions by the heads of the departments of the National Police of Ukraine is considered by us in connection with the implementation of the tasks set before the law-enforcement system for the protection of the rights, freedoms and legal interests of individuals and legal entities, the interests of society and the state from illegal encroachment, the fight against offenses, public order protection, public safety - on the one hand, and as a means of organizing, providing and coordinating the implementation of these tasks - from another one. Legal norms provide modeling of the procedure for making managerial decisions in the police, its valuation and formalization.

As G.V. Atamanchuk notes, the legal support of any activity, including the managerial inherent unity of sociological, normative and practical aspects (Atamanchuk,

2000, p. 68). The sociological content of legal provision consists in the fact that it only begins when it has a social need, that is, it is necessary to regulate one or another aspect of social relations, or vice versa cancel such regulation. Normative aspect of legal provision appears, as development and legal (in acts of state bodies) consolidation (setting) of the rules (rules) of human behavior and conduct socially significant cases. The practical aspect of legal provision is the real application of legal norms in public practice. The presence of this aspect requires awareness of the fact that any norm is worthless if its implementation is not provided by organizational and state structures. Thus, the presented aspects of legal support are interdependent, that is, those that are in constant interaction with each other. And the absence or inappropriate implementation of any of them can lead to the destruction of the entire system of legal provision of any socially useful activity (Atamanchuk, 2000, pp. 69-70).

In general, the system of legal support for the adoption of managerial decisions by the heads of units of the National Police of Ukraine is a set of laws and by-laws that create the legal framework for their functioning. Hence, the entire regulatory framework that managers should take into account when making managerial decisions can be divided into external, which is formally created outside the departments of the National Police, but the creation of which law enforcement bodies have a direct relationship, directly developing or participating in the development of projects of one or another normative acts, and the internal normative base, that is, the legal acts adopted by the police. The peculiarity of the legal provision of management decisions at the National Police is that the latter are endowed with the right of departmental rulemaking, the result of which is the adoption of orders, instructions, instructions, orders, etc., which are some types of administrative decisions, in particular legal ones, and can be both normative and individual (Konoplyov, 2006, p. 101).

Consequently, the normative legal basis for the activities of the heads of the National Police units of Ukraine regarding the adoption of administrative decisions is: the Constitution of Ukraine, international treaties, laws of Ukraine, decrees of the President of Ukraine, legal acts of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, acts of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and the National Police of Ukraine. other subordinate (departmental) acts taken within the limits of their authority and in accordance with the Constitution of Ukraine and laws of Ukraine, as well as acts of individual action, issued on the basis of specific legal norms (individual regulation).

2. External normative base when making managerial decisions by managers.

The Constitution of Ukraine forms the basis of the system and content of all sources of law in our state. In addition, it is the basis for the further development of Ukraine's law enforcement legislation, and, based on its provisions, all other normative acts regulating the activities of the police authorities of Ukraine are adopted. In the course of law enforcement activities, police units are guided by the rule of law principle enshrined in Article 3 of the Constitution of Ukraine, according to which a person, his rights and freedoms are recognized as the highest values and determine the content and direction of the state's activities. In carrying out their tasks, the police units ensure the observance of human rights and freedoms guaranteed by Section II of the Constitution of Ukraine (Constitution of Ukraine, 1996).

To understand the meaning of the basic law in legal provision of managerial decisions by heads of police, it is that it plays a leading role in limiting the unlawful encroachment on the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of individuals and legal

entities. The Constitution is at the top of the hierarchy of sources of law; it must necessarily meet all the regulations without exception. Being the highest act of legal force, the Constitution of Ukraine is an element of the national system of legislation. It is not passed beyond the current law, and at the same time is a specific legislative act. Its norms are of a primitive nature, they have the highest stability, the highest legal force (Commentary on the Constitution of Ukraine, 1996, p. 40).

But it should be noted that the Constitution is not able to regulate all aspects of public life. Therefore, in legal provision of managerial decisions, heads of units of the National Police have a significant place in international treaties, laws that are adopted in a special manner by regulations that directly reflect the national will and have a higher (after the Constitution) legal force. The objective need to ensure that the main issues of the adoption of managerial decisions in the police are regulated by laws, is determined by the fact that they concern a large number of individuals and legal entities, supervision and control of which activities are entrusted to law enforcement agencies.

In accordance with Article 9 of the Constitution of Ukraine, current international treaties, the consent of which is binding on the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, is part of the national legislation of Ukraine (Constitution of Ukraine, 1996). According to the provisions of the Law of Ukraine "On National Police", in its activities it is guided by international treaties of Ukraine, the consent of which is binding on the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, while in carrying out its tasks, the police ensure observance of human rights and freedoms guaranteed by the Constitution and laws of Ukraine, as well as international treaties of Ukraine, the consent of which is binding on the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine, and promotes their implementation (Law of Ukraine "On National Police", 2015).

Based on the foregoing, the heads of the units of the National Police of Ukraine should be classified into international normative legal acts, which should be guided by the adoption of management decisions: the Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 10.12.1948; The Declaration on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination of 20.11.1963; International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights dated December 16, 1966; The Declaration on the Protection of All Persons from Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment of December 9, 1975; The Code of Conduct of Officials in Support of Law and Order of 17.12.1979; Basic principles of the use of force and firearms by law enforcement officials, adopted by the UN Resolution of 07.09.1990; European Code of Police Ethics of 19.09.2001 (Policy and Administration Police in Questions and Answers, 2017, p. 20). The international treaties that constitute the basis for making managerial decisions by heads of units of the National Police must include those whose legal assistance in criminal matters is the subject of which define the conceptual principles of protection and protection of the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of a person in the state, determine the bases and permissible limits law enforcement activities of the police, etc.

Among the basic laws of Ukraine that regulate the external and internal activities of police units and which managers should take into account when making managerial decisions, it should first of all be noted: Code of Ukraine on Administrative Offenses of December 07, 1984 (with amendments and additions); Labor Code of Ukraine of 10.12.1971 (as amended); Law of Ukraine "On administrative supervision of persons released from places of imprisonment" of 01.12.1994 (with amendments and supplements); Law of Ukraine "On Citizens' Appeal" of 02.10.1996 (with amendments

and supplements); The Law of Ukraine "On Prevention of Corruption" of 14.10.2014 (with amendments and additions); The Law of Ukraine "On National Police" dated 02.07.2015 (with amendments and additions) (Police Administration in Questions and Answers, 2017, pp. 17-18).

The secondary forms of legal support for the adoption of management decisions by the heads of units of the National Police are regulatory acts issued by the subjects of executive power and ensure the effectiveness of constitutional and legislative norms. Yes, the President of Ukraine, in pursuance of the assigned powers, issues decrees and orders aimed at improving the activities of the units of the National Police in making managerial decisions. Examples of such acts include the following: Decree of the President of Ukraine "On the list of positions that may be replaced by police officers in state bodies, institutions and organizations" of 09.12.2015; Decree of the President of Ukraine "On the Symbols of the National Police of Ukraine" dated 09.12.2015; Decree of the President of Ukraine "On the Day of the National Police of Ukraine" dated 09.12.2015 (Administrative Activities of the Police in Questions and Answers, 2017, p. 18).

An important place in the system of legal acts, which form the basis of legal support for the adoption of management decisions in the departments of the National Police, occupy the normative and individual legal acts of the Cabinet of Ministers as the supreme body in the system of executive power. According to the Law of Ukraine "On the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine" of 27.02.2014, its main tasks include the implementation of measures to ensure the defense capability and national security of Ukraine, public order, the fight against crime, the liquidation of the consequences of emergencies (Law of Ukraine "On the Cabinet of Ministers Ukraine", 2014).

The Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine directs and coordinates the work of ministries and other central executive authorities that ensure the implementation of state policy in relevant spheres of public and public life, the implementation of the Constitution and laws of Ukraine, acts of the President of Ukraine, and the observance of human and civil rights and freedoms.

The acts of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, which regulate the activities of the units of the National Police and influence the adoption of management decisions by their leaders, include the following: Road Traffic Law of 10.10.2001; Regulations on single officers from 30.09.2015; Regulations on the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine dated October 28, 2015; Regulations on the National Police of Ukraine dated October 28, 2015; The provision on the provision of cash for police officers seconded to state bodies, institutions and organizations as of 04.11.2015 (Policy and Administration of Police in Questions and Answers, 2017, pp. 18-19).

The peculiarity of the legal acts of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine regarding the topics of our study is that they establish the foundations, requirements and procedures for making managerial decisions by the heads of units of the National Police.

3. An internal normative base that regulates the adoption of managerial decisions by managers

The Ministry of Internal Affairs is developing draft state programs on issues of public security and order, crime prevention, road safety, border guard, protection of objects and territories in the event of emergencies, as well as on migration issues. The orders of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, adopted within the powers envisaged by the law, are mandatory for execution by central executive authorities, their territorial bodies, local state administrations, authorities of the Autonomous Republic of Crimea, local

self-government bodies, enterprises, institutions and organizations irrespective of the form of ownership and citizens. , including the National Police of Ukraine when making managerial decisions by managers.

Therefore, the following orders of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine and the National Police of Ukraine should be noted, which should be taken into account when making managerial decisions by their leaders: the Regulations on the procedure for dealing with appeals of citizens and organization of their personal reception in the system of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine dated 10.10.2004; Instruction on the organization of the work of duty units and units of internal affairs of Ukraine, aimed at protecting the interests of society and the state from unlawful encroachments, dated April 29, 2009; Regulations on the patrol service of the Ministry of Internal Affairs dated 07.07.2015; Regulations on the Department of Patrol Police dated November 6, 2015; Regulations on the Department of Criminal Investigation of the National Police of Ukraine dated November 14, 2015; Instruction on registration of materials on administrative violations in the police authorities from 06.11.2015; Instruction on registration of police materials on administrative violations in the field of ensuring road safety, recorded not in automatic mode, from 07.11.2015; Instruction on the procedure for detecting signs of alcohol, narcotic or other intoxication or staying under the influence of drugs that reduce the attention and reaction speed of drivers from vehicles from 09.11.2015; Instruction on the organization of control over the execution of documents in the National Police of Ukraine from June 13, 2016; Instruction on automated accounting of administrative offenses from 04.07.2016; The order of the organization of the interaction of the National Guard of Ukraine and the National Police of Ukraine during the provision (protection) of public (public) security and order of 10.08.2016 (Administrative Activities of the Police in Questions and Answers, 2017, p. 19).

Individual acts are common in the practice of state-management activities, since they correspond most to its executive purpose and are the most important means of operational solution of current management issues (Neugendnikov, 2009, p. 205). Individual acts reflect the legal norms taking into account the specific situation and the actual specificity of the legal situation. The main requirement for individual acts is their strict compliance with legal acts, which establishes all the specifics of management of units of the National Police. The main thing in these acts is the concreteness, that is, the resolution through their help of individual cases and issues concerning specific individuals, the emergence of personalized administrative legal relationships, caused by these acts (Administrative Law of Ukraine, Academic course, 2004, p. 95). The most striking examples of acts of individual action are legal acts on personnel issues taken by heads of units of the National Police to establish an unimpeded process for the performance of police duties (for example, orders for appointment and dismissal), disciplinary measures to employees of these actors, decision on the interaction between individual organs and police units, etc.

They usually relate to one person or are limited by certain features of the circle of individuals and are aimed at resolving clearly defined issues.

Particular attention deserves the procedure for the adoption of individual legal acts that occupy a significant part of the entire array of legal acts of the National Police of Ukraine. These are the acts that reflect mainly in-house activities.

Individual legal acts have the following characteristics:

- Individual character, since it resolves very specific questions and specifies the specific addressee who must adhere to or is concerned with the order contained in the act;
- has a state-power character for those to whom it is addressed;
- is always issued unilaterally;
- causes the emergence, change, termination of administrative legal relations, that is, it is a legal fact (Salmanova, 2016, pp. 312-313).

In addition, distinguish the following signs of individual acts:

1) the subject of the adoption of individual administrative acts is the public administration, that is, the executive authorities, local self-government bodies, as well as other entities authorized by law;

2) individual administrative acts are decisions of public administration, that is, contain the will of the authorized entity;

3) individual administrative acts are unilateral decisions of the public administration, the addressees of such acts have the right to influence the content of the decision, but the final decision is always taken by the public administration;

4) individual administrative acts are authoritative decisions of public administration, which entails legal consequences for certain individuals or legal entities. Documents drawn up by the public administration in the course of adopting an individual administrative act, but not involving legal consequences (for example, an act of inspection or a protocol), do not belong to individual administrative acts;

5) individual administrative acts determine specific legal relations and concern specific individuals and legal entities;

6) under individual administrative acts, we understand only acts of external action, and internal administrative acts that define the legal relationship within the system of public administration bodies are a separate category;

7) individual administrative acts are usually taken in writing, however, in cases provided for by law, may be adopted either verbally or in conciliation;

8) due to the insufficient systemic development of administrative legislation, the names of the individual administrative act are different (orders, permissions, licenses, decisions-reports, etc.), determined by the laws, depending on the subject of acceptance or the sphere of legal relations. Thus, an individual administrative act is a generic term that covers the various names of acts;

9) individual administrative acts should be taken in strict accordance with the procedure established by law. As of today, the procedure for the adoption of such acts in Ukraine is not systematized and to a certain extent regulated only in special and legislative legislative, as well as, unfortunately, in by-laws (Salmanov, 2016, pp. 313-314).

The procedure for the adoption of individual legal acts differs from the general procedure for the publication of legal acts. In this case, it is possible to distinguish two of its types depending on the content of the act, namely:

- proceedings on the realization by citizens of their rights and responsibilities in the field of public administration;

- proceedings on the adoption of individual legal acts in the field of internal management of the subject of authority.

In the first case, the procedure includes the following steps:

- submission by citizens of the relevant application and its acceptance for consideration by the authorized entity;

- case review, analysis and selection for the application of relevant legal rules;

- decision making;
- execution of the decision;
- appeal or protest decision (Salmanova, 2016, pp. 314-315).

In the field of internal management, the initiator of the adoption of an individual legal act is a competent official. Reasons for making such a decision may be rules of law, events that have legal consequences, or other circumstances that led to the need for such an act. The proceeding begins with an analysis of the situation or the rules of law. Then, the legal rules on which the legal act will be based will be chosen and a corresponding decision is made, which will be issued in the established order. The decision taken may be challenged or challenged by the person concerned. The receipt of complaints does not stop the execution of the decision, which must be executed immediately or in accordance with the terms specified by the individual legal act.

Adoption of an individual act of management in one person's manner is carried out by its signing by an appropriate official. Possible and collegiate order of adoption of an individual management act. Such an arrangement involves discussing an act that is adopted and conducting a vote on its adoption.

Thus, the adoption of legal acts of the National Police of Ukraine is conditioned by the specifics of its work and differs depending on the type of legal act. To date, in this body of state power there is no normative legal act that would regulate this procedure, which negatively affects the quality of legal acts and the procedure for implementing the procedure for their adoption. In such an act it is necessary to consolidate the procedure of approval, discussion, registration, publication of legal acts and bringing them to the notice of performers, based on the division of legal acts into general and individual ones (Salmanova, 2016, p. 315).

We share the point of view of VV Konoplyov, who in his dissertation explores the following tasks of legal support for the adoption of managerial decisions by managers, and we believe that they are relevant to the departments of the National Police:

- ensuring the exact distribution of competences (rights and responsibilities) between the units (officials, individual employees) of the police;
- rationalization of the construction of a system for the adoption of managerial decisions and accurate correlation with the institution of responsibility;
- ordering the distribution of time required for the preparation, adoption and execution of management decisions;
- Personnel, information, financial and logistical support for the preparation, adoption and execution of management decisions;
- definition of criteria of efficiency of administrative decisions;
- providing a system of supervisory and supervisory activities for making managerial decisions in law enforcement activities of the units of the National Police of Ukraine (Konoplyov, 2006, p. 114).

Hence it follows that the essence of legal support for the adoption of managerial decisions by heads in the units of the National Police is as follows:

- 1) the legal consolidation of tasks, competencies, functions, organizational structure of all units of the police;
- 2) normative determination of the forms, methods and techniques of the most effective foreign-administrative and internal-organizational activities of the police;
- 3) the details of social relations, which are regulated by normative acts of higher legal force.

The competence for the preparation and adoption of managerial decisions by the heads in the units of the National Police of Ukraine is determined by the place of the head in the hierarchical system of the police. The higher the rank is taken by the head, the broader his competence and the higher legal force are his managerial decisions (Konoplyov, 2006, pp. 114-115).

The preparation and adoption of legal acts by heads of units of the National Police of Ukraine consists of a set of successive actions, which are united in the appropriate stages of the proceedings. To date, there is no single view on the number and content of the stages of rule-making proceedings. However, after analyzing the scientific views at the stage of the rule-making process and taking into account the specifics of the legal acts of the National Police of Ukraine, let us dwell on the point of view of O. Y. Salmanova concerning the stages of adoption of legal acts:

- 1) identification of needs and planning of preparation and publication of legal acts;
- 2) drafting a legal act;
- 3) promulgation and discussion of the draft legal act;
- 4) consideration and adoption of a legal act;
- 5) registration of a legal act;
- 6) the official publication of the legal act and its application to execution.

Each of these steps includes a number of stages and management actions. Their totality and order differ depending on the type of legal act, its contents and the range of persons to whom its action applies. At the same time, there are a number of general rules that the procedure for adopting legal acts must comply with (Salmanov, 2016, pp. 260, 263-264).

To date, the legislation lacks a clear list of legal acts that may be issued by the National Police of Ukraine. Their species are found on the list of powers of the head of the police, which states that he:

- signs the orders of the police;
- abolishes, in full or in a separate part of acts of territorial police bodies;
- within the limits of the authority, issues orders that are mandatory for police officers, civil servants and police officers;
- approves the provisions on independent structural units of the police apparatus.

That is, orders, orders and regulations are used in the activity of the police. This list is not exhaustive, since in practice there are such legal acts as instructions, instructions, statutes, decisions, etc. (Salmanova, 2016, pp. 285).

Summing up, I would like to note that the legal framework for the adoption of managerial decisions by heads in the departments of the National Police of Ukraine is provided by a large number of various normative acts. As G.V. Atamanchuk notes, in order to achieve the optimal structure of legal provision of public administration, the process of establishing rights should be systematically organized. It is important to achieve interaction: by the time the publication of legal acts; in the content of the norms governing the same type of relations; for bodies that make up subsystems of public administration; by the legal force of legal acts belonging to one level of the organizational structure of governance (Atamanchuk, 2000, pp. 179). The same applies to the legal provision of the preparation and adoption of managerial decisions by heads in police units, the norms of which should be coordinated (coordinated) by the legal force, the bodies issuing them, as well as the time and content of their regulations.

Conclusions.

In order to increase the effectiveness of law enforcement activities, the heads of the National Police units who take legal management decisions, that is, those that entail certain legal consequences, must take into account the following:

1. The system of normative legal acts that form the basis of legal support for the preparation and adoption of managerial decisions by heads in the units of the National Police of Ukraine can be divided into two groups: external - those that exist outside the scope of the police, and internal - covered by the competence of the police.

2. Legal support for the adoption of management decisions by the heads of the departments of the National Police of Ukraine contains normative acts that stipulate certain requirements for the procedure for the preparation and adoption of management decisions, their contents, registration, etc.; is the reason or condition for the adoption of appropriate managerial decisions in the police.

3. To achieve the effectiveness of legal support for the adoption of managerial decisions by the heads of the units of the National Police of Ukraine can be provided that the requirements of legal acts on legal consolidation are harmonized:

1) the competence of managers to make managerial decisions on certain issues of the foreign-administrative or internal-organizational activities of the police;

2) the content of managerial decisions;

3) the order of their preparation and acceptance, legal technique of registration;

4) the system of entities that are authorized to exercise control and oversight responsibilities for the implementation of management decisions.

4. The work on making managerial decisions requires the heads of the departments of the National Police of Ukraine to have a high level of competence, time, energy, experience. It also provides for a high level of responsibility, since in order to implement the decisions made, it is necessary to ensure an efficient and coordinated work for the entire unit. Therefore, understanding the peculiarities of legal support for making managerial decisions is extremely important for all managers who want to ensure a high level of efficiency of their activities and activities of the unit as a whole.

5. Preparation and adoption of legal acts by the National Police is one of the main procedures in the executive and regulatory activities of its leaders. The development and implementation of legal acts is intended to ensure the proper implementation of the current legislation in the activities of the police, to determine the peculiarities of the implementation of legal norms and to improve the effectiveness of law enforcement activities. It is from the proper implementation of this procedure, the observance of all rules and techniques depends on the accuracy and quality of the tasks performed by the police.

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WPLYW ŚRODOWISKA EDUKACYJNEGO NA ROZWÓJ UCZNIA SZKOŁY PODSTAWOWEJ W WARUNKACH NOWEJ SZKOŁY UKRAIŃSKIEJ

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Adnotacja. Ministerstwo Edukacji i Nauki Ukrainy wdrażając reformę szkół średnich przewiduje utworzenie szkoły, w której dzieci będą uczyć się poprzez działania, natomiast nacisk zostanie położony na rozwój kompetencji, a nie na zapamiętywanie faktów. Artykuł ujawnia główny cel innowacji - stworzenie Nowej szkoły ukraińskiej, centrum wiedzy i możliwości samorealizacji i wszechstronnego rozwoju osobistego każdego dziecka. Ustalono, że szkoła podstawowa jest podstawą (bazą) dla dalszego rozwoju dziecka (wszechstronny rozwój dziecka zgodnie z wiekiem i indywidualnymi cechami i potrzebami psychofizjologicznymi), jej postrzeganie i stosunek do uczenia się. Uzasadnione, że reforma nowoczesnej branży edukacyjnej przewiduje troskę o środowisko edukacyjnym. Okazuje się, że głównie nie jest tutaj technika czy meble, ale zmiana środowiska edukacyjnego, która polega na zmianie nastawienia do dziecka: szacunku, uwagi i chęci znalezienia najlepszego sposobu na jego skuteczne uczenie się.

Słowa kluczowe: środowisko, środowisko edukacyjne, nowa szkoła ukraińska, harmonijny rozwój

THE INFLUENCE OF EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT ON THE JUNIOR'S DEVELOPMENT IN CONDITIONS OF THE NEW UKRAINIAN SCHOOL

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Abstract. The Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, implementing the reform of secondary schools, provides for establishment of a school where children will be trained through activities, while focus will be on development of competencies but not memorizing facts. The article reveals the main goal of innovations – establishment of the New Ukrainian School, a center of knowledge and opportunities for self-realization and comprehensive personal development of each child. It has been determined that the elementary school is the basis (base) for the child's all further development (the child's comprehensive development in accordance with age and individual psychophysiological features and needs), its perception and attitude to learning. The reformation of the modern educational branch involves concern about educational environment is substantiated. It is determined that the main thing here is not machinery or furniture, but change of educational environment, which involves change of the child's attitude: respect, attention to it and a desire to find the best way for its effective training.

Key words: environment, educational environment, new Ukrainian school, harmonious development

ВПЛИВ ОСВІТНЬОГО СЕРЕДОВИЩА НА РОЗВИТОК МОЛОДШОГО ШКОЛЯРА В УМОВАХ НОВОЇ УКРАЇНСЬКОЇ ШКОЛИ

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Анотація: Міністерство освіти і науки України, здійснюючи реформу середнього шкільництва, передбачає створення школи, де діти будуть навчатися через діяльність, а основна увага спрямована на розвиток компетентностей, а не запам'ятовування фактів. У статті розкрито головну мету нововведень – створення Нової української школи, осередку знань і можливостей для самореалізації та всебічного особистісного розвитку кожної дитини. Визначено, що початкова школа є основою (базою), на якій вибудовується весь подальший розвиток дитини (всебічний розвиток дитини відповідно до вікових та індивідуальних психофізіологічних особливостей і потреб), її сприйняття та ставлення до навчання. Обґрунтовано, що реформування сучасної освітньої галузі передбачає турботу про освітнє середовище. Визначено, що головним тут виступає не техніка чи меблі, а зміна освітнього середовища, яка передбачає зміну ставлення до дитини: повага, увага до неї і прагнення знайти оптимальний спосіб для її ефективного навчання.

Ключові слова: середовище, освітнє середовище, нова українська школа, гармонійний розвиток

Introduction.

At the current stage of society's development, education is being reformed. In order to provide high-quality educational services, the new Law of Ukraine "On Education" is being implemented in the state, implementation of measures envisaged by the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine Decree No. 988-r of December 14, 2016 "On Approval of the Concept of Implementation of State Policy in the Field of General

Secondary Education Reform" New Ukrainian School for the Period till 2029 "and December 13, 2017 No. 903-p" On Approval of the Action Plan for 2017-2029 on the Implementation of the Concept for the Implementation of the State Policy in the Reform of General Secondary Education "But a Ukrainian school. "

As Oleksandr Savchenko notes, primary school, earlier than other levels of education, became the object of updating the educational process on the basis of childhood cynicism, partnership, taking into account the children's vital needs, developing new state standards, educational programs, evaluating educational results (Savchenko, 2018, p. 3).

It is in elementary school that the foundation of preparation for life is laid, intellectual, spiritual and physical formation of the personality is provided. In the elementary school children are interested in art, engaging in music and artistic and creative activities. The initial link of education is designed to form a holistic worldview and attitudes of students, to ensure the development of aesthetic ideals and tastes, a sense of responsibility for preserving the cultural heritage of society.

O. Savchenko notes that the goal of primary education is the comprehensive development of the child, his talents, abilities, competencies (key, general subjects, subject) and cross-cutting skills in accordance with age and individual psycho-physiological characteristics and needs, formation of values, development of autonomy, creativity and curiosity (Savchenko, 2018, p. 4). The child's comprehensive development involves mental, physical, and aesthetic. Common for all competencies are the so-called cross-cutting skills: reading with understanding, ability to express their own opinion orally and in writing, critical and system thinking, ability to logically justify a position, creativity, initiative, ability to constructively manage emotions, evaluate risks, make decisions, solve problems, ability to co-operate with other people.

We hope that in the New Ukrainian school all conditions will be created for the harmonious development of the younger generation. The Methodological Recommendations on the organization of the educational space of the New Ukrainian School state that the specialty of such a school is, among other things, the organization of such an educational environment that will promote the free development of the child's creative personality.

Main part. The purpose of our article is to theoretically substantiate the influence of the educational environment on the harmonious development of a junior high school student at the New Ukrainian School. Objectives of the study: to investigate the concept of "educational environment"; determine how the educational environment affects the development of a junior schoolboy; what conditions need to be created in the educational environment, so that the student can thoroughly develop and comfortably feel.

To achieve the purpose of the article and the solution of problems was used as a method of research, analysis of psychological and pedagogical, philosophical literature on the organization of the educational environment and its impact on the development of the individual.

The essence of the notion "educational environment" has been substantiated by both domestic and foreign psychologists and educators over the last decades. The study of the educational environment is carried out from the point of view of the modern understanding of education as a special sphere of social life, and the environment as a factor of education (N. Gontarovsky, S. Deryab, V. Zhelanova, V. Kozyrev, T. Meng, K.

Pridchochenko and etc.); generalized models of the educational environment (V. Davydov, Y. Korchak, V. Lebedev, V. Orlov, V. Panov, V. Rubtsov, V. Slobodchikov, V. Yasvin, etc.).

The term "educational environment" is interpreted by the researchers as: it is a collection of all possibilities of learning, upbringing and development of the individual, both positive and negative (Deryaba, 2007, p. 39); the system of influences and conditions for the formation of the individual according to the given model, as well as opportunities for its development, contained in the social and subject-spatial environment (Yasvin, 2001, p. 14); the product of relations between subjects of the educational space; a complex of additional factors that provide children with comfortable conditions for development, education and upbringing (Kruty, 2009, p. 35); the unity of social and substantive means of ensuring the diverse activities of the child (Novoselova, 1995, p. 21). The educational environment is developing if it is able to provide a set of opportunities for the self-development of all subjects in the educational process.

In particular, Sedova L. notes that the idea of creating a developing environment as a means of development and self-development of the child is not new for modern psychological and pedagogical science. Its formation is associated with the introduction in the Enlightenment of the term "environment", which was understood as certain social, material and spiritual conditions of human existence, its activities. It was found that the environment is one of the decisive factors in the formation and development of personality (Sedov, 1999, p. 27).

In psychological and pedagogical science there are several approaches to the definition of the concept of the educational environment as one of the most important factors in the development of personality. A number of researchers (B. Bim-Bad, A. Petrovsky, L. Sokhan, I. Ermakov, L. Novikov, Yu. Manuilov) believe that the educational environment is a sphere of vital activity of the child, which is constantly changing. It absorbs the wealth of pupils' interconnected culture with the surrounding world, teaches to remove knowledge from their own activities, from observation and perception, to reveal the vital importance of the objects being studied, to understand the principles of their actions and to guide them in new situations (that is, to carry out transfer, which occupies an important place in the educational process and practical life) (Bim-Bad, 1996, p. 6).

The educational environment in the psycho-pedagogical literature is also regarded as a subsystem of the socio-cultural environment as a combination of factors, circumstances, historical situations, and as the integrity of the specially organized conditions for the development of the student's personality (O. Gazman, E. Klimov, G. Kovalev, K. Levin, V. Panov, K. Rogers, V. Rubtsov, I. Slobodchikov, S. Tarasov, V. Yasvin, and others).

In particular, Y. Klimov distinguishes the following components of the educational environment: the social-contact component; information component; somatic component; substantive component. The social-contact component of the environment includes: a personal example of people around them, their culture, experience, lifestyle, behavior, relationships, etc., state institutions and organizations, groups of people and their representatives with whom the person interacts in one way or another; personal relationships in a group that is "native" to this person. The information component of the environment is created by certain rules that arise in the process of

personal interaction. The somatic part of the environment consists of a person's state of health, the state and capabilities of the human body. The substantive component includes material conditions of life, study, life, biological, hygienic conditions, microclimate, air purity, etc.) (*Klimov, 1969, p.*).

Unlike E. Klimova, G. Kovalev distinguishes the following structural components of the educational environment: the physical environment - the room, its design, the size and spatial structure of the study facilities, the conditions for the transfer and placement of students; - the human factor - the selection of students, the filling of classes and groups and its impact on the social behavior of students, the characteristics and success of students, ethnic characteristics, the quality of teacher training, gender-age structure of the student contingent; training program - the innovative nature of the contents of study programs, teaching technology, the style and methods of teaching, the forms of educational activity, the nature of control (*Gontarovskaya, 1996, p. 6*).

Most authors agree that the central among other structural components of the educational environment is the psychological component (social or communicative component in terms of different authors). The psychological component of the educational environment is, first of all, the nature of the communication of the subjects of the educational process. This component carries the main load on providing opportunities for satisfaction and development of the needs of the subjects of the educational process in the sense of security, in preserving and improving self-esteem, in the formation of a positive "I-concept, in recognition of the other, in a respectful attitude to himself and to around, in self-actualization. As a key psychological characteristic of the educational environment of the educational institution, many scholars (I. Baiva, S. Vershlovsky, O. Lebedev, V. Slobodchikov, etc.) consider the safety and psychologically safe educational environment as a condition for the positive personal growth of its participants.

V. Slobodchikov considers the educational environment as a specially organized space, a "place" in a society where subjectively there are many relations, relationships and various activities of various systems of individual development and socialization. The scientist believes that the specific property of the educational environment is its saturation of educational resources. The saturation of the environment with educational resources transforms it into an educational environment. In his view, the boundaries of the educational space can expand and narrow, they are determined by the scale of professional activity of teachers, the scale of involvement of the socio-cultural environment in the educational activity itself. This activity is reduced to the size of a separate institution, one program, one subject, transforms the space into a set of atomized places of education, destroying its unity and continuity (*Slobodchikov, 2000, p. 176*).

Y. Kulyutkin notes that "the educational environment can be characterized as a set of social, cultural, as well as specially organized in a educational institution psychological and pedagogical conditions, as a result of interaction with which the individual is becoming an individual" (*Kulyutkin, 2001, p. 6*).

Along with the term "educational environment", the notion "developing environment", "educational and development environment" is considered. As O. Pysarchuk notes, in the broadest context, the educational-developing environment is a socio-cultural space, within which a process of personality development is carried out with different degrees of organization. According to the author, in order for the

educational space to become a developing environment, it must acquire the following properties: flexibility; continuity; variability; Integration; openness; the mood for a joint active communication of all subjects of the educational process (*Pisarchuk, 2016, p.4*).

The organization of educational developmental environment is defined as: the provision of a set of conditions associated with material and technical and programmatic and methodological provision of the educational process; creation of conditions for creative comfortable interaction of children between themselves, with teachers, parents; using various methods and means of activating activity that provides creative development of personality.

Different aspects of the influence of the educational environment on the development of the child have been reflected in the modern scientific researches of I. Baeva, B. Bim-Bad, I. Bulakh, A. Valitskaya, V. Verbitsky, B. Wolfov, I. Ermakov, A. Katushova, E. Klimova, O. Kobernik, N. Kudikina, Yu. Manuilova, L. Novikova, A. Petrovsky, H. Pustovita, A. Sbrueva, V. Slobodchikova, L. Sokhan and others.

Consequently, the educational environment - a set of objective external conditions, factors, social objects, necessary for the successful functioning of education. It is a system of influences and conditions for the formation of the individual, as well as opportunities for its development, which are contained in the social and spatial-subject environment.

The importance of solving the problem of creating an educational environment today is conditioned by the need for its holistic renewal and alignment with the general transformational changes that take place in society. Changing the educational environment is a change in the attitude of the child: respect, attention to it and the desire to find the best way for its effective learning. This is exactly what the New Ukrainian School should be like. The Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine approved the Methodological Recommendations on the organization of the educational space of the New Ukrainian School. In particular, the document states that the feature of the New Ukrainian School is, among other things, the organization of such an educational environment that will facilitate the free development of the child's creative personality. To this end, the spatial-subject environment, programs and means of training change.

Planning and designing the educational space of the school are aimed at developing the child and motivating her to study. General purpose equipment must meet the aesthetic requirements: to have an attractive appearance, modern design; compliance with the general style of the premises (https://osvita.ua/legislation/Ser_osv/60372/).

The school in which the student is during the school day begins with a nursery school. The appearance of the school, the decorating of the premises, study rooms, corridors, and the improvement of the preschool manor are of great importance for the comprehensive development of elementary school students. Multi-faceted and expedient use of school interior is possible only in case when its aesthetics will meet modern requirements. Modern aesthetic design of school interiors should promote the aesthetic education of children, develop their imagination, individual aesthetic tastes, and stimulate creative activity in various activities.

During the aesthetic design of the school interior, you can use such arts as monumental, decorative-applied and propaganda-registration.

According to N. Artemenko, "the aesthetics of school life is the situation of classes, offices, halls, corridors, etc. Lobby decoration, the design of a cool corner,

stands - all these are silent assistants of the teacher in the aesthetic, and, consequently, in the ethical the upbringing of schoolchildren, or his enemies "(Artemenko, 1978, p. 14).

Elementary school is a classroom with an established learning environment equipped with modern learning equipment and school equipment in accordance with sanitary and hygiene standards and regulations.

In accordance with the methodological recommendations of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine regarding the organization of the educational space of the New Ukrainian School, the educational environment should contribute to the free development of the child's creative personality. And this can be done through the creation of peculiar centers of pupils' activity in the classroom, in particular the educational-cognitive center of activity, thematic thematic centers, a cell for the game and artistic and creative activity, a corner of the wildlife, a recreation center, a children's library and a teacher's cell with the proper equipment.

The initial element of the school is the first to test new standards for Nursery and New Educational Space, where stands are an integral part of the design of elementary school cabinets. The introduction of new standards completely opens up new demands for student material delivery, new ideas for motivating students to learn, and radically change their design. Special attention is paid to the design, because the modern educational process requires changes not only in the process of information, but also in the design. Beautiful design directly affects the effectiveness of the educational process, where, with the help of various color schemes, drawings on the walls, posters, stands for the elementary school, creates an interesting, motivating, educational atmosphere, which is so lacking today.

According to the Regulation on the study rooms of general educational establishments, approved by the order of the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine dated July 20, 2004, No. 601 (<https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/z1121-04>), a school room for students elementary classes should be aesthetically appealing. In educational rooms for junior pupils, color monotony should be avoided. You need to create a cheerful atmosphere.

For registration of the Cabinet it is foreseen the creation of educational and methodical expositions of variable and permanent character. The permanent expositions of the cabinet of primary classes include: state symbols; rules of fire safety and traffic; a cool place where the rights and responsibilities of schoolchildren, rules of student behavior, self-government, and the life of the class collective are reflected.

In section cabinets of the cabinet are shown devices, collections of photo exhibitions, etc. Expositions of variable character include: exhibition of the best works of students; materials for the topic of the following lessons, indicative tasks of the thematic evaluation, state certification; additional information according to the curriculum; results of experimental and research work of students; results of student competitions, tournaments, etc.

The idea behind the design of school rooms in elementary school is that the walls of the school, its interior attract children's attention to such important aspects of our lives as ergonomics and aesthetics. Therefore, the school should not have standard classes, corridors and a boring lobby. But there should be a lot of bright and fun elements, and modern design solutions should be applied (*Bespala*, http://freepapers.ru/16/shlyahi-ta-zasobi-estetichnogo_vihovannya/ / 292273.2002739.list1.html).

It is important in the elementary school to decorate the premises, but it should not be placed on the front wall, because it diverts the attention of students from the board. The main thing in color design of school premises is the maximum comfort of its students. First of all it concerns the elementary school, where the first learning skills and social behavior are formed. A schoolboy should feel comfortable at school everywhere - in the school room, gym, recreation room, library, dining room, in the school yard, even looking at the premises of the school and the adjoining territory. Under such conditions, the state of health improves, the interest of children in the process of learning increases, the ability to fully absorb learning material increases significantly.

The criteria of evaluation of the functioning of the educational environment are determined: the educational environment provides for the harmonious development of children; the effectiveness of children's creative and research activity; creation of conditions for self-realization of personality in creative activity; the ability of the environment to meet the needs of the child and to form a system of social and spiritual values in it. An integrated criterion for the quality of the educational environment is its ability to provide all subjects of the educational process a system of opportunities for effective personal self-development.

Conclusions.

Thus, having made the theoretical substantiation of the problem under study we can conclude that the functional possibilities of the educational environment consist of the following components: various types of active, conscious and useful activity of students: educational, professional, sports, labor, creative, cognitive, social, economic, ecological, aesthetic and others. Life situations, discussions, and conversations in informal settings are also important; great saturation of sensory stimuli: design of the premises, aesthetics of the natural and social environment, works of art and architecture; spatial and temporal mobility in the organization of diverse student activities. The school should have a favorable psychological climate, a positive emotional and psychological atmosphere in the students' and pedagogical groups.

In the future, we plan to experiment with the study of the influence of the educational environment on the harmonious development of a junior schoolboy.

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PRAWNY ASPEKT WPŁYWU NA FORMOWANIE OPTYMALNEGO PARADYGMATU FILOZOFICZNEGO

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Streszczenie. Artykuł poświęcony jest ujawnianiu różnych aspektów wzajemnego oddziaływania filozofii i religii, ponieważ przeomyślenie wartości religii, jej treściowego, znaczeniowego elementu jest konieczne i ma oczywisty wymiar praktyczny, który wpływa na tworzenie optymalnego paradygmatu filozoficznego.

Słowa kluczowe: filozofia religijna, kultura, podejście teologiczne, podejście filozoficzne, światopogląd, społeczna funkcja religii, religia, materialistyczna dialektyka, świadomość społeczna, indywidualna świadomość, zjawisko religijne.

LEGAL ASPECT OF THE INFLUENCE ON FORMING OPTIMAL PHILOSOPHICAL PARADIGM

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Abstract. The article deals with the analysis of various aspects of the mutual influence of culture and religion, because reinterpretation of religion values, a meaningful, semantic element of religion is necessary and has evident practical dimension that affects forming of the optimal cultural paradigm.

Keywords: religious philosophy, culture, theological approach, philosophical approach, worldview, social function of religion, religion, materialistic dialectic, social consciousness, individual consciousness, religious phenomenon.

ЮРИДИЧНИЙ АСПЕКТ ВПЛИВУ НА ФОРМУВАННЯ ОПТИМАЛЬНОЇ ФІЛОСОФСЬКОЇ ПАРАДИГМИ

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Анотація. Стаття присвячена розкриттю різних аспектів взаємовпливу філософії та релігії, адже переосмислення цінностей релігії, її змістовного, значеннєвого елементу є необхідним та має очевидний практичний вимір, що впливає на формування оптимальної філософської парадигми.

Ключові слова: релігійна філософія, культура, теологічний підхід, філософський підхід, світогляд, соціальна функція релігії, релігія, матеріалістична діалектика, суспільна свідомість, індивідуальна свідомість, релігійний феномен.

Formulation of the problem. Questions of the essence of religion have long been controversial. As a result of controversy, several basic approaches to understanding and defining religion, namely, theological, philosophical, sociological, psychological, and others, were formed. They mainly differ in the explanatory principle. At the same time, all approaches are interconnected and, first of all, due to the influence of one on another, the use of one or another ideological tradition of the specific ideas of their opponents, and so on.

Analysis of researches and publications. Such foreign and domestic scientists as S. Aleksieiev, V. Babkin, G. J. Berman, M. Koziubra, O. Kostenko, V. Nersesians, A. Sukhov, D. Uhrynovych, S. Tokariev, M. Andrianov, A. Kolodnyi, A. Poleshko and others made significant contributions to the research of various aspects of this problem.

The purpose of the article is to investigate the possibilities, which religion offers for man, for the culture of our era, changes not only the consciousness of people and the conditions of their existence in the world, but also the world itself. Therefore, a detailed analysis of the anthropological and ontological reasons for the existence of religion, its cultural possibilities is required.

Statement of the main material. Unlike theology, philosophy is characterized by a critical attitude to all phenomena of reality, including religion. Theological approach is based on the perception of religious belief as the primary and unconditional truth within the religious experience. However, philosophy demands to go beyond this experience and consider religion in the context of mind and its research methodology developed by it and other sciences.

As we know, one of the main tasks of philosophy is the development of conception of the world that corresponds to the modern level of science, historical practice and intellectual needs of man.

Analyzing the degree of development of the problem, it should be noted that religion was the object of philosophical consideration throughout its existence, its development. The degree of development of its problems in different epochs, in different countries, different philosophers was not the same.

They have a certain scientific and cognitive value, the right to life and the conclusions on religion, which are contained in many philosophical writings of Democritus, T. Hobbes, B. Spinoza, P. Holbach, I. Kant, G.W.F. Hegel, L. Feuerbach, J. Meunier, Voltaire, V. Soloviov, M. Berdiaiev, S. Frank, K. Marx, F. Engels, H. Plekhanov and other thinkers.

In Ukraine, the origin of the philosophical foundations of religious knowledge falls on the 19th century. It is associated with the names of M. Drahomanov, O. Potebnia, I. Franko, P. Yurkevych, M. Hrushevskiy and others. H. Skovoroda turned his mind to his assessments of the religious phenomenon. It is clear that these prominent creators of philosophy do not complete their list.

As L. Mytrokhin states, there are at least two reasons explaining the interest of philosophy to religion:

- firstly, it is impossible to understand the specifics of religion, its social functions and the mechanism of their activity without having carried out the study of "concluding" (i.e., socio-ontological) foundations of religious worship, behavior, and faith. And it is the prerogative of philosophical science. It is no coincidence that the attention of the greatest creators of "science of science" was invariably attached to religion;

- secondly, in religious conceptions and in their generalized theological concepts, a centuries-long moral and psychological experience is imprinted, which represents a special value for philosophical reflections of the human problem. That is why a number of philosophical schools were closely associated with the Christian doctrine and a little later separated from it (*Mitrohin L. N. 1989, p. 25*).

Scientists can consider a religion in the context of subjective-idealist, objective-idealist, dialectical-materialist and other positions.

The main thing in religious philosophy is the doctrine of the relation of man to God and God to man. In practice, it differs little from the theological concepts. If the latter undoubtedly interpret the dogmas of the sacred writings, then the religious philosophy submits them to analysis, exercises its interpretation.

Along with religious philosophy there is a philosophy of religion, in which the positive tendency in the assessment of religion in the life of man and society prevails. Within the philosophy of religion, deism has been developed, which states that although God exists in the world in the form of the root cause, however, after its creation, the movement of the universe is carried out without the participation of God, as well as pantheism, which defends the identity of God and the universe.

The philosophy of religion should highlight the works of Hegel (*Gegel' G. V. 1976*) and a German philosopher L. Feuerbach, a vivid representative of the materialist tendency. In his writings "The Essence of Christianity" and "Origin of Religion" (*Gegel' G. V. 1976*), the latter tried to prove that man is the beginning, middle and end of any religion and God is a perfect and mighty man.

A more developed form of materialism, rather than the anthropology of L. Feuerbach, stands for dialectical materialism.

Significant progress in understanding the essence of religion from the standpoint of materialist dialectics has been made by representatives of the so-called Marxist school. For example, in the paper "To the critique of the Hegelian philosophy of law" K. Marx gives an appropriate philosophical characterization of this phenomenon, saying that "religion is self-consciousness and self-control of a person who has either not yet found himself or has lost his life again. But man is not an abstract creature that lives somewhere outside the world. Man is the world of man, state, society. This state and this society generate religion, a false worldview, because they themselves are a false world. Religion is the general theory of the whole world, its encyclopedic compendium, its logic in a popular form, its spiritualistic point d'honneur (the point of honor), its enthusiasm, its moral sanction, its solemn addition, its universal basis for comfort and justification" (*Marks K., Enhels F. 1964, p. 384*).

From this and other definitions of religion by the classics of Marxism it is possible to distinguish a number of socio-philosophical principles of the analysis of this phenomenon, by which the sciences of social science are also guided today. Namely:

- there is no "personal" in religion. Its origins are in real life. In order to overcome religiosity, it is necessary to create an existential situation that would not give rise to any illusions. K. Marx wrote, "The abolition of religion as illusory happiness of the people is a requirement of their true happiness" (*Marks K., Enhels F. 1964, p. 385*);

- religion is a part of the social and individual consciousness, a fantastic form of reflection of reality;

- religion, as a social phenomenon, has a historical nature. This means that this phenomenon is a product of not eternal, but of transient social conditions;

- as a result of religiousness, the earthly forces, which take the form of the unearthly, are reflected in the minds of people;
- in the religious consciousness, the world surrounding the person has a real, terrestrial and unreal, unearthly basis;
- religion is a certain system of knowledge, ideology, moral and legal code, a stratum of culture, a sphere for the satisfaction of people during the period of their alienation from real life, etc.

However, today, not everything that is cultivated by Marxist science is the truth in the last instance.

For example, Marxist doctrine came from the fact that religion, as a historical phenomenon, has its beginning and its end, it will die with its natural death (*Il'in H. A. 1993, p. 112*). You can argue with the author of this idea. After all, K. Marx noted that religion itself is devoid of sense; its origins are not in heaven, but on earth. This is also confirmed by Karl Marx's thesis that the "religious feeling" is a social product, the totality of all social relations (*Marks K. 1976, p. 265*). To destroy the distorted reality, the expression of which is religion, is impossible. Difficulties, contradictions, due to the presence, removal, solution of which any society is always developed, nourish religion. It should also be noted that, in addition to social, it has gnoseological (due to the complexity of the process of knowing reality itself) and psychological (as individual for each person, and characteristic of society in general) basis. It is the eternal companion of man, society. The "eternity" of religion proved the German scholar D. Goldschmidt who wrote: "Religion existed and will exist in all societies at all times ... People need God to ritualize their way of life. God will never die. Man will not let him die" (*Bilko T. 2005, p. 8*). It is impossible to deny this conclusion, since the best symbol, the ideal, than God, humanity has not yet been found for itself.

Religious phenomenon has long been considered by many specific sciences of the so-called secular religious studies direction – sociology, psychology, history of religion, etc. It was not easy to approach such a consideration. Indeed, religion, in contrast to other objective phenomena (objects), in connection with its particular "divine nature," was considered "irrational", inaccessible to scientific analysis. But the revolution happened and it was successful.

A German sociologist M. Weber began studying the role of Protestant ethics in the genesis of Western European capitalism. His fundamental work "Protestant Ethics and the Spirit of Capitalism" (*Weber M. 1990*) brought to life a number of investigations related to the analysis of the "economic role" of world religions, the identification of social functions of religion, its place in culture, and modern forms of religiosity. The importance of the emergence of a sociological approach to religion lies in the fact that modern theology is not detached from sociology, but, on the contrary, tries to put it into service. There is sociologization of theology. Consequently, there is an opportunity for a world-view and theoretical dialogue between secular humanistic thought and different trends of theology, as well as corresponding joint practical actions.

In his papers, M. Weber elaborated ideas and conclusions of the French thinker E. Durkheim (*Djurkgejm Je. 1991*). The latter considered religion as a social phenomenon. The great scientist regarded the general beliefs, values and practical life orientations of religion as the basis of the social organism, allowing the functioning of society as certain integrity. That is why the purpose of religion is the same as morality and law. Religion should ensure social balance, which is constantly disturbed by various social

impulses and shifts. If religion is not able to maintain such a balance, it, according to the sociologist, is replaced by other religious entities. We should note that this conclusion is obviously more acceptable and important for a democratic society. In an antagonistic society, religion, or rather the church often acts as a "maid" of exploiting classes and may restrain progressive changes in their favor. In general, E. Durkheim' conception of religion as an integrating force and a stimulator of social development (it also found justification in his papers) is a significant contribution to the treasury of academic religious studies and philosophical science in general.

Religion is not only a social but also a psychological phenomenon. This is an important component of the inner emotional-volitional and spiritual life of a believer. The representatives of the psychology of religion make an emphasis on this side of religion in their researches.

In the psychology of religion, an important place occupies a psychoanalytic direction, represented by the works of Z. Freud, K. Jung, and E. Fromm (*Frejd Z. 1991*). Thus, Z. Freud's scientific works highlighted the important questions of constructing the inner world of the individual, of his motives and experiences, of conflicts between desires and sense of duty, the causes of mental stresses, and the illusory conceptions of man about himself and his environment. In religion, Z. Freud saw "a store of conceptions" generated by the need to make human helplessness less painful for both man and society.

In our opinion, the theoretical elaborations of psychologists of religion are of great importance in the aspect of knowing the mechanism of psychological influence of this phenomenon on society and man. It is well-known that certain spiritual, moral and psychological principles are needed for stabilization and evolutionary development of society. In the difficult time for Ukraine – the crisis period in the economy, political differences, the break-up of the old and the lack of a new ideology, there is a tendency to increase the asthenic state of society, which manifests itself in the spread of crime, drug addiction, neurological disorders of health, etc. In such circumstances, religion can perform a "medical" mission, dissolve personal neuroses, and soften or "remove" social hardship.

But it should be emphasized that in the psychology of religion there is also the "reverse side of the medal" – religion cannot only stabilize but also destabilize the psyche of church parishioners, which is clearly evident in the examples of the activities of separate confessions, totalitarian sects, and newest non-traditional church structures. All this requires a profound objective scientific study of this aspect of religion, the elaboration of appropriate legislative and organizational recommendations.

Z. Freud noted that in the process of his life, man develops a sense of fear and guilt with the inevitable appearance of neurosis under the influence of a social environment, which constantly monitors the individual giving him certain taboos. He compares this illness with individual religiosity, and defines religion as "universal collective neurosis." That is, Z. Freud deduced the idea of God, referring to the so-called Oedipus complex, to the suppressed desires of man displaced in the subconscious sphere of the soul (*Frejd Z. 1991*).

Theologians and clergy try to use Freud's psychoanalysis as a theoretical justification of the need for religion in the life of man and society, as well as in practical religious psychotherapy. There is a paradox: freethinker and rationalist Z. Freud, with

the help of representatives of theological tradition, himself, not wanting this, took the place of "the apostle of the psychoanalytic gospel".

According to the theory of the psychoanalyst K. Jung, religion helps people who are in need of access to the secret and symbolic, that is, plays an important role, first of all, in artistic creative work. According to the representative of the psychoanalytic direction E. Fromm, religious experience may not necessarily be related to theism. He considers the idea of God as symbolic and creates his concept of "new theology" (*Frejd Z. 1991, p. 3*). Religion is in any service of ideals, regardless of whom the person worships: whether idols, gods and saints, or leaders, class, nation, party or his success, wealth and power.

There are several other approaches to the definition of religion. For example, a German philosopher I. Kant considered religion to be a person's awareness of his moral duties; Hegel instead of the concept of God introduced the concept of "absolute idea" into the scientific circle, giving decisive importance of intellectual moment in religion; an English ethnographer E. Tylor considered the most important sign of religion to believe in spiritual beings, and a French historian of religion Reinak, understood religion as the system of prohibitions (taboos), and everything related to religious phenomena was forbidden.

There is the concept of "evolutionary-cosmic Christianity" of Tayar de Chardin. Based on the recognition of the universal "spirituality" of matter, Tayar de Chardin exercises the traditional division of Christianity into two substances – spiritual and material, divine and earthly. During the creation of the evolutionary-cosmic picture of the world, he applies a number of principles of dialectical methodology and, above all, the principle of development (*Tjejar de Sharden P. 1987*).

Religious consciousness of people, religious phenomenon in our society, is a fact, or rather, a mass phenomenon, which requires not only more or less correct definition, but also its further study.

In general, from a socio-philosophical point of view, religion is a multidisciplinary category. It can be considered in the broad and narrow sense of the word.

Such a twofold approach to the consideration of religion was substantiated by E. Fromm. He understands religion as "any system of views and actions, which is followed by a certain group of people and provides the individual with a system of orientations and object of worship" (*Frejd Z. 1991, p. 236*). From the standpoint of E. Fromm, each person is religious, and religion is inherent in all historical epochs.

In our opinion, religion is not only a manifestation of piety, entering man in the transcendence. History knew the communist, Nazi and other totalitarian ideologies, which represented a kind of secular religion with its obligatory attributes (doctrine, emotional and psychological treatment of the population, ritualism, the presence of certain organizational structures). According to M. Berdiaev, any totalitarianism prefers to be a church itself, and the ideological myth that is perceived by faith is essentially reinterpreted by religion (*Berdjaev H.A. 1989*).

According to Aristotle, man by nature (among other things) is ideological, has the inherent need for his own beliefs (convictions) serving as a reliable protection of his private interest, of his rights to a place in earthly existence. It proceeds from the definition of ideology given by K. Jaspers. According to his vision, ideology is a system of ideas or conceptions, which is "absolute truth" for the thinking subject and which

forms a one-sided interpretation of the world and his place in it (*Jaspers K. 1994*). Thus, his personal faith with signs of ideological frustration, even fantastic, constantly permeates the psychic life of every person. Faith allows the invisible (the expected), potential, and perspective to perceive as the real, visual, not necessarily turning to God or entering into the so-called beyond.

Religion is one way or another connected with popular creeds and beliefs. All mythological and demonological conceptions, magic rites, customs and rituals belong to science fiction, religious philosophy. They play an important role in human life, form spirituality, reflect the rich experience of people, and sometimes recreate their age-old aspirations, have not only historical-cognitive but also practical interest (*Ukrainci: narodni viruvannia, poviria, demonolohiia, 1992, p. 21*). The process of national revival of Ukraine can be accelerated, in particular, through the adoption the spiritual wealth of the people accumulated by many generations.

Religion, any faith or belief for a person, including signs of mysticism, is a means of asserting the personality, seeking his sense of his being, expressing his confidence in his plans and expectations.

An analysis of various philosophical approaches to understanding religion, knowledge of many provisions of the Scriptures, theological and religious-philosophical literature, communication with clerics and believers allows us to explain our vision of the essence of this phenomenon.

Man, who associates itself with religion, changes not only ideological orientations, but also is renewed spiritually, rebuilt psychologically (sensibly), deliberately chooses a verbally prescribed, and often ascetic way of life. The righteous, just and true thoughts and actions become an indisputable rule for true believers.

Conclusions. Summing up, we can state that religion is a special sphere of the spiritual life of the individual and society, a social phenomenon characterized by a deeply conscious high-spiritual mission, psychological mood and the corresponding practical actions of the individual or the human community associated with their attitude to the transcendental and the supernatural. Therefore, it is necessary to remember that the essence of the knowledge of religion is to consider it from different worldview positions in the light of social life and consciousness of the individual in the context of social space and time.

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POZALEKCYJNA WYCHOWAWCZA PRACA JAK JEST WAŻNA SKŁADOWA EDUKACYJNY-WYCHOWAWCZEGO PROCESU W ZAKŁADACH WYKSZTAŁCENIA PODSTAWOWEGO

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Streszczenie. W artykule rozpatrzono istotę i efektywność pozalekcyjnej wychowawczej pracy w zakładach wykształcenia podstawowego. Przeanalizowano stopień badania danej problematyki współczesnymi pedagogami-teoretykami i praktykami. Wyjaśniono treść pojęcia «pozalekcyjna praca» we współczesnej ukraińskiej pedagogice. Zarysowano wymogi do klasowego kierownika-głównego organizatora pozalekcyjnej wychowawczej pracy w zakładach wykształcenia podstawowego. Opisano charakterystyczne właściwości, zadania, warunki i formy organizacji pozalekcyjnej działalności. Rozpatrzono ogólne zasady pozalekcyjnej wychowawczej pracy i jej znaczenia w kształtowaniu osobistości młodszych uczni. Określono rolę pozalekcyjnej wychowawczej pracy w edukacyjny-wychowawczym procesie szkoły. Śledzą współczesne podejścia do pozalekcyjnej wychowawczej działalności. Uzasadniono myśl o tym że, interes uczni młodszych klas wpływa na efektywność przeprowadzenia pozalekcyjnej wychowawczej pracy.

Kluczowe słowa: wychowawczy proces, zakłady wykształcenia podstawowego, klasowy kierownik, młodzi uczniowie, nauczania, pozalekcyjna praca.

EXTRACURRICULAR EDUCATIONAL WORK AS AN IMPORTANT COMPONENT OF EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN ELEMENTARY EDUCATION ESTABLISHMENTS

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Abstract. The article deals the essence and efficiency of extracurricular educational work in elementary education establishments. The stage of studying this issue by modern pedagogues-theorists and practitioners is analyzed. The essence of the concepts «extra-curricular activity» in the modern Ukrainian pedagogy is clarified. The requirements for a class teacher, who is the main organizer of the extra-curricular activity on students moral education, are determined. The characteristic features, tasks, conditions and forms of organizing of extracurricular activities are described. The general principles of extracurricular educational work and its importance in the formation of the personality of elementary students are considered. The role of extracurricular educational work in the educational process of the school is determined. Modern approaches to extracurricular activities are traced. The opinion that the interest of elementary students influences the efficiency of extracurricular education work is substantiated.

Keywords: educational process, elementary education establishments, class teacher, elementary students, teaching, extracurricular activities.

ПОЗАКЛАСНА ВИХОВНА РОБОТА ЯК ВАЖЛИВА СКЛАДОВА НАВЧАЛЬНО-ВИХОВНОГО ПРОЦЕСУ В ЗАКЛАДАХ ПОЧАТКОВОЇ ОСВІТИ

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Анотація. У статті розглянуто сутність та ефективність позакласної виховної роботи в закладах початкової освіти. Проаналізовано ступінь дослідження даної проблематики сучасними педагогами-теоретиками та практиками. З'ясовано суть поняття «позакласна робота» у сучасній українській педагогіці. Окреслено вимоги до класного керівника – головного організатора позакласної виховної роботи в закладах початкової освіти. Описано характерні особливості, завдання, умови та форми організації позакласної діяльності. Розглянуто загальні засади позакласної виховної роботи та її значення у формуванні особистості молодших школярів. Визначено роль позакласної виховної роботи в навчально-виховному процесі школи. Простежено сучасні підходи до позакласної виховної діяльності. Обґрунтовано думку про те що, зацікавленість учнів молодших класів впливає на ефективність проведення позакласної виховної роботи.

Ключові слова: виховний процес, заклади початкової освіти, класний керівник, молодші школярі, навчання, позакласна робота.

Formulation of the problem. The main task of the modern school is to ensure the physical, intellectual, social and spiritual development of the student's personality, which is the basis for further education and work. The holistic development of the individual as an ideal of the educational process is formed in an adequate social and pedagogical situation by including the student in the system of relations of the common, that is, perceived by business interpersonal relations, educational-cognitive, subject-transformative, social-communicative, physical-recreational, artistic-aesthetic etc. activities. It is in the activity that creates favorable socio-psychological conditions for the development of creative potential, life activity of students. This should be aimed at both academic and extracurricular educational activities of schoolchildren. This extracurricular activity, which creates an atmosphere of relentlessness, initiative, amateur activity, has a special content, peculiar forms and activities, is an integral part of the whole educational and educational activity of the school. Out-of-school work is a continuation and development of the process carried out in the classroom and is subordinated to the general educational-educational task.

Out-of-school educational activities are aimed at the development of a harmonious personality and is based on the laws of creativity, which involve involving children in real co-creation, intellectual dialogue, harmonization of communication, success, the ability to feel free. Out-of-school activities promote the development of independent thinking, the development of methods of co-creation and intellectual stress.

One of the features of extracurricular work as a pedagogical process is that the child is not afraid to receive an unsatisfactory score. Relying on the uniqueness and uniqueness of each child, the teacher must develop the knowledge gained, transform them into social experience. Due to this, the functional approach to the child, fragmentation in education, intellectual overload are neutralized. The pedagogical process in extracurricular activities contributes to the development of a sense of personal exclusiveness for children in the search and creation of creative ideas. The activities of

the teacher in this process must be organically linked with the activities of children, their mood and the internal state.

The problem of organizing the educational process in extra-curricular time in a modern school is investigated in various aspects: the definition of conceptual foundations for the organization of extracurricular educational work (S. Goncharenko, V. Novoselsky, V. Orzhehovskaya, V. Postavy, L. Khlebnikova, K. Chorna, etc.); psychological aspects of the organization of extra-curricular work in a modern school (I. Bech, M. Borschevsky, A. Grechishkina, O. Krutenky, S. Maksimenko, L. Sokolov, etc.); the problem of content and areas of extra-curricular educational work (T. Demyanyuk, L. Kanishevskaya, A. Kapskaya, B. Kobzar, V. Rybalka, S. Sviridenko, P. Scherban, etc.); teaching and upbringing of students in the process of extracurricular activities (P. Blonsky, V. Kuz, A. Makarenko, S. Rusova, M. Stelmakhovich, V. Sukhomlynsky, K. Ushinsky, S. Shatsky, M. Fitsula, P. Podkassisty, M. Yevtuh, etc.).

The analysis of the pedagogical practice of the modern school has shown that extracurricular education remains a weak link in the activity of the school, it has not acquired a systematic purposeful nature, since the episodicity of educational activities involving individual children, the expansion of the network of subject circles, in which children continue to study, reduce the number of circles by interest lead to the fact that the school life for children ends at the same time as the bell from the last lesson, and then the street takes them. This phenomenon is especially dangerous for the younger generation.

The purpose of the article is to analyze the essence and efficiency of extracurricular educational work in institutions of primary education.

Presenting main material. Out-of-school educational work as an important component of the educational process has undergone a complex and long-term path of formation in educational institutions of Ukraine, respectively, to understand this progress and characteristic tendencies can only from the standpoint of present day, given the current state of its functioning.

Some elements of extracurricular educational work are traced in the works of the teachers of the XIX century, namely - in justifying them the idea of the need for its organization. K. Ushinsky opposed the deprivation of the school's educational functions and tasks and emphasized the expediency of the logical continuation of the student's work in the classroom in the system of influence of reason on the mind, morality on morality, character in character (Sukhomlynskaya, Antonets, Berezovska, 2005, p. 289). The teacher advised to divide the pupils into small circles, in which they must carry out a genuine, actual education (*Nedilko, 1989, p. 189*).

In this context, we are considering the views of M. Pirogov, who noted that "this progress is achieved only by one way - through education." He first drew attention to the importance of developing human dignity in schoolchildren, having established humanity and humanity in education. His most important form in extracurricular work was gymnasium talks, literary evenings, conversations, etc. (*Sukhomlynskaya, Antonets, Berezovsky, 2005, p. 311*).

V. Sukhomlynskyi, who was deeply convinced of the possibilities of extracurricular hours for the comprehensive development of schoolchildren, makes a special contribution to extra-curricular educational work. The essence of extracurricular work was seen by the great teacher in a pedagogically thought-out organization of free time, rational use of leisure students. Necessary conditions recognized the clear

organization of the whole system of extracurricular educational activities, pedagogical support for the system and structure of extracurricular activities, the diversity of forms and methods; the study of the interests of children, the practical orientation of classes, the interest of teachers in this work (*Sukhomlinsky, 1976, pp. 645-647*).

Modern researchers (T. Ilyina, M. Fitsula, S. Smirnov, I. Kotov, E. Shiyarov, and others) define extra-curricular work in school as one of the forms of leisure activities for students, which is organized and conducted in extracurricular time by the children's self-governing bodies for active help and tactical guidance from the pedagogical team, especially class leaders, educators, organizers of extracurricular work.

According to T. Ilyin, the term "extracurricular work" is often determined by the educational work carried out by a class teacher and teacher with students of his school in extra-curricular time (Ilyina, 1984). The definition of M. Fitsula is similar. According to him, extra-curricular work is a diverse educational and educational work aimed at satisfying the interests and requests of children, which is organized by the school's pedagogical team with students during the extra-curricular time (*Fitsula, 1997*). Y. Konarzhevsky notes that extracurricular educational work is an activity that takes place in a school outside the classroom, but under the direct pedagogical care of a class teacher or other teachers, which consists of such forms that go beyond the classroom and, within the limits of others, Unions of students, including in circles involving pupils of different classes, and educational associations (*Basilchuk, 2009*).

Scientists S. Smirnov, I. Kotov, E. Shiyarov define extracurricular educational work as an organization as a teacher of various types of activity of pupils in extra-time time, which provide the necessary conditions for the socialization of the child's personality (*Basilchuk, 2009*).

We share the opinion of specialists who, under extra-curricular educational work at school, understand the purposeful educational work with schoolchildren, which is organized and carried out by teachers, educators, children's self-government bodies at school after lessons, and which is aimed at achieving a single goal: the harmonious development of children and youth, satisfaction of their interests and requests, identification of talented and gifted pupils, creation of conditions for self-education and self-realization of each student (*Biletska, 2017, p. 9*).

In the context of the problem under investigation, it should be noted that modern Ukrainian legislation defines a class leader as the main organizer of the student collective, which creates conditions for organizing meaningful leisure activities, including organizing and visiting museums, theaters, exhibitions, excursions, events on nature conservation; is responsible for the prevention of neglect, offenses, plans and conducts appropriate educational activities. Organizes educational work taking into account the age and individual psychological characteristics of pupils (pupils), their inclinations, interests, desires, readiness for certain types of activities, as well as the level of formation of the student group, holds thematic class lessons aimed at raising moral values, interest in the question of belonging to the chosen profession (*Beletskaya, 2017, pp. 9-10*).

Education and education is the only pedagogical process that ensures the formation and versatile development of the student's personality. Experience shows that pedagogical tasks are successfully solved only with the organic combination of educational - educational work during a classroom with a targeted action on the pupil in

extra-curricular time, so extracurricular work is fairly considered as an important part of the school's work.

As you know, extra-curricular educational work is called such activity of the teacher which is directed at the education of the child's personality. The teacher's direction can be either direct or with the help of invitees for this purpose from other institutions, students, senior students. An essential educational element of extracurricular activities - the implementation of socially useful tasks, during which the students develop a sense of responsibility, careful attitude to material values, respect for labor.

It is worth emphasizing another very important aspect of extracurricular work. Wonderful teacher V. Sukhomlynsky wrote: "The logic of the educational process conceals the danger of isolation and isolation, because at school every step emphasizes: to achieve success by your own efforts, do not rely on others because the results of mental work are evaluated individually. To ensure that school life is inspired by the spirit of collectivism, it should not be exhausted by lessons." Out-of-school work brings students together in friendly collectives, connected with common interests and hobbies. It helps to overcome such negative personality traits as closeness, selfishness, undisciplined. Work in collectives, sections - educates students in a spirit of sociability, purposefulness, deep and active interest in science.

According to I. Bekh, when organizing the activities of junior pupils it is necessary to take into account the specifics of this age: mobility, specificity of thinking, greater vulnerability, ability to immitate, the impossibility of long focusing on something for one. Younger students are attracted to cases in which children enter into relationships of cooperation, mutual help, friendship. If collective activity is in the interests of schoolchildren, captures them with their goals, children need to help each other, take care of improving the surrounding life.

As a result of the analysis of modern psychological and pedagogical literature on the organization of extracurricular educational work, one can conclude that the following types of activities are the most optimal for extracurricular educational work with junior pupils: cognitive activity; employment; game activity; artistic and aesthetic activity; sports activities.

The cognitive activity of primary school students in extracurricular activities was the subject of study of many theorists and practitioners (M. Anzhiyevsky, T. Biletska, G. Gavrilichev, I. Demakova, L. Zelenina, I. Kiyancuk, T. Peshkova, I. Podlasy, T. Rabchenyuk, V. Yurchik, etc.).

Cognitive activity of junior pupils should not only satisfy their cognitive interests, but also be designed in such a way that children from simple tasks pass to solving more complex. In elementary classes, cognitive activity in connection with the peculiarities of children's thinking must be under constant pedagogical control and conducted in a certain sequence. Perpetual cognitive activity in comparison with the educational process has more various forms. Children participate in contests, quizzes, listen to conversations, stories about the newest in the world of science and technology, nature, participate in games of a cognitive nature.

According to scientists and practitioners (M. Galaguzov, Y. Grintsay, A. Zhuravlev, L. Kayukov, I. Krasovitsky, A. Solodkov, etc.), the work activity is organized according to the level of preparedness of junior pupils to one or another type work Children organize study guides, make diverse collections, collect natural material

for lessons, remove premises, take care of flowers, and more. In 2-3 grades, the focus is on the social orientation of students' work activities, which contributes to the formation of collective work skills, the education of interest in work. The results of work give children positive emotions, feelings of pleasure, which prompts them to new labor activities. A characteristic feature of the work of junior pupils is that it is accompanied by an acquaintance with the work of adults.

Priority is the value of gaming activity in the lives of junior pupils. Classics of pedagogy and modern educators and psychologists continue to explore the problem of organizing gaming activities. This problem is important in the researches of theorists and innovators, teacher-organizers (L. Aydarova, O. Byk, O. Gazman, T. Dudova, K. Dyakonova, G. Ivochkivna, D. Koishch, E. Kuteyev, C. Lybid, L. Onysyuk, S. Pirog, E. Pristup, M. Solodka, etc.).

Game activity of junior pupils acts as a special form of collective activity and as an element, an important component of all other activities. In the games of children, the world of adults is reflected, because the game younger students know the surrounding reality. The game activity of junior schoolchildren is multifaceted. There are various classification games, among them the most common are games mobile, sports, didactic, developmental, etc. (*Kazanshi, 2014, pp. 62-64*).

Extracurricular activities to a greater extent than a lesson and elective, adapted for the upbringing of certain classes of personality in junior pupils. Part-time classes are non-lesson forms of organization, methods and content. For such work, the teacher must be armed with relevant knowledge. Out-of-school educational work needs to be planned: perspective for the school year and more for half and a quarter. The need for this is determined not only by the association of extracurricular activities with curricula, but also in order to avoid overloading students with extra-curricular activities. Plans for extracurricular work, both in individual subjects and in schools as a whole, are discussed with students' assets, approved by the school principal and then transferred to the entire school in special charts, posters, announcements. Moreover, informing students about certain measures of a mass character is necessary in advance (*Volkova, 2003, pp. 176*).

It should be emphasized that there can be no successful extracurricular educational work without beginning it at the lessons. The principle of the unity of labor and extra-curricular work - the most important principle of the organization of the educational process. It is at the lessons that the teacher sets questions to the students, which should stimulate their curiosity, give the first impulses to reading additional literature on the subject, cause the desire to do with their own hands what is said in the textbook and in the books read. The path to organizing mass and group extra-curricular work lies in the compilation and reading of small additional messages by students at lessons, conducting initially episodic, and then more systematic mass events. Engaging in intensive extra-curricular work is thus from a lesson to mass work. Then, from the total number of students involved in mass work, an active participant is formed - the participants of the circles work and individual students, especially assist the teacher in organizing mass educational work. So the atmosphere of enthusiasm of the subject is gradually created in school, the involvement of everyone in the affairs of the whole team and a coherent system of extra-curricular work arises, in which each element does not exist separately, not in parallel with the other, but in close relationship with them and with the work work.

All extra-curricular work in school is based on the principle of voluntariness. Therefore, especially at first, it is important to find incentives that could be of interest to the students before they get deeper into the subject in the order of passing the school curriculum. Such stimulus may be elements of curiosity, external effectiveness of various demonstrations, elements of the game and theatricalization. Of course, boredom is not a place and a lesson, but extracurricular activities provide exceptionally great opportunities for exciting students' interest, to enter elements of curiosity in extra-curricular classes. They, however, should not be an end in themselves, but should obey the general task of learning.

Extracurricular educational work not only targets the education, but also mastering the subject, and solves the tasks of the curriculum. In the education of volitional qualities, discipline, and healthy situation in the team, it is important to have a proper understanding of the principle of voluntary participation of schoolchildren in extracurricular work whose goal is education. This question does not become a regular type of course, but for extra-curricular work, it seems very significant, which was noticed by many organizers of extra-curricular educational work. This principle means that students of their choices and desires take on one or another work, but do it necessarily. It is this understanding of voluntarism that helps educate a sense of responsibility, a conscious attitude towards oneself, voluntarily assumed responsibilities. Assists in the implementation of this principle of involving a team of younger students in the organizational autonomy and amateur activities. It is useful to get the students to evaluate their work.

The most important place in the system of extracurricular educational work is the implementation of tasks that have a socially useful orientation. One should strive to ensure that all types of activities of individual work of junior pupils during performance, one way or another, could be used in the work of the team in the goal: not just to read a popular book on an issue that is interesting, but also to tell about read comrades in the classroom, interest them in these or other issues. Not just performing an experiment, but also showing it at a lesson, explaining the nature of the observed phenomena, and making sure that the experiment is convenient for demonstration in the audience. The possibilities of the student team, as the practice of many teachers shows, is extremely high, and the students' work can seriously help in expanding the theoretical basis. Without neglecting this, the aspect of the work of students should also take into account the enormous educational effect of work, because nothing contributes to the education of self-esteem, the development of labor skills, careful attitude to material values, as an active, creative work with a specific socially useful purpose.

Conclusions.

So, under extra-curricular work at school, we understand the purposeful educational work with schoolchildren, organized and implemented by teachers, educators, children's self-government bodies at school after classes. It is aimed at achieving a single didactic-educational goal - harmonious development of students, satisfaction of their interests and requests, identification of talented and gifted pupils, as well as creating conditions for self-education, self-education and self-realization of each student.

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STAN NAUKOWEJ PROBLEMY ROZWOJU PRZECIWDZIAŁANIA UDZIAŁU NIELETNICH W DZIAŁALNOŚĆ PRZESTĘPCZĄ I JEJ METODOLOGIA BADANIA

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Streszczenie. W tym artykule dotyczy stanu badań naukowych w takim kierunku działalności instytucji państwowych i publicznych, jak przeciwdziałanie zaangażowaniu nieletnich w działalność przestępczą. Nacisk kładzie się na fakt, że nowej wiedzy nie można uzyskać bez korzystania z wcześniejszych osiągnięć i wiedzy uzyskanej w wyniku ich postępowania. Ustalono, że takie podejście pozwoli na kompleksowe spojrzenie na możliwości zwiększenia skuteczności przeciwdziałania i dochodzenia przestępstw przewidzianych w art. 304 kodeksu karnego Ukrainy i innych powiązanych przestępstw. Za pomocą metod empirycznych, ogólnych, żydowskich i specjalnych stwierdzono, że większość badań naukowych na ten temat poświęcona jest prawu karnemu i kryminologicznym problemom przeciwdziałania zaangażowaniu nieletnich w działalność przestępczą, a ostatnie zmiany w zakresie poszukiwań operacyjnych i kryminalistycznych przeciwdziałania tej przestępczości prawie nie istniały. Stosując podejścia terminologiczne i historyczne, ustalono, że rozwój międzynarodowych instytucji prawnych w celu ochrony praw dziecka, nowe koncepcje działalności organów ścigania i organów sądowych w celu wdrożenia podstawowych dokumentów mających na celu ochronę dzieci w obcych krajach stały się podstawą aktywnego rozwoju instytutu karnego dla nieletnich na Ukrainie. Zwrócono uwagę na kluczowe metody i podejścia do badań naukowych w tej dziedzinie.

Słowa kluczowe: badania naukowe, stan badań, jednostki operacyjne, nieletni, przeciwdziałanie nieletnim udziałom w działalności przestępczej, metodologia.

THE STATE OF SCIENTIFIC ELABORATION OF PROBLEMS OF COUNTERACTION TO INVOLVEMENT OF MINORS IN CRIMINAL ACTIVITY AND THE METHODOLOGY OF ITS STUDY

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Abstract. In the article the questions of the state of research in this area of activity state and public institutions, opposing the involvement of minors in criminal activity. The attention is focused on what new knowledge is impossible to obtain without using previous designs and knowledge that was obtained as a result of their conduct. Determined that this approach will allow to develop a comprehensive idea of the possibilities of increasing the efficiency of prevention and investigation of crimes under article 304 of the criminal code of Ukraine and other related crimes. Using empirical, zagalnego, heuristica and special methods found that the majority of research on this topic is devoted to criminal law and criminology combating the involvement of minors in criminal activity, and the latest developments in investigative and forensic combat this crime almost not carried out. With the help of a terminological and historical

approaches revealed that the development of international legal institutions to protect the rights of the child, a new concept of law enforcement agencies and judicial authorities on the implementation of fundamental documents aimed at protection of children in foreign countries have become the basis for active development of the institution of criminal juvenile justice in Ukraine. Attention is drawn to the key methods and approaches of scientific research in this direction.

Keywords: research, state research, operational units, juvenile, opposition to the involvement of minors in criminal activity, methodology.

СТАН НАУКОВОЇ РОЗРОБЛЕНОСТІ ПРОБЛЕМИ ПРОТИДІЇ ВТЯГНЕННЮ НЕПОВНОЛІТНІХ У ЗЛОЧИННУ ДІЯЛЬНІСТЬ ТА МЕТОДОЛОГІЯ ЇЇ ДОСЛІДЖЕННЯ

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Анотація. У статті розглянуто питання стану наукових досліджень у такому напрямі діяльності державних та громадських інституцій як протидія втягненню неповнолітніх у злочинну діяльність. Акцентовано увагу на тому, що нове знання неможливо отримати не послуговуючись попередніми розробками і знаннями, що були отримані внаслідок їх проведення. Визначено, що такий підхід дасть змогу сформуванню комплексне уявлення про можливості підвищення ефективності протидії та розслідування злочинів, передбачених ст. 304 КК України й інших супутніх злочинів. Із застосуванням емпіричних, загальнологічних, евристичних та спеціальних методів констатовано, що більшість наукових досліджень на цю тему присвячено кримінально-правовим та кримінологічним проблемам протидії втягненню неповнолітніх у злочинну діяльність, а новітніх розробок щодо оперативно-розшукової та криміналістичної протидії даному злочину майже не проводилося. За допомогою термінологічного та історичного підходів встановлено, що розвиток міжнародних правових інституцій щодо захисту прав дитини, нові концепції діяльності правоохоронних та судових органів з реалізації основоположних документів спрямованих на захист дитинства в іноземних державах стали основою для активного становлення інституту кримінальної ювенальної юстиції в Україні. Звернено увагу на ключові методи та підходи наукового дослідження в даному напрямі.

Ключові слова: наукові дослідження, стан дослідження, оперативні підрозділи, неповнолітні, протидія втягненню неповнолітніх у злочинну діяльність, методологія.

Scientific research - is the study of a particular object, phenomenon or object in order to reveal the laws of its origin and development, which is the basis of the formation of new scientific knowledge. Scientific research is carried out in order to obtain a scientific result. The scientific result is new knowledge gained in the course of fundamental or applied scientific research and recorded on the carriers of scientific information in the form of scientific report, scientific work, scientific report, scientific report on research work, monographic research, scientific discovery, etc. (Zatserkovny VI., 2017, p. 30). So, the scientific result, new knowledge can not be obtained without using previous developments and knowledge gained as a result of their conduct.

The specificity of counteracting the involvement of minors in criminal activity as one of the priority areas for the formation of law-conscious citizens and the protection of children from criminal influence can not be limited to narrow or exclusive knowledge in the field of criminal justice. The scope and diversity of the knowledge of the objective and

subjective processes taking place in society and the unlawful relations which children are involved in and which are associated with these processes determine the professionalism of the operational officer of the criminal police in counteracting the criminal influence on them. Indeed, in this area of law enforcement, the operational units of the criminal police are among the main actors. According to some scholars, the results of the implementation of the doctrinal theoretical provisions on ensuring human rights (Onishchenko N., 2013, pp. 176-193) depend on the legal and actual content of their activities.

Therefore, according to the researchers, one of the important ways to improve the operative-search theory is its integration with related scientific knowledge, which will facilitate the effective solution of the practical tasks of operational-search activity (Kushpit VP, 2016, p. 467).

A meaningful analysis of the state of scientific research on the problems of counteracting the involvement of minors in criminal activity, as well as the investigation of crimes related to juvenile delinquency, the definition of the possibilities of using certain provisions of operational search and forensic methods and recommendations that were developed earlier in the modern operational and investigative practice, as well as finding out the state of modern scientific research in this area. This will enable to form a comprehensive view of the possibilities of increasing the effectiveness of counteraction and investigation of crimes provided for in Art. 304 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine and other related crimes through the use of available techniques and recommendations, as well as identify problems that need to be addressed in the light of the current state and needs of law enforcement practice.

As A. Kolodiy rightly observes, an important methodological component of the scientific search for effective ways of forming a civil society in Ukraine, the development of a social and legal state is the study of law-enforcement, law-enforcement and right-realization activities of various actors (Kolodiy A., 2013, p. 271). It is in this context that we are interested in the activities of the units of the criminal police, in the first place the criminal investigation as one of the operational measures to counteract the involvement of minors in criminal activity from the point of view of doctrinal theoretical positions and modern legal and practical, practical realities.

The crime that we are investigating is stipulated in Art. 304 and is placed in the section XII of the Criminal Code of Ukraine entitled "Crimes against public order and morality". Obviously, the legislator deliberately, analyzing the rules of the laws on criminal liability of European countries, referred to the article "Involvement of minors in criminal activity" to the section, which is intended to protect one of the most important social values, to secure the foundations of formation in a genuinely civil, legal and high moral society.

Most of the research on this topic is devoted to criminal-legal and criminological problems of counteracting the involvement of minors in criminal activity, developed theoretical positions, in which it is not just described individual elements of the legal structure of the crime of the foreseen article. 304 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine and the special norms of this part of the crime stipulated by other articles, but also describes the features of each of the components of such crimes, proved the necessity of transformation of the national legislation to ensure proper criminal-legal protection of childhood as a socially significant category, the creation of new institutions, etc.

One of the most striking developments in this area among Ukrainian scientists was initiated in the dissertation study "Criminological problems in preventing criminal

attacks on the moral and physical development of minors" (2002) V.V. Vitvitskaya, who was concerned with the formation of a minor, considered them through the prism of criminal influence on children. The purpose of the dissertation work was to identify the problems of criminological prevention of crimes that encroach on the moral and physical development of minors, the formulation of proposals and recommendations for improving the directions and ways to increase the effectiveness of preventive activities of the state and criminal law protection of the rights and interests of minors, the development of criminological characteristics of crimes against minors and persons who committed them. As a result of the study, a solution to the discussion issues in the field of the theory and practice of prevention of this group of crimes, proposals were made for improving the effectiveness of criminal-law norms and preventive action of the subjects of prophylaxis (Vytvitskaya V.V., 2002, pp. 5-6).

Somewhat wider, concerning the process of counteraction to the investigated crime, came in his scientific research "Criminal-legal and criminological aspects of combating the involvement of minors in criminal or other anti-social activities" (2004) I.O. Topolskova Part of the purpose of the study was to develop scientifically substantiated recommendations for improving the effectiveness of the system of criminal-legal and criminological measures to counteract the involvement of minors in criminal or other anti-social activities. The expediency of the division of the criminal-law norm of art. 304 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine on two: art. 304 of the Criminal Code «Involvement of a minor in committing a crime» and Article 304-1 of the Criminal Code «Involvement of a minor in committing antisocial activities», differentiating the responsibility for involving a minor in committing a crime and involving a minor in committing antisocial activities. In the opinion of the dissertation, an important role is played by factors such as the historical process of forming the territorial community of people, the cultural gene pool of the population of a separate region (Tolpolskova IO, 2004, 2-11). In general, we support the author's opinion on the division of norms in Art. 304 taking into account the different levels of social danger. However, the legislator has not approached the qualitative reconstruction of this article for 15 years, and in 2008, within the framework of the reforms of juvenile justice, only heightened the sanctions of the norms defined in art. 304 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine and added special subjects (family members).

The advantage of criminal law aspects of counteracting the involvement of minors in criminal activity in his study was given by V.V. Dzunza In the comparative aspect, the scientist considered the objective and subjective features of the crimes set forth in the general and special norms of the Criminal Code of Ukraine and the countries of the near abroad regarding the responsibility for the involvement of minors, and the shortcomings of these norms were identified. For the first time, taking into account objective and subjective features of special norms on responsibility for the involvement of minors in anti-social actions, their imperfections and contradictions are established, especially those which are foreseen at the level of qualifying sign of certain crimes, and it is concluded that they need to be excluded from the Criminal Code. the Code of Ukraine and the concentration of signs of all these acts in the general norm - art. 304 of the Criminal Code, which will allow to obtain the law of accuracy, logical completeness and instability, as well as to provide uniform for all types of involvement of juvenile qualifying attributes of the crime and optimal sanctions (Dzundza VV, 2005, p. 4).

The development of international legal institutions for the protection of the rights of the child, new concepts of the activities of law enforcement and judicial bodies on the implementation of the basic documents aimed at protecting childhood in foreign countries have forced Ukraine to take on the wave of active reforms of juvenile justice. Thus, on April 8, 2008, by the decree of the president of Ukraine, the Concept of reforming of criminal justice in Ukraine was approved (Decree of the President of Ukraine, 2008), where the partly mentioned was also about juvenile justice. At the same time, the significant theoretical positions and foundations of juvenile justice, and the activation of the state's actions in protecting children's rights are highlighted in their scientific research "Juvenile Law of Ukraine: Genesis and Contemporary Status" (2008) N. M. Krestovsky The urgency of the topic of the dissertation is determined by the need for a theoretical understanding: childhood as a special legal phenomenon; value-normative regulation of the juvenile sphere of civil society, legal status of the child in Ukraine; participation of children in the legal life of a modern society; improvement of the legal regulation of child protection and child-friendly relations; the constitution of a new scientific discipline related to the study of norms, institutions and actions of juvenile law. Conceptual is the presentation of the theoretical model of a special type of offense - juvenile misconduct - an unlawful act, punishable only in the case of the child's commission, and also the theoretical model of a new type of legal responsibility - juvenile liability (Krestovsky N.M., 2008, pp. 5-10).

In paragraph 4.8. "Protection of the rights of children who have committed a crime" of the National Program "National Action Plan for the Implementation of the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child" for the period up to 2016, approved by the Law of Ukraine of March 5, 2009, established the need for an adequate juvenile justice system in the framework of judicial reform systems for the improvement of national legislation in the field of children's rights protection, improvement of preventive and preventive work aimed at preventing children from committing crimes and other offenses, An effective system for the rehabilitation of juvenile offenders (Law of Ukraine on the national program "National Action Plan for the Implementation of the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child for the period up to 2016" ", 2009). This gave impetus to new research on ensuring protection of children from unlawful influence, their involvement in criminal or anti-social activities.

During 2010-2015, there has been a partial decline in scientific activity regarding the development of substantive provisions and methods of counteracting and investigating such crimes as involving juveniles in criminal activities. This situation is partly due to factors such as the socio-political exacerbation in the state caused by the authorities' reluctance to establish European legal values, the restructuring of state institutions, the provision of a free European legal nature, reforms and transformations of the police as the main subject of law and order in the state, cyclic reforms and liquidations of separate structures and their subdivisions, armed aggression on the part of the Russian Federation. All this gave rise to some short-term uncertainty, lively discussions and conflicts both in the scientific environment and among the subjects of law enforcement.

As a result of the Ministry of Internal Affairs's reform, the units of the criminal police for children's affairs were eliminated, which partly led to gaps in the police's activities to counteract the involvement of minors in criminal activity by operational means. Despite the emergence in the eastern regions of our state of illegal armed

formations, terrorist and separatist groups that actively pursued and continue to carry out propaganda work and involve the children of Ukraine in areas beyond its control to commit crimes against humanity, conduct of hostilities, engage in terrorism, prostitution and committing hundreds of other crimes of a general criminal nature, the state authorities did not create a new subdivision, either within the Ministry of Internal Affairs or in the SBU, which would oppose this direction. After all, the proper state of the organization and provision of juvenile criminal justice is characterized primarily by the opportunities and measures that were used to prevent the child from becoming a criminal, preventing her conflict with the law. The newly created juvenile police units in the police can not provide even the level that was sometimes achieved by the CMSA units through operational capabilities. However, in recent scientific studies, this issue is not really covered.

And more recently, the refinement, additions, transformations and bringing to the modern realities of existing scientific achievements concerning this problem are going on. Scientific research, which has raised a number of problematic issues of operational detection and due process of investigation of crimes against public morals covered by the above-mentioned Section XII of the Criminal Code of Ukraine "Crimes against public order and morality", which also includes Art. 304, a dissertation V.Yu. Mosyazhenko "Operative-search and forensic detection and investigation of crimes in the field of public morality" (2015). The author solved the scientific task, the content of which consisted in the development of modern methodological, organizational and tactical foundations of operational search and forensic provision of detection and pre-trial investigation of crimes in the field of public morality. However, from the point of view of the mentioned National Program for the year 2016, the study did not adequately study the problem of moral health of children, and in particular the crime stipulated by Art. 304 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine. However, in substantiating the relevance of the work, the author notes that the previous destruction of ideological dogmas and moral values has been reflected in the spread of crimes related to: the circulation of information that propagates the cult of violence and cruelty, racial, national or religious intolerance and discrimination, as well as pornography ; the formation or retention of places of deportation and bribery, pimping, or the involvement of persons in prostitution. Such a state of affairs has the greatest impact on youth, children and family values, affects the image of our state, as Ukraine occupies a leading position in negative ratings on prostitution, the spread of pornography, including childhood, cruelty and violence, etc. (Mosyazhenko V.Yu., 2015, pp. 5-16).

Deepened criminal law protection of childhood, normal physical, mental and moral-spiritual development of children, investigated I.O. Bandurka in the work "Criminal-legal protection of childhood in Ukraine" (2016). The purpose of the dissertation research was the new solution of the theoretical and applied problem of criminal-legal protection of childhood in Ukraine, as well as the development of new mechanisms for improving the current legislation and practice of its application in this area. As for the direct punishment of minors who committed a crime, it is important to understand that imprisonment or its restriction is connected with the isolation of the convicted person from the ordinary environment and results in a weakening and, sometimes, loss of socially useful links, a significant restriction performed social roles. As a result, the personality of the convicted person is subject to change, and is far from always the best. The concept of criminal legal protection of childhood in Ukraine is

proposed, which is based on the comprehensive criminal-law and criminological description of crimes against children and child crime, the system of counteraction to them taking into account the international experience of such activity (*Bandurka I.O., 2016, pp. 2-26*).

One of the latest researches on the issue of counteracting the involvement of minors in criminal activity was "Criminological characteristic and prevention of juvenile involvement in criminal activity" (2018), which O.M. Sitnik The purpose of the study is to form a comprehensive criminological characteristic of juvenile involvement in criminal activity (Article 304 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine) and to develop scientifically grounded recommendations on prevention of these crimes on this basis. Knowledge about the system of non-jurisdiction and jurisdictional measures of special-criminological prevention of juvenile involvement in criminal and other anti-social activities, based on which is dominant non-repressive influence on the basic determinants of crimes stipulated in art. 304 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine, in conjunction with law-making in the field of counteraction to crime, effective enforcement activities of the National Police, prosecutors, probation bodies, penal institutions in co-operation with the court, other actors for the prevention of crimes. Among the main organizational and managerial factors involved in juvenile delinquency in criminal and other anti-social activities is the negative role of depriving juvenile preventive units of the powers to carry out operational-search activities, preserving the practice of covering offenses against registration, undeveloped mechanisms of juvenile justice, etc. (*Sitnik O. M., 2018, pp. 2-10*).

The concept of juvenile involvement in criminal activity as a crime, its criminological aspects and criminal-legal characteristics are an important foundation for the scientific knowledge necessary for use within our research, but besides, we are interested in operational-search and forensic methods, characteristics and other provisions in this in the direction of ensuring the proper counteraction to operative and investigative capabilities, and not only preventive measures. As we see, these criminal offenses are generally accepted by scholars as anti-moral and anti-social. They exist as caused by objective reality, but legislation does not accumulate them in one section of the Criminal Code of Ukraine, thus envisaging their special composition, which also gives rise to the curiosity of the study as representatives of the science of criminal law, criminology, and researchers of various aspects of counteracting crimes in this the field of operational search and forensic means.

A comprehensive analysis of the above studies, as well as the work of other scholars in this area, will provide an opportunity to formulate a proper understanding of the concept of involvement of a minor in criminal activity, to investigate the problem of counteracting this crime by operational and investigative capabilities and, taking into account the practical needs, to formulate relevant provisions.

The theoretical positions should take into account the transformational processes of crime, innovations in the mechanisms of committing the crime under investigation, using modern technologies, the current state of regulatory regulation and determining the necessary positions for its improvement, in order to achieve the objectives of operational and investigative activities and criminal justice in general. It is necessary to determine the priorities of scientific research regarding the qualitative change in the activity of separately operating unit of the criminal police and the activity legal unison with other units and bodies and the construction of relevant concepts.

Thus, the researchers note that within the philosophy and theory of law, science of the criminal process and the ODI, the content and interrelation of the activities of investigative and operational units of law enforcement agencies are investigated. At the same time, when investigating the activity (separate aspects of the activity) of specific law enforcement bodies (their units or officials), scholars for the most part do not resort to an analysis of its content from the standpoint of philosophy, doctrinal provisions of the theory of law, the ORD and the criminal process (*Sukhorada I.O., 2014, p. 97*).

At the same time, the philosophical level of methodology is the most general methods and principles of scientific knowledge, which is an instrument of finding the truth not only for the very scientific knowledge, but also performing a regulatory function in relation to the philosophy itself and its teachings. The servicing task of this level in both cases is to establish the most probable directions of the formation and evolution of scientific research, as well as possible destruction of systems that are formal or have no prototypes.

Therefore, some scholars point out that philosophy can not interfere with the concrete process of the scientist's activity at the empirical and theoretical levels of scientific knowledge, but it largely influences the choice and interpretation of the basic principles of the archetypal level, which depend on the prevailing in this historical epoch of philosophical attitudes. And the archetypal level of scientific knowledge, as the author points out, is the part of concrete scientific knowledge, where the most constructive union of philosophy with specific sciences is possible (*Danylyan O.G., Dzoban O.P., 2017, p. 257*).

Some researchers point out that the process of knowledge as the basis of any scientific research is complex and requires a conceptual approach based on a certain methodology, the application of certain methods. It is the desire to develop methods capable of qualitatively verifying theoretical hypotheses, as well as determining the criteria for assessing the objectivity of the new knowledge received and has caused a meticulous attitude to the methodology and methods of scientific research (*Zatserkovny V.I., 2017, p. 63*).

The theory of operative-search activity is a kind of process of cognition of objective reality, the dialectical reflection of objects and phenomena of the material world in the minds of people, and other laws, which consist in the field of counteracting crimes. By the cognitive essence, it practically does not differ from other sciences, since it is based on the application of a set of methods of scientific research (situational approach, system-structural analysis, conflict interaction, etc.). Unconditional is the recognition of the supremacy of the general dialectical method (*Kushpit V.P., 2016, p. 468*).

The content of the subject of our scientific research, the logical methods of finding and studying the laws of the existence of the process, which we aim to study, encourage the distribution of scientific knowledge in the form of theories, concepts, paradigms and tactics on independent lines. These directions according to philosophical doctrine should be correlated as "general", "special", "single". Extrapolating this provision to our study as part of the general, it is necessary to analyze the categories that serve as the basis for the formation of substantiated provisions, which is: the theory of counteraction to crime, its concepts and components; the concept, content and legal basis of the operational units of the criminal police; the mechanisms of such an offense as the involvement of minors in criminal activity. That is, the study of these categories is

conditioned by the need for their analysis and synthesis of results to clarify the essence of the mechanisms of activity in this direction.

All of this is a prerequisite for a special study by our intelligence organization to counteract the involvement of minors in criminal activity at its various stages, including interaction with other actors and proper information provision of this activity.

And in the end, the study of the unit as a specific and inherent only to this object - is a tactic of detection, documentation of the involvement of minors in various forms of criminal activity, as well as the implementation of collected development materials.

Consequently, during our scientific research, it is necessary to distinguish the object of research from among others, and in the future to draw attention to the similarity with such objects, which is also part of the mechanism of counteracting crime and ensuring the proper legal order in the state.

However, as noted by the researchers, without a scientific understanding of the content of the operational units it is impossible to determine their role in ensuring constitutional guarantees, the place in the mechanism of the state (in particular, in the context of the conceptual framework for improving the system of law enforcement agencies), to resolve legal, organizational, tactical and other Problems (*Sukhorada I.O., 2014, p. 97*).

To this end, it is necessary to apply a comprehensive research methodology, since, along with commonly used scientific methods, the essence of the phenomena and processes occurring in law-enforcement activity, and especially in the secreted operational part thereof, is to be revealed.

The methodological approach is a form of attracting research resources to the law as a philosophical and meta-scientific plan, as well as other sciences (*Kellman MS, 2011, p. 245*).

That is why methodology is sometimes also understood as a certain system of methods used in the process of cognition within a particular science (*Danylyan O.G., Dzoban O.P., 2017, p. 231*). This opinion is adhered to and MS Kellman, noting that the method of legal science is one and the same applies to both the general theory of law, as well as branch sciences and applied legal disciplines. Other cases that in researches carried out within the framework of the general theory of law or branch disciplines, due to different research tasks and goals may be dominated by either philosophical or general scientific, or some "law" methods. At the same time, the core of the method of any legal science is its own methods of jurisprudence, legal means of knowledge of law (*Kellman MS, 2011, p. 245*).

V.P. Kuspit correctly asserts that in the methodology of operative-search activity general science and special methods of related sciences are modified, acquiring specific features characteristic of the subject of operational-search activity (*Kushpit V.P., 2016, p. 471*).

R. Descartes in his work "Reflections on the method" identified so-called "rules for the direction of reason and the search for truth in the sciences." Actually, these are elementary norms of the activity of the mind, which are known from the ancient times in the form of rules (formal) logic. The main merit of Descartes is precisely that he formulated them as rules of cognitive activity and this laid the foundation for the development of scientific methodology. There are three rules for Descartes:

1) the dismemberment of the heavy, not solvable in the general case of problems, into separate tasks that can be solved;

2) the transition from the less complex to the more complex, from the proven to the unproven, and not vice versa (in the logic it is a prohibition to determine through the unknown);

3) preventing the loss of logical chains in reasoning (Zatserkovny V.I., 2017, p. 53).

However, such a dismemberment at this stage of the evolution of scientific research is considered as a characteristic of the universal maternal method, which is part of the general scientific methods.

At the same time there is a need for objective analysis as a principle of scientific research. It gives rise to the need to use methods that help to allocate maximum of objective knowledge, following "sound logic", and as a result to make a reliable justification provided by evidence. In this way, the truthfulness of the investigated facts, which holds ethics in science, is achieved. Leveling the objectivity of the research leads to distortion of its results, unreliability of conclusions and questions the process of scientific research.

One of the popularized fundamental methods of cognition, which did not go away and our study, is a synergistic approach. The essence of the synergistic (synergistic) approach is to study the processes of self-organization and the formation of new orderly structures. It is implemented in the study of systems of various nature: physical, biological, social, cognitive, informational, ecological, and others. The subject of synergetics is the mechanisms of spontaneous formation and preservation of complex systems, in particular those which are in a state of stable equilibrium with the external environment. In the field of its study come the nonlinear effects of the evolution of systems of any type, crises and bifurcations - unstable phase of existence, which predict the plurality of scenarios of further development. The synergetic approach demonstrates how and why chaos can be considered as a factor in creation, the constructive mechanism of evolution, as a new organization can develop with the chaos itself (Zatserkovny VI, 2017, pp. 59-60).

Man has a tendency to the truth. In this context, the relevance of the problem is to find a scientific method that would allow reliable and reliable results of research. Possessing such a method, one could make objective and substantiated conclusions that would deserve attention (Zatserkovny VI, 2017, p. 63).

As a **conclusion**, I would like to note that in the general concept of the problem of counteracting the involvement of minors in criminal activities (taking into account the special rules establishing the responsibility for the crime), the criminal-law, criminological means have been sufficiently developed, which is not to say about the operational-search and forensic sphere. Nevertheless, changes in the legal regulation of the criminal process in general and operational activities, in particular, the reformation of certain law-enforcement agencies and their units, the emergence of a new trend in crime for involving minors in criminal activity with the use of information technologies, the impact on children in the eastern regions of Ukraine in the connection with the armed aggression of the Russian Federation led to the emergence of practical problems requiring theoretical reflection and the definition of concrete solutions. Therefore, the definition of these problems should be based on the study of practical activities, for the application of scientifically grounded provisions (tools) to them and the formation of a doctrinal understanding of the concepts related to the content of the study. Accordingly, these processes can not take place without a critical analysis of the results of scientific

research of specialists in the criminal process, criminalistics, operative and investigative activities, which developed general, special and unitary questions of counteraction to the crimes we are investigating.

The solution of these problems involves the comprehensive use of general scientific (empirical - observation, comparison, experiment, empirical and theoretical - abstraction, analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction, modeling, generalization, theoretical - analogy, axiomatic method, extrapolation, idealization, historical method, system approach, systematization, classification, typology, formalization, definition, description, interpretation) and special methods of legal science, in particular: historical and legal; system-structural; comparative legal; logical and legal; dogmatic; statistical sociological simulation and so on.

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ZMYSŁY METAFIZYCZNE UKRAIŃSKICH LAMENTÓW BAROKOWYCH I EPITAFONÓW XVII WIEKU

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Streszczenie. Artykuł dotyczy specyfiki artystycznego wcielenia złożonych zagadnień egzystencjalnych w ukraińskich barokowych dziełach XVII wieku. ku czci zmarłych - lamentach i epitafionach. Ujawniono rolę emocjonalności, zdeterminowaną przez naturę gatunków, w traktowaniu autorów do uniwersaliów egzystencjalnych, takich jak transcendencja duszy ludzkiej, istota świata, płynność życia, fatalność losu itp., Chodzi o wpływ prawosławnej tradycji chrześcijańskiej, w szczególności na poglądy na temat śmierci i pośmiertnego przeznaczenia duszy ludzkiej. Nacisk kładziony jest na funkcję płaczu, który łączy antyetyczne motywy „łez” i „radości”; rolę komponentu duchowego w hierarchii wartości wyznawanych przez autorów; natura syntezy kwestii duchowych i teologicznych z racjonalistycznym spojrzeniem na obiekty obrazu. Ujawnia się rola barokowych środków artystycznych i stylistycznych w przekazywaniu sacrum i profanum w analizowanych pracach.

Słowa kluczowe: baroko, poezja barokowa, poezja metafizyczna, lament, epitafium, płacz.

THE METAPHYSICAL MEANINGS OF UKRAINIAN BAROQUE LYAMENTS AND EPITAFIONS OF 17th CENTURY

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Abstract. The article deals with the expressions of metaphysical meanings in Ukrainian baroque lyaments and epitafions of the 17th century. The role of emotionality caused by the nature of genres by which authors address to existential universals such as the transcendence of the human soul, the essence of the world, the fluidity of life, fatality of fate etc are revealed in the article. It concerns the influence of the Orthodox Christian tradition in particular views on death and posthumous fate of the human soul. The attention is on the function of crying that connects antithetical motives "of tears" and "joy"; the role of the spiritual element in the hierarchy of

values professed by the authors; the character of synthesis of spiritual and theological issues with rationalist view of image objects. The article clarifies the role of baroque artistic and stylistic means for the transfer of sacral and profane in the analyzed works.

Keywords: Baroque, Baroque poetry, Metaphysical poetry, lyaement, epitaftion, crying.

МЕТАФІЗИЧНІ СЕНСИ УКРАЇНСЬКИХ БАРОКОВИХ ЛЯМЕНТІВ ТА ЕПІТАФІОНІВ XVII СТОЛІТТЯ

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Анотація. У статті розглянуто особливості художнього втілення складних буттєвих питань в українських барокових творах XVII ст. на честь померлих осіб – ляментях та епітафіонах. Розкрито роль емоційності, зумовленої природою жанрів, у зверненні авторів до буттєвих універсалій, таких як трансцендентність людської душі, сутність світу, плінність життя, фатальність долі тощо. Йдеться про вплив православної християнської традиції, зокрема в поглядах на смерть та посмертну долю людської душі. Акцентовано на функції плачу, що сполучає антитетичні мотиви «сліз» та «радості»; ролі духовної складової в ієрархії цінностей, що сповідують автори; характері синтезу духовно-теологічних питань з раціоналістичним поглядом на об'єкти зображення. З'ясовано роль барокових художньо-стильових засобів для передачі сакрального й профанного в аналізованих творах.

Ключові слова: бароко, барокова поезія, метафізична поезія, лямент, епітафіон, плач.

Introduction. Artistic works of the Baroque era are distinguished not only by the charm and elegance of forms, the complex symbolic-allegorical nature, the attraction to the synthesis of arts, and above all - the peculiarity of Baroque authors' attitudes, their attraction to artistic comprehension of complex existential issues. Among them - the problems of human destiny, life and death, the mysticism of being, which was given much attention in scientific and philosophical writings and scholarly discussions during the Baroque period. In literary works, they almost entirely embodied in metaphysical poetry, genre varieties of which were verse slays and epitaphs, written about the death of famous persons and violated the eternal existential questions.

For a long time the problem of metaphysical discourse of ancient Ukrainian poetry in Ukrainian literary criticism has not been considered. Only in the early 2000s, due to the emergence of a number of explorations and monographs of O. Yakovin (*Yakovina, 2010, 216 pp.*), The theoretical understanding of metaphysical meanings in Ukrainian poetry of the Baroque period was formulated, its content and national peculiarities were determined. The study of early-bacon motifs in this aspect was started only in recent years by a series of articles by I. Melnychuk (*Melnichuk, 2012, pp. 57-63;*

Melnichuk, 2015, pp. 205-208; Melnichuk, 2015, pp. 131-134), devoted to the anatomical discourse and macabre images and motifs of Ukrainian Baroque poetry.

The purpose of this article is to reveal the peculiarities of the artistic comprehension of metaphysical meanings by the authors of the poetical laments and epitaphs of the 17th century. Considered the role of emotion, caused by the nature of genres, in the treatment of authors to existential universals; the influence of the Orthodox Christian tradition, in particular the views on death and the posthumous destiny of the human soul; functions of baroque artistic and stylistic means for the transfer of sacred and profane in the analyzed works.

The material of the research is the most famous examples of the Baroque elements and epitaphs of the period of the formation and prosperity of the Ukrainian Baroque: "The Lament of the House of the Princes of Ostrozhky ..." (1603) Demyan Nalivayka, "The Blessing in the World of the Poor in a Pitiful Presentiment of the Holy Prophet ... Father Leontiy Karpovich" (1620) Melety Smotrytskyi, "Wailing, the album, the Song of the Eternity of this world ... Gregory Zheliborsky" (1615) by Petr Prezterer, "The Blessing on the Sacrificial Letter ... Father Ioanni Vasilievich" (1628) David Andriyevich, "The Epitaph to the Hetman Ivan Bryukhovetsky" and "The Grump ... Father Tukals'kyi scree-Nelyubovych "Lazarus Baranovychi. Historical and literary analysis of the stated topic will be conducted on the basis of historical-cultural, psychological, structural-semantic research methods.

The main part. Versed slogans and epitaphs belong to the original works of the Baroque period. On the Ukrainian cultural ground, these genre forms were actualized under the influence of realities of a spiritual, cultural and historical nature, and during the XVII century they belonged to the common types of Baroque creativity.

The term "lament" comes from the Latin word *lamentum* - crying, mourning (Literary Encyclopedia, 2007, pp. 588). The term "epitaphion" derives from the term "epitaph", which in Greek means the tombstone (Encyclopedia of Literature, 2007, p. 342). The epitaphs served as conditional appeals to the dead above their gravestones, so the emotional component in them is not as powerful as in the patterns that were written right after the death of the addressee. Some epitaphs acted as part of the slogans (for example, in the works of P. Prezterer, M. Smotrytsky, D. Andreevich), others functioned independently (for example, "The Epitaph to the Hetman Ivan Bryukhovetsky" or "The Grump ... Father Joseph Tukul-Nielubovychy" by Lazar Baranovych).

The poetic world of melodies and epitaphs combines the spiritual and theological principle with the rationalist. Their characters are people known, connected with the community, the state, the society. The laments in their honor are artistic patterns of official, public crying. The authors of these works mourn not only people, but state or religious leaders, therefore, build a journalistic version of the tragic event. As a matter of fact, the word becomes, according to V. Koval, "to a public service with the proclamation of the spiritual virtues of the deceased" (Koval, 2005, p. 4). At the same time, these genres violate the eternal existential and existential questions that lead out such texts beyond the limits of rational knowledge.

The originality of the words and epitaphs as unique genres of poetic creativity of Ukrainian Baroque authors is manifested primarily at the level of poetic emotion (rhetorical emotionality). V.V. Koval writes about the role of feelings in the forms: "According to the typology of the genre, feelings in a slate play a predominant role. As a lyrical work, Lyudmila did not demand from the writer additional means of percussion,

since in lamenting the deceased person ... there was no need to convince. This function was provided by the peculiarity of the genre emerging as a natural reflection of the total tragedy and common to all sorts of grief "(Koval, 2005, p. 6). It is emotionality, according to O. Yakovin, "became a creative synthesizing factor that excited the idea of finding existential universals" (Yakovin, 2001, p. 7). At the level of the form it turned out to be the branching out and the complexity of the poetic expression, a certain freedom of possession in word, manner, and rhythm.

The complaining monologue of the addressee, whose forms are most often acquired by Baroque leagues and epitaphs, was directed not only to cause the reader to sympathize, experience, move him, but also to induce reflection on death, the transience of life, the futility of the world, the temporal presence of a man in him, and other problems of transcendental order.

In the center of attention of such works, there is no doubt a phenomenon of death. Death becomes the point, the limit and the field of struggle leading man to reconciliation with the world and God: "Death to everyone's duty, and not bondage, / not a case of confrontation, but God's will," says the "Knight of the Ostrozky's Lyan of the House" (The word is invaluable, Rev 1, 2006, p. 529). The theme of death in molds is developed in the theological plane: it is a natural pattern ("In the nature of human is not natural racing, / as birth, so the departure from the world is a spontaneous course" (Word of many value, book 1, 2006, p. 529)), an inevitable reality ("Such is a severe death, you are already unintelligible" (Word of many value, book 1, 2006, p. 560), "Uncertain day, certain death. We live now / We do not know whether we will die and at what time" (The Word is Highly Valuable, Book 1, 2006, p. 569), "But nobody has been able to wash this death, / You will not be able to stand before it and with the sword" (Word of Many Values, June 1, 2006, p. 624). "As in the war, just in the peace-calm, / Every day you wait for death in the battle" (Word, p. 1, 2006, pp. 661)), the fact of accomplishing the earthly existence of man and his connection with God. At the same time, it is emphasized on the premature death, its injustice, because it shortens the age to worthy people. M. Smotrytsky, for example, reproached the death of "the miraculous, sacred to this man [Leontius Karpovich], / prematurely shortened to the time the thread of eternity" (Word of many value, book 1, 2006, p. 556), emphasizes that death - it is only the end of the futile life and the beginning of eternity: "Let it not reach yet / the Death, and it is good that the death devoured / Life is useless and for eternity, the road has stretched out. / The bitter path was over - it was happy" (Word is precious, book 1, 2006, p. 564). Her strength is beyond the control of true values - says the poet in the Epitaphon: "Although force / you, death, in the world, / But you can not waste / Treasures worthy of the sky" (Word of many value, Book 1, 2006, p. 572).

Since the slogans and epitaphs were addressed to the state and church leaders, they emphasize the equality of all before death, as in L. Baryanovich's "Epitaph Ivan Bryukhovetsky, for example:" No one of the people of death can not rest, / And the royal crown is not a defense, / Hetman's mace is not glory in death. / ... No one will stand what He wants to do! "(Word is precious, 2nd ed. 2006, p. 341).

Pictures of death are full of mystical concepts and images. Such, in particular, are the images of the dead who appear in the works as alive, able to speak, analyze, give instructions to relatives. Yes, in "Lyanet ..." D. Nalivayka, the late Prince Alexander Ostrozkyi, makes speeches addressed to his wife, comrades, sons, servants and all the people who are here in communion (Word of many value, book 1, 2006, pp. 526-528).

In "Lyamen ..." M. Smotryts'kyi sounds a long monologue of the deceased ("The Voice of the Father to the Sons"), turned to the spiritual "brothers" (Word of Many Values, Book 1, 2006, pp. 564-572). Such an artistic method serves not only to express the image of the protagonist by his own characteristics, but also gives texts a metaphysical color.

The death in baroque melodies and epitaphs appears predominantly as an idea that goes through the entire text. Sometimes she gets a traditional Christian embodiment in the form of a skeleton with a skew, as, for example, in "Lyanet ..." M. Smotrytsky: "It would be better for you to be blind and irresistible, / About one or several braids grew up, / Or about the faint women or children / In which life is like death (what should they do!) "(Word of many value, book 1, 2006, p. 560) or:" The shadow of the sun, for every one the death of a wild man is floating, / His brow is on who is looking for a hedge "(The Word is Valuable, Book 1, 2006, p. 569). In the "Tombstone ... Tukul-Nilubovychy" L. Baranovich's death is likened to a beast: "I have eaten the beast of Joseph, repent, God! / The death of a grown up in a thorn ripped off this beard "(Word of many value, Rev. 2, 2006, pp. 342). In the Baroque chimerical character, there are those fragments with the descriptions of death, built on the game of words, repetitions and consonants: "Blessed is he who knows death to death, / Since he does not have death to die in death" (Word is precious, the book 1, 2006, p. 565).

The theological intentions of death are characteristic both for works in honor of spiritual priests, and those with secular recipients. In both cases, the motive for the inevitability of death is combined with another topos - the need to fill the meaning of life with eternal Christian values. Indicative are the following lines from "Lament ..." M. Smotrytsky: "If one who lived a hundred years could have a day to live sincerely! / The one living in the world is not alive. / To the one who devoutly lives all his life / Death, like a healthy dream, never hurts "(Word of many value, book 1, 2006, p. 565). Christian or civic virtue gets the most important vital credo of the deceased - to live by Christian or to self-serve the fatherland. It is not in vain that the texts of letters and epitaphs are structured as a reminder of the righteous personality traits. The range of praises is contained in a moral-ethical or socio-social aspect. So, M. Smotrytsky, mourning L. Karpovich, emphasizes on how he "Destroyed sins, misfortunes, lies of all sorts," "rescued from misery, left us from passion," to the road of salvation. "(Word of many value, book 1, 2006 , p. 561). From here - the idealization of the image of the addressee (in M. Smotrytsky he is the "bearer of all the virtues of the church"), designing his image in the plane of stoic heroism, which in the Christian sense implies suffering, persecution, overcoming obstacles and the reward of eternal life for these trials (Semeniuk, 2016 , pp. 191-199). In works dedicated to state figures (Alexander Ostrozky, Grigory Zheliborsky), the very earthly affairs of a person and higher goals for the good of the fatherland give meaning to their existence and ensure the existence after death. Thus, the address of Alexander Ostrozky to his sons in "Lyanet ..." D. Nalivayka concludes with the words: "Let us rise up with the steadfastness of the faith of your princely states / your house and I with him with a good glory from the dead" (1, 2006, p. 528).

The mournful monologues of Baroque speeches and epitaphions are most often addressed either to the deceased himself or to God the Father, who often engages in dialogue with celibacy. Appeal to God as the supreme protector of the righteous, who have lost his guardian, is an important composite component of M. Smotrytsky's words

(Vol. 1, 2006, pp. 562-564) and P. Prezterter (Word of Many Values, Book 1, 2006) , pp. 628-629). So, in "Lymeti ..." M. Smotrytsky, the Creator addressed all the complaints of the community due to the loss of a worthy father. God, as a witness to the extraterrestrial being of the human soul, speaks of a well-known philosophical and theological truth: the departure from the world of the earthly person is an absolute blessing, provided that his sonly humility towards the Creator: "He is alive. He is right in the sky. / And he prays for you, my holy man is asleep - / Now he asks you for your kindness, you do not feel like yourself "(Word of many value, 1, 2006, p. 563).

As examples of poetic works of reflection, the laments and epitaphs are interesting in that they depict the boundary state of man between the material (earthly) and the real (spiritual) worlds. Being between the two worlds (between the earthly and the heavenly), man directs the process of knowledge into the sphere of the unconscious - "supersensible" and "subconscious" experience. This leads to a "reorientation of cognitive activity into the sphere of emotional and aesthetic perception" (Koval, 2005, p. 1). The authors tried to feel, to experience this boundary state of the deceased person and to find the existential-psychological means of expression adequate to him. Such means, in particular, were emotional and expressive images (tears, crying), stylistic figures (lexical repetitions, anaphora, gradations), rhetorical techniques (continuous appeals, exclamations), and others like that.

According to V. Koval, the spiritual experience associated with the loss of a loved one of the author suggests a combination of antinomic states, it "contains sadness and joyful bliss, and thus awakens new images of triumph and grace at the level of adherence to the transcendental sphere" (Koval, 2005 , p. 1). In the Baroque genres of Lyudmila and the epitaphion, this emotional experience in a situation of irreparable loss primarily results in the emotional and aesthetic form of crying. The original archetype of crying in folklore (in the genre of folk laughs) is structured in two contrasting emotional and psychological planes - "tears" and "joy". Such antinomy of emotions, as V. Koval asserts, "is a kind of" shock therapy ", a spiritual purification for a sense of the paradox of life: eternity through death" (Koval, 2005, p. 1).

The antinomic structure of this archetype has been consolidated also in the artistic consciousness of the Baroque authors and is clearly traced in the genres of the Lyun and the epitaphion. It is seen in "Lyanet ..." by D. Nalivayka (in particular, in appeals, "rejoice", "comforted", turned to the widowed wife) (Word of many value, book 1, 2006, p. 527). The quotation from the Psalter begins with "Lyantmom ..." by M. Smotrytsky: "They say that joy is followed by sorrow, / Of fun, fun, often gives birth to anger. / The Psalmist said to us: "Yesterday we will cry, / Morning joy will come; the world will forget the sorrow "(Word is a precious one, Rev 1, 2006, p. 555). The main part of the work, too, has an antinomic semantic ending: "Let's get out of the evening. Anxiety took us. / The joy will appear in the morning. Then the will of God, / the higher right, the other is already coming "(Word is a precious one, Rev. 1, 2006, p. 564).

"Slippery" (mournful) part, as a rule, is a noticeable component of the texts. It expresses all the sensual polyphony of the experiences of the authors. It is achieved by artistic methods of gradation, synonymous series, expressive epithets for expressing the extreme tension of feelings: "Greater we are sorry, worse pain, the most painful torment - / In one father with all separation ...", "Unspent sorrow in heart and soul ..." "... we cry a lot. / And over the measure, not to the extent. The thoughts became hard. / Weeping the church, crying all, orphans and widows, I know, / Mysl will not stop "(" Lament ...

"by M. Smotrytsky) (Word is precious, book 1, 2006, p. 555). The modus cry is amplified by images of continuous tears, wounds, and a number of lexical notions for the expression of grief: "Complete dwellings, streets of pain and groaning, / Full corners of pity, full of complaints", "Hard in pain, deep wound, / Mystery, the mind is not human given ... "(Word of many value, book 1, 2006, pp. 559-560)," Sadness! The horror of this is the rejection, / Defamation forever, a dull one "(Word of Many Values, Rev. 1, 2006, p. 626).

Especially powerful emotional mode of crying we can see in "Lyanet ..." D. Andreevich. He is presented in a dramatized form of the monologues of the Mother Church and the poor scupedes of a fraternal school, turned to parishioners, students, families, with a common leitmotif-refrain "Oplachte" (Word of many value, Book 1, 2006, pp. 652-659). This creates the movement of a spiral of the main motive (despair from the loss of the most expensive person), which takes the form of gradation.

The emphasis on the same motive, the slowing down of the narrative (in fact, its concentration on one and the same thing), the sensuality of the content contribute to the fact that the texts of the words acquire two parallel meanings - the real (with an inclination to idealization) and mystical (exalted, meditative). Such simulation of parallel artistic worlds, on the one hand, forms an idealized image of the recipient, and on the other - it expresses the individual author's experience to the level of unreal, mystical.

As in M. Smotryts'kyj, D. Andreevich's remarkable emotional and metaphorical expressions of regret, sorrow, pain concerning the death of Father Ivan Vasilevich are: "We are sad, the hard, the pain of pain" (Word of many value, book 1, 2006, p. 651), "Sorrow me very hard overwhelms me" (Word of many value, book 1, 2006, p. 652), "And now sorrow is hard! We are losing you, / Our father, you are pitying with hide!" (Word is precious, dated 1, 2006, p. 658). "The motive of despair from irreparable loss is updated with lexical repetitions, anaphora, tautological expressions, amplifications, numerous examples of biblical history. Thanks to these means, the tragic pathos "Lyan ..." becomes comprehensive, becoming part of the pain of every reader "(Semeniuk, 2016, p. 195).

To strengthen the mode of experience in "Lyanet ..." D. Nalivayka in the structure of the text involves crying members of the family (wife, brother) and the treatment of the deceased to his wife, children, servants, friends ("Ode to the deceased to the wife", "To the comrades", " One to the sons ", " To the servants ", " To all the people ") (Word is precious, book 1, 2006, pp. 526-530). M. Smotrytsky, for the same purpose, introduces the touching author's appeals to the natural elements (heaven, sun, air, earth) and to the goddesses of the fate of ancient Roman mythology (Clotot, Lahesi, and Atrop), which did not protect the deceased from death (Word is precious, the book 1, 2006, pp. 556-557).

In the epitaphs, unlike the slugs, the "tearful" element is given without verbal accompaniment. Individual experience is as if out of the text (Word 1, 2006, pp. 572-573, 629-630, 663-664; The Word is Profound, Rev. 2, 2006, pp. 341-344).

Contrasting to the tears, the motive of "joy" is most often seen in the short thought of the eternal life of the deceased after death, as, for example, in "Lyanet ..." D. Andreevich: "The soul is because of his earthly habitation, / From the wanderings of those, the hard work, / Go home, go to the mountains in a hurry / And there will begin to comfortably live with the Creator "(Word of many value, book 1, 2006, pp. 663). For the

deceased change of his status - this is an approach to the Creator, this is the highest degree of existence, incommensurate with the earth.

Similarly, the completion of the earthly life of the protagonist and in "Lyanet ..." by M. Smotrytsky are shown. Archimandrite Leontius Karpovich appears as a man who separated himself from the temptations of the world, than he had received purification from the passions and rewards of eternal life in the extraterrestrial world: "Satisfied, Lord, you are his desire, / And to us all left idleness of moaning. / His soul from death to the blessed path / Born. And to Us, You sent death everyday "(Word is precious, 1 st, 2006, p. 559). Therefore, the tragedy of death in this work "coexists with the triumph of" eternal spiritual life, "which the hero gained with his ministry and piety before God. As a result, "the form of lamentation loses its tragic pathos" (Koval, 2005, p. 7).

As we see, in the general anti-theatrical structure of the Baroque words and epitaphs, the motive of tears (crying) is opposed to the Christian concept of salvation, which justifies generally the optimistic orientation of the texts.

The boundary condition in which the lieutenant's addresser is located also expresses other existential meanings, in particular, the hierarchy of values, both in ethical terms and in epistemological (out-of-office, transcendental). The artistic structure of Baroque words and epitaphs is intended to recreate this unique state and to show the merits of spiritual values over material things. Therefore, it is not by chance that we observe here a constant emphasis on the problems of human life that dissociate from the emotionally-exalted perception of extraterrestrial being.

Life on earth is compared to a "comedy", which in its essence is "mournful tragic suffering", with an endless walk in a circle, with a prison, with a storm, exile, pilgrimage (Word of many value, Book 1, 2006, pp. 565, 566) The human body correlates with the shaky rotten house (Word of Many Values, Book 1, 2006, p. 565), Prison (Word Highly Valuable, Book 1, 2006, pp. 662), it is "Various Difficult Nests and Dwellings" (Word Multivariate, Rev 1, 2006, p. 623). "The Wicked World" reminds a treacherous comrade, he is unpredictable and insidious: "Artificially coloring all his neighbors, he / she saves them, and mortally wounds them" (Word of Many Values, Book 1, 2006, p. 571).

Baroque poets constantly emphasize the temporality of life, its meagerness, emphasize that everything in it is "vanity of vanities": "For me all, oh, vanity will become vanity, / And all the world's pump will be melted like a smoke" ("Crying, or Lament ... "P. Prezerator) (Word of many value, Rev. 1, 2006, p. 623). Prehistoric things of the past. The preacher is metaphorically called "Profit of darkness, a place for all the trappings," the deep swamp, the soul of defamation by the coffin, "namely earthly life," the shadow of death "(Word of many value, book 1, 2006, p. 627). The same meager, vain appears in Baroque "lamentations" and a man, regardless of his social status: "What, man, on earth, you have to boast, / Or something, meager, you raise yourself, / When every man is like vanity, / Although well-off I tried, too much, I could do it?" (Word is precious, book 1, 2006, p. 623).

Involving the aesthetics of the ugly, the disadvantages of this world are depicted by the authors in a brutally naturalistic way. "What the world has, it will be - the worms of food", "The spirit will go away, the earthly corpse will be unclean, / In mildew, in the worms, smelly, unwise", - notes M. Smotrytsky (Word of many value, 1, 2006, p. 564 , 565). "Before the death of an ill person it is not easy to turn away, / In the stench must, in the gunpowder still flip over", - notes with sadness P. Prevvyter (Word of many

value, 1, 2006, p. 623). Such pictures create a sense of the world "as a volatile conglomerate of evil forces, a chaotic environment full of drama and dangers that resembles the martyrs' theater of Calvary" (Koval, 2005, p. 8). As a result, the apocalyptic mood of the end of the world and the Last Judgment appears in the mourning: "The world is hurting all - the fall has come! / Not a sign of aging, the end of my age, / A is a sign of the end of the world's end "(Word of many value, book 1, 2006, p. 565).

The emphasis on the shortcomings, the contradictions of earthly existence, in which "both war and evil are internally - / Casemates, shackled, captive, everything is not good" (Vol. 1, 2006, p. 565), further exacerbates the drama of the universe, which is approaching death: "Luxury, waste, arbitrariness, trickery, distrust - / All of them shrinks mortal ax" (Word of many value, book 1, 2006, p. 566). "Life is human! How do you humble all disasters, / It's like running slippery, trembling step, dimness is immeasurable, "" Oh, the evil life on the thread! It is necessary, therefore, to think back from the living, who cares for the barbells, / Cleanses, bites, learns in the world ", - such profoundly philosophical conclusions about the world and life are made by M. Smotrytsky (Word of many value, book 1, 2006, p. 567).

True values, according to the authors, are those waiting for the deceased in the extraterrestrial world, beyond the realm, which is a true homeland for a Christian: "My children! - Calls on M. Smotrytsky. - In your fatherland you have to rush! / For the sake of the sake of the land, do not lose the sky! "(Word of many value, book 1, 2006, p. 566). To this end, the poet advises to guard "the purity of conscience", to guard the riches, to help the poor (Word a lot of value, Book 1, 2006, p. 569). In the vanity of this world, he contrasts eternal life in heaven, because only there can be achieved "eternal glory" (Word of Many Values, Book 1, 2006, p. 571). P. Presbyter, warning of sinful death, emphasizes the need to descend from the wide offer of fornication "on a narrow path", which can achieve the luxury of eternal life (Word of Many Values, Book 1, 2006, p. 627). D. et. Andriyevich writes about the "eternal fatherland", the direction "to the mountain houses" of the deceased father Ivan Vasilevich: "From the land to the homeland, the mith passes, / With the saints, everybody finds eternal peace" (Word of many value, book 1, 2006, p. 661). The poet emphasizes that for a righteous man, who was Father John Vasilevich, death is a blessing, a way of moving from the "crying field" to "Celestial Palaces" (Word of Many Values, Book 1, 2006, p. 662). This motive is also dominant in the Epitaphion: "The soul is his earthly habitation, / From the wanderings of these, the hard work, / Comes to the homeland, goes to the mountains in a hurry / And there will comfortably live with the Creator" (Word of many value, book. 1, 2006, p. 663). About "peace in the sky" as a reward of the deceased from God for his pastoral ministry is also mentioned in the "Tombstone ... Tukul-Nielubovichy" by L. Baranovich (Word of many value, 2nd ed., 2006, pp. 342-344).

According to V. Koval, the reproduction of reality "as a rhetorical antithesis to the ideal" was intended "to move the reader and bring him to an" affective "state" (Koval, 2005, p. 7). This antinomy is realized in two planes: the real one, which is the manifestation of the material (profane world), and the real one, which acts as the embodiment of the ideal, the righteous (sacred environment). Thus, a picture of the coexistence of two worlds - the real (earthly) as the world of obedience and beyond, whose understanding goes beyond traditional Christian representations, emerges. In both

cases, the concept of human fate is full of light and deep sadness because of the impossibility of full comprehension of the Absol.

Conclusions. Thus, the metaphysical attitude of the authors of Baroque speeches and epitaphions is beyond doubt. To the search for existential universals they were stimulated by emotionality, due to specific genres. On these works, the consistent Orthodox tradition was observed, according to which death is merely a state of affairs, a form of human transition into other, extraterrestrial dimensions. The spiritual experience of the authors is transmitted in the form of crying, which combines the antithetical motives of "tears" and "joy". The boundary state recognizes the hierarchy of material and spiritual values, contributes to the emotionally-raised perception of extraterrestrial being. At the same time, the anthropological attitude of the authors turned out to be on the level of content in emphasizing the problems of human life, journalism, idealization of objects of the image and in emotionally perceived irreparable loss. At the level of the form it was found expression in the branching out and complexity of the poetic expression, the involvement of a wide range of baroque means for the transfer of sacral and profane within a single work.

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WPLYW ZAJĘĆ LECZNICZEGO WYCHOWANIA FIZYCZNEGO NA WSKAŹNIKI HEMODYNAMICZNE OSÓB WIEKU STARSZEGO

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Streszczenie. Obecnie wzrasta liczba osób starszych i bardzo starych na całym świecie. Analiza danych statystycznych sugeruje, że wraz z wiekiem wzrasta ciśnienie krwi. Wysokie ciśnienie skurczowe tętnic powoduje rozwój zawału mięśnia sercowego, choroby wieńcowej, udaru, a nawet śmierci. Dlatego celem było zbadanie wpływu fizykoterapii na stan układu sercowo-naczyniowego osób starszych na etapie szpitalnym. W badaniu wzięło udział 27 kobiet i 20 mężczyzn w wieku od 69 do 85 lat. Pacjenci w obu grupach mają prawdopodobne zmniejszenie częstości akcji serca i średnich wartości współczynnika sprawności układu krążenia (tylko kobiety). Zaproponowane przez nas klasy wychowania fizycznego przyczyniają się do możliwego zmniejszenia średnich wartości ciśnienia skurczowego i rozkurczowego tętnic, średniego ciśnienia krwi oraz możliwej poprawy średnich wartości objętości skurczowej i minutowej krwi.

Słowa kluczowe: układ sercowo-naczyniowy, ciśnienie tętnicze, osoby starsze.

INFLUENCE OF TREATMENTAL PHYSICAL CULTURE ON HEMODYNAMIC INDICATORS OF ELDERLY PERSONS

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Abstract. Nowadays, the number of elderly people is increasing throughout the world. Analysis of statistical data shows that blood pressure increases with the age. High arterial systolic pressure is the cause of the development of myocardial infarction, coronary heart disease, stroke and even death. Thus, the purpose was to study the influence of medical physical therapy to the state of the cardiovascular system of the elderly people at the hospital stage. 27 women and 20 men aged from 69 to 85 years old were investigated. The probable decrease in the average values of heart rate and coefficient of efficiency of the blood circulation system are recorded in patients of both groups. The classes of medical physical therapy offered by us contribute to a probable decrease in the average values of arterial systolic and diastolic pressure, medium arterial pressure, and a probable improvement in the average values of systolic and minute blood volumes.

Key words: cardiovascular system, blood pressure, heart rate, elderly persons.

ВПЛИВ ЗАНЯТЬ ЛІКУВАЛЬНОЮ ФІЗИЧНОЮ КУЛЬТУРОЮ НА ПОКАЗНИКИ ГЕМОДИНАМІКИ ОСІБ ПОХИЛОГО ВІКУ

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Анотація. На сьогодні в усьому світі спостерігається збільшення кількості людей похилого та старечого віку. Аналіз статистичних даних свідчить про те, що з віком артеріальний тиск підвищується. Високий артеріальний систолічний тиск спричиняє розвиток інфаркту міокарда, ішемічної хвороби серця, інсульту і, навіть, смерть. Тому мета полягала у дослідженні впливу лікувальної фізичної культури на стан серцево-судинної системи людей похилого віку на лікарняному етапі. У дослідженні брали участь 27 жінок і 20 чоловіків у віці від 69 до 85 років. У пацієнтів обох груп зареєстровано вірогідне зниження частоти серцевих скорочень і середніх значень коефіцієнту економічності системи кровообігу (лише у жінок). Запропоновані нами заняття лікувальної фізичної культури сприяють вірогідному зменшенню середніх значень артеріального систолічного та діастолічного тиску, середнього артеріального тиску, вірогідному покращенню середніх значень систолічного та хвилинного об'єму крові.

Ключові слова: серцево-судинна система, артеріальний тиск, особи похилого віку.

Formulation of the problem. Today, according to statistics, in all economically developed countries, the number of elderly and elderly people has almost doubled (Metody analiza i vozrastnye ..., 2003; Moreva D.U., Stadnik L.A., Prihodko V.U., 2016). Thus, according to the estimation of the State Statistics Service of Ukraine in 2017, among the entire population of our country, about 16% are elderly and senile people (according to data - 2 409 049 men and 4 770 461 women) (Naseleňná Ukraïni na 1 siĉna, pocinauci z 1990 roku ...; Ukraine [The World Factbook ..., 2017]. Experts' forecasts suggest that by 2050, in Ukraine, persons over the working age will make up almost 38% (Naseleňná Ukraïni na 1 siĉnâ, poĉinauĉi z 1990 roku ...; Ukraine [The World Factbook ..., 2017).

The analysis of statistical data shows that today the average life expectancy of men in Ukraine is about 67 years, and women are 77 years old (Širina M.G., 2010; Ukraine [The World Factbook ..., 2017]. It should be noted that in the countries of Eastern and Western Europe the life expectancy of the population is on average 9-10 years.

According to data from literary sources (Furman Ū., Sulyma A., 2015; Sulyma A., Tkachenko T., 2018; Zaboľevaniâ serdca i rehabilitaciâ ..., 2000) with age there is a violation of biological rhythms of various systems of the organism, including cardiovascular diseases, vascular system. At the same time, circulatory system diseases are responsible for more than half of all deaths. According to statistics, over the past year alone, more than 300,000 deaths from cardiovascular diseases have been registered in our country (Naseleňná Ukraïni na 1 siĉnâ, poĉinauĉi z 1990 roku ...; Ukraine [The World Factbook ..., 2017].

Consequently, the above suggests that the study of the regularities of changes in the blood circulation system in the process of aging is important and relevant.

The state of scientific research. Analysis of statistical data in 2017 shows that in our country, almost 40% of people over the age of 60 have elevated arterial systolic and diastolic pressure (Ševčuk V.G., 2000; Zabolevaniâ serdca i reabilitaciâ ..., 2000). However, only 12% of patients with cardiovascular diseases are under constant medical supervision and one third of all patients receive effective and adequate treatment.

The results of experimental studies of many authors (Dzâk VG, Drynovec VI, Vasil'eva LI, Hanûkov AA, 1999; Metody analiza i vozrastnye ..., 2003; Širina MG, 2010) indicate that almost 25% of people over 65 have an arterial pressure of 160 / 100 mm Hg Art., and 53% - 150/90 mm Hg. st ..

Based on the analysis of the data of scientific literature (Furman Ū., Sulyma A., 2015; Metody analiza i vozrastnye ..., 2003; Širina M.G., 2010) it was established that with age, arterial pressure rises. So, in literary sources (Čebotarev DD, Korkusko OV, 2008; Sulyma A., Tkachenko M., 2018; Vitomskiy V., Hruzevych I., Salnykova S. et al., 2018), we find information that an increase in systolic and diastolic pressure is up to 60 years old. In the future, diastolic pressure does not change with age. On the contrary, systolic pressure continues to increase for women under 80 and for men up to 70 years old (Čebotarev DD, Korkusko OV, 2008; Morêva D.Ū., Stadnûk LA, Prihod'ko V.Y., 2016; Sulyma A., Tkachenko M. ., 2018). Such age dynamics of changes in blood pressure contributes to the prevalence of so-called "isolated systolic hypertension". According to the results of randomized studies of SHEP and Syst-Eur, isolated systolic hypertension is observed in almost 6% of people aged 60-69, in 8% of 70-79 years of age and in 18-25% of people aged 80 years.

Clinical and statistical data indicate that high arterial systolic blood pressure is the cause of myocardial infarction, coronary heart disease, stroke, and mortality.

Treatment of patients with cardiovascular diseases is carried out by the complex application of various medical devices, among which physical rehabilitation facilities deserve special attention.

Thus, the purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of therapeutic physical culture on the state of the cardiovascular system of the elderly at the hospital stage.

To achieve the goal we solved the **following tasks:**

1. On the basis of the analysis of scientific and methodological literature, to reveal the features of the cardiovascular system in the elderly, as well as to explore the possibilities for improving the state of this system by applying therapeutic physical culture and massage.

2. To investigate the effectiveness of the influence of training physical education on the state of the cardiovascular system of patients 69-85 years at the hospital stage.

Methods and contingent of research. During the research, we used the following methods: theoretical analysis and generalization of literary sources; pedagogical observation; pedagogical experiment; pedagogical testing using methods of pulsometry, sphygmomanometry; methods of mathematical statistics.

The frequency of heart rate was determined palpated. The magnitude of arterial systolic and diastolic pressure was measured with the help of a sifigmomanometer "LD-81" in rest.

Pulse pressure (PT), which reflects the state of vessels, namely, their permeability and elasticity, as well as the functioning of the myocardium, were calculated as the difference between systolic and diastolic pressure.

In addition to systolic and diastolic blood pressure in medical practice, there is also mean arterial pressure (AT blood), which in clinical practice is called the pressure of the entire cardiac cycle. This pressure was calculated by the formula:

$$AT_{\text{cep}} = AT_{\text{диаст}} + 1/3 \cdot PT,$$

where AT diast - arterial diastolic pressure, millimeters of the mercury column
PT - pulse pressure, millimeters of the mercury column

Sufficiently common indicator, which is determined by the calculation method, is the coefficient of cost-effectiveness of the blood circulation system (KEK, cu). The value of this indicator was determined as the product of the frequency of heart rate and pulse blood pressure.

The systolic volume of blood is the volume of blood that moves from the heart to the blood vessels for one systole (Aronov D.M., Bubnova M.G., Pogosova G.V., 2006; Bogdanovs'ka N.V., Kal'onova V.V., 2012).

During the study, we calculated the systolic blood volume (SOC) using the formula Malikov MV, Bogdanovskaya N.V. (Bogdanovs'ka N.V., Kal'onova V.V., 2012):

$$COK = 0,53 \cdot AT_{\text{sist}} + 0,617 \cdot DT + 0,231 \cdot MT - 1,07 \cdot AT_{\text{diast}} - 0,698 \cdot B - 22,64,$$

where ATsist - arterial systolic pressure, mm Hg;

DT - body length, cm;

MT - body weight, kg;

ATdiast - arterial diastolic pressure, mm Hg;

B - age, years;

22.64; 1.07; 0.698; 0.617; 0.53 and 0.231 are the coefficients of the multiple regression equation.

A minute volume of blood, which shows the amount of blood transmitted by the heart for 1 min in a large or small circle of blood, was determined as a product of systolic blood volume and heart rate.

The minute volume of blood increases with chas muscle activity, after eating, as well as intravenous fluid injection and decreases in blood loss.

The probability of the difference between the mean values was determined by the t-criterion of Student. Reliability was considered significant at 5% level of significance $p < 0,05$.

Our research was conducted on the basis of the Vinnytsia Regional Clinical Hospital Veterans of the War. We studied 27 women and 20 men aged 69 to 85 years. All the patients were on inpatient treatment.

All subjects were divided into 2 groups: control group (CH), which numbered 23 persons (including 13 women and 10 men), and the main (CO) - 24 persons (14 women and 10 men). The patients of the KG were engaged in the program of the medical institution, and the patients of the OG additionally visited the classes we developed by the medical physical education.

The content of physical education classes included various exercises for muscle relaxation and general developmental exercises that stimulate extracardiac factors in hemodynamics and improve blood flow in the vessels of the brain. Includes also respiratory exercises with respiratory depression on exhalation, which affect the receptors of the vagus nerve, which leads to a decrease in blood pressure, a decrease in peripheral resistance to blood flow and a slowdown in the heart rate.

Duration of studies at the beginning of the study lasted 25-60 minutes, and later - 75-90 minutes. Moreover, the duration of the session depended on the intensity, that is, the less intensity, the greater the duration. Frequency of classes with therapeutic physical cultures 3 times a week.

Many specialists (Bogdanovs'ka NV, Kal'onova V.V., 2012; Korol'chuk AP, Sulyma AS, 2018; Širina MG, 2010) have proved that the mass influences positively on the changes of the indicators of central hemodynamics, in particular, contributes to the expansion of peripheral vessels, the facilitation of work of the left atrium and the left ventricle, to increase the myocardial ejection fraction. That is why all patients also visited massage, in particular, back massage, collar zone, and massages of the heart.

It is well-known that the adequacy of physical exercises in an age group is estimated by the heart rate after the termination of physical activity. To do this, we used the formula for determining the optimal heart rate:

170 - Age of person (years)

The formative study lasted for 21 days during the course of a flat course of treatment in a hospital on the basis of the Vinnytsia Regional Clinical Hospital of the Veterans of the War. An analysis of the functional state of the circulatory system of the elderly was carried out before and after physical rehabilitation.

Results of the research and their discussion. Prior to conducting a molding study, no statistically significant differences were recorded between the hemodynamics of the control and the main groups ($p > 0.05$).

As can be seen from Table 1, during the 21st day of treatment in the hospital, patients with both control and the main group registered probable changes in arterial systolic blood pressure.

Table 1
Hemodynamic indices of persons 69-85 years of control (n = 23)
and main (n = 24) groups

Indexes		Average value, $\bar{X} \pm m$	
		at the beginning of the study	at the end of the study
AT syst. mm hg Art.	KG	155,65±1,66	150,9±1,10*
	OG	159,6±1,61	149,6±1,61*
AT dist., mm hg Art.	KG	107±1,65	103±1,65*
	OG	112,9±1,61	104±1,08*
AT mid., mm hg Art.	KG	122,9±2,57	119,28±0,92
	OG	128,5±1,96	119±1,08*
PT, mm hg Art..	KG	49,13±1,10	47,9±1,10
	OG	46,67±1,08	45,8±1,08*
ЧСС, уд/хв	KG	85,78±0,66	83,9±0,61*
	OG	84,38±0,86	80,8±0,91*

Note: * - the differences with regard to the output data are statistically significant ($p < 0,05$)

Thus, the average value of the aforementioned indicator in CH patients probably decreased by 3,06%, and in CO patients - by 6,3%.

Attention is drawn to the fact that in patients who under our program, there is a probable decrease in the average group value of arterial diastolic pressure of 7.9%.

While the average of the aforementioned indicator decreased by only 3.7% in the KY subjects and continues to remain high for patients aged 69-85.

It is worth noting that, after 21 days of training in the physical cultures, no person with arterial systolic blood pressure of 180 mm Hg had been arrested among the women and men of the CO. Art., and diastolic pressure - 130 mm Hg. Art. Although in the beginning of the study, there were 5 patients and 6 people, respectively. While among the elderly COG at the end of the study, 1 patient had arterial diastolic pressure at 130 mm Hg. Art.

The frequency of cardiac contractions in the studied KGs probably decreased by 2.19%, and in COs by 4.2% and corresponds to the normal values for persons in this age group (norm 75-80 beats per minute).

Unlike the patients of the COG, in the elderly who were engaged in our program, the average changes in mean blood pressure, which, after the completion of the molding study, were 119 ± 1.08 mm Hg, also aroused the probable changes. Art.

In the middle group, the pulse pressure values of both groups decreased, however, there was no significant change (see Table 1).

After 21 days of physical therapy training in persons aged 69-85, a significant increase in mean values of systolic blood volume by 24.09% was recorded (Fig. 1). At the same time, there are no significant changes in this indicator in KG patients.

*

Fig. 1. Dynamics of changes in the average value of CC in persons 69-85 years of control (KG) and main (CO) groups

* - the differences with respect to the initial data are statistically significant ($p < 0,05$)

Attention is drawn to the fact that the patients in both groups continue to show low mean values of central hemodynamics, which characterize the cardiac function of the heart. Thus, the average value of the systolic blood volume after the completion of the molding study in people with CO and OG is less than 60% (the normal value is 50-70 ml).

Given the fact that in the elderly who were engaged in our program, there is a probable reduction in the mean values of heart rate and a likely increase in the mean values of systolic blood volume in them is observed and a possible increase in average values of the indicator, which determines the amount of blood, which is moved by the heart for 1 minute in a large or small circle of blood circulation.

Analysis of the results of the study shows that in patients aged 69-85 years of age, the mean value of the minute volume of blood increased by 1.2% ($p > 0.05$), while the OG representatives increased significantly by 21.1% ($p < 0.05$) compared to the output danes, which is higher in percentage terms than in the control group patients.

Figure 2 shows that the average value of the coefficient of efficiency of the circulatory system in men and women of both groups decreased, indicating positive dynamics.

Fig. 2. Dynamics of changes in the average KEK in persons 69-85 years of the control (KG) and the main (CO) groups

* - the differences with respect to the initial data are statistically significant ($p < 0,05$)

It should be noted that at the end of the molding study in women of KG and CO the decrease in the average of the KEC with respect to the day off was 7.4% and 7.9%, respectively, was statistically significant. Men in both groups also experienced a decrease in the average of the above indicator (by 4.7% and 2.7%, respectively), but there was no statistically significant difference.

It should be noted that in percentage terms, the reduction of average values of the coefficient of efficiency of blood circulation in persons 69-85 years of CO is higher than in patients with KG, which testifies to the effectiveness of our developed physical education cultures.

Conclusions.

Analysis and synthesis of literature data on the subject of research suggests that with the age of people there are violations of the cardiovascular system. And data from the World Health Organization state that over the past decades in our country, mortality from diseases of the above system has increased. Consequently, taking into account the above, many researchers are seeking new techniques for the physical rehabilitation of the elderly with cardiovascular diseases.

The main task of physical rehabilitation of patients with diseases of the cardiovascular system is the use of such therapeutic physical culture, which help to normalize blood pressure, improve the function of the cardiopulmonary system and higher nervous activity.

Application in the process of physical rehabilitation of the elderly with diseases of the cardiovascular system of training physiotherapy and massage improves the functional state of patients. Positive functional changes under the influence of occupations according to the proposed program of physical rehabilitation contribute to a veracious reduction in mean values of systolic and diastolic pressure, as well as mean arterial pressure. Patients who were engaged in the program of a medical establishment, registered a probable reduction in only arterial systolic blood pressure.

Physical training in combination with massage helps to improve the average values of systolic and temporal volume of blood in persons aged 69-85.

Patients in the control group and the main groups have registered positive dynamics of changes in the average values of the coefficient of blood flow efficiency.

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WARUNKI ZAPOBIEGANIA KONFLIKTOM INTERPERSONALNYM STUDENTOM INSTYTUCJI SZKOLNICTWA WYŻSZEGO

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Streszczenie. Autor analizuje podejścia do rozumienia zapobiegania konfliktom interpersonalnym w środowisku studenckim. Wyjaśnia pojęcie „zapobiegania konfliktom”. Określa przyczyny, etapy konfliktów w studentów instytucji szkolnictwa wyższego. Artykuł podkreśla rodzaje, etapy zapobiegania konfliktom interpersonalnym w środowisku studenckim. Autor przeprowadził badanie wśród studentów specjalności „Praca socjalna”, które obejmuje analizę treści programu edukacyjno-zawodowego, planu pracy naukowej, podane wyniki badań eksperymentalnych, przedstawionych w celu określenia zachowania studentów w sytuacjach konfliktowych. Autor podsumowuje potrzebę systematycznego i ukierunkowanego zapobiegania konfliktom interpersonalnym w środowisku studenckim.

Słowa kluczowe: student, konflikt, uniwersytet, przyczyny, zapobieranie, środowisko, praca socjalna.

CONDITIONS OF PREVENTION OF INTERPERSONAL CONFLICT OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION

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Anotation. The author analyzes the approaches to understanding the prevention of interpersonal conflicts in the student environment. Clarifies the concept of "prevention of conflicts". Determines the causes, stages of conflicts in students of institutions of higher education.

The article highlights the stages, stages of prevention of interpersonal conflicts in the student environment. The author conducted a study among the students of the specialty "Social Work", which includes an analysis of the contents of the educational-professional program, the plan of academic work, the results of experimental studies presented to determine the behavior of students in conflict situations. The author concludes the need for systematic and targeted prevention of interpersonal conflicts in the student environment.

Key words: Conflict, pedagogical conflict, prophylaxis, interpersonal interaction, compromise, cooperation, competition, avoidance, resist.

УМОВИ ПРОФІЛАКТИКИ МІЖСОБИСТІСНИХ КОНФЛІКТІВ СТУДЕНТІВ ЗАКЛАДІВ ВИЩОЇ ОСВІТИ

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Анотація. Автор аналізує підходи до розуміння профілактик міжособистісних конфліктів у студентському середовищі. Уточнює поняття «профілактика конфліктів». Визначає причини, етапи виникнення конфліктів у студентів закладів вищої освіти.

В статті виділені види, етапи профілактики міжособистісних конфліктів у студентському середовищі. Автором проведене дослідження серед студентів спеціальності «Соціальна робота», яке включає аналіз змісту освітньо-професійної програми, план навчальної роботи, подані результати експериментальних досліджень для визначення поведінки учнів у конфліктних ситуаціях. Автор робить висновок про необхідність проведення систематичної та цілеспрямованої профілактики міжособистісних конфліктів у студентському середовищі.

Ключові слова: студент, конфлікт, університет, середовище, причини, запобігання, соціальна робота.

Introduction. The success of students in the educational process depends on many factors, including the their character of interpersonal relations in the academic group. Formation and operation of academic groups, as well as any group is not possible without such phenomena as the origin, prevention and conflict resolution

Entering to the university, young people begin a new life, where trained to express themselves, form new goals, objectives and values during functioning of the academic group.

The structure of personal relationships and team structure constantly interact, influence each other and converge more stronger, if better organized joint activities of people. It is known that in the development of any team is its infancy, the conflict period, rule-making, business activity and decay. Especially important in periods of becoming and rule-making groups and provide necessary assistance to first-year students, explain the law and to teach ways to overcome conflict.

Features of conflict prevention in the student team depends on understanding the reasons, procedural aspects of the conflict, its types and functions. Realizing that the conflicts inherent in interpersonal interactions people believe that prevention work on conflicts in interpersonal interactions, students must be made consistently and is aimed to improve communication, optimizing the educational process of identity formation and professionally competent professional using with rational methods of conflict resolution (Grybok, 2014).

The most common type of conflicts among students is the conflict between personality and group. The emergence of it is associated with a situation where one of the groupmates does not want to adhere to established norms of behavior or communication. For example, students are accustomed to always prepare all the questions of a seminar for a couple, but one of their groupmates refuses to do this and inclines others to divide the question. This causes dissatisfaction with most of the group, because if you work in this mode, the level of knowledge will be low. Thus, there is a conflict situation between a group and a person (individual student).

The same kind of conflict is between the group and the old man, when the latter tries to subjugate other students, not taking into account their thoughts and positions. Such behavior from the side of the old age prevents others from showing themselves, defending their own point of view and taking a decent place in the team. It is known that today our society needs creative, creative people with a non-standard position and vision on the world. Therefore, the emergence of such situations is unacceptable: if they appear, then they need an immediate solution.

At the same time, besides the personal-group conflict in higher education institutions, there is also an intergroup conflict - conflict situations of a student group with representatives of the administration, the dean's office, the trade union committee or with other groups (*Nazarenko, 2009, p.496*).

The problem of conflicts in peer groups, including student groups were engaged in such domestic scientists as E. Durmanenko, I. Zaitsev, Leonid Losev, AP Luzan, and others. The problem also was investigated by foreign scientists, including James. Kaprara, J. Servon, L. Steinberg and others.

Main part. In modern literature, the definition of "conflict prevention" and "prevention of conflicts" are often used as synonyms. We consider it appropriate to distinguish these allegations. Conflict prevention is a broader concept, and preventing conflicts is a form of prevention.

Conflict prevention is a system of managed activities that provides scientific, theoretical and practical implementation of measures aimed at preventing conflicting behavior (*Khersonskii, Dvoryak, 2010, p.199*).

O.Y. Antsupov and O.I. Shipilov, taking into account the negative effects of conflict interaction, noted that conflict prevention is an even more important component than a constructive solution to them. It is possible to avoid negative consequences if timely responding and prevention of conflict situations covering four areas: 1) creating objective conditions that prevent the emergence and destructive development of pre-conflict situations; 2) optimization of organizational and managerial conditions for the creation and operation of organizations; 3) eliminating socio-psychological factors of conflict, 4) blocking personal factors of conflict. As scientists point out, in order for prevention to be successful, all points should be used in direct interaction and simultaneously in all directions (*Antsupov, Shipilov, 1999, p. 241*).

A. Antsupov and A. Shipilov note that social interaction is consistent in the case when it is balanced. They identified five balances, which may cause a conflict to violate.

1. Balance roles. In social interaction, its participants can play each other in the role of senior, equal or younger in their social status. If the communication partners take their roles, there is no role conflict. The highest conflict potential has the role of senior, although it is often psychologically most comfortable for a person. The most favorable in terms of preventing conflicts is the interaction with the environment on equal terms.

2. Balance of interdependence in decisions and actions. All people seek freedom and independence. However, our freedom must not restrict the freedom of those who are near. If one person feels excessive dependence on the other, it can cause discomfort, provoke conflicting behavior.

3. Balance of mutual services. Throughout the life of each person, they help other people and receive help from other people. However, no matter how altruistic feelings a person would be guided by, he deliberately or unknowingly fixed the services that he provided himself or received from others.

4. Balance of losses. People have a sense of revenge: if we suffer damage as a result of other people's actions, we also want to cause some kind of damage to the guilty person. The task of damage can break the relationship and become the basis for the emergence of conflict.

5. Balance of self-assessment and external evaluation. In the process of social interaction, people are constantly evaluated by each other. The most intensive process of mutual evaluation takes place in the dyad "subordinate leader", "teacher-student".

6. D.G. Scott allocates a balance of responsibility. In her opinion, a situation in which one of the parties assumes too much or too little responsibility is potentially a conflict. In the first case, an individual who has taken too much responsibility may experience overload, fatigue due to the need to perform extra work and lack of support. If liability is too small, one may feel reduced its significance, dependence on others and loss of individuality. In both cases, there may be feelings of insult and annoyance that underlie the conflict. Consequently, one of the conditions for the prevention of conflicts is the fair distribution of responsibility (*Antsupov, Shipilov, 1999, p. 241*).

Most scientists allocate primary and secondary prevention of conflicts among students. These types of conflict preventions scientists believe, the need to provide as external (primarily organizational and administrative measures), as internal or proper warning of the psychosocial measures.

Primary prevention of conflicts in interpersonal interactions provides students the conflictological education and development of the conflict potential or actual participants. Repeated (secondary) prevention of conflict include direct work in risk groups, relieve tension, confrontation, in groups with high potential for conflict and escalation of conflicts.

Analysis of the above, allows us to conclude that the most effective is approach by E. Durmanenko, that along with prevention activities to update the constructive conflict resolution, which are difficult to understand conscious purposeful influence on the clash of parties in conflict at all stages of its origin, development and completion to prevent destructive conflicts and resolve them constructively (*Durmanenko, 2004, p. 23*).

In prevention work to prevent conflicts among students used different methods.

The methods of preventing interpersonal conflicts, E. Durmanenko defines the following:

- cognitive - clear and specific clarification of positions, relationships, concepts; provide feedback; collect additional information

- motivational - forecasting perspective; common constructive solution to the problem of competition or cooperation

- Active - increase of efficiency of joint activity

- organizational - increasing flexibility and roles dynamic (*Durmanenko, 2004, p. 25*).

An effective method of prophylaxis and conflict prevention, according to V. Andreyev, avoiding the typical conflicts. In particular, he recommended to observe the following behavior: do not seek to dominate anything; be a principal, but not only fight for principles; remember that straightforwardness - is good, but not always; often smile (smile was worth valued but expensive); remember that tradition - it is good to a certain extent; you need to tell the truth, but this must be done skillfully; strive to be independent, but not arrogant; not to turn to pragmatism pragmatism; do not expect justice for yourself if thou wicked; do not overestimate their abilities and capabilities; do not take the initiative where it does not need; to show goodwill; to exercise restraint and calm in any situation; realize itself in the work and not in conflict. Please also note that

the most positive feature of the conflict is that it is a source of development and gives an opportunity improve the situation (*Anczupov, 2007, p. 19*).

Analyses of plans of educational and educational work of students of Lesya Ukrainka Eastern European National University demonstrates that prophylaxis of conflicts in interpersonal interactions of students is carried systematically and comprehensively.

Formation of the conflictological culture of students, which includes a system of knowledge, a system of educational work (learning disciplines educational degree "bachelor" specialty "Social pedagogy" - "Fundamentals of educational Conflict" (course) "Psycho-pedagogical foundations of interpersonal communication" (year), "Self-education and self-regulation of the individual" (course), educational degree "Master" specialty "social work" - "conflict management in socio-pedagogical process" (120 hour, classroom - 42 hrs.), educational degree "Master" specialty "Pedagogy of higher school "(90 hrs., classroom - 36 h.)

The purpose of these educational courses is to develop knowledge on the causes, mechanisms of pedagogical conflicts and ways of their prevention and constructive solution, specific conflict management in socio-pedagogical process and of their acquisition of skills to control the conflict situation, diagnose conflict constructively to solve it; positively perceive the conflict and its pragmatic use it in educational activities.

In the process of study mentioned above disciplines students form the knowledge about the nature of conflict as phenomenal phenomenon of social development, its structure, functions and types; acquainted with the specific features of teaching conflict and the mechanism of a social and educational environment, including high school; analyze the main konfliktogeny in the pedagogical process of high school; analyze different ways of solving pedagogical conflicts; learn to predict the occurrence of teaching conflict constructively to solve it, and effectively manage the conflict in the pedagogical process

Accordingly, the goal is only possible on the mastering of knowledge, patterns and characteristics of education; principles of education and ways of their realization in the educational process; organizational forms and methods of education; method of forming a student group; the nature, role and importance of student government in high school; basic historical stages of the conflict theory; current concepts and research areas in Conflict as a whole and particularly in educational Conflict; Specific features of the conflicts in the socio-pedagogical process; the nature and structure of teaching conflict, its features and characteristics, diagnosis; typology of pedagogical conflicts and their dynamics; basic styles of behavior in conflict situations and how to address the structural social and educational conflict; and skills, trained to plan process in higher education; apply optimal organizational forms and methods of education for its main areas; Students rally kolektyvanalizuvaty conflicts, identify the conflict issue, the conflict, overt and hidden interests and concerns; analyze conflictogen (communication, trust, content, technology, etc.) educational system; predict conflict in the pedagogical environment; determine the phase of the conflict; plat teaching conflict; resolve conflicts constructively teaching in different ways; choose the best style of behavior in conflict situations; effectively manage teaching conflict.

This knowledge students embody and improve the process of course, diploma and master's studies, the result of writing which is to develop training programs, interactive methods of prevention of various conflicts that are used in educational work with students to practice in educational institutions and social services.

Participation in the organization of educational activities:

- in academic groups, according to the work plan curator;
- at the Faculty of Education, according to the plan of educational work of the Faculty;

- General university, according to the plan of educational work Lesya Ukrainka Eastern European National University

Attracting students to the activities of structural subdivisions of the student government, cooperation with civil society organizations, which is coordinated by the Department of Youth Policy and Social Work Lesya Ukrainka Eastern European National University. The aim of this partnership are:

- comprehensive support spiritual and physical development of students, instilling in them a sense of civic consciousness and patriotism

- enforcement of orders and instructions, guidance letters on the problems of youth policy and educational work.

- development of proposals to improve organizational and functional structure of management of educational process at the University and the definition of the functional responsibilities of management

- coordination of structural subdivisions, student government and cooperation with civil society organizations in matters of youth and educational work.

- promoting broad involvement of students in the activities of the student government, the development of progressive forms of government

- study of the problems of students and the creation of necessary conditions for full youth organizations and social formation of youth

Social activities implemented by students during their activities in different associations in terms Lesya Ukrainka Eastern European National University, Student Council, Volunteer Center "Dovira" Youth Policy Council, the Council of young scientists, sports clubs, art groups and others. Participation in these associations on the one hand generates socially active students on the other side - in the absence of conflictological culture creates the conditions for confrontation, unhealthy competition and conflicts of interest of students.

To identify the effectiveness of the prevention of conflicts in interpersonal interactions students of specialty "Social work" and "Pedagogy of high school" we have the study of conflict detection level students. The study involved 42 students, including 22 students of 1 year and 10 students of the 5th year full-time specialty "Social work", 10 students of 6 courses of specialty "Pedagogy of high school."

We conducted research offered students "Research Methodology response characteristics in a conflict situation" K.Tomasa (adaptation N.V.Hryshynoyi) (*Lozhkin, 2002, p. 105*). Method to determine the typical ways of responding to conflict situations and contains 5 scales, describing ways to respond to conflict situations (Table 1.):

Table 1.

Characteristics of ways of behavior in conflict situations

Ways of behavior	Characteristics
Rivalry	characterized by the desire to achieve satisfaction of their interests at the expense of the other
Cooperation	occurs when participants come to the alternative situation that fully meets the interests of both parties
Compromis	characterized by reaching an agreement, in which both sides are certain damages
Avoidance	characterized by a lack of desire of cooperation and lack trend own goals
Adaptation	Characterized by disregard for their own interests of another

Each of these five ways of behavior described by 12 th judgments about individual behavior in conflict situations. In various combinations, they are grouped into 30 pairs, each of which examined choose that judgment, which is a typical characteristic of his behavior. Results of research at picture 1.

Picture 1. The ways of behavior in conflict situations

As we can see on table 1 the way of behavior in a conflict situation with "cooperation" is inherent in the fifth and sixth students rate (40%), "compromise" is used 30% of students and 20% respectively. First-year students at conflict resolution using the "adaptation" (27.3%). Thus, the first-year students tend to devices, avoidance, compromise and competition in a conflict situation, the least they share cooperation. Students in the fifth and sixth course most peculiar behavior as a way to cooperation and compromise.

Conclusions. An analysis of the prevention of conflicts in interpersonal interactions students Lesya Ukrainka Eastern European National University and the Department of Social Education and Pedagogy of high school presents us with a system of lines of prevention in the context of improving the conflict of culture and humanization of relations partners of which affects the quality of teaching and educational work, prevention of destructive forms of social behavior in the conflict, which is essential for optimizing social and educational factors, educational interaction among students.

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POZAPROGRAMOWA PRACA MŁODZIEŻY STUDENCKIEJ NADDNIPRIANSKICH UNIWERSYTETÓW XIX WIEKU

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Streszczenie. Temat artykułu ujawnia osobliwości rozwoju szkolnictwa wyższego Naddniprianschchyną, które były uwarunkowane wydarzeniem historycznym XIX wieku, i wpłynął na stopniowy rozwój edukacji. Szczegółowy jest wpływ wewnętrznych i zewnętrznych uwarunkowań społeczno-kulturowych, co znalazło odzwierciedlenie w obiektywnym zróżnicowaniu procesu edukacyjnego przyszłych specjalistów w dziedzinie specjalizacji przyrodniczych i humanitarnych.

Przedmiotem badania była merytoryczna treść pracy, niezwiązanej z audytem w kontekście najlepszych światowych tradycji edukacyjnych wyznaczonego okresu historycznego. Celem artykułu jest analiza treści wariacyjnej nie audiologicznej formy pracy przez pryzmat światowych tradycji edukacyjnych XIX wieku. Metodologiczny zestaw badań został opracowany metodami biograficznymi, chronologicznymi, etapowymi, historyczno-genetycznymi, historyczno-pedagogicznymi i porównawczymi.

Opracowanie bazy źródłowo-studyjnej umożliwiło ustalenie, że w badanym okresie nie było jasnych formalnych regulacji dotyczących tego, jaki powinien być system dydaktyczny nowo odkrytych uniwersytetów na Dnieprze na Ukrainie. Postępowe postacie, pedagodzy aktywnie pracują nad rozwojem etnograficznej treści edukacji i edukacji.

Analiza problemu tytułowego opierała się na przemyśleniu najlepszych teoretycznych osiągnięć badanej epoki, które problematyzowały wysoce ideologiczne poglądy pedagogiczne i przekonania ówczesnych członków wydziału. Refleksja nad określonym tematem opierała się na holistycznej aksjologicznej, humanistycznej i osobiście zorientowanej konstrukcji badawczej.

Potwierdzono, że działalność edukacyjna nauczycieli badanych uniwersytetów miała na celu dywersyfikację dyscyplin i form zgłaszania studentów, organizację działań estetycznych i środowiskowych (wycieczki po terytorium, zakładanie towarzystw ochrony środowiska itp.).

Przeprowadzona analiza historyczna i pedagogiczna pokazuje, że dla wszystkich dyscyplin akademickich nauczanych na uniwersytetach w Dnieprze na Ukrainie w XIX wieku, system zajęć klasowych charakteryzował się względnym zjednoczeniem. Nie towarzyszące zajęcia i formy zgłaszania studentów dla każdego przedmiotu były indywidualne, ponieważ odzwierciedlały specyfikę każdej dyscypliny naukowej.

Należy zauważyć, że potrzeba utworzenia lokalnej specjalności określonego systemu społecznego wymagała od przedstawicieli uniwersytetów skorelowania elementów procesu studiów regionalnych i szkolenia zawodowego z zadaniami nauczania i edukacji. Udowodniono, że działalność nauczycieli opierała się na idei indywidualnego rozwoju świadomości i odpowiedzialności indywidualnej, obywatelskiej i narodowej. Należy zauważyć, że taka progresywność poglądów często nękała znaczące prześladowanie ze strony obecnych przywódców politycznych, ale nie dewaluowała pod wpływem destrukcyjnych procesów tamtych czasów.

Materiały drukowane przekonują, że działalność nauczycieli uniwersytetów w Dnieprze w badanym okresie nie tylko ukierunkowała studia nad lokalnymi studiami i edukacją młodzieży studenckiej, ale również stała się jednym z czynników rozwoju pedagogiki narodowej. Lokalna

wiedza o działalności pedagogicznej przedstawicieli badanych instytucji edukacyjnych opierała się na szkoleniu wysoko wykwalifikowanych specjalistów i edukacji prawdziwych patriotów. Podkreślono praktyczną orientację i znaczenie nauk przyrodniczych dla coraz głębszego przemyslenia fizycznych i geograficznych cech ich ojczystej ziemi, które korelowały z edukacją patriotyczną i estetyczną w badanym okresie.

Słowa kluczowe: praca pozalekcyjna, młodzież studencka, Naddniprianszczyna, proces społeczno-kulturowy.

EXTRACURRICULAR WORK OF THE STUDENT YOUTH OF NADDNIPRYANSHCHYNA UNIVERSITIES OF THE XIX CENTURY

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Abstract. The subject of the article reveals the peculiarities of the development of the natural science field of higher education of the Naddnipryanshchyna, which were conditioned by the historical events of the XIX century and affected the gradual development of education. The influence of internal and external socio-cultural determinants, which were reflected in the subjects' differentiation of the future specialists' educational process in natural and humanitarian specialties, is detailed.

The subject of the study was the substantive content of extracurricular work in the context of the best world educational traditions of the defined historical period.

The purpose of the article is to analyze the differentiated content of extracurricular form of work through the prism of world educational traditions of the XIX century.

The research tools for the study were biographical, chronological and content, incremental, historical, pedagogical and comparative methods.

The study of existing sources and database made it possible to establish that in the period under the study there was no clear formal regulation as to what should be the didactic system of the newly discovered universities of Naddnipryanshchyna. Progressive figures and teachers actively worked on the development of ethnography-oriented content, forms, principles, methods and means of education.

The analysis of the titled problem was based on the analysis of the best theoretical developments of the studied epoch, which challenged the highly ideological pedagogical views and beliefs of the professorial teaching staff. A rethinking of the subject was based on a holistic axiological, humanistic, and personally-oriented study construct.

It was confirmed that the educational activity of the universities teachers under the study was aimed at the diversification of the disciplines and forms of students' reporting, as well as at the organization of aesthetic and environmental measures (excursions around the territory, establishment of environment protection societies, etc.).

The conducted historical and pedagogical analysis shows, that for all the academic disciplines that were taught at the universities of the Naddnipryanshchyna during the XIX century, the system of face-to-face classes was characterized by relative unification. Extracurricular activities and forms of student reporting for each subject were individual because they reflected the specific character of each scientific discipline.

It is noted that the need for the formation of a local lore specialist of a specific social system required from the representatives of universities to correlate the components of the process of regional studies and professional training with the tasks of teaching and education. It was proved that the activity of teachers was based on the idea of individual development, civil and national consciousness and responsibility. It is highlighted that such progressiveness of

views often suffered considerable harassment on the part of the current political leaders of the day, but did not devalue under the influence of destructive processes of that time.

Printed material confirm that teachers activities of Naddnipyrianshchyna universities during the studied period not only directed the study of local studies and education of student youth, but also became one of the factors of national pedagogy development. Local lore content of pedagogical activity of the studied educational institutions representatives was based on the training of highly skilled specialists and the education of true patriots. The importance of natural sciences for a more profound rethinking of the physical and geographical features of their native land, which was correlated with patriotic and aesthetic education in the period under study, was emphasized.

Subsequently, the content of the scientific and pedagogical searches of graduates proved the importance and fundamental meaning of the theoretical and practical directions of local lore and pedagogical activity, which was carried out by their scientific mentors - teachers.

Keywords: extra-curriculum work, student youth, Naddnipyrianshchyna, socio-cultural process.

ПОЗААУДИТОРНА РОБОТА СТУДЕНТСЬКОЇ МОЛОДІ НАДДНІПРЯНСЬКИХ УНІВЕРСИТЕТІВ ХІХ СТОЛІТТЯ

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Анотація. Тема статті розкриває особливості розвитку природничого напрямку вищої освіти Наддніпрянщини, які обумовлювалися історичною подієвістю ХІХ ст. та позначилися на поступальному розвитку освіти. Деталізовано вплив внутрішніх та зовнішніх соціокультурних детермінант, які віддзеркалювалися у предметній диференціації навчально-виховного процесу майбутніх фахівців природничих та гуманітарних спеціальностей.

Предметом дослідження виступила змістова наповненість позааудиторної роботи у розрізі кращих світових освітніх традицій означеного історичного періоду.

Метою статті є аналіз варіативного змісту позааудиторної форми роботи крізь призму світових освітніх традицій ХІХ ст.

Методологічним інструментарієм дослідження послуговував біографічний, хронологічно-змістовний, поетапно-проблемний, історико-генетичний, історико-педагогічний та порівняльний методи.

Опрацювання джерелознавчої бази дало змогу встановити, що в період, який досліджується не було чіткої офіційної регламентації стосовно того, якою має бути дидактична система нововідкритих університетів Наддніпрянської України. Прогресивні діячі, педагоги активно працювали над розробкою краєзнавчо-орієнтованого змісту навчання та виховання.

Аналіз титульної проблематики засновувався на переосмисленні кращих теоретичних напрацювань досліджуваної епохи, які проблематизували високоідейність педагогічних поглядів та переконань тогочасного професорсько-викладацького складу. Відрефлексування визначеного предмету будувалося на врахуванні цілісного аксіологічного, гуманістичного та особистісно зорієнтованого конструкту дослідження.

Підтверджено, що освітньо-краєзнавча діяльність викладачів досліджуваних університетів була спрямована на урізноманітнення дисциплін і форм звітності студентів, організацію естетично-екологічних заходів (екскурсії по території краю, створення природоохоронних товариств тощо).

Проведений історико-педагогічний аналіз свідчить, що для усіх навчальних дисциплін, які викладалися в університетах Наддніпрянської України упродовж XIX ст. система аудиторних занять характеризувалася відносною уніфікацією. Позааудиторні заняття та форми звітності студентів для кожного предмета були індивідуальні, оскільки відображали специфіку кожного наукового напрямку.

Зазначається, що потреба у формуванні краєзнавчо обізнаного спеціаліста конкретної соціальної системи потребувала від представників університетів співвідносити складові процесу краєзнавчо-професійної підготовки із завданнями вчити та виховувати. Доведено, що діяльність викладачів будувалася на ідеї індивідуального розвитку особистості, громадянської і національної свідомості та відповідальності. Зауважено, що така прогресивність поглядів нерідко зазнавала значних утисків зі сторони діючого політичного керівництва, проте не девальвовувалася під впливом руйнівних процесів того часу.

Друковані матеріали переконують, що діяльність викладачів університетів Наддніпрянщини досліджуваного періоду не лише спрямовувала краєзнавчо-освітню підготовку студентської молоді, але й стала одним із факторів розвитку національної педагогіки. Краєзнавчий зміст педагогічної діяльності представників досліджуваних закладів освіти базувався на підготовці висококваліфікованих фахівців і вихованні справжніх патріотів. Підкреслено практичну зорієнтованість та значущість природничих знань для все більш глибокого переосмислення фізико-географічних особливостей рідної місцевості, що співвідносилося у досліджуваній період із патріотичним та естетичним вихованням.

Ключові слова: позааудиторна робота, студентська молодь, Наддніпрянщина, соціокультурний процес.

Introduction. The orientation of the educational paradigm to the formation of the individual, as well as preparation for life involves deepening knowledge about the environment, the history of the native land and regional identity. At all stages of the history of Ukraine, the spread of regional education contributed to the social, economic, cultural and national development of the state. The introduction of progressive ethnographic, historical and pedagogical traditions is based on axiological, acmeological, human-centered indicators and meets the requirements of the National Doctrine of Education Development in Ukraine, the State National Program "Education" (Ukraine XXI Century).

Some aspects of the problem under study are found in the works of V. Andrushchenko, T. Zavgorodnaya, V. Syrotyuk, N. Demyanenko, A. Sukhomlinskaya, M. Sheremet and others. However, the issue of the extra-curricular work content of Naddnipryanshchyna in the context of the best educational traditions of the given century remains to be studied.

The purpose of the article is to analyze the differentiated content of extracurricular form of work through the prism of world educational traditions of the XIX century.

In accordance with the purpose, *the tasks* of the study are the following:

- to analyze the state of the investigated problem;
- to follow the peculiarities of pedagogical theory and practice development during the investigated historical epoch;
- to popularize national historical and pedagogical experience.

The methodological research tools for the study were biographical, chronological and content, incremental, historical, pedagogical and comparative methods.

The Kharkiv University. The teachers of the Kharkiv University provided numerous theoretical and practical recommendations to representatives of general educational institutions regarding how to correctly study and compile a description of the territory of the region. The Dean of the History and Philology Faculty G. Uspensky independently prepared an instruction for collecting statistical, topographical and historical data for secondary schools. His colleague, Professor I. Gut, developed a special project for conducting geodetic, meteorological and astronomical observations for gymnasiums. Similar methodological instructions were also compiled for the purpose of geographic data recording (*Bagalej, D. Y. 1906, p. 74*).

In 1814, speaking at a regular meeting of teachers, Uspensky said: "... it is important for every nation to know the ancient and present condition of its land ..." [2, p. 74]. In order to direct the local lore work of teachers in the right direction, he developed a special program in 1815. For the purpose of its content filling the representatives of the university had to visit all the schools that were in the district. Structurally, the program contained two parts - general and special ones. The first part reflected the level of the educational process at schools, and the second – provided for the collection of local lore information by teachers and their pupils according to the plan.

In accordance with Uspensky's assumption, the collected materials, after being elaborated by experienced teachers, should have entered the circulation not only at secondary schools, but also universities. The scientist believed that only in this way it will be possible "to collect the necessary historical, topographical and statistical data, which the university still does not possess" (*Bagalej, D. Y. 1906, p. 74*). So, the high school teacher Zozulin collected nine notebooks of the topographical descriptions of the Poltava province.

Analyzing the local history and pedagogical plan of the professor, it becomes clear that it was based on the didactic principle of continuity in learning. In accordance with which, part of local lore knowledge was acquired by pupils at school, and deepened - in university conditions.

However, G. Uspensky's ambitious plan for the collection of local lore materials could not be fully realized in practice because of technical reasons. Although, the pedagogical content of the educational - linguistic project in the scientific regard was perfect. The compilation of newsletters proceeded rather slowly due to the fact that the materials sent to the Main College Committee of the Ministry of National Education contained a number of errors and a significant amount of unnecessary information. Technical gaps were caused by the directives of the Ministerial Committee, which sought to turn valuable materials into chaotic management statistics.

Professors of the Naddniprovyanshchyna universities, which were members of the regional lore scientific communities, had close cooperation with high schools, lyceums and schools. M. Sumtsov expressed his own pedagogical vision of what should be local lore excursions for students. At the regular meeting of the Pedagogical Department of the Kharkiv Historical and Philological Society (October 3, 1897), the scientist made a presentation: "On the issue of organizing local educational student excursions." In the introduction, the educator emphasized that recently in the pedagogical press, many wishes have been highlighted on how to properly organize and conduct a regional study tour for pupils. As a result, Sumtsov noted, teachers from Kharkiv University received a variety of questions from different regions from pedagogues-organizers of excursions, among them were the following:

- 1) "... what is interesting from the educational point of view in Kharkiv and the Kharkiv province?
- 2) What educational establishments and scientific societies are present in the region?
- 3) How are student excursions organized within the boundaries of the region? " (*Sumczov N. 1897, p. 2*).

Professor Sumtsov wrote that when considering student excursions, "... I mean exclusively male secondary schools" (*Sumczov N. 1897, p. 4*). Although it is possible, the teacher argued, that all instructions could be used to conduct such activities at higher and lower secondary schools. The scientist was convinced that the smaller the age and the class of the pupils - the more difficult it is to organize them for this or that local event. The true teacher is the one who is able to organize walks so that his students will always be occupied with inspecting the area. However, according to the teacher, the walks should not be identified with educational excursions. It is best to organize excursions on the territory of the region with a group of students of 5-8 grades.

From a methodological point of view, the teacher recommended those educators who are preparing for the tour, "... to determine what you will show and how you will show it in advance, and how the shown things should enter into a complex system of meaningful comments" (*Sumczov N. 1897, p. 6*).

Looking at the territory of his own region, Sumtsov proposed, first of all, to pay attention to the temples and monasteries, as well as to get acquainted with "church archeology and ancient books ..." (*Sumczov N. 1897, p. 7*). After that, you should visit museums "... not only urban, and especially university ones" (*Sumczov N. 1897, p. 7*). When listing numerous exhibits of the university exposition, the he suggested that teachers should draw pupils' attention to the ethnographic, photographic and pottery materials. Professor of Kharkiv University noted that "university museums ... contain a mass of the highly valuable educational material that needs to be further studied in detail. Among them, there were the zoological, mineralogical and little-known numismatic rooms " (*Sumczov N. 1897, p. 8*). Sumtsov recommended visiting local factories and plants, which are a kind of driving force of industrial development of the region.

Concluding his report, Sumtsov emphasized that it was necessary to propose to the pedagogical department to elect a special Commission at the university, which would accumulate local lore material collected by regional professional educational institutions. According to the scientist, the data would be processed by university representatives and subsequently represented in the publications of the Historical and Philological Society. Representatives of the Naddnipyrianshchyna universities, which were members of scientific societies, developed ethnographically oriented visual materials that were actively implemented in the educational process of the above-mentioned institutions. In 1820 a member of the Kharkiv Naturalists' Association, Professor V. Chernyayev, conducted the first botanical expedition, which covered the territory of Poltava, Dnipropetrovsk, Bessarabia, Odessa and the southern coast of the Crimea. During the trip, the scientist collected valuable samples of the representatives of the flora of different regions of Ukraine. Reporting to the Academic Council of the Kharkiv University about the results of the expedition, the professor in one of his letters said: "... the plants collected for the past two years I passed on to the Kharkov gymnasium ..." (*Kalenychenko, Y. O. 1876, p. 163*). It was not the only collection that

the teacher presented to the mentioned above institution. During his trip to European countries, Chernyaev collected a new collection, which he wrote: "... I have the opportunity not only to transfer a more or less complete herbarist (Herbarium) to the university, as the correct guide for anyone who is studying botany, but also to pass on one herbarist to all the gymnasia that belong to the educational district of the university, ..." (*Bagalej, D. Y., 1904, p. 526*).

In the summer 1832 Chernyaev went to the Tavia province to analyze the educational process of gymnasiums and other educational institutions. It should be noted that during the time off work, the scientist, together with his teachers and students, conducted a study of the typical flora of the territory of the southern coast of the Crimea. All samples collected by them entered the museum collections of gymnasiums.

Professor O. Potebnya made a significant contribution to the development of educational regional studies. He repeatedly organized meetings with the youth of the "narrowly-formed" educational institution - the Kharkov collegium (later - the seminary), in which he spoke "... about the historical past of the region, about our songs, about our poetry, and called for research and love, and the students with pleasure listened to him for hours" (*Bagalej, D. Y. 1906, p. 38-39*).

The Kiev University. In the 1860's the issue of the opening of Sunday schools for adults became of paramount importance, and Potebnya was actively involved in this activity. The teacher prepared a Ukrainian primer, which was built on "full-fledged words"; the content was saturated with local material and was "completely deprived" of religious motives.

A significant contribution to the development of pedagogical regional studies at the Kremenets Gymnasium was made by the Society of Naturalists and the first Professor of Botany at Kyiv University V. Besser. The scientist made every effort to bring a zoological collection to the gymnasium, which contained a lot of exhibits of local representatives. The above-mentioned collection was more numerous than in the Vilno Medical and Surgery Academy. It consisted of varieties of fish (119 units), insects (2585 units), birds (453 units), mammals (79 units), molluscs (2220 units), as well as a number of specimens of reptiles, bats and worms.

The educator entered the history of regional studies not only as a famous researcher, who managed to combine medical practice and research of representatives of local flora and fauna, but also as the founder of the Kremenets Botanical Garden. On the territory of the mentioned garden there were systematically numerous excursions not only for pupils of general and professional educational institutions, but also for all interested persons.

The head of the Zoology Department of the University of Vilno, and later Professor of Kyiv University E. Eichwald introduced the visual materials of local lore content at Kremenets Lyceum at the high methodological level. This is how the graduates of the Lyceum describe the teacher in which he worked from 1819 to 1821: "... considering himself a natural scientist, he was a specialist in the zoology of the local fauna and in paleontology ..." (*Ivanciv V. E., 2001, p. 112*). In 1829, Eichwald visited the Kremenets Lyceum in the framework of an expedition on the territory of Volyn, where he had the opportunity to get acquainted with the natural-historical exposition. This is evidence of the fact that at that time the lyceum owned the regional collections. Analyzing the seen, the scientist noted that in the above-mentioned educational institution it was necessary to create a museum of local lore, in which there should be a

geological exposition. During the 5-month trip, the professor collected many samples for the museum, and repeatedly organized a two-week tour of the local limestone and chalk mountains. It should be noted that Eichwald, while outside Volyn, continued to collect geological, botanical, zoological and paleontological collections for the museum in the territory of Odessa, Kherson and other territories (*Eichwald E., 1830*). Z. Fedorovich, the researcher of the creative heritage of E. Eichwald, in his work "Zarys rozwoju fizjografii Polski ze szczegolnym uwzględnieniem faunistyki (od czasow najdawniejszych do roku 1918)" emphasized that the professor was concerned not only with the replenishment of the collections of the local lore, but also the liceum museum (*Fedorowicz Z., 1963*).

V. Antonovich (Kyiv University), on his own initiative, prepared an archaeological map of Volyn, which was used in the educational process of the lyceum and gymnasium. This work consisted of two parts - the explanatory text and the actual map, on which the archaeological monuments of various types were marked with colored symbols.

In addition, the representatives from the Naddniproshchyna universities expressed a lot of comments as to what the educational process should be. Thus, Davien noted that chemistry was not included in the list of gymnasium disciplines, which was an important basis for understanding the course of chemical processes in the nature of the region. Another disadvantage, according to the professor, was that natural history (ethnography) was studied by pupils in separate parts. On the initiative of the representatives of the high school on June 17, 1861, the approval of such a procedure of natural sciences teaching in gymnasia was:

1st form - mathematical and physical geography of the region (2 lessons per week);

2nd form - physical and chemical phenomena occurring in nature (1 lesson per week);

3rd form - characteristic of external forms of animals and plants, characteristic of the area of the region (2 lessons per week);

4th form - chemistry, which included the topic of chemical processes characteristic of the region (1 lesson per week);

5th form – zoology, containing topics in the region's zoology (2 lessons a week);

6th form - botany, which includes topics from the regional botany (2 lessons a week);

7th form - geology and mineralogy, which focused on the consideration of geological and mineralogical characteristics of the territory of the region (2 lessons a week) (*Vtoroj sjezd estestvoysputatelej v Kyeve, p. XXIV-XXB*).

In addition, the meeting considered the level of educational institutions' provision with educational materials. Initially, the professors stopped at choosing the most appropriate microscopes for the educational process. Then, they turned to the consideration of an extremely serious issue - the provision of educational institutions of different levels with natural collections. Professor A. Rogovich drew the attention of all those present to the fact that these collections can be collected locally by the teachers of natural sciences. Professor Kessler volunteered to help and make for them a special catalog of items that should have been included in the collection. Davien emphasized that, taking into account the research and material level of the university, only he can act

as a sponsor and at the same time a compiler of all natural collections collected in the territory.

The purpose of the second Kyiv congress of naturalists was outlined at the opening by its organizer prof. K. Kessler. The teacher expressed his thoughts about the fact that the subject of pedagogical meetings should be the discussion of the natural sciences teaching in secondary schools, as well as "... a detailed consideration of issues related to the compilation of natural collections at gymnasia and the purchase of other teaching aids for teachers of the Natural Sciences " (*Vtoroj sjezd estestvoysputatelej v Kyeve p. 10*).

Considering foreign lore and pedagogical experience, Professor D. Bagalij noted that European educators were following the fact that the acquaintance of the students "... first of all, with what they see next to and around themselves ..." (*Bagalij, D. I. 1991, p. 14*) began from the elementary school. The teacher believed that only under such conditions the pupils "... will revere, appreciate and love the land" (*Bagalij, D. I. 1991, p. 15*). Professor repeatedly emphasized that many European nations had a great commitment to their local history, archeology, "... we see there even local museums ..." (*Bagalij, D. I. 1991, p. 14*). For this reason, Bagalij emphasized that the content of programs of folk schools, schools for adults and for extracurricular education should have involved the local history that would familiarize students with the historical events that took place in Slobozhanshchyna.

As a conclusion. On the basis of the foregoing, we see that the multifaceted educational and linguistic activities of teachers, which they realized practically during the XIX – early XX centuries, were not limited to the boundaries of the Naddnipryanshchyna universities. Employees of higher educational institutions provided theoretical and practical recommendations for teachers of local schools, gymnasiums and colleges on how to organize and conduct properly a local lore event. Thus, professors who were members of university research societies developed a lot of visual materials that were used by students of general education institutions to familiarize themselves with the region. In our opinion, the most significant manifestation of the introduction of the results of local lore and pedagogical activity of university teachers in the practice of educational institutions can be considered the holding of the first two nature researchers' congresses. At the congresses mentioned above, the teachers held several pedagogical meetings, which provided a lot of methodological recommendations for teachers of educational institutions. The results of fruitfully held congresses of nature researchers can be followed also in conducting numerous local lore events for the students not only of domestic, but also foreign general educational institutions.

The prospects of further researches are seen in the study of the axiological content of the creative heritage of pedagogical staff, who have made a significant contribution to the development of higher education in various regions of the world.

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